

**A contextual framework for E-Government
implementation in the SADC region: A case of
Zimbabwe**

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Thesis accepted in fulfilment of the requirements for the degree
Doctor of Philosophy in Information Systems
at the North-West University

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Graduation ceremony: December 2020

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Firstly, I express my indebtedness to Professor Nehemiah Mavetera and Prof. Mmaki Jantjies, for they taught me that in the doctoral endeavor it is not about the destination but the journey. They chose to walk with me on this trying and testing journey. Their wisdom and constructive critiques that they shared with me each time I sent them my partial work for review and when we interacted in our virtual and face to face meetings, kept me engaged. They have certainly shaped my research technical skills. I cherish the effort. I cannot thank them enough, but God has a way.

I acknowledge the support from the North-West University academic team that participated in my doctoral colloquia for their support, critiques and comments moderated by my supervisors which contributed to shaping and strengthening of my PhD work. Without them, I would not have reached this goal. Thank you so much.

To all those who participated in the study interviews and those who responded to the study questionnaires, I thank you: this study would not have been without your participation.

To Dr. Makambe and Dr. Gumbo, I will remember the shared experiences and academic debates that we had on our journeys in pursuit of this doctoral qualification. I have caught up with you.

DEDICATION

To my daughter, Tariro Natasha, I owe her an apology for depriving her of that motherly connection in the greater part of my PhD journey. I am back.

To my mother, Maria Chikerema: she has been my pillar of strength in this journey. This is to her health!

Lastly but not least, to my young sister Primrose Chikerema (MSc Degree in Statistics and Operations Research) whose critiques of my quantitative analysis enhanced my statistical analysis skills. This is to us.

ABSTRACT

Presently e-Government has turned out to be every country's endeavour though its potential is yet to be achieved by many. Extant literature on e-Government emphasizes on the barriers to its implementation and the opportunities arising therefrom, favouring its adoption by the supply side. Additionally, though e-Government is complex in nature, the lack of rigour in e-Government studies contribute to its misconstrued status with particular mention of the developing countries. The dearth in research on its adoption by the demand side that considers its complexity and multidimensional nature, and the shared socio-technical peculiarity of the Southern African Development Community (SADC) member states, has contributed to the low acceptance in the region.

The study, therefore, from the perspectives of the demand side, explored the meaning of e-Government in the SADC with emphasis on Zimbabwe to develop a framework to enhance its implementation and adoption of the phenomenon in the region. In consideration of the interplay of human and non-human actors in the phenomenon, a socio-technical perspective approach was adopted from the ontology of Actor-Network Theory, Innovation translation, and Technology Acceptance Model. To the mix, design thinking was added to knit together how the designers and the participants perceive the e-Government as a solution. Against this backdrop, a mixed method approach was used to balance the actuality with the user experiences. Eight participants were interviewed and the resulting qualitative data was analysed using ATLAS.ti 8. The results informed the development of the quantitative instrument. A total of three hundred and seventeen (317) questionnaires drawn from participants from Zimbabwe, Botswana, South Africa, and Namibia were considered for the quantitative analysis using SPSS and AMOS (a Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) component of the SPSS package); the F. Hayes process tool; and the interaction plotter.

The findings confirmed the success of e-Government implementation owes to the design-reality gap and that the notion of '*gap*' is not merely the current realities such as technical capabilities, context, capacity, and situational factors but also about how Governments often mirror a technical and functional approach rather than a needs-based and design thinking approach. Consequently, a framework to facilitate the enhancement of e-Government implementation and adoption by various stakeholders. The supply side was recommended to tap into the local context in which the innovation should work.

Key Terms: e-Government, framework, TAM, Actor-Network Theory, human-centered, Context, Trust, Culture, design thinking

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

ANT	Actor-Network Theory
ATMs	Automated Teller Machines
ICTs	Information and Communication Technologies
CAQDAS	Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software
DOI IDT	Diffusion of Innovation or Innovation Diffusion Theory
EGDI	E-Government Development Index
FOI	Freedom of Information
GnB	Governments and Businesses and their reverse
GnC	Government and Citizens and its reverse
GnG	Within and across Government agencies
GoZ	Government of Zimbabwe
HU	Hermeneutic Unit
HCD	Human Centred Design
IDI	ICT Development Index
IS	Information Systems
InT	Innovation Traslation
ITAX	Integrated Tax Administration System in Tanzania
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
MoFEA	Ministry of Finance and Economic Affairs
MMR	Mixed-Method Research
NECTA	National Examinations Council of Tanzania
OPP	Obligatory Passage of Point
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PATU	Perceived Ability to Use
PA	Public Administration
PEOU	Perceived Ease of Use
PIF	Perceived Internet Familiarity
PD	Power Distance
PerSQ	Perceived Service Quality
PrSC	Privacy and Security Concerns
PV	Perceived Value
PU	Perceived Usefulness
RTC	Record of Rights, Tenancy and Cultivation
RDP	Reconstruction and Development Programme

SADC	Southern African Development Community
SADCC	Southern African Development Coordination Conference
SEM	Structural Equation Modelling
ST	Structuration Theory
TCU	Tanzania Commission for Universities
TANESCO	Tanzania National Electricity Corporation
TRA	Tanzania Revenue Authority
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TPB	Theory of Planned Behaviour
TPV	Third Party Vendors
TieG	Trust in e-Government
TiG	Trust in Government
TiT	Trust in Technology
TRA	Theory of Reasoned Action
UA	Uncertainty Avoidance
UML	Unified Modelling Language
UCD	User Centred Design
UTAUT	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology

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1 THE PROBLEM AND ITS SETTING

1.1 Introduction

The chapter initiates a discussion of the background to the study in which the context of the problem investigated was delineated, with specific focus on the aims, question to be answered and the knowledge to be derived in the study, the purpose and significance- of the study.

1.2 Background to the study

The study sought to give the participants space to share their perspectives on the meanings they attached to e-Government in Zimbabwe and consequently in the Southern African Development Community member states. What motivated the study was one of the classic findings on e-Government's scarce successes in in countries such as Zimbabwe. The success of e-Government has been found to owe to the Design-Reality gap (Heeks, 2002b; Santos & Heeks, 2003) perceived as the misalignment of the present realities and the design of e-Government solutions (Heeks, 2002b, p. 104; Santos & Heeks, 2003, p. 3). Gasson (2003a, p. 29) reiterates that the approaches to Information Systems Design are technology centered instead of supporting human interests with technology. This follows that e-Government has become a global agenda with each country partaking in designing country specific solutions (Helbig et al., 2009; Schuppan, 2009; Al-Hujran, Al-Dalahmeh & Aloudat, 2011; Chikerema, Mavetera & Jantjies, 2016, p. 416), evidenced through the increase in e-Government projects by the existing governments and multiple stakeholder involvement in the growth of e-Government (Carter & Bélanger, 2005; Chikerema, Mavetera & Jantjies, 2016). The investment by Governments and their agencies in launching e-Government services warrants their adoption by the general populace otherwise a lack of usage of these e-services is a real setback.

Research shows that Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) are pillars in the transformation of traditional government services (Schware & Deane, 2003; Helbig, Ferro, Superiore, & Boella, 2005; Al-Hujran, Al-Dalahmeh, & Aloudat, 2011), recognising therefore the potential of ICTs in reforming organisational structures towards the achievement of organisational objectives (Helbig, Gil-García & Ferro, 2005). The pervasiveness of ICTs in regular operations have altered the way organisations, universities, and governments interact and collaborate amongst themselves (Kumar *et al.*, 2007; Chun, Luna-Reyes & Sandoval-Almazán, 2012; Nkwe, 2012; Majdalawi *et al.*, 2015). The ICTs have promoted the increase of technology contexts including e-communication, e-Health, e-commerce, e-marketing, e-learning, e-banking, e-payments, e-voting and e-billing (Bwalya & Healy, 2010). It is the increase of the e-

contexts that underscores the ubiquity of ICTs that create multiple ways in which the citizens interact with governments.

ICT acceptance and usage has changed the way Government stakeholders interact and engage each other (InfoDev & The Centre for Democracy and Technology, 2002, p. 1; The World Bank, 2004, p. 1; Ruhode, Owei & Maumbe, 2008, p. 2; Schuppan, 2009; Chun, Luna-Reyes & Sandoval-Almazán, 2012, p. 6; Chikerema, Mavetera & Jantjies, 2016), including promotion of instantaneous access to and retrieval of information and enhanced access to government services by a wider population (Majdalawi *et al.*, 2015, p. 212). This redefinition of the expectations is particularly influenced by the increase in the penetration of mobile technologies amongst the citizenry. In the study e-Government is defined as the utilisation of ICTs for the enhancement of the delivery of public services and stakeholder participation.

Whilst the e-Government concept originated from developed countries, it is significant that the context in which the concept is introduced be understood fully (Heeks, 2002a, p. 3,18; Schuppan, 2009, p. 118). E-Government experiences are blindly followed from developed by undeveloped countries despite infrastructural and social differences specifically in the nation states that adopt this mechanism (Heeks, 2002a, p. 18; Chen *et al.*, 2006, p. 26) and consequently these have failed (Heeks, 2002b, 2002a, 2003; Gupta, Dasgupta & Gupta, 2008; Nkohkwo & Islam, 2013; Rana & Dwivedi, 2015). Understanding that each country though to some extent shares some common aspects with other countries, has its own peculiarity that requires context specific e-Government solutions to address the human needs and solve problems that the general populace faces is key. E-Government goes beyond the provision of technological solutions to the users, it also warrants the understanding of the characteristics of the target audience, their needs, their technology experiences prior to the awareness of the e-Government solution, and their learning styles, coupled with the learning patterns drawn from the experiences of the designers towards the development of human centric e-Government solutions. Undoubtedly the nature of e-Government is complex.

However, the complexity is worsened by the availability of diverse criteria, foci, and objectives in the evaluation of e-Government solutions (Heeks, 2002b; Heeks & Bailur, 2007; Cocchiglia & Vernaschi, 2008, p. 5; Rorissa & Demissie, 2010; Wei *et al.*, 2013). Apart from having a diverse population of stakeholders who are the e-Government user groups including citizens, residents and immigrants, government employees and international users (Bertot, Jaeger, & McClure, 2008), who in this study are perceived as actors, the field of e-Government has been approached from the two extreme perspectives: the technological determinism and the socio determinism (Jansen, 2005; Beynon-Davies, 2007; Alshawi & Alalwany, 2009). Past researches

on e-Government demonstrate an inclination towards essentialism, showing a serious lack of the holistic socio-technical perspective and thereby underrating the dynamic interaction between technology and the social (Cordella & Shaik, 2006; Beynon-Davies, 2007; Heeks & Bailur, 2007; Cocchiglia & Vernaschi, 2008, p. 5; Gupta, Dasgupta & Gupta, 2008, p. 141; Guha & Chakrabarti, 2014). The dichotomy of the perspectives taken by the scholars in Information systems is typical of an unromantic approach that sways the understanding and meaning of e-Government by its adopters.

On the other hand, e-Government affordances to public administrations include a myriad opportunities to become effective, accessible to the people (Siskos, Askounis & Psarras, 2014, p. 51; Putra *et al.*, 2018), and also to be an instrument for sustainable development (UN, 2014). In some developing countries including Zimbabwe, such affordances continue to be liminal (Chikerema, Mavetera & Jantjies, 2016). The e-Government potential may not be comparable to that of the industrialised countries owing to the intermediary models applied in Africa. In Africa a handful may directly own ICT intermediaries - typically internet-connected; the greater part may directly use institutionally owned ICT intermediaries such as libraries, schools, post offices and tele centres; and many would directly use ICTs from people close to them. Yet the rest would neither own nor have direct access to institutional ICT intermediaries (Heeks, 2002a, p. 7).

Heeks (2002a) posits that e-Government in African countries is challenged by the lack of national infrastructure. As such, e-Government success in some these countries remains somewhat ironic and low owing to the design-reality gap (Heeks, 2002a, 2003; Anthopoulos *et al.*, 2015). Additionally, in acknowledgement of and corroboration with extant literature on the inadequacy of infrastructure, Gupta, Dasgupta and Gupta (2008, p. 141) argued that the greater population in the developing world resides where scaling of e-Government infrastructure and initiatives is problematic. In response to these findings on e-Government success, Guha and Chakrabarti (2014) argued on the persistence of the design-reality gap even where infrastructural problems have been rectified. In reality, the design-reality gaps were found to be owing to the misunderstood interplay of actors in e-Government (Beynon-Davies, 2007; Heeks & Bailur, 2007; Heeks & Stanforth, 2007; Guha & Chakrabarti, 2014). To this effect, Al-Hujran, Al-Dalahmeh and Aloudat (2011) called for additional empirical studies that could help the governments understand e-Government from the perceptions of the citizenry.

1.3 Problem Statement

To a certain extent, the challenges on e-Government in the SADC member states are so common to think that there is a common solution. The biggest challenge that affects many countries is benchmarking and non-contextualization combined which may lead to the adoption

syndrome instead of adaption. In a similar vein Twizeyimana, Larsson and Grönlund (2018) argued that adaptation to local conditions begins at home. Kromidha (2012) argued that the benchmarking lessons should be considered to suit the local and regional context with the ability to evaluate the progress being the most important. The purpose of benchmarking is to identify the processes of those organisations that are flourishing and use the information to evaluate the current status of the benchmarking organisation. If the benchmarking is used as a way of copying and replicating what is happening in other countries or organisations then it would only mean that the target population's needs are not being addressed. Heeks, 2003 (p. 5) argued that the existence of country context gaps looms large. The scholar captured it in the catchy phrase: 'Think Global, Act local.' The phrase largely mirrors the propensity by the SADC member states to pander to global imperatives to remain competitive in the global context, neglecting the local imperatives.

What then motivates the study is that despite the identification of e-Government challenges over years by researchers, low success rate of e-Government perseveres (Guha & Chakrabarti, 2014). This has led the scholars to question the criticality of the identified e-Government challenges. Similarly, Cocchiglia and Vernaschi (2008) argued that the limited effort to understand the challenges and the misinterpretation of the e-Government concept has contributed to the crippling of the phenomena. It is against this background that the study responded to the call by Al-Hujran, Al-Dalahmeh and Aloudat (2011), the persistent lack of adoption of e-Government initiatives by many countries in the developing countries (Jonathan and Rusu, 2019), and advanced the notion of 'gap' captured in the 'design-reality gap' by Heeks (2003) and (Anthopoulos *et al.*, 2015). The current study submits that the notion of 'gap' is not just about the current realities such as technical capabilities, capacity, context, and situational factors but it is also about how Government often mirrors a technical and functional approach rather than a needs-based and Design Thinking approach.

Undoubtedly, the extant literature recognises the effort to enhance e-Government adoption. The current study acknowledges a dearth of research with an emphasis on understanding why e-Government adoption from the demand side continues to be low and slow in Zimbabwe and in Southern African Development Community (SADC). The literature remains limited and problematic owing to the following reasons:

- a. Some studies focus on e-Government challenges instead of understanding the predictors for its adoption (Guha & Chakrabarti, 2014).
- b. The e-Government literature shows lack of rigour (Heeks & Bailur, 2007) evidenced in the manifest absence of the application of theories that give room for the actors to

express themselves, something that Latour (2005, p. 143) confesses can only be achievable through the Actor-Network Theory.

- c. Past researches on e-Government demonstrate an inclination towards essentialism, showing emphasis on select perspectives rather than their dynamic interaction (Cordella & Shaik, 2006; Beynon-Davies, 2007; Heeks & Bailur, 2007; Cocchiglia & Vernaschi, 2008, p. 5; Gupta, Dasgupta & Gupta, 2008, p. 141; Guha & Chakrabarti, 2014).
- d. Additionally, Kumar et al. (2007, p. 64) identify that there is limited effort to develop e-Government theory that recognises the heterogeneity of actors and drivers of the phenomenon.
- e. Limited attention given to the research that looks into several country contexts and how national culture affects the implementation of e-Government initiatives (Jacob *et al.*, 2019; Kumar *et al.*, 2020).

It is against this backdrop that the current study sought to identify and explain what exactly influences e-Government implementation from the voices of the citizens and to clarify possibilities for its enhancement.

1.4 Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study was to obtain an understanding of the complexity of e-Government phenomenon by exploring the human needs-based e-Government adoption predictors in Zimbabwe and examine the possibilities of its enhancement in the SADC. The study was underpinned by a mix of TAM, the Actor-network Theory, Innovation Translation, and Design Thinking to explore the phenomenon. This matrix was adopted to enhance the rigour that was limited to technological determinism in the field of Information Systems. Drawing from the Actor-Network Theory, the study acknowledges the involvement of multiple stakeholders and their dynamic relationships in e-Government. The study gives voice to participant citizens who shared their experiences to afford the supply side to tap into the local context in which the innovation should work. Consequently, the study operationalises a contextual framework of e-Government adoption which is expected to recognise the multiple potent drivers of adoption.

1.5 Main Research Question

How could e-Government stakeholders' interactions be enhanced to improve adoption of e-Government in the Southern African Development Community?

1.6 Sub research questions

- i. How does the translation process aid in understanding the e-Government adoption trajectory in SADC?*
- ii. What are the factors of e-Government adoption that derive from non-focal actors' experiences of e-Government in the SADC?*
- iii. How do the identified factors that influence e-Government services adoption relate?*
- iv. How do these participants' perceptions of e-Government factors differ by country in SADC?*
- v. How can the e-Government adoption be enhanced in the region?*

1.7 Integrated Research Question

To what extent do stakeholders' voices and perceptions facilitate the understanding of e-Government adoption predictors in the SADC, using the developmental mixed method?

1.8 Research Aim

The study, therefore, aimed at investigating e-Government adoption predictors and examined the possibilities of increasing e-Government adoption in the SADC.

1.9 Research Objectives

To achieve the aim, the objectives of the study were to:

- i. Investigate the dynamic interaction of human and non- human e-Government actors in the SADC to identify opportunities that promote the adoption of e-Government in SADC*
- ii. Develop a SADC e-Government framework that takes into cognisance the technical, contextual, social, cultural dimensions and multiplicity of stakeholders involved.*

1.10 Chapter Outline

Chapter 1: The problem and its setting - The chapter sets the scene by discussing the context of what has been and not achieved in e-Government setting. The chapter discusses: the background to the study, statement of the problem, objectives, research questions, delimitations and limitations, and the significance of the study.

Chapter 2: Setting the SADC Context - This chapter explains the key concepts of the study and then examines the Southern African Development Community context. In addition, the chapter reviews the existing related e-Government literature to elicit the e-Government experiences

from within and outside the Southern African Development Community member states from empirical studies.

Chapter 3: The central theoretical perspectives - Chapter 3 situates the research within the matrix of theories that underpin the study facilitating the context of explaining the problem under study. Consequently, an e-Government framework and its components are proposed to guide the study.

Chapter 4: Research Design and Methodology - The Chapter discusses the TAMANT assumptions framework that informs the methodological decisions taken to carry the study through. The framework includes the ontological, epistemological, lenses, and methodology assumptions of the study. In addition, the quality aspects of the study are also explained and interrogated.

Chapter 5: Qualitative Data Analysis and interpretation - - The chapter discusses the processes that were used to collect and analyse the pilot and main qualitative data. Additionally, the chapter foregrounds the lessons learnt from the pilot study and how they informed the enhancements, and rigour of the main qualitative study. The chapter also brought to fore how the pilot and main qualitative studies formed the basis of the quantitative study instrument in the succeeding chapter.

Chapter 6: Quantitative data Analysis and Interpretation - The chapter discusses the processes used to collect and analyse the pilot and main study quantitative data.

Chapter 7: Answering Research questions - The chapter presents the findings through cross-referencing, and establishing interconnections and meanings resulting from the qualitative and quantitative data analysis and the key questions of the study.

Chapter 8: Conclusions, Implications and limitations of the study Based on the data analysis the chapter makes inferences of the data analysis results to the objectives of the study. In addition, the chapter discusses the study implications to the stakeholders and that which inhibited the achievement of the objectives.

Chapter 9: Evaluation of the study- The chapter evaluates the study and how it contributed to the to the e-Government knowledge. Consequently, an e-Government Framework validated in the SADC is presented as the singular contribution to the frontiers of knowledge in e-Government.

1.11 Chapter Summary

Chapter one outlined the problem of inquiry with emphasis on the existing literature on e-Government. Whilst e-Government has arrived in Africa, its success is yet to be enjoyed in some countries as what sets them apart is the technological infrastructure that each country adopts. However, the chapter outlined that national technological infrastructural inadequacy need not be used as the only pointer to low e-Government adoption. Rather, unpacking the complexity of e-Government and embracing the multiplicity of actors and their roles in creating an e-Government experience was found to be imperative. The study acknowledges the methodological gap created by the dearth in the extant literature of studies that seek to understand the dynamic interaction between the human and non-human actors in e-Government adoption. The paucity of such literature with reference to the SADC region was acknowledged and the current study was motivated to fill in this gap.

Chapter 2 weaves in the e-Government experiences in the SADC for a sharper understanding of the context under which the phenomenon was investigated. The chapter also shares the experiences from outside the SADC in order to benchmark the possible solutions against the SADC e-Government problem.

2 SETTING THE SADC CONTEXT

2.1 Introduction

This chapter sets the scene by first explaining the key concepts of the study. Secondly, it sets the Southern African Development Community context by reviewing the e-Government experiences within and outside the Southern African Development Community member states from empirical studies.

2.2 Defining the key concepts of the study

This section unpacks concepts such as e-Government, e-Government adoption, service, and value as used in the study so that the readers resonate with the discussions thereof.

2.2.1 Service, e-service and value

Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) have been defined as technologies that include the internet, intranets, and extranets and those that improve services and operations in an organization (Gupta, Dasgupta & Gupta, 2008, p. 140; Schuppan, 2009, p. 119). The use of ICTs has enhanced the service provision, efficiency, flexibility, and accountability amongst other benefits. The terms 'service' and 'e-service' are widely used in e-Government scholarly articles but they are hardly defined. Borrowing from the marketing literature, there is also a close connection between a 'service' and 'value' (Grönroos, 2008). Similarly, Grönroos (2006, p. 324) posits that whilst a service is a process and the good a resource, they both facilitate value creation.

An e-service is "a technical artefact that is typically internet-based and connected to other information systems" of which accessibility and usability are key aspects (Lindgren & Jansson, 2013). The study draws particular attention to the phrase 'typically internet-based' within the definition of an e-Service. The word internet-based is qualified by the word "typically", implying that the internet is just one of the ways through which an 'e-service' could be provided. Hence, in the present study, an e-service is taken to mean a service that is electronically mediated.

There are three aspects to a service as used in marketing literature:

- i. *Service as an activity* - a process where a service provider does something to assist a customer (Grönroos, 2008, p. 300). A typical example is the provision of mobile or Internet apps to citizens for checking and payment of municipality bills.
- ii. *Service as facilitator of the customer's value creation* - relates to the way customers create value for themselves (Grönroos, 2008; Grönroos, 2011). In this case the provider gives the context (resources and processes such as information, activities and goods) and

the customer uses his/her skills to engage with the service to create value (Grönroos, 2008, pp. 301–302). An example of service as a customer perspective or logic is when the customer manages to use the provided app and successfully pays for a municipality bill. This is known as self-service as the customer managed to achieve his/her goal using only the services provided by a service provider. In self-service, the customer is without neither the assistance nor intervention of the service provider. However, as is in the case that the customer pays for the municipality bill over the counter, then it becomes a full service. The role of the customer included supplying the person at the counter with the necessary details (such as account number and account name) to process the payment.

- iii. *Service as the provider's creation of value supporting strategies (provider service logic)* - relates to how the supply side provides value-creating strategies to support customers' service consumption (Grönroos, 2008, p. 302). A typical example is the provision of the e-filing systems and its interactive processes to the taxpayer.

With the service being an enabler of value creation, it is imperative that the supply side/service provider understand the needs and activities in the value chain of the demand side to inform the kind of services that can create demand-side perceived value (Ravald & Grönroos, 1996). The perceived value for customers (value-in-use) has been defined as the benefits they get after using the service (Grönroos, 2008), including getting efficient and effective responses (Savoldelli, Codagnone & Misuraca, 2014). The concept of value creation extends the one that focuses on the sacrifice the customer has to make to encompass the commitment of both the provider and consumer of the service in influencing the customer's perception of value episode (Ravald & Grönroos, 1996). The customers integrate the resources in the context and their technology skills to create value for themselves, whilst the providers facilitate the creation of value by providing the context (Grönroos, 2011).

2.2.2 E-Government

E-Government has become so pervasive that it forms part of the investment portfolio in many governments. Conceptualising the term e-Government is still nascent despite it being widely used in scholarly articles and it being defined in different ways mirroring various contexts by various researchers in different epochs (Grant & Chau, 2005). See Table 2-1 for the variations.

Table 2-1: e-Government definition(s)

Author(s)	Definition of e-Government	Focus
(Fang, 2002, p. 1)	The use of most innovative ICTs in the provision of: accessible quality services to citizens; and enhancing stakeholder participation	The focus is on the provision of quality services and e-participation using innovative ICTs
(InfoDev & The Centre for Democracy and Technology, 2002, p. 1)	“Use of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) to transform government by making it more accessible, effective and accountable”	Improving accessibility, effectiveness and accountability
(Schware & Deane, 2003, p. 10; The World Bank, 2004, p. 1; Wang & Liao, 2008, p. 718)	The use of ICTs in changing the how the government stakeholders relate	Transformation of relationships through the use of ICTs
(Grant & Chau, 2005, pp. 748–749)	E-Government seeks to enforce the potential of Information technology in the delivery of Government services at all levels (such as local and national)	The use of IT in enhancing service delivery
(Cocchiglia & Vernaschi, 2008, p. 7)	“Public sector’s use of Information and Communication Technologies for transactions and information exchange with citizens, business, governments, and every other institution in society”	Use of ICTs in transacting and information exchange amongst actors,
(Helbig et al., 2009, p. 6)	The use of ICTs to support efficient service delivery, or enhance public policies and stakeholder engagement.	Enhancement of public policies and d service delivery, and citizen engagement
(Zimbabwe Ministry of Information Communication Technology, 2010, p. 5)	“Use of information and communication technology to provide and improve government services, transactions and interactions with citizens, businesses and other arms of government”	Enhancement of service delivery and interactions amongst stakeholders
(Abu-Shanab, 2013)	Use of ICTs, to provide citizens need-based services, improves performance and public participation.	The use of IT in enhancing service delivery and e-participation
(UN, 2014, p. 2)	The usage and application of ICTs in “public administration to streamline and integrate workflows and processes, to effectively manage data and information, enhance public service delivery, as well as expand communication channels for engagement and empowerment of the people”	Enhancement of service delivery, data management, communication channels for engagement and citizenry empowerment

As shown in Table 2-1, the conceptualisations of e-Government vary from enhancement of service delivery to a combination of improved information exchange; citizen engagement; transacting, the transformation of relationships amongst involved actors including businesses, government agencies and citizens; and transformation of the government. According to Cocchiglia and Vernaschi (2008, pp. 6–7); Yildiz (2007), amongst the reasons of e-Government initiative failures is the inadequacy in the conceptualisation of the phenomenon. These scholars argue that narrow conceptualisations challenge the full potential of the

phenomenon, whereas unrealistic conceptualisations may lead to failures at the actualisation of e-Government. E-Government is not only about service provision but providing e-services that are usable by the citizenry (OECD, 2009). Similarly, Grant and Chau (2005) state that the definition of e-Government has surpassed that of focus on service delivery to that of interactions amongst e-Government actors. In an endeavour to increase interactions, there is a need to also convert those interactions into engagements for empowerment to happen, thus confirming the UN (2014) definition of e-Government.

Relationship marketing in the context of e-Government can be considered as a competitive strategy of cajoling the citizenry into using 'e' services. To achieve e-Government services usability, Governments as facilitators of value creation should ensure that the resources and the interactive processes that they provide are human-centred in an endeavour to allow for value creation by the very citizenry as they interact with the services. Such efforts have a bearing on service adoption. It is against this background that in the present study, e-Government is perceived as the use of ICTs to enhance service delivery, channels for engagement amongst stakeholders, and value creation. The present e-Government definition takes as the first tenet the enhancement of service delivery in which it is expected that the supply side provides an enhanced context as a way of facilitating value creation. The second tenet is the enhancement of channels of engagement which is intended to promote and encourage dialogue and capture the human needs in an endeavour to make the third tenet come to fruition. Emphasis on the need for citizenry-centricity in e-Government conceptualizations towards the enhancement of the adoption of the phenomenon by the demand side is critical. That is e-Government adoption is expected to be improved when the needs of the citizens are addressed through the services that are launched by the supply side and the citizens are able to create the value in use.

2.2.3 Intermediaries and actors

Commonly known as go-betweens or middlemen, intermediaries bring together two or more parties together through interaction. Callon (1990, p. 134) states that "an intermediary is anything passing between actors which defines the relationship between them". For example, the service that the government provides as the context is the intermediary between the government and its citizens, the skills that the citizens has in creating the value is what hooks the two parties together. In e-Government, ICT adoption can be used as a vehicle to model 'digital citizens' through the digital interactions that occur between Governments and other stakeholders. These interactions can be between: Government and Citizens (*GnC*) and its reverse, Governments and Businesses(*GnB*) and its reverse, and within and across Government agencies (*GnG*) (The World Bank, 2004; UN, 2005, p. 15, 2014, p. 2; Chun, Luna-Reyes & Sandoval-Almazán, 2012, p. 7).

The four types of intermediaries in circulation in interactions are: firstly, the literal inscriptions that circulate on paper or digitally. Examples of such include books, reports, articles, patents and notes. The second type is the technical artefacts that include machines, robots, and consumer goods. These are known to be stable, structured groups of non-humans. Thirdly, is a group comprising of human beings, their skills, knowledge, and know-how that they incorporate. The fourth is money in all its forms (Callon, 1990, p. 135). The four types of intermediaries are expected to manifest in e-Government. The use of e-books, e-offices, pamphlets, flyers, websites, and mobile technology, and online payments is imperative. Most commonly, the interactions would be digital (e-intermediaries). Their role is critical in e-Government ecosystems. The e-intermediaries in e-Government provide decentralised points of accessing and interacting with the Governments and improving the availability of e-Government services.

“An actor is an entity that associates the different types of intermediaries such as texts, human, non-humans, and money” (Callon, 1990, p. 135). Actors must have some agency, modifying/transforming or making a difference to the state of the art (Callon, 1990; Latour, 2005) wherein intermediaries both order and form the medium of the network they describe, making an actor synonymous to an intermediary (Callon, 1990, p. 135). The actors include governments, citizens and businesses (Grant & Chau, 2005; Bertot, Jaeger & McClure, 2008; Rowley, 2011), immigrants, government employees, international users/ service users (Bertot et al., 2008), enterprises, government agencies, e-Government project managers, designers, IT developers, researchers and evaluators (Rowley, 2011), associations between humans, and associations between non-humans (Callon, 1990, p. 140). Not only are the actors human, but they can also be technological and organisational resources or processes.

2.2.4 E-Government Adoption

The study was centred on the adoption of e-Government; hence this subsequent section explains the adoption concept as used in the study. Governments are expected to improve e-Government adoption by both the citizenry and the supply side (providers) of which its realization would be made possible by having a citizens need and expectations based understanding (Bertot & Jaeger, 2008; Bertot, Jaeger & McClure, 2008; Jacob *et al.*, 2019). Understanding e-Government adoption is two-fold. Firstly, there is adoption by the supply side, and secondly, that of the demand side. The former is the launch of e-Government initiatives by agencies and the latter is the actual usage of e-Government services by the citizens and business (Reddick, 2005; Bertot, Jaeger & McClure, 2008, p. 138; Lee, Kim & Ahn, 2011; Lim *et al.*, 2011, p. 111; Abu-Shanab, 2014). However, “the context in which users and providers of e-Government services reside is at a crossroads” (Editorial, 2006, p. 164), largely owing to e-Government perspectives that are often explored separately (Reddick, 2005). This separation is

evidenced in the low adoption of e-Government services by the users, particularly in developing countries (Heeks, 2002b, 2003; Mutula, 2008; Al-Hujran, Al-Dalahmeh & Aloudat, 2011; Jonathan & Rusu, 2019) and in many other governments (Belanger & Carter, 2008; Gupta, Dasgupta & Gupta, 2008; Rana & Dwivedi, 2015). Based on the perspectives of the demand side, scholars define adoption to mean the unidirectional constructs, including intent to use e-services (Carter & Bélanger, 2005) and willingness to use e-services (Gilbert, Balestrini & Littleboy, 2004); intention to engage in e-services (Warkentin *et al.*, 2002; Bwalya & Healy, 2010), and behavioural intention (Carter, Schaupp and Evans, 2008, p. 159; Abu-Shanab, 2017). However, Kumar *et al.* (2007, p. 69) perceive adoption as a combination of multi-directional constructs selected from: the decision to use e-services; frequency of usage of e-services; scope of usage of the e-services with reference to the e-Government maturity stages; and preference of the medium of interaction with the government such as choice of interacting through the website over telephone. Regardless of technical merits, and the facilitation levels, it is the user's decision to adopt some technology/service or not. Also, what informs the decision vary with the technology, the user, and the context (Davis, Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1989; Mathieson, 1991, p. 173; InfoDev & The Centre for Democracy and Technology, 2002, p. 5). The existing literature shows that there are numerous and varied determinants for e-Government adoption (Yonazi, Sol & Boonstra, 2010, p. 175) and these are not 'one-size' fit all in all national contexts (Alomari, Woods & Sandhu, 2012, p. 208).

2.2.5 E-Government service maturity stages

The e-Government service maturity stages/phase models have been extensively researched with the commonly agreed stages as shown in Table 2-2. Each stage determines the level of advances in technology and the level of interactions amongst the stakeholders. (Moon, 2002). However, the stages need not be followed sequentially as shown in Table 2-2 though it is a common sequence amongst agencies (InfoDev & The Centre for Democracy and Technology, 2002). It is therefore important that researchers find out to what extent governments incorporate the necessary features/services at these stages (West, 2004, p. 17). In addition, in which the government is in need not matter, rather finding ways of increasing adoption at a particular stage (Shareef *et al.*, 2011, 2014).

Table 2-2: Government service maturity stages

Stage	Description
Stage 1 : The billboard stage	Information flows in one direction (Layne & Lee, 2001, p. 124; InfoDev & The Centre for Democracy and Technology, 2002, p. 2; Moon, 2002, p. 426; Santos & Heeks, 2003; West, 2004, p. 17)
Stage 2 : The interact stage	Services tend to be interactive (users can search for information, fill online forms). However, accessibility issues still persist (information still presented in a mono language) (Layne & Lee, 2001, p. 124; InfoDev & The Centre for Democracy and Technology, 2002, p. 2; Moon, 2002, p. 426; Santos & Heeks, 2003; West, 2004, p. 17)
Stage 3 : The transact stage	At this stage, Online transactions can be done fully online. (InfoDev & The Centre for Democracy and Technology, 2002, p. 2; Moon, 2002, p. 426; Santos & Heeks, 2003; West, 2004, p. 17)

2.3 E-Government potential

The e-Government benefits are not just about harnessing ICTs by the agencies but to efficiently and effectively provide services (InfoDev & The Centre for Democracy and Technology, 2002; The World Bank, 2004; Editorial, 2006; OECD, 2009, p. 114). The e-Government initiatives need to be citizen-centred to provide public value innovatively in order for governments to communicate with and serve its people (Editorial, 2006; Bertot et al., 2008). Public services facilitate the creation of public value (Alford & Flynn, 2008, p. 9). According to Lindgren and Jansson (2013, p. 9) public organisations are” formal entities that decide on and organise public administration”. E-Government has the potential to promote efficiency (Heeks, 2002a, p. 18; Schware & Deane, 2003; Ndou, 2004; UN, 2014, p. 2); improve quality of decision making (Ndou, 2004; Chun, Luna-Reyes & Sandoval-Almazán, 2012, p. 7); enhance transparency, anti-corruption, and accountability (Schware & Deane, 2003; Ndou, 2004; The World Bank, 2004; Colesca & Dobrica, 2008; UN, 2014, p. 2); reduce bureaucracy; cut costs (The World Bank, 2004; Chen *et al.*, 2006, p. 24; Colesca & Dobrica, 2008; OECD, 2010); improve the quality of public service provision (Ndou, 2004; Colesca & Dobrica, 2008; Bwalya, 2009, p. 2; Schuppan, 2009, p. 120; UN, 2014, p. 2; Magayane, Mokuia & Lanrong, 2016, p. 47); afford greater convenience, increase and capture revenues efficiently (such as taxes, fines and licence fees) (InfoDev & The Centre for Democracy and Technology, 2002; Schware & Deane, 2003; The World Bank, 2004; Schuppan, 2009, pp. 120–121), engage the citizenry through collaboration, knowledge and information sharing (Heeks, 2002a, p. 6; Chun, Luna-Reyes & Sandoval-Almazán, 2012, p. 6; Ruhode, 2013; UN, 2014, p. 2; Magayane, Mokuia & Lanrong, 2016, p. 47), increase state effectiveness (Heeks, 2002a, p. 18; Schuppan, 2009, p. 120) increase efficiency of service provision (Chen *et al.*, 2006, p. 24; Pina, Torres & Royo, 2010, p. 3; UN, 2014, p. 2; Magayane, Mokuia & Lanrong, 2016, p. 47), promote green governments, skills delopment, capacity building for sustainable development, employment opportunities and provision of better health and education (UN, 2014, p. 2).

Of these benefits, transparency, accountability, reduction of corruption, cultivation of e-cultures, and strengthened democracy are indirect beneficial products of e-Government. In totality, these e-Government benefits contribute to promoting governance and public administration. The underlying contribution that these facets make to e-Government is the effectiveness and efficiency in state administration (InfoDev & The Centre for Democracy and Technology, 2002; Schuppan, 2009, p. 118). Thus, e-Government in a broader perspective encompasses all the key factors of good and efficient governance (Gupta, Dasgupta & Gupta, 2008, p. 141).

2.4 The Southern African Development Community (SADC) setting

This study focuses on the Southern African Development Community (SADC) which was initially established as the Southern African Development Coordination Conference (SADCC). The formation of this Southern African bloc is indebted to the common historical, political, economic, social and cultural experiences that affected the peoples of the region. The launch of the SADCC in 1980 on the 1st of April in Lusaka, Zambia, was a sequel to the political independence of the majority-ruled states in the region. However, colonialism left a trail of economic dependence and conflicts that were prohibitive to the development and growth of the region. Hence, the SADCC was mandated with the task of fighting against apartheid, reduction of economic dependency, and a fight for the equitable regional integration (SADC, 1998, n.d b).

2.4.1 Southern African Development Community

The SADCC made great strides in forging a regional identity to the Southern African fraternity and defeating apartheid. However, the SADCC fell short of meeting one of its core objectives: the region's economic integration. The establishment of the SADC was inaugurated on August, 17th 1992 with ten (10) member states namely: Tanzania, Angola, Zambia, Mozambique, Zimbabwe, Botswana, Namibia, Swaziland, Malawi and Lesotho (SADC, 1998). To date, the community comprises of fifteen (15) countries including the Democratic Republic of Congo, Madagascar, Seychelles, South Africa, and Mauritius with Seychelles, Madagascar and Mauritius being islands in the Indian Ocean as illustrated in Figure 2-1.

The convergence of these countries was necessitated by a vision of a shared future: the need to drive regional integration and cooperation that would facilitate development and economic growth, poverty alleviation, enhancement of the standards and quality of life of the peoples in the region, balance equity and mutual long term benefits in Southern Africa. This entailed ensuring regional approaches and harmonization of the sector policies and plans for the different protocols that the member states were to engage in; promotion of the development of human resources, transfer and mastery of technology (SADC, 1998, pp. 5–6).

Figure 2-1: SADC member states
 Source: (Adapted from <http://www.sadc.int/member-states/>)

2.4.2 The role of ICT in the SADC agenda

In support of the declaration by the SADC, Tambo (2004) posits that there is evidence from the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries that a balance in investment policy and ICTs is a determinant in the facilitation of the economic growth process. ICTs have not only been perceived as tools that have an impact positively on the mainstream development objectives (such as health, education, changing livelihoods, digital divide-reduction, empowerment) but also have an impact on the productivity and enhancement of intranational economies and the world at large (Kundishora, n.d, p. 3; Tambo, 2004, p. 4). The SADC secretariat also acknowledged the need for the development of policies for the ICTs to have a substantial impact on the region’s core objectives. As a consequence of this acknowledgment, an e-SADC strategy framework was adopted in Luanda, Angola, in May 2010 (SADC, n.d). It is the SADC overarching regional agenda on co-operation and integration, the e-SADC strategy framework and the SADC 2001 declaration of the ICT policy and strategy that member states should use as resources to drive their national agendas towards the

enhancement of e-Government adoption and economic growth. In this regard, the SADC member states are mandated to derive their country ICT visions and strategic agendas from the community agenda in context. Table 2-3 reflects some of the visions or strategic agenda from selected SADC countries.

Table 2-3: Extract of some of the SADC member states' ICT visions or strategic agendas

Country	ICT Vision or Strategic agenda
South Africa	"South Africa as a global leader in the development and use of information and communication technologies for socio-economic development" (Management_of_the_Department_of Communications, no date, p. 11)
Mauritius	Make the" ICT the fifth pillar of the economy and transform Mauritius into a regional ICT hub" (Gillwald & Islam, 2014, p. 17).
Namibia Is to be a world-class institution in creating an inclusive information society to promote knowledge for development and to establish Namibia as a recognized regional hub in Southern Africa (Namibia_MICT & Palladium_Strategy_Consultants, 2009, p. 7)
Zambia	"A Zambia transformed into an information and knowledge-based society and economy supported by consistent development of, and pervasive access to ICTs by all citizens by 2030" (Zambia_Min_Communication_and_Transport, 2006, p. 19).
Zimbabwe	"A knowledge-based society with ubiquitous connectivity by 2020" (Zimbabwe_MICT, 2015, p. 11)

The extract ICT visions or strategic agendas in Table 2-3 convey visions that extend beyond the country. Except for visions like the one from Zambia that was coined based on its local agenda (at country level) and directly speaking to the infrastructure development and improvement of the accessibility of the services by stakeholders, the rest speak to the region, the global context, or both. The latter largely mirrors the tendency by the SADC member states to pander to regional or global imperatives so as to remain competitive in the regional or global context, neglecting the local imperatives. Grant and Chau (2005) suggest that key factors that drive the success of e-Government are the country e-Government visions and strategic agendas from which the focus of e-Government is derived. The country visions and strategic agenda need to be realistic for their actualisation.

However, the actualisation of the ICT visions of the SADC member states is far in the horizon according to the International Telecommunication Union's ICT Development Index (IDI) of 2016 (see Table 2-4). The IDI is calculated on the basis of three measures: Access to and Use of ICTs and ICT skills weighted at 40%, 40% and 20 % respectively.

Table 2-4: SADC member States IDI ranking 2016

Economy	SADC Ranking	Global Ranking	IDI Rank 2016	Access Sub Index	Use Sub Index	Skills Sub Index
Mauritius	1	73	5.55	6.86	3.78	6.45
Seychelles	2	87	5.03	6.81	3.37	4.79
South Africa	3	88	5.03	5.46	4.00	6.23
Botswana	4	108	4.17	4.33	3.26	5.69
Namibia	5	120	3.64	4.25	2.91	3.85
Zimbabwe	6	133	2.78	3.35	1.91	3.38
Lesotho	7	134	2.76	3.41	1.80	3.37
Swaziland	8	136	2.73	3.28	1.61	3.86
Zambia	9	147	2.22	2.84	1.17	3.06
Angola	10	154	2.03	2.76	1.10	2.43
Mozambique	11	163	1.75	2.90	0.62	1.71
Madagascar	12	166	1.69	2.39	0.44	2.77
Tanzania	13	167	1.65	2.65	0.30	2.33
Malawi	14	168	1.62	2.03	0.86	2.30
DRC	15	170	1.50	1.83	0.41	3.01

Source: (Adapted from ITU, 2016)

The SADC region's Mauritius, Seychelles and South Africa are leading both the African and the SADC groups. Table 2-4 reflects that only Mauritius, Seychelles and South Africa are above the *Global IDI Average* (4.94); Botswana, Namibia, Zimbabwe, Lesotho, and Swaziland are above the Africa IDI average with the rest falling below the Africa IDI average. The differences in e-Government strategic decisions and in infrastructural investments have become a contributing factor to the digital divide amongst the developing and between developed countries. These visionary, strategic agendas and contextual application differences increase the difficulty in assessment, explanation, and comparison of e-Government efforts.

2.4.3 SADC Countries Websites

Countries such as Zimbabwe and Namibia had their level e-Government found at the billboard stage (Ruhode et al., 2008; Tomlinson & Rabina, 2011; Mhlanga, 2013). The Lesotho and Namibian Government portal and website respectively focus more on government centeredness. Tanzania has a low penetration of ICT spending and high mobile phone penetration (Yonazi, Sol, & Boonstra, 2010; Wangwe, Eloff, & Venter, 2012; Yonazi, 2013). The Tanzanian government ministries have websites in stages one and two of the e-Government maturity models and the national website of Tanzania is in English and Swahili (Kaaya, 2003; Magayane, Mokuia & Lanrong, 2016).

The SADC countries websites have been found to be prone to use English as the language of communication (Akakandelwa, 2011). In this regard, Magayane et al. (2016) argue that of the 51 websites for ministries and government agencies in Tanzania that the scholars studied, 63% were in both English and Kiswahili; 33% were in English and 4% in Kiswahili forcing the users to

apply and work in the language provided on the site. The scholars argue that the bilingual nature of most websites in Tanzania owes this to the recognition of both languages as official languages. E-Government in Angola, Botswana, Lesotho, Madagascar, Malawi, and Seychelles is at the billboard stage where information is static and unidirectional. E-literacy is critical in improving citizens' ability to access and use e-information yet it is lacking in these countries (Ngulube, 2007). Despite having invested in e-Government initiatives, governments cannot justify these investments as the adoption of the initiatives is low (Al-Adawi, Yousafzai & Pallister, 2005).

2.4.4 E-Government experiences in the SADC

UN (2014) reports that Mauritius had a very high score in the whole e-Government apparatus and has invested heavily in infrastructure, communication and education resulting in the improvement of the country's Human Capital Index and the EGDI ranking. Mauritius is a small island and is leading in EGDI amongst 54 African countries surveyed. The country has also invested in its online portal accessible at www.gov.mu. The portal affords its citizens a vast number of services based on the ministry, department, domain, target persons and parastatals. In addition, it offers the citizens access to blogs, chat rooms, media library, discussion forums and platform for e-participation (UN, 2014, p. 23). The United Nations found that Mauritius is still leading the region in 2018 despite dropping from rank 58 to 66 of 193 countries. The findings on the Mauritius e-Government initiative give impetus to this study as it provides the citizenry the voice through blogs, chat rooms and discussion forums. By so doing, the concerned department could capture the needs, suggestions and reservations of the people. On the other hand, Zambia, one of the countries with middle EGDI in the SADC offers the Mwana mHealth (health services provided through mobile technology) programme. The technology provides early infant HIV diagnosis and sends SMSs via the mobile network. However the adoption of this service by citizens is not known (UNICEF Zambia, 2012). Bwalya, Du Plessis, and Rensleigh (2014) claim that the barriers to citizen interaction in e-Government in Zambia include unavailability of and cost internet access points lack of awareness strategies to educate the citizens on the benefits of e-Government; and lack of language diversity in presenting the information (Bwalya, 2009).

Bwalya and Healy (2010) posit that Botswana has made some strides in investing in infrastructure evidenced by the setting up of the Kgalagadi optical fibre network and *Botswana* IT hub. In addition, the country has dedicated ICT policy, regulatory and institutional frameworks (p. 26).

In terms of access to electricity, South Africa and Tanzania have more than two-thirds of the households and less than twenty percent of households connected to the electricity grid respectively. As a consequence, computer usage in South Africa is high with the preferred place of access being the home, whereas in Tanzania computer usage is very low (less than 2%) and the preferred place of access is the internet café (Stork, Calandro & Gillwald, 2012). The South African government has embraced the need for the ICTs and have invested significantly toward the enhancement of service quality, standards and efficiency. The country boasts of an e-procurement system developed by an Independent Electoral Commission (IEC), and the IEC leverages tools that allow for free and fair elections (Mutula & Mostert, 2010b). Despite high e-Government ranking amongst the SADC member states, Kaisara and Pather (2011) posit that there are some challenges that South Africa is currently faces including a massive digital divide and low internet uptake. In this regard, the government of South Africa has been determined to curb this challenge through various policies and the continued government support in the growth of the ICT industry (Kaisara and Panther, 2011 p. 213). Despite having poverty alleviation programmes such as Reconstruction and Development Programme (RDP) in place, and the service delivery principle “Batho Pele”, South Africa continues to have traces of poor service delivery (Mutula & Mostert, 2010b). Some of the challenges include poverty, inequality, corruption, insecurity, illiteracy, lack of skilled technical labour, digital divide as alluded to by Kaisara and Pather (2011), accessibility Meyer (2007); and also systems integration issues (Mutula & Mostert, 2010b).

Stork et al. (2012, p. 13) argue that amongst the eleven countries that were studied on internet access and usage, the involved participants (non-internet users) from SADC member countries namely South Africa, Botswana, Tanzania, and Namibia, expressed that their lack of usage of the internet was driven by lack of internet connectivity. The participants (non-internet users) from Namibia also stated that their lack of internet usage owed to the lack of skills and costly internet as alluded to by UN (2014). In Tanzania citizens are conversant and satisfied with services provided through mobile phones. The services include Sim-Banking, Mobile Money (M-Pesa, TigoPesa, and AirTel Monet), mobile money payments (e.g. DSTV payment), buying of electricity credits through Tanzania National Electricity Corporation (TANESCO), Higher education online applications and admissions through Tanzania Commission for Universities (TCU) website (<http://www.tcu.go.tz/>). Other e-Government initiatives in Tanzania though still at a low scale, include electronic revenue collection (e.g. Electronic Fiscal Devices by Tanzania Revenue Authority), payment of water bills using mobile phones (DAWASCO), VAT registration at Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA) using ITAX (Integrated Tax Administration System in Tanzania), provision of online results for secondary school teachers and colleges in Tanzania through the National Examinations Council in Tanzania (NECTA). However, examination results

publication (by the National Examination Council), Higher Education loan application (HESLB) indicate a seasonal high rate of adoption (Yonazi, Sol & Boonstra, 2010a; Yonazi, 2013). Through ITAX, transparency and tax revenue increased, processing time and corruption have been significantly reduced (Schuppan, 2009).

Yonazi, Sol, and Boonstra (2010) posit that the perceived organisational preparedness, citizen preparedness, service intrinsic issues, access limitations, and organisational context are challenges that influence adoption of e-Government initiatives in Tanzania based on their investigation of three organisations namely the National Examinations Council of Tanzania (NECTA), Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA) Ministry of Finance and Economic Affairs (MoFEA). The factors affecting the adoption of e-Government in Tanzania include lack of awareness, low ICT skills, culture, perceived unpreparedness of the provider of services (poor customer service, lack of infrastructure, lack of policies), poor service quality (ease of use, user-friendliness, accessibility, affordability and availability through multi-channel using multi-languages), reliability, trust (security and privacy of data online), digital divide, frequent power outage (Rukiza *et al.*, n.d; Bakilana, 2009; Yonazi, Sol & Boonstra, 2010a; Yonazi, 2013).

A recent study of the *Zimbabwe* e-Government context was carried out by Ruhode (2013) with a focus on how the Ministry of Tourism and Hospitality responds to the e-Government strategy through information sharing with national and international ministries, departments, and institutions. The scholar posits that the Ministry of Tourism and Hospitality in Zimbabwe shares information through letters, face to face interactions, mail, internet chat and telephone but mostly they use traditional channels which cause delays in service delivery. Amongst the inhibitors of e-Government success in Zimbabwe is a lack of resources, political uncertainty, poor energy infrastructure, bureaucracy, restrictive policies, and inadequate technological Infrastructure (p.190). Cocchiglia and Vernaschi (2008); Ruhode (2013) argue that political instability effectively hinders the e-Government implementation as it contributes to public mistrust of their government. Ruhode used a critical realism paradigm and collected data through interviews. However, the interviews were focused on the supply side personnel such as the permanent secretary and director in the ICT ministry; director in the research, infrastructure development and management (ICT Ministry); and director in the office of the president (e-Government services). The stride was applauded though it fell short of understanding the levels of e-Government adoption from the demand side.

2.5 E-Government success

The success of e-Government in the developing world has always been reported in varying degrees as low. Based on 40 e-Government cases from the developing countries, Heeks (2003)

found that the success rate was very low with 85% of the projects being partial or total failures owing to the design-reality gaps. The scholar argued that there is a tendency of hard-soft gaps wherein at design time e-Government is seen only as harnessing of technologies whereas in reality people, politics, emotions and culture populate the local actuality. The technical and the social were clearly treated as dichotomies. Heeks (2002b) stressed that the difference between the two in terms of technology dimension was that the former was 'an enabling mechanism' (Heeks, 2002b, p. 107) whereas the latter was a 'complex value-laden entity' (Heeks, 2002b, p. 107). To rub salt into an open wound, the existence of country context gaps looms large (Heeks, 2003, p. 5) which the scholar captured in the catchy phrase: 'Think Global, Act local.' The phrase largely mirrors the propensity by the SADC member states to pander to global imperatives to remain competitive in the global context, neglecting the local imperatives. However, there are some counties like Tanzania whose endeavours in advancing the language diversity in their websites are acknowledged in the study. Unpacking the study key concepts of service, value, and e-Government adoption concepts in relation to the e-Government success compelled the current study to investigate further the essential role played by the end user of the e-Government services in determining the success of the adoption of the phenomenon.

2.6 Understanding the local contexts: Best practices

Gupta, Dasgupta and Gupta (2008, p. 141) posit that there is a challenge of scaling up e-Government infrastructure development and initiatives in underserved spaces such as the rural areas. As a solution, the government's creativity and responsiveness is called upon in the endeavour to improve accessibility and reduction of the digital divide gap. The World Bank (2004) suggests the enhancement of service delivery through reduction of bureaucratic procedures, one-stop shop portals, promoting services through rural kiosks either government or privately owned and publishing rules and procedures to increase transparency is not just the service delivery to the citizens but its enhancement using ICTs. ITU (2016) acknowledged the great increase in mobile cellular penetration in Tanzania, South Africa and by a slight margin in Namibia; and a considerable increase in mobile broadband penetration in Botswana and Namibia. It is evident in this regard that enhanced access to the mobile intermediaries would improve the e-Government potential in the SADC if coupled with e-Government awareness campaigns.

Lobo and Balakrishnan (2002) stated that the Department of Revenue, of the Government of Karnataka in India, set up a Bhoomi project to provide farmers with the Record of Rights, Tenancy and Cultivation (RTC). The Bhoomi centres are computerized land record kiosks. Traditionally, to get the RTC a farmer needed to seek the services of the village accountant and the process was marked with delays, bribery and harassment. The introduction of the Bhoomi

project saw the Village Accountant being available full-time at these kiosks. An empirical assessment of Bhoomi service centres in India was carried out as part of the Governance Knowledge Sharing Programme of The World Bank using a Report Card and interviews. The data was collected from six districts namely Bijapur, Koppal, Hassan, Udipi, Chamrajnagar and Mandya representatives of regions in Karnataka. The benefits of the Bhoomi centres included reduced average waiting time to get the certificates; reduced weighted average value of bribes paid; reduced queuing time to get the needed documents and timely response on complaints. The Bhoomi kiosk was expected to be extended to disseminate information on the disadvantaged and the vulnerable. Voutinioti (2013) reiterates the effect of citizen service centres at local government and their role as intermediaries in building relationships between the government and citizens.

Industrial countries provide e-Services through a self-service delivery model whereas in developing countries it is a mix of automated and manual processes. A lesson is learnt from Bahia, in Brazil. Instead of self-service, bringing together a number of e-Government services to one centre where citizens congregate would be convenient for citizens. However, some services may still be accessed at the government offices as the as a country gradually transitions to fully automated processes.

The Karnataka and Bahia case studies in India and Brazil respectively provide support to the study in that the former offers the e-Government services to the most neglected population namely the rural folk and the latter helps develop insights as to how the governments can innovatively address the needs of a diverse population. This also brings to fore the need by Governments to understand the context of their countries, and ensuring that their people to garner sufficient trust in the undertaking. The two case studies confirm the finding that kiosks and mobile centres can be used as opportunities where there are infrastructural inadequacies (InfoDev & The Centre for Democracy and Technology, 2002; Ebrahim & Irani, 2005; Ruhode, 2013). Such kind of services could come in handy as they create employment; bring services to the people and could help in tapping into the trust that is most sought enhance demand side adoption of the e-Government services.

Additionally, the role of the local governments cannot go unnoticed. Carbo, Williams, and Emeritus (2005) in Nabafu and Maiga (2012) posit that the local governments are the media through which government services reach the citizenry and they extend the service provision to the local communities. The scholars argue that the greater effect and interactions of e-Government happen at the local level. In support, Vabo and Røiseland (2012) argue that local governments are critical information hubs in areas that may also be exploited to carry through

the governance network activities. However, most researches amongst the scholars focus on e-Government at the national level (Tassabehji, Sharif & Wilkinson, 2009) neglecting the regional and local levels. In some cases Norris and Reddick (2012); Shackleton and Dawson (2007) posit that a lack of funding affects e-Government adoption at those levels. Also the local governments are currently offering non-transactional services, they are providing services at the Information and communication stage (Fan, 2011; Norris & Reddick, 2012).

2.7 Chapter Summary

The chapter discussed the key concepts as used in the study, including the notion that a service facilitates the creation of value by either the citizen or the government and its arms. Hence, the 'e'-service in e-Government terms hereafter was considered a service mediated through technology. The conceptual discussion in the chapter also showed that despite the duality of e-Government adoption perspectives, the corresponding frameworks and models are often treated in isolation neglecting how the main two stakeholder groups collectively influence value creation in the service provision. The e-Government status in the SADC region was also discussed and the study showed that there was a trail in the effort of investments in e-Government initiatives. The chapter concurrently showed that there is still a lowly adopted e-Government in the SADC member states owing to a combination of shared challenges at the country level. These included low internet penetration; inadequate infrastructure; lack of awareness of the existing services; inadequate technical capabilities; lack of citizen-centricity; accessibility issues such as lack of access points; security issues; culture; mono, or bi-lingual approach in the provision of services; lack of e-Government trust; low human development index amongst other challenges. The use of English as the global language of communication across stakeholder groups of the e-Government websites in the SADC was highlighted as a challenge to those potential users who would rather get the interface through other national languages. The monolingual approach largely mirrors the tendency by the SADC member states to pander to global imperatives to remain competitive in the global context, neglecting the local imperatives. In that regard, Schuppan (2009) suggests that governments should serve its citizens first by considering language diversity when offering services to specific target groups. The most significant stride noted in the chapter identifies the best practice case of SADC's own Mauritius for lessons learnt; and the opportunities that are available for developing countries explored in the bid to close the gap created by e-Government challenges in the SADC region. Looping back to the first chapter of the study was the mention of one of the classic predictors of e-Government initiative successes in which Heeks (2002a) argues that the e-Government initiative failures are attributable to the design-reality gaps. The scholar suggests that the existence of best practices to close the gaps need not to be followed thoughtlessly but should focus on appropriateness to the realities in context. As such, chapter three knits the first two

chapters by discussing the underpinning theories that guided the study methodology decisions. In addition, chapter three weaves in 'design thinking' as a needs-based approach to e-Government solutions and drawing on the emphasis to think globally and act locally.

3 THE CENTRAL THEORETICAL PERSPECTIVES

3.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the theories that served as an epistemological guide that underpinned the study. In addition, a contextual e-Government framework for SADC was proposed.

3.2 Theory in research

Theory in research gives a basis of interrogation between researchers and practitioners; it provides theoretical rigour; it aids in the explanation of phenomena and promotes understanding; it provides a framework for discussion; it ropes the knowledge areas of e-Government, and supports the recognition of the field as an academic discipline (Sahay & Walsham, 1995; Law, 2009; Bannister & Connolly, 2015, p. 1). Heeks and Bailur (2007) suggest that e-Government research lacks rigour and theoretical perspectives that explain the status of the phenomenon. However, Bannister and Connolly (2015, p. 6) argued in contrast, stating that the under-theorization of e-Government by some scholars is overemphasized as the argument should be viewed from three perspectives in the use of theory by researchers. This includes differentiating between native theory and imported theory; determining what qualifies as 'theory'; and assessing the extent of theory used in the literature/research. An imported theory is perceived as the 'adoption or adaptation of the theory from another field or discipline in e-Government research' (Bannister & Connolly, 2015, p. 6) such as the use of the Technology Acceptance Model in e-Government. On the other hand, native theory includes theories such as the e-Government stage or maturity models that have been discussed by many scholars from a local context. E-Government is multidisciplinary and is drawn from Information Systems (IS) and Public Administration (PA), which are multidisciplinary in their own right, making it difficult to develop coherent theories for this new development and disciplinary practice (Bannister & Connolly, 2015).

3.3 Review of central theoretical perspectives

Literature reflects that e-Government studies concentrate more on the extremes of the continuum bar as depicted in Figure 3-1. The essentialist way of viewing e-Government separates the two extreme perspectives make it seem as if technology adoption is dependent on either the technology or the social factors in the continuum bar, and not both.

Figure 3-1: The current e-Government status from the perspective of a continuum bar
Source: Author

It is the techno-socio deterministic dichotomy that has also contributed to the incommensurability of the paradigms in research. However, there is consensus amongst scholars that technology is a social product; influenced by the social, use, political, and economic factors (Mackay & Gillespie, 1992; Williams & Edge, 1996; Tatnall & Burgess, 2002; Bruni, 2003; Law, 2009), thus making the social and technical aspects equally influential. To help explain the complexity of e-Government, four underpinning theories: Actor-Network Theory, Innovation Translation and Technology Acceptance Model are discussed as the underpinning perspectives of this study.

3.3.1 Gidden's Structuration Theory (ST)

The varying effects of the factors used in TAM by some researchers delineate the study in that they indicate the need to assess these at the country level and thereby enabling researchers to capture the context. Also the lack of the social aspect in the original TAM and the findings by Davis (1993), that technology is not the solution since its characteristics may also constrain the individual's beliefs and the individual may also have his/her intentions moderated by the society in which he/she exist. This extends the need of a holistic perspective of e-Government. Hence, the discussion of the following theories imported from sociology to fill the gap created in TAM. Bwalya et al (2014) employed the Structuration Theory to elicit the predictors of interactions between employees and the organisational structures in Zambia. In context, the structure in the structuration theory is dichotomous in that the organisational norms, rules and resources coerce the actions or practices of employees and vice-versa (Chaffee & Lemert, 2009). This demonstrates that the interconnectedness of the action and structure is recursively dependent. In concordance with the duality of structure, Chikerema, Mavetera and Jantjies (2016) posited that argue that the humans are who they are thanks to the social processes but at the same time their actions also regulates the very processes that created them. Similarly, the scholars argue that the trajectory that ICTs/technology takes into *social* processes is determined by its adoption by the target audience. This structuration perspective of the interplay of human action and technology gives emphasis to human action (Cordella & Shaik, 2006). As such, it helps understand the how technology is used by different people in different situation (Chikerema, Mavetera & Jantjies, 2016). However, Mavetera (2011) posits that the involvement of humans and technology in Information Systems warrants that both these actants have interests that

require accommodation by the other through negotiation. The disregard of the role played by the object/technology in the structure (Law, 1992) is a cause of concern in the current study. In concordance, Cordella and Hesse (2015) argue that technology does not have a linear impact on e-Government; it is the dynamic interactions and negotiations of varied actors that model the phenomenon. Consequently, the ST does not give the basis to enhance the design (Chikerema, Mavetera & Jantjies, 2016). This motivates the theory discussed in the next section.

3.3.2 Actor-network theory (ANT)

“...reducible neither to an actor alone nor to a network...An actor-network is simultaneously an actor whose activity is networking heterogeneous elements and a network that is able to redefine and transform what it is made of” (Callon 1987, p.93).

Contrary to the structuration perspective that has an emphasis on human action, the ANT considers the human and non-human influences in sociological analysis. The role of both the human and non-human is valued in their complementarity in influencing the social processes. Viewing the human and the non-humans indistinctly emanates from the fact that the two are embedded in each other; they define and shape each other (Gasson, 2003a; Law, 2009). This dynamic human-non-human interplay is what Law (2009) would call *semiotic-relationality*. The actor network is configured by the heterogeneous actors who have a role to play in the shaping of each other. According to Latour (2005, p. 46), “An ‘actor’ in the hyphenated expression ‘actor-network’ is not the source of action but the moving target of a vast array of entities swarming toward it”. There source of action is distributed in the network. Figure 3-2 illustrates that B (actor) has been made to act by A and A is trying to cut all the links that B has with the other actors. At the same time C, D, and E in their effort to cajole B into their networks, are swarming toward B. A typical example is that, given Bank A, say Barclays Bank and Bank B which is hypothetically First National Bank, these banks are not actors. Actors are a group of followers who use the services of the bank. As Latour (2005) would put it, it is never clear what the origin of action is, hence the name ‘actor’. What makes an actor act is hidden and that is what matters, otherwise the apriori distinctions are simply relational effects that “ offer no framework for explanation”(Law, 2009, p. 147).

Figure 3-2: Sources of action
 Source: (Adapted from Callon, 1986, p. 21)

The key aspect of the ANT is the translation process and is defined as “... how one entity gives a role to others.” The ANT focuses on power as an effect of how the network is patterned (Callon, 1986; Law, 1992, 2009, p. 146; Singleton & Michael, 1993, p. 229). The configuration of the networks determines its durability and stability. Hence, the study seeks to validate how the ANT aids in understanding the evolution (“Hows” vs. “whys”) of networks in e-Government.

Translation Process

The four moments of translation are shown in Figure 3-3. The power of the focal actor in ANT is reflected by its effects seen in the growth of the network. However, the growth of the e-Government networks does not depend solely on the focal actor; it is hinged on the configuration of the network. Thus, the source of action in networks is relational and distributed (Chikerema, Mavetera & Jantjies, 2016). Each network is formed by a collection of actors (animate and inanimate) that define their roles, practices and how technology is used to establish the identity of a network. The actors that have been mobilized together in a network are free to exit it. Thus, as Law (1992) would put it, the analysis of ordering struggle (patterning, social orchestration, ordering and resistance) is at the core in ANT. In the context of e-Government, using the banks (as means to an end: government) that were mentioned as actants not actors earlier on, the clientele base of the banks is never static. It shrinks (clientele lowers) and swells (clientele base increases) depending on what is happening in the market. The Barclays Bank and the First National banks share the same actors whose decisions are equally dynamic.

Figure 3-3: Moments of Translation
Source: Extracted from (Rhodes, 2009, p. 6)

According to Callon (1986) the four moments of translation are:

Problematisation - the ability of the focal actor to define the problem which is consistent with the interest of other actors. The focal actor proposes a solution to the problem. By so doing, the focal actor has created an Obligatory Passage of Point (OPP) that must be negotiated through persuasion and cajoling of other actors to join and form an alliance. In this moment of translation, Barclays Bank for example, would provide say an e-service such as online banking, which the clientele would feel obliged to use as they think it is the solution to their problems such as long winding queues, and rigidity of transacting times with the bank. Barclays Bank should know and understand the needs of the clientele to provide the enticing e-service; otherwise, the clientele would prefer to go to First National Bank if there is a better solution to their problems.

Intèressement -. At this stage, the other actor show interest and get attracted to the solution proposed in the Problematisation stage. According to (Chikerema, Mavetera and Jantjies, 2016), it is at this stage that the interested actors are detached from any other ties and are locked in the network that cajoled them as shown in Figure 3-2.

Enrolment - As argued in this chapter, the source of action in the ANT is distributed, hence, it is the relational effect of the other actors that maintain the power in the network and cause the attracted acted to yield (Singleton & Michael, 1993). Other actor-networks from which actors such as have been cajoled from will just give up. The actor-network is expected to maintain the

good fight by developing network stability through strategic and material durability. The focal actors will have to find ways of enrolling, including physical violence.

Mobilization - This stage seeks to develop loyal delegate actors who continue to be spokespersons of the network.

OPP - is an acronym for Obligatory Passage Point which is a point of negotiation centred on a focal actor through which other actors must pass. Admitting being part of the network/alliance through OPP in this study demonstrates interests in e-Government. The stability of a network is dependent on the configurations of its elements.

'Paradox' of power in the ANT

Latour (1986) stated that there are two forms of power: power in '*potentia*' and power in '*actu*'. The former does not cause change (rendering the focal actor powerless); and the latter looks at power as relational, the focal actor is rendered powerful by the ability of the other actors to cause change. In the same vein, Callon (2007) underscores that it is this radical indiscriminacy of the actor that forms the basis of the ANT. Thus, the ANT actor may alternatively "be a power which enrolls and dominates or, by contrast an agent with no initiative which allows itself to be enrolled" (Callon, 2007, p. 272). Furthermore, the power in '*potentia*' is not synonymous to the static concept of power '*over*' but a dynamic concept of power '*to*' (Heeks & Stanforth, 2007, p. 165). In the e-Government context, the power is the supply side is determined by the number of citizens using the e-services as they reflect the following that has been persuaded into the e-Government network. The ANT actor could be the government, an organisation or company, technology, a process that can act as an influencer in the adoption of the e-services. Chikerema, Mavetera and Jantjies (2016) posit that "... the government is made by the people for the people; hence the adoption of e-Government is not just a mere fact of being in power without enrolment of followers who share the same interests". As Latour (1984) would put it, power is not possessed but is a result of the action. Considering that action comes from the association it brings to fore the importance of having networks in e-Government.

Application of ANT in e-Government Literature

E-Government is a complex phenomenon; failures and scarce successes have been and continue to be investigated worldwide (Heeks & Stanforth, 2007). Some scholars focus on the techno-deterministic perspective of the phenomena while others look at how the social shapes the technology (Tatnall & Burgess, 2002; Heeks & Bailur, 2007; Cordella & Hesse, 2015).

Table 3-1: Summary of research work that used ANT

Author(s)	Focus area of study	Actors	Major Findings
(Tatnall & Burgess, 2002)	B-B e-commerce Portal as the OPP for regional SMEs in Melbourne, Australia	Local semi-government organization, Internet service provider (ISP), a computer software company, portal software designers, computer hardware and software, modems, telephone lines, Web development tools, and human entities including local business proprietors from SMEs, customers, programmers, development managers, and local government staff, Portal project manager, business champions (Tatnall and Burgess, 2002, p. 186)	The complexity of adoption was laid bare as service providers share their reasons for adoption that does not take into consideration the end user of the technology. At the same time, the importance of interactions between human and technology in the portal project became evident.
(Tatnall & Lepa, 2003)	Adoption and use of ICTs by older people	Older internet users, email, the internet, family members, computers, Internet Service Providers	The findings included the drivers of Internet technologies and electronic commerce and the theory that best describes the adoption process. The older internet users used the technologies to fulfil their social interactions Translation theory was found as the ideal theory to understand the adoption process.
(Shim & Shin, 2015)	Analysis of the process of standards setting based on the case of long-term evolution time division duplex (LTE TDD) deployment in China.	China Mobile, LTE TDD, Datang Mobile (telecommunication equipment manufacturers), Global TD-LTE Initiative (GTI), and Chinese Government as focal actors	Insights on the policy successes and failures of 4G mobile networks in China; the understanding of the influence of technology in forming alliances and competition amongst actor networks were gained
(Cordella & Hesse, 2015)	The case of how the Akshaya e-Government project in Kerala, India evolved	Kerala State Information Technology Mission (KSITM) in Trivandrum as well as in the Malappuram district Telecentres project office, the entrepreneurs, the citizens, policy and the district councils	Findings showed the unpredictability of e-Government initiatives owing to the dynamic interactions of actors over time. Context centrality is important in e-Government initiatives
(Lee, Harindranath, Oh, & Kim, 2015)	Examined the dynamics of competition and collaboration among mobile carriers, banks, and other related parties for mobile banking in Korea during the burgeoning period of mobile banking in the early to mid-2000s.	The major actors included banks, mobile carriers, mobile phone manufacturers, customers, and mobile banking technology.	The dynamic interplay of pattern and structure of competition and collaboration of actors involved in offering mobile banking services was better understood

(Al-Hajri & Tatnall, 2012)	Reinterpretation of the comparative study of the adoption of Internet Technology in Banking in Oman and Australia using Innovation translation	Bank managers, bank tellers, other bank employees, bank shareholders, banking transactions, customers, the Internet, communications infrastructure, computer systems at the bank, customer's home or business computers, Internet cafés and the mass media	Some interview data reflected the associations of actors, though needed to be explored further;
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Technology does not have a linear impact on e-Government; rather it is shaped by the dynamic interactions with other actors (Cordella & Hesse, 2015). ANT can be used as a tool to unearth the complexities of the sociotechnical world; to explain the 'how' of relational materiality; and to evaluate networks (Cressman, 2009). Table 3-1 shows some of the research work in e-Government that used ANT as ontology of analysis.

Mobile banking in Korea, just like in any other country, requires the interaction of various actors to deliver services to customers. These may include customers as the end users, the Internet service providers, the mobile phone manufacturers, banks, telecommunication personnel and infrastructure. The transactional nature of mobile banking would require assurance of the provision of secure, trustworthy, and easy to use services to the customer. The assurance in question may be explained by the dynamic relationships of the involved actors through the translation process. Consequently, the resulting 'power' of the focal actor determines the acceptance level of the technology. Figure 3-4 shows how the actor networks of mobile banking services in Korea developed.

Figure 3-4: Actor-networks of mobile banking services in Korea
Source: (Extracted from Lee et al., 2015, p. 559)

Mobile banking in Korea transitioned through three actor-networks and within each are the focal actors who carried the technology through. In the first phase, the focal actor failed to mobilize customers. The IC chip mobile phones as a competitor of mobile carriers cajoled various actors that included the mobile phone manufacturers', banks and customers to form an alliance and lastly the emergent actor-network as shown in Figure 3-4. Lee et al. (2015) argue that the study showed how the dynamic interactions created, destroyed, and created alliances owing to the competition and collaboration of mobile carriers and banks and the advancement of technology. The study explains how each of the alliances was formed by using the ANT.

3.3.3 Innovation Translation

Whilst Innovation Diffusion (sociologist Everett Rogers, 1962) focuses on how the innovation use spreads amongst the intended users, the level of diffusion is dependent on the innovation itself, how its communicated to the target audience, the amount of time that it has been put to the audience, and the social system (Rogers, 1995). Otherwise, the assumption is that over time, adoption will increase as users do not adopt the innovation at the same time. In the case of e-Government adoption in the SADC region, the time has elapsed but still its levels of adoption remain low. Therefore, it becomes problematic to explain e-Government using the Innovation Diffusion model where diffusion does not happen (Chikerema, Mavetera and Jantjies, 2016). In this context, Innovation Translation ideal as it considers the dynamic interplay of the animate and the inanimate (ibid). The complex composition of the e-Government actors requires that the phenomenon be viewed holistically. Al-Hajri and Tatnall (2012) posit that the adoption of technological innovation may be put in context through the translation process.

3.3.4 Human and User Centered Information Systems Designs

The section briefly discusses the User Centred Design (UCD) and the Human Centred Design (HCD) as frameworks that guide the design of Information Systems. The Design thinking is then explicated as an approach that is inclined to the HCD.

3.3.4.1 User centred Information systems Design

Gasson (2003a) argues that Information Systems literature often disregards the social context while focusing on the usability aspect of technology owing to the greater attention to the User Centred Design. The UCD is focused on solving problems that are technology-centric: emphasising the *interactions* between the human and the technology Gasson (2003a); enhancement of the product aesthetics (Serrat, 2010); the service, object, interface, space or the communication (Sanders, 2002). The traditional approaches (Interaction design,

participatory design, Use Cases in Unified Modelling Languages (UML), and in Agile Development) used in the design of information systems often mirror the user-centricity at the expense of human-centeredness as shown in Table 3-2 (Gasson, 2003a).

Table 3-2: Summary of human-centred approaches

Approach	Intended Focus	Actual focus
Traditional IS design approaches	The structuring of ill-structured problems: goal-driven decomposition.	Explicit (management) focus is goal-driven and decompositional. Implicit strategies are opportunistic, to deal with goal emergence.
Prototyping and participatory design.	Negotiation and exploration of ill-structured problems.	The iterative and cyclical process of stakeholder involvement limited by the political selection of user-representatives and technology-centered requirements focus.
Interaction Design	Exploration of IT-supported user work-processes.	Technology-centred, individual user focus. Assumes consensus among system users, with well-understood IS goals.
UML and Use Cases	Modeling of business processes and user-interactions with the intended IT system.	Models formal information processing (business processing rules). Technology-centered and decompositional (so no opportunity to redefine goals as these emerges through the design process).
Agile Software Development	Adaptation of an evolving system design based on user interaction and scenario generation.	Technology-centered prototyping accomplished by the development of individual user-scenarios

Source: (Extracted from Gasson, 2003a, p. 38)

The notion of ‘user’ forces designers to concentrate on functionality, the design of the technology and the convergence to the *consensual* goals without considering human needs, skill, creativity, and context. In participatory and exploratory design, there are traces of user involvement (though inadequately represented owing to the political selection of who participates) as a critical component in the design as shown in Table 3-2. However, the lack of balance between the technical and human dimensions is still evident. In contrast, interaction design involves single users followed by a generalisation of how users use technological solutions and this does not make the approach human centred (Gasson, 2003a). It is a plausible effort though, that interaction design considers user interactions and experiences, however inadequate. Some of the effects induced by the limited attention to the user need in designing information systems are evident from the extant literature concerning the current and contemporary technologies that are used to interact with the governments.

3.3.4.2 Human-centred Design

Human Centred Design (HCD) is focused on solving problems that seek to understand how technology can be used to support human activity. The HCD is anti-essentialist as it

acknowledges that the way the human interacts (social) with the technology is constrained by the design of the technology solution (technical) and vice versa, making the approach socio-technical (Gasson, 2003a). This socio-technical interplay of organisation and the technology is evidenced in the dual cycle model of HCD in Figure 3-5. The HCD cycle uses the notion of designing technology solution ‘with’ as opposed to ‘for’ users by firstly understanding the needs of people to inform the intended solution.

Figure 3-5: The dual cycle model of HCD
Source: (Extracted from Gasson, 2003a, p. 40)

3.3.5 Design thinking approach

Design thinking is innovative and innovation is not incremental (it is not about tweaking the existing solutions); rather, it is about creating new choices that lead to divergent thinking (Owen, 2006; Serrat, 2010). According to Tim Brown (CEO and president of IDEO), designers are expected to design for experience innovation by way of integrating and resolving three tensions to an idea that solves all:

- i. *Desirability: understanding the needs of people*
- ii. *Technical feasibility: finding ways of using technology in addressing human needs and,*
- iii. *Economic viability: finding ways of making the solution sustainable*

The approach is empathic, personal, subjective, interpretive, integrative, synthetic, pictorial, dialectical, opportunistic, and optimistic (Serrat, 2010) and creative (Owen, 2006). Designing products or services that are usable by the target population is core in design thinking as it requires understanding the end user environment, social factors, emerging trends and marketing adjacencies (Holloway, 2009, p. 51; McLoone *et al.*, 2010). The heterogeneity of the e-Government actors makes design thinking an alternative, as Owen (2006) endorses that design thinking strives to make the solutions adaptive to address the varying needs where possible. Design thinking balances the technical and human dimensions (Holloway, 2009) by involving the users in shaping how the design takes place. It may be necessary that the central governments give support to the local government initiatives that focus on enhancing service delivery to the people. The e-Government strategies of the latter should align with those of the central government.

3.3.6 Technology Acceptance and use Model (TAM)

The government, in principle, should address the needs of the people it purports to serve (Chikerema, Mavetera and Jantjies, 2016). As e-Government is mediated through ICTs, it was compelling that the study uses related theory to measure technology adoption. A plethora of theoretical and conceptual frameworks have been developed in the field of Information Systems to measure the users' acceptance of technologies (Lee, Kozar & Larsen, 2003; Venkatesh *et al.*, 2003; Bwalya, Du Plessis & Rensleigh, 2014). These include Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) by Fishbein and Aizen in 1967, Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1986, 1989; Davis, Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1989), Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB), the model combining TAM and the Theory of Planned Behaviour, the Innovation Diffusion Theory, Extended Technology Acceptance Model (TAM2) (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000), Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) (Venkatesh *et al.*, 2003). The underlying concept of these acceptance models is the description of how motivational processes mediate between the system characteristics and the system (see Figure 3-6).

Figure 3-6: The conceptual framework for TAM
Source: (Extracted from Davis, 1986, p. 10)

Davis (1986) argues that system developers have an influence on the system features which consequently influences the degree of the system usage by the target population. The

determinants include: *attitude (A)*, *Perceived Usefulness (PU)*, subjective *Perceived Ease-Of-Use (PEOU)*, *Behavioural Intention (BI)* and the actual system use. TAM presupposes that *A* is jointly influenced by the *PU* and *PEOU*; *BI* is jointly determined *Attitude* and *PU*; and the actual usage of the system is determined by the *BI* as shown in Figure 3-7.

Figure 3-7: Technology Acceptance Model
 Source: (Adapted from Davis, Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1989, p. 985)

The fundamental determinants of TAM are defined as follows:

Perceived usefulness (PU) - "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance" (Bandura, 1982; Davis, 1989, p. 320; Davis, Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1989, p. 985). *Perceived ease-of-use (PEOU)* - "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free from effort" (Davis, 1989, p. 320; Davis, Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1989, p. 985).

3.3.6.1 The motivational constructs and e-Government

The relationship between the TAM motivational constructs (*A*, *PEOU* and *PU*) has been endorsed in literature. There is a consensus among researchers that *PU* has a direct effect on the intention (Davis, 1989, 1993; Davis, Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1989; Lee, Kozar & Larsen, 2003; Belanche, Casaló & Flavián, 2012; Gracia & Ari, 2015); *PEOU* does not significantly determine the intention to use technology (Subramanian, 1994; Igbaria, Guimaraes & Davis, 1995; Keil, Beranek & Konsynski, 1995; Belanche, Casaló & Flavián, 2012); *PEOU* has a direct influence on *PU* (Davis, 1989, 1993; Wangpipatwong, Chutimaskul & Papasratorn, 2008; Mahadeo, 2009); *PEOU* and *PU* have a joint causal effect on *A* (Davis, 1989; Davis, Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1989; Mathieson, 1991; Al-Hujran, Al-Dalahmeh & Aloudat, 2011; Al-Hujran *et al.*, 2015). With respect to the effect of the behavioural intention on usage, *PU* has been hypothesized to have a direct and indirect influence on the actual system usage; and *A* has a direct effect on *Actual usage of the system* (Davis, 1993). From the perspectives of randomly selected Jordanians across the country, the perceived usefulness (*PU*) and Perceived Ease of Use (*PEOU*) was

found to have a causal effect on the use intention of the e-Government services (Al Hujran, Aloudat & Altarawneh, 2013; Abu-Shanab, 2014). In a different context, in Ontario, Canada, the key factors of e-Government adoption have been found to differ at each of the service maturity stages (Shareef et al., 2011, 2014).

Trust and e-Government

Trust is perceived as “ the willingness of a party to be vulnerable to the actions of another party based on the expectation that the other will perform a particular action important to the trustors, irrespective of the ability to monitor or control the other party” (Mayer, Davis & Schoorman, 1995, p. 712). It is the beliefs that the actors (human) hold that determine their adoption attitudes or intentions. It is expected that the higher the level of trust the trustors have for the e-Government, the higher the intention to use the e-services (Abu-Shanab, 2014; Abu-Shanab, 2017). Jordan, as a country, has gained substantial recognition for the provision of e-Government services to the public. However, the adoption of these remains low specifically in accessing e-Government websites (Al-Hujran, Al-Dalahmeh & Aloudat, 2011). Similar behaviour in the adoption of the e-tax filing service was observed in Taiwan and the US. The literature claims that the initial numbers of adoption by tax-payers rose each year but increasing the numbers to reach the predicted target became a challenge (Fu, Farn & Chao, 2006; Carter, Schaupp & Evans, 2008). In this regard, scholars identified trustworthiness as an influential determinant in use intention of the e-Government services (Warkentin *et al.*, 2002; Abu-Shanab, 2012; Al Hujran, Aloudat & Altarawneh, 2013; Abu-Shanab, 2014), especially in the transaction stage (Shareef *et al.*, 2011, 2014; UN, 2014).

Different constructs for trust in different contexts of e-Government have been researched. Some of the constructs include: trust in government (TiG) (perceptions on the Government's responsibility); trust in technology (TiT) (OECD, 2003; UN, 2003; UN, 2008, 2014; Cocchiglia & Vernaschi, 2008; Colesca, 2009; Dashti, Benbasat & Burton-jones, 2010; Papadopoulou & Nikolaidou, 2010; Karunasena & Deng, 2012; Savoldelli, Codagnone & Misuraca, 2014; Abu-Shanab, 2012, 2017); trust in information/information quality (Papadopoulou & Nikolaidou, 2010; Shareef *et al.*, 2011; Abu-Shanab, 2014); trust in stored data; trust in the government agency; trust in the transaction, and institution-based trust (Papadopoulou & Nikolaidou, 2010); and trust in service (Papadopoulou & Nikolaidou, 2010; Gracia & Ari, 2015). Whilst these trust types are broader and have sets of requirements necessary for the trust type to be met (see Table 3-3) some scholars focused on select dimensions such as privacy and security concerns (P&SC) (Abu-Shanab, 2014), and perceived security (Venkatesh, Brown & Bala, 2013; Shareef et al., 2014). The different types of trust are interdependent and they vary with context; in the transact stage of the e-Government maturity model, the PATU/PEOU and Perceived Security

(PS) become critical with the PS being most influential for the citizens as they disclose personal identification and financial information (Shareef et al., 2014, pp. 396–398). In agreement, the transact stage has also been identified as a stage that needs robust data protection and security (UN, 2014, p. 6).

Table 3-3: E-Government Trust Topology

Trust type	Definition	Dimensions/Requirements
Trust in Stored Data	<i>Trust in the specific e-government stored data management (data in storage / data access and usage)</i>	Authentication, Authenticity, Authorization, Identity management, Confidentiality, Privacy, Integrity
Trust in Service	<i>Trust in the specific e-government service</i>	Problem responsiveness, Transparency, Efficiency, Communication, Usefulness, Ease-of-use
Trust in Information	<i>Trust in the information provided by e-government (information quality)</i>	Information Reliability/validity, Information Adequacy, Information Relevance, Information Understandability , Information Accuracy, Information Currency
Trust in System	<i>Trust in the system / infrastructure of the government organization</i>	Correctness, Availability, Security, Failure, Accountability, Response time
Trust in Transaction	<i>Trust in the e-government transaction (data in transit / data transmission)</i>	Integrity, Confidentiality, Non-repudiation, Privacy, Security
Trust in Government Organization	<i>Trust in the specific government agency</i>	Benevolence, Competence, Integrity, Predictability
Institution – based trust	<i>Trust in the institutional system supporting e-government</i>	Legal and regulatory framework, Third-party guarantees, International standards, Directives, Escrows

Source: (Extracted from Papadopoulou & Nikolaidou, 2010, p. 3)

Familiarity with e-Government (FeG)

E-Government familiarity is perceived as “the level of citizens’ awareness of the advantages, disadvantages, requirements and value of e-Government projects” (Abu-Shanab, 2017, p. 103). The PEOU, PU, Perceived Familiarity with e-Government was found to have a strong influence, specifically in the static stage of the e-Government maturity model (Alsaghier & Ford, 2009; Shareef et al., 2011, 2014). The need for e-Government familiarity from the demand side helps influence their knowledge. People cannot develop an intention to use, nor use services that they are not aware of. In addition, the role of government is to serve the people both in rural, peri-urban and urban areas. As such, Shareef et al. (2011, p. 27) called out to the countries (especially the developing countries) to launch awareness campaigns for the citizens, with particular reference to the rural folk, to avoid the digital divide. Abu-Shanab (2014) argues that familiarity with the internet construct’s failure to predict trust in e-Government in Jordan was contextual and typical of countries where technology is not widely used.

Social Influence (SI)

Information systems are social entities that must take cognisance of the heterogeneity of the involved components (Tatnall, 2007). Similarly, citizen adoption of e-services in e-Government is a voluntary behaviour that is driven by socio-political factors, warranting an integrative approach (social, political and cultural) for a deeper understanding (Carter *et al.*, 2011). Approached from a social perspective, the citizen does not exist in isolation; he/she is a social being. However, TAM revolves around how different *individual* characteristics such as PEOU, PU, and behavioural intentions. The two main constructs (PU and PEOU) in TAM derive from the Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) of Bandura (1982) as Expected Outcome and Self-efficacy beliefs respectively. Bandura (1982)'s Social Cognitive Theory presupposes that the perceived self-efficacy can also be induced vicariously by watching and copying others. In concordance with Bandura(1982), social influence is a predictor of behavioural intention to use the e-Government services and is commonly defined as the extent to which people in one's social circles hold the belief that one should use the e-Government services (Venkatesh *et al.*, 2003, p. 451; Weerakkody, El-Haddadeh & Al-Sobhi, 2013, p. 718; Abu-Shanab, 2014, p. 499).

Culture in e-Government

From a cultural stance, Belanche, Casaló, and Flavián (2012); Al-Hujran et al. (2015) argue that trust and culture have a strong influence on beliefs. Culture in this study is taken to mean the shared beliefs and values that identify a group as a people. Culture varies from one group or country to another. In that regard, the e-Government determinants discussed above were tested and validated in other countries such as Romania, Canada, US, and Jordan and when tested in another country may differ owing to context-specific aspects including cultural differences. The study is then compelled to research the influence that culture has on behavioural intention in the SADC as a response to the calls from the extant literature and the experiences of the participants in the qualitative study. Al-Hujran, Al-Dalahmeh and Aloudat (2011) argue that the persistent low usage of e-Government services in developing countries demands a deeper understanding of the determinant factors not only from a technical or social but cultural perspective. Informing a cultural perspective is Hofstede's framework of national culture, with dimensions such as power distance (PD), Uncertainty Avoidance (UA), Individualism versus Collectivism (INDIV), masculinity versus femininity (MASC), and short versus long term orientation. The culture constructs that the current study adopted are defined as follows: *PD*: "the extent to which a less powerful person in a society tolerates inequality of power in the society" (Hofstede, 1984, p. 390). *UA*: "the extent to which people within a culture are made nervous by the situation that they consider unstructured, unclear or unpredictable and the extent to which they have to avoid such situations by adopting strict codes of behaviour and a belief in absolute truth" (Hofstede, 1984, p. 390). Al-Hujran, Al-Dalahmeh and Aloudat (2011) posit that

PD and UA were the only two determinants of culture that significantly influenced the intention to use e-Government services in Jordan. In the US, PD and UA were found to significantly influence PU and PEOU (Warkentin *et al.*, 2002).

Facilitating conditions (FC)

An e-Government service is a package that comprises the core service, facilitating services/goods (Venkatesh *et al.*, 2003; Venkatesh, Chan & Thong, 2012; Weerakkody, El-Haddadeh & Al-Sobhi, 2013), and the supporting service (Venkatesh, Chan & Thong, 2012). An example of such a service package is making a withdrawal or deposit as a self-service (core), the ATM and ATM card (facilitating goods/services) as they establish the link between the client and the bank, and the security measure as a supporting service. Venkatesh, Chan and Thong (2012) posit that the transition from traditional provision of government services offline to the online provision has not been easy for citizens as they still need to seek facilitating and/or supporting services/ goods to succeed in using an e-service such as tax-filing.

3.4 Chapter Summary

The central perspectives that underpin the study were discussed in detail in the chapter. The actor-network theory (ANT) was expected to guide the study in approaching it “from a socio-techno perspective of the e-Government phenomenon as the social and the technological” constrain each other. The ANT explains the how and the whys of the phenomenon through the participants’ voices. Closely connected with the ANT, the Innovation Translation was also discussed. As a consequence of the ANT, the innovation translation considers the success of the phenomenon to rely on the role the focal actors are expected to play: carry through the innovation. Thus, their ability or failure in cajoling the other actors into accepting their solutions and expanding the networks would define the success of e-Government adoption. As emphasised in the Translation process, the other actors can only resonate with the solution proposed by the focal actors if the solutions are consonant with and consistent in resolving their problems. It is against this backdrop that the chapter further discussed the need for human-centered approaches to launching e-Government services as opposed to user-centered approaches which focus on aspects such as functionality, interaction, and aesthetics. To promote the sustainability of e-solutions, the chapter also explicated design thinking as an approach to developing human centred e-Government solutions and how it could influence the promotion and successful adoption of resultant solutions. Technology Acceptance Model was also discussed as another underpinning theory to the study. The subsequent chapter looks at the methodology of the study taking into consideration the underpinning perspectives discussed in the current chapter.

4 RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

4.1 Introduction

The philosophical assumptions informing this study are discussed in this chapter, paving way for describing the research methodology of the study. The chapter further addresses the research design, research methods, the research plan for data collection and how the collected data was analysed. The description of the population and sample of the study, ethical considerations and research quality aspects are also explained and interrogated.

4.2 Research Paradigms

Rather than being an interpreter, the scientist who embraces a new paradigm is like a man wearing inventing glasses. —Thomas Kuhn

Defined broadly, a research approach is a plan for conducting research. The research plan is composed of philosophical assumptions, research design and the research methods (Creswell, 2014). There is consensus amongst researchers that the justification of the choice of a specific research approach and methods extends to assumptions about the reality of the study, that is the theoretical perspectives (Crotty, 1998, p. 2), perceived by other researchers as paradigms (Guba & Lincoln, 1994; Mertens, 2010; Bhattacharjee, 2012). Paradigms are frames of reference that are employed to guide the researcher's reasoning and observation (Bhattacharjee, 2012, p. 17). The definition of a paradigm was earlier endorsed by some scholars as meaning, the belief systems that define the worldview for the inquirer based on the identification of the what is there to be known, how it comes to be known, values and approaches used to know the reality (Burrell & Morgan, 1979; Guba & Lincoln, 1994; Crotty, 1998; Pourdehnad, Wexler & Wilson, 2011). In philosophical terms, ontology is what is there to know (Crotty, 1998, p. 10; Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009).

As such, an ontological assumption answers the questions:

What is the structure and nature of reality? ;

What is there that can be known about it?

(Orlikowski & Baroudi, 1991; Guba & Lincoln, 1994, p. 108; Crotty, 1998; Neuman, 2014).

This translates to that which exists in the research problem that should be known, be it real or abstract. On the other hand, the term epistemology comes from the Greek word 'episteme', that means knowledge (Krauss & Putra, 2005, p. 758; Mavetera, 2011, p. 39). The epistemological assumptions are concerned with the nature of the relationship between the knower or would be knower and what can be known (Crotty, 1998; Guba & Lincoln, 1994, p. 108; Neuman, 2014). Such assumptions entail what forms of knowledge are to be obtained, how the knowledge can be sought; how this knowledge is communicated to other human beings as hard, soft, spiritual

or transcendental (Burrell & Morgan, 1979). The epistemological positions address the role of the human factor in the problem. These humanist aspects relate to the nature of reality assumed in the ontological position. According to Guba and Lincoln (1994, p. 108), the methodological assumptions are concerned with how the inquirer goes about finding what he/she believes can be known from the assumed nature of reality. The debate on paradigms dates back to the Greek philosophers (see Box 4-1) and continues (Weber, 2004). Box 4-1 gives us a perspective into those times.

The discussions of paradigms date back to the Greek philosophers including Plato (427-347 B.C.), Socrates (469-399 B.C.) and Aristotle (384-322 B.C.). Prior to the 3rd Century BC, knowledge used to be based on theological principles based on faith. Knowledge used to be transmitted from the Priest to the people (Austin, Orcutt & Rosso, 2001; Bhattacharjee, 2012).

During the middle of the 3rd Century BC, Greek philosophers contested the faith orientation by the Romans. Plato as a rationalist suggested that knowledge can be discovered within us by self-reflection. Rationalism assumed reason/intellect is the source of knowledge (Austin, Orcutt & Rosso, 2001; Bhattacharjee, 2012). The French philosopher Rene Descartes (1596-1650) supported the Platonic debate and he was the first to put across the idea of the mind being separate from the body. He added that behaviour can be influenced by the environment and the mind (Austin et al., 2001).

By the 16th century, a British Philosopher, Francis Bacon (1561-1626) suggested that knowledge is not a reasoning activity but is based on observation in the real world (empirical). Bacon fathered the branch of philosophy called empiricism which was supported by other British philosophers including John Locke (1632-1704), and David Hume. John Locke equalled learning to a child's mind that he called a blank tablet (tabula rasa) that gets shaped by what the child experiences (Austin, Orcutt & Rosso, 2001; Bhattacharjee, 2012). In support of empiricism, Aristotle developed methods of discovering the truth about the world around him and Socrates developed one for discovering the truth through conversations with fellow citizens (Austin et al., 2001).

Around the 19th century, the German philosopher Immanuel Kant (1724-1804) intercepted the on-going debate between the rationalists and the empiricists developing a new concept called German idealism. He suggested that knowledge (innate) existed prior to experience. Kant argued that 'a priori' knowledge organizes the data that is received through the senses. Furthermore, he posited that experience is purely subjective, hence processing these using pure reason without consideration of the subjective nature of the experience is as good as a theoretical illusion (Austin, Orcutt & Rosso, 2001; Bhattacharjee, 2012).

Box 4-1: Debate of paradigms in the early years

The following sections explicate the underpinning assumptions of social research including Information Systems.

4.2.1 The positivist orientation of the study

While Kant developed the German Idealism, the Positivist Orientation was born, influenced by the French philosopher *Auguste Comte (1798–1857)* and then by the French sociologist *Emile Durkheim (1858-1917)*. Auguste Comte, according to Bhattacharjee (2012, p. 8), is the father of the sociology discipline and posited that while theories are created through reasoning, they are

better verified through observation “The determining cause of a social fact must be among antecedent social facts and not among the states of the individual consciousness” (Durkheim, 1982, p. 134). The French sociologist further suggests that social facts should be ascertained through empirical investigation and by observation (p. 2-3). The positivist paradigm postulates that objective truth can be discovered through observation and measurement. In an endeavour to explain the how of e-Government adoption in the SADC, this study is underpinned by the Technology Acceptance Model. The ontological assumptions in the study are that the e-Government key variables such as technology, countries, culture, people, skills, services, e-Government, governments, adoption of e-Government services, processes amongst others, exist as ontological aspects of reality. Guha and Chakrabarti (2014) acknowledge that ICTs have created the digital divide that separates the ‘haves’ and ‘have not’s’. It is against this backdrop that ‘digital divide’ is taken as an ontological aspect (reality) in the study.

The epistemological assumptions from an objectivist standpoint, are that causal relationships the study variables can be reached at independently of the researcher (Guba & Lincoln, 1994; Myers, 1997; Crotty, 1998; Creswell, 2003; Weber, 2004; Heeks & Bailur, 2007). One of the ontological aspects of the realist world in this study is the culture. The realist epistemological assumption is that the researcher objectively detached from the gathered data. This implies that the truth is known. Heeks and Bailur (2007) argue that from a positivist position, culture has an objective existence such that its impact upon e-Government can be observed and measured. Orlikowski and Baroudi (1991) attest that there is a positivist perspective dominance that binds information systems researchers together and limits the way and how the information systems are studied. The scholars posit that the positivist world view is premised on *a priori* understanding of some phenomena, hence serve to test the theory.

4.2.2 The constructivist orientation of the study

This study responds to the cries of Orlikowski and Baroudi (1991, p. 7) when they argued that a larger chunk of Information Systems research takes a positivist orientation, thereby neglecting the perspectives of the other paradigms. Crotty (1998) and Mavetera (2011) suggest that the role of the enquirer is to emerge as partners in the construction of meanings of social action. The constructionist epistemology assumes that knowledge comes from the society as the individuals experience the world (Creswell, 2003; Cordella & Shaik, 2006). In context, through the ontology of interpretivist, the “reality” about e-Government is thus subjectively created through the researcher’s interpretations of the e-Government processes and experiences by the citizenry. Using the same phenomenon of the ‘digital divide’ described above, the constructionist or social constructionist ontology recognises the existence of the ‘digital divide’ and the individual differences in using the technological innovation as ontological aspects. The

epistemological assumptions are that the truth is experientially created by individuals or shared by groups as they interact with the technology. Hence reality is an outcome of multiple perspectives of the participants in any given phenomenon”(Chikerema, Mavetera and Jantjies, 2016). Similarly, culture is thought of as an ontological aspect of the relativist world, but Heeks and Bailur (2007) argue that in such a worldview the meaning of culture and its relationship to e-Government might be constructed through social interaction. The scholars argue that the methodological assumption is to use a subjective method such as an interview.

Actor-Network Theory, through its principles of agnosticism, generalised symmetry and free association, refutes the socio-constructivist epistemology in that it is essentialist. However, the principle of free association in particular according to Callon (1986) encourages that there be no a-priori distinctions and dichotomies the diverse actors. Therefore, the ontological assumption of the ANT acknowledges the existence of people, technologies, services, policies, skills, issues of adoption in a relativist world. What is there to know in the relative reality are the relationships amongst the ontological aspects. In the same vein, Mavetera (2011) in his discussion of the humanist grounding in Information systems, clarifies that the experiences of human actors are not determined by the environment. The scholar argues that these experiences are created as the human actors interact with the environment. What constitutes the environment are not only human actors, but non-human actors with which the human actors interact. The role of the inquirer in this case is descriptive rather than participatory. Therefore, the ANT takes the intermediary approach between constructivism and techno-determinism along the continuum of philosophical assumptions. On one end of the continuum, constructivism assumes that technology does not matter as reality is socially constructed and on the other end technology exerts an impact that is well-defined regardless of context (Heeks & Bailur, 2007).

Cordella and Shaikh (2003) argue that, in contradiction to its ontological foundation, the Actor-Network Theory has been used in Information Systems as a lens (means) to extract data (Interpretive construction) rather than as ontology. Cordella and Shaik (2006) argue that the reality of the ANT assemblages is constructed by the interplay of the actors. The philosophical assumption in such a worldview is constructivism. However, the source of construction of the meanings is what distinguishes ANT from the foundational interpretive constructivism. To understand the e-Government trajectory “one may need to look beyond a flavouring of ANT, to the direct application of the specific framework”: the translation process (Heeks & Stanforth, 2007, p. 3) and knowing what is being translated (Cressman, 2009).

4.2.3 Realist orientation of the study

The realist philosophical position postulates that objects exist independently of the mind (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009, p. 114). The scholars argue that realism exists in two forms: direct realism is predicated on what we experience through the senses; on the other hand, critical realism argues that experience can be viewed in two forms: the actual experience and a mental model (say an advertisement which is a part of the bigger picture). The critical realist position argues objects exist independently of the mind but values also the interpretive perspective (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009, p. 114; Maxwell & Mittapalli, 2010; Ruhode, 2013). In totality, critical realism fills in the gaps created by the positivist and interpretive positions (Ruhode, 2013). This view is echoed and explained in the following observation:

“we will only be able to understand - and so change - the social world if we identify the structures at work that generate those events or discourses...These structures are not spontaneously apparent in the observable pattern of events; they can only be identified through the practical and theoretical work of the social sciences” (Bhaskar, 1989, as cited in Maxwell & Mittapalli, 2010).

Bhaskar illustrates that natural science is not just about observable patterns of events but also about the structures from social science that generate the events that are observed. As Saunders et al. (2009) argue, the direct realist perspective suggests an unchanging world whereas the critical realist perspective recognises that a multi-level study can change how the inquirer perceives that which should be known. Critical realists would want to understand and explain the phenomenon using a variety of research methods (Mingers, 2002). In acknowledgment, Maxwell and Mittapalli (2010) posit that critical realism maintains ontological realism while accepting some form of epistemological constructivism.

4.2.4 Pragmatist orientation of the study

Pragmatism was advanced through the works of Charles Peirce (1839-1914), William James (1842-1910) and John Dewey (1859-1952) amongst other American philosophers. The philosophers advanced the notion of examining practical consequences and empirical findings in attempting to understand phenomena and to decide on the next steps (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004). The pragmatist paradigm refutes the view of paradigm incompatibility, but rejects their pluralism in support of merging them into one (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Johnson, Onwuegbuzie & Turner, 2007; Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). Pragmatism, as a position, is characterised by its pluralistic nature, allowing it to draw from both quantitative and qualitative methods, affording methodological eclecticism and strengthening the fuller understanding of a research problem (Creswell, 2003, 2009; Saunders et al., 2009). Pragmatism is “...aimed at producing useful information rather than understanding the true nature of the world” (Mingers, 2002, p. 297).

4.2.5 Paradigmatic comparisons

Saunders et al. (2009) summarise the comparisons of paradigms and data collection techniques that are plausible for use with each paradigm as illustrated in Table 4-1.

Table 4-1: Comparisons of paradigms

Assumption	Positivism	Realism	Interpretivism	Pragmatism
Ontology: the researcher's view of the nature of reality or being	External, objective, and independent of social actors	Is objective. Exists independently of human thoughts and beliefs or knowledge of their existence (realist), but is interpreted through social conditioning (critical realist)	Socially constructed, subjective, may change, multiple	External, multiple, view chosen to best enable answering of the research question
Epistemology: the researcher's view regarding what constitutes acceptable knowledge	Only observable phenomena can provide credible data, facts. Focus on causality and law-like generalisations, reducing phenomena to simplest elements	Observable phenomena provide credible data, facts. Insufficient data means inaccuracies in sensations (direct realism). Alternatively, phenomena create sensations which are open to misinterpretation (critical realism). Focus on explaining within a context or contexts	Subjective meanings and social phenomena. Focus upon the details of the situation, a reality behind these details, subjective meanings motivating actions	Either or both observable phenomena and subjective meanings can provide acceptable knowledge dependent upon the research question. Focus on practical applied research, integrating different perspectives to help interpret the data
Axiology: the researcher's view of the role of values in research	Research is undertaken in a value-free way, the researcher is independent of the data and maintains an objective stance	Research is value-laden; the researcher is biased by worldviews, cultural experiences, and upbringing. These will impact on the research	Research is value bound, the researcher is part of what is being researched, cannot be separated and so will be subjective	Values play a significant role in interpreting results, the researcher adopting both objective and subjective points of view
Data collection techniques most often used	Highly structured, large samples, measurement, quantitative, but can use qualitative	Methods chosen must fit the subject matter, quantitative or qualitative	Small samples, in-depth investigations, qualitative	Mixed or multiple method designs, quantitative and qualitative

Source: (Extracted from Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009, p. 119)

4.3 Paradigm gap in Information Systems

Scholars have focused on the difficulties of reducing the Information Systems (IS) complexities using quantitative figures (Law, 2009; Goldkuhl, 2012) owing to the fact that IS are conducted within social organizations, making social science relevant in IS research (Mingers, 2002). According to the review of eighty-four papers on e-Government research, the studies were either explicit or implicit on philosophical assumptions (Heeks & Bailur, 2007). The scholars argued that under a quarter of the papers adopted a loose view of positivism (without statistical analysis), one was truly positivist and none took a constructionist stance. Three-quarters of the researches took an interpretive perspective. The greater part of the researches that were reviewed lacked both the theory and practice. Similarly and particularly looking at studies on e-Government in different countries of the SADC, it is interesting to note that some papers are silent on the paradigm though the inclination can be picked based on the underpinning theories or models that tend to be more on the positivist side in papers such as Bwalya (2009); Bwalya & Healy, (2010); Bwalya *et al.*, (2012); Bwalya, Du Plessis & Rensleigh, (2014); explicit critical realism (Ruhode, 2013); weak interpretive with theoretical framework used interchangeably within paradigms (Macueve, 2008); explicit post-positivist (Mtingwi & Belle, 2012); silent with just the mention of research approaches (Mutula & Pieter Van, 2006; Magayane, Mokuu & Lanrong, 2016), silent on both the philosophical assumptions and methodology (Mutula & Mostert, 2010b; Akakandelwa, 2011).

Such discrepancies demonstrate a dearth in the philosophical grounding in e-Government studies in the SADC. The existing studies on e-Government in the SADC hardly take a techno-socio deterministic stance except for the study by Ruhode (2013) that took a critical realist stance. Critical realism treats key factors as if they were real but accepting subjectivity or intersubjectivity in the way the factors are perceived (Mingers, 2002; Heeks & Bailur, 2007). Though the critical realist worldview accepts realism and subjectivism, it is essentialist owing to its skewness towards the realist position. Because of the on-going paradigmatic debates, researchers are hesitant to take the middle position that mixes the positivist and constructionist paradigms as underlying assumptions are regarded as incommensurable. In the same vein, Denzin, Lincoln, and Guba (1994) also posited that the incommensurability of paradigms such as positivist and interpretivism owes to the fact that the axioms of each are contradictory and mutually exclusive. However, they also argue that methodologies are what can be mixed within a paradigm.

4.4 Pragmatism as a paradigm of choice in the study

Rejecting the essentialist view of systems, Law (2009) argues that systems are social entities comprised of technical bits and pieces and humans. In response to Law's actionable observation, this study is bounded by two philosophical extremes on a continuum running from the positivist and constructionist. Consequently, the approach led to the pluralism of paradigms and of methodologies in the study as reflected in Figure 5-1. Pourdehnad, Wexler and Wilson (2011) postulate that anomalies in a paradigm may give rise to yet another into which they may fit. The incommensurability of these two paradigms (according to the paradigmatic incompatibility thesis) means that the study must seek other paradigms that accept the co-existence of methodologies accepted in both worldviews. Similarly, Weber (2004) contends that even if the debate on positivist vs. interpretivist were true, the critical aspect to consider is the goal of research that each is trying to enhance, echoing Tashakkori and Teddlie (1998, in Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009) who suggest that what matters is what is of value to each worldview and the contributions of the findings within that particular value system. As a reinforcement to the line of thought of Weber, Teddlie, Tashakkori, Sandelowski and Law (2009) argued that paradigms are a culture that guides "puzzle-solving" and whose success is a practical matter. Advancing the argument, Teddlie posited that pluralism of paradigms serving as the underlying philosophy is characteristic of Mixed Methods Research. E-Government studies are practice-oriented as actors are expected to interact to define their subjective reality. It is the dearth in the middle position paradigms in the e-Government research especially in the SADC that motivated the current study. Unlike the positivist and constructivist extremes which are treated as philosophical dichotomies, pragmatism stands in the middle of the continuum. According to Saunders et al., 2009 (p. 109), the pragmatist stance contends that "the research question is the determinant of the" ontological, epistemological and axiological assumptions. E-Government is not a new phenomenon; the reconstruction of meaning (constructionist) is intended for better understanding and to aid explanation; at the same time the existence of a human in the study, whose perceptions (as social facts) have an objective existence, motivates the blending of philosophical assumptions.

It is against this background that the study adopts the paradigm that underpins mixed method research (MMR) and epistemologically justifies the choice of mixing approaches and methods as pragmatism. Pragmatism seeks the balance of the underlying paradigms. Figure 4-1 illustrates this discussion based on the current study.

Figure 4-1: TAMANT Assumption framework
Source: Author

4.5 Research Approach

Research approaches are classified into three, namely Qualitative, Quantitative and Mixed Methods.

4.5.1 Quantitative Research

The quantitative research approach attempts to test causal relationships amongst the variables using statistical measures (Creswell, 2009, 2014; Mavetera & Kroeze, 2009; Clark & Ivankova, 2016), wherein the researcher should be independent of the researched (Neuman, 2006). Consequently, the data sources are expressed as numbers or scores obtained from precise measurements (Neuman, 2006; Creswell, 2009; Clark & Ivankova, 2016).

¹ : The broken lines leading to pragmatism signify, that "mixed method studies are not mixtures of paradigms of inquiry per se, but rather paradigms are reflected in what techniques researchers choose to combine, and how and why they desire to combine them" Sandelowski (2000, pp. 246–247)

4.5.2 Qualitative Research

Qualitative research is perceived as “ any type of research that produces findings not arrived at by statistical procedures or other means of quantification” (Strauss & Corbin, 1990, p. 11; Mavetera, 2011, p. 47). In addition, the truth about a phenomenon can only be socially constructed as participants interact with the world (Kaplan & Maxwell, 1994; Merriam, 2002; Mavetera, 2011; Clark & Ivankova, 2016). Yin, (2011, pp. 7-8) qualifies the qualitative research as applicable under the following five features:

- i. Studying the meanings of people’s lives under real-world conditions;
- ii. Representing the views and perspectives of the people;
- iii. Covering the contextual conditions within which people live;
- iv. Contributing insights into existing or emerging concepts that could help to explain human social behaviour; and
- v. Striving to use multiple sources of evidence rather than relying on a single source.

The five features underscore the ‘emic’ perspective (that is the participants’ frames of references) in qualitative research. In addition, Snape and Spencer (2003, p. 7) allude that the psychological, social, historical, and cultural factors also play an integral part in shaping the participant's world. Kaplan and Maxwell (1994) argue that the participants’ subjective meanings about their world allow for an understanding of the context as they experienced it, and aiding explanation of the influences of the phenomena. The qualitative research process is primarily inductive (data is gathered to build concepts not deductively deriving hypotheses to be tested) according to Kaplan & Maxwell (1994); Merriam (2002); Creswell (2009); Mavetera & Kroeze (2009). Qualitative research is richly descriptive as words and pictures help convey the truth of the phenomenon in context. The data can be in various formats including quotes, field notes, participant interviews and observations, excerpts from videos or tapes (Kaplan & Maxwell, 1994), electronic communication, the researchers’ impressions and reactions (Myers, 1997; Merriam, 2002).

4.5.3 Mixed Method Research (MMR)

Several scholars have argued that Information Systems are social and technical systems and as such information systems research lags behind as it fails to sufficiently explain the social phenomena using positivist positions (Hirschheim, no date; Kaplan, Duchon & Study, 1988; Cordella & Shaikh, 2003; Venkatesh, Brown & Bala, 2013). Hence, the wedding of quantitative and qualitative methodologies to generate what is commonly termed as Mixed Methods Research has become the bane of IS research (Creswell & Garrett, 2008; Creswell, 2009; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Clark & Ivankova, 2016). The Mixed method Research (MMR)

when used in one study affords the researchers the opportunity to minimize alternative explanations, simultaneously providing enough detail to explain divergent aspects of the phenomena (Clark & Ivankova, 2016, p. 9). MMR affords researchers the space and opportunity to develop and test the theory in single research (Mavetera & Kroeze, 2009).

Based on the analysis of nineteen (19) definitions on MMR and five themes namely: 'What is mixed?'; 'At which stage does the mixing occur?'; the breadth of the research; 'Why mix in research' and the orientation of the research, Johnson, Onwuegbuzie, and Turner (2007) expanded and coined the definition of mixed method research as:

“... the type of research in which a researcher or a team of researchers combines elements of qualitative and quantitative research approaches (e.g. use of qualitative and quantitative viewpoints, data collection, analysis, inference techniques) for the broad purposes of breadth and depth of understanding corroboration” (p. 123).

In addition to the stated mixing stages, mingling of the methods can happen at the stage of formulating research questions (Bryman, 2006; Creswell & Clark, 2007; Tashakkori & Creswell, 2007). MMR has also been known to promote the following: methodological eclecticism amongst researchers owing to its expansive, inclusive and pluralistic nature (Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009; Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2012); paradigm pluralism (Teddlie & Tashakkori, 2012, p. 776). Echoing the theme on breadth, scholars argue that wedding both the quantitative and qualitative research strengthens and broadens the understanding of research problems as opposed to their individuated approaches (Kaplan, Duchon & Study, 1988; Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Creswell & Garrett, 2008; Creswell, 2009; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Caruth, 2013; Venkatesh, Brown & Bala, 2013; Jokonya, 2014). Acknowledging the strength of MMR, some scholars posit that the fruits of this method add value to meta-inferences through the provision of varied perspectives and their intersections (Mason, 2006; Lisle, 2011, p. 87). Similarly, the MMR provides for the multiplicity of sources that can be used for triangulation and enhancing the research validity (Venkatesh, Brown & Bala, 2013). This view echoes the corroboration in the MMR definition by Johnson et al.(2007). The need for mixing research methods owes to the complexity and multi-dimensionality of the social phenomena that is being studied (Mason, 2006; Lisle, 2011).

4.5.4 Appropriateness of MMR in the study

The purpose of mixing methods is predicated on several rationales by different authors and varying contexts. These include: corroboration/ confirmation/ triangulation (Greene, Caracelli & Graham, 1989; Bryman, 2006; Creswell & Clark, 2007; Venkatesh, Brown & Bala, 2013; Clark & Ivankova, 2016); development/sequential; exploratory /explanatory (Greene, Caracelli & Graham, 1989; Bryman, 2006; Creswell & Clark, 2007; Venkatesh, Brown & Bala, 2013); complementariness (Greene, Caracelli & Graham, 1989; Venkatesh, Brown & Bala, 2013; Clark

& Ivankova, 2016); initiation (Greene, Caracelli & Graham, 1989); expansion (Greene, Caracelli & Graham, 1989; Venkatesh, Brown & Bala, 2013); compensation, completeness, diversity (Bryman, 2006; Venkatesh, Brown & Bala, 2013); embedded (Creswell & Clark, 2007; Creswell, 2009); and integrating (Creswell, 2009). The list is not exhaustive. However, Tashakkori and Creswell (2007); Creswell (2009); Fetters, Curry, and Creswell, (2013) argue that when a study has research questions with both quantitative and qualitative components, then the final product should use both the approaches. In the same vein, Venkatesh et al. (2013) argue that the reason for mixing should be determined by the research questions, purpose and context. Since the study research questions (see section 5.2) have the two components and the study follows a pragmatist position, it is logical that acceptable knowledge could be gleaned from a blend of the approaches and their perspectives as advanced by Saunders et al. (2009) in Table 5-1. The main purpose of using MMR in this study is “the development of enhanced perspectives using multiple angles” (Romm & Ngulube, 2015, p. 163). The rationale entails using results from one method to inform the other method, thereby enhancing validity through the effective and refined conclusions (Greene, Caracelli & Graham, 1989; Bryman, 2006). The development occurs at the instrument development level (Bryman, 2006), sampling and implementation levels (Greene, Caracelli & Graham, 1989).

E-Government is a social and complex phenomenon that needs appropriate conceptualization for its adoption challenges to be comprehensively addressed. As such there is inherent need to understand the context (specific settings/microsystems) within which the phenomenon is delivered. In this regard, it cannot go unmentioned that e-Government is not a new phenomenon and a plethora of research works have been published addressing the challenges that hinder its adoption. However, there is not much of a change to the low adoption levels in many governments (Belanger & Carter, 2008; Gupta, Dasgupta & Gupta, 2008; Rana & Dwivedi, 2015) including in the developing countries (Heeks, 2003; Mutula, 2008) despite knowing the nature of the challenges. The e-Government phenomenon needs to be explained using the voices of stakeholders through shared experiences (co-construction of the meaning) to aid in understanding and interpreting the findings reached by using statistical analysis. This approach could help understand the phenomenon as it occurs in heterogeneous diverse contexts and cultures across borders. In this regard, the study has a second rationale: *context*. According to Bryman (2006) the rationale entails using qualitative findings for a contextual understanding and the quantitative findings for broader understanding of the relationships amongst the study variables. The other rationale for mixing the methods in the study is to garner a diversity of perspectives (Bryman, 2006; Venkatesh, Brown & Bala, 2013). E-Government adoption has two perspectives, namely the supply and the demand side perspectives (see section 2.2.3). However, these are treated separately in the e-Government literature, yet they

should demonstrate a dynamic relationship where one perspective mediates and affects the other. Hence, mixing the qualitative and quantitative researches assists in achieving the sought diversity of perspectives in a single study and to broaden the understanding of the phenomena. This echoes the suggestion that mixed methods should be used only to provide a holistic understanding of a phenomenon whose existing research is fragmented (Venkatesh, Brown & Bala, 2013). It is expected that the interplay of the two groups of perspectives clearly informs the e-Government decision makers.

4.5.5 Integrated Research Question

The 'integrated' mixed research question that answers the study based on the nature of mixing (Creswell & Clark, 2007; Tashakkori & Creswell, 2007), and the methods or procedures (Tashakkori & Creswell, 2007) is given in Box 4-2.

To what extent do stakeholders' voices facilitate an understanding of the factors affecting adoption levels of e-Government in the SADC, using the developmental mixed method?

Box 4-2: Integrated Research Question

The integrated research question is hinged on eliciting stakeholders' perspectives on the factors that enhance the e-Government adoption in the SADC. Adoption is two-fold: firstly, adoption as the actual usage of e-services by citizens and business; and secondly, adoption in terms of the launch of e-Government initiatives by the Government and its agencies. This takes into consideration the heterogeneity of the stakeholders who are involved in the adoption of the phenomenon. Also, the integrated research question augments the purpose of MMR.

4.6 Research Design

A research design is a plan used for conducting research (Creswell, 2009). In addition, in MMR, it is a framework that guides the researchers on how qualitative and quantitative methods are implemented in the study (Clark & Ivankova, 2016). The integrated research question reflects the pluralism of methodologies. In terms of sequencing, the rationale for choosing the MMR in this study is for development. It is in this vein that, of the three MMR designs namely: concurrent, sequential and the embedded discussed by Creswell (2003, 2009), the sequential design stands out. The mixing of the qualitative and quantitative researches was done in sequence, one after the other.

However, whether the quantitative or the qualitative comes first (priority) is dependent on the "... interests of the researcher, the audience for the study... and what the investigator seeks to emphasize on the study" (Creswell, 2009, p. 207). The qualitative component was used first to

garner a deep understanding of the context of the Zimbabwe e-Government (with a smaller sample) and then explored with a larger sample in varied contexts. In acknowledgment, Mason (2006) suggests that mixed methods designs (whether sequentially or concurrent) that explore the qualitative data first add value to understanding complex components of the research. The two studies were equally weighted.

4.7 Case Study Research Strategy

A case study is a research strategy that seeks to understand in depth the dynamics of a phenomenon happening within specific single settings (Eisenhardt, 1989, p. 534; Yin, 2009, p. 18). Case studies have the potential: "...of generating novel and ground-breaking theoretical insights" (George & Bennett, 2005; Welch *et al.*, 2011, p. 741); and for the consideration of contextual factors (George & Bennett, 2005, p. 19; Mavetera, 2011, p. 59). However, Wieviorka (1992, p. 60) argues that a 'case' has no meaning until its interpreted or placed in its context by the observer. A 'case' can only be a 'case' if it has a unit of analysis that must be observed. Its significance can only be recognized if the observer considers a theoretical or analytical frame that becomes a point of reference at the time of interpreting the findings (Wieviorka, 1992; Yin, 2009). However, drawing from the Actor-Network theory, and borrowing from its principle of free association, there is no need to bring in a priori analytical frames of reference as these are made by the actors. The role of the researcher is to capture these through the descriptions of the actor-worlds by the actors themselves. In addition, Latour (2005) posits that if a case needs a frame, then it was not the correct choice of a case. The source of the construction of meanings in ANT is what distinguishes it from the foundational interpretive constructivism which is explanatory rather than descriptive. The latter is only plausible if we follow the actors and actants.

4.7.1 Research Design of the study

The study adopts a mixed-method design namely Sequential Exploratory within which a Multiple-Case is adopted as a case study research strategy. Hence, taking into consideration the two designs yielded a consolidated research design for the study as illustrated in Figure 4-2.

Figure 4-2: Integrated Research Design

Source: (Adapted from Creswell, 2009; Spinks & Canhoto, 2015; Yin, 2009)

Case Selection

A population defines the totality from which the research sample is drawn (Eisenhardt, 1989, p. 537). The study is grounded in the SADC context implying that the population takes into consideration the SADC population predicated on the populations of the individual countries in the region. The selection of cases is not synonymous to “the sample of cases” or “sample units” as if they were respondents in a survey; the cases are experiments (Yin,2009) and do not require representative sampling (Stiles, 2007). The cases are selected for theoretical reasons (Glaser & Strauss, 1967, as cited in Eisenhardt, 1989), to develop theory and illuminate relationships amongst constructs (Eisenhardt & Graebner, 2007). The scholars argue that the most important way of doing theoretical sampling is through consideration of “polar types”. However, in this study, the extreme cases were not considered as such, the study considered the middle cases. According to UN (2014), the e-Government survey reflected that of the fifteen (15) SADC member states Mauritius, Seychelles, and South Africa are amongst the six African countries whose EGDIs surpassed the world average of 0.4712. Eighty percent of the SADC countries fell in the middle EGDIs, inclusive of South Africa. However, only six of the SADC countries managed to surpass the Africa average EGDIs as reflected in Table 4-2.

Table 4-2: The Top SADC EGDIs from 2014 - 2018

Country	2014 EGDIs	2014 Rank
Mauritius	0.5338	76
Seychelles	0.5113	81
South Africa	0.4869	93
Botswana	0.4198	121
Namibia	0.388	117
Zimbabwe	0.3585	126
Swaziland	0.3056	138
Angola	0.297	140

Africa Average EGDIs 0.2661; World Average EGDIs 0.4712
 Source: (Adapted from UN, 2014, p. 22)

Each of the countries was a potential case in the study. However, borrowing from the words of Marshall (1996, p. 522), “it is rarely practical, efficient, nor ethical to study the whole populations”. Based on the reduced list reflected in Table 4-2, means the potential cases were reduced to eight countries as their EGDIs are above the Africa average of 0.2661 and have the potential of improving the e-Government adoption levels in their respective countries. From the listed eight countries, South Africa, Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe were then conveniently selected for ease of access to the sample. South Africa was amongst the exemplars in the

SADC region (in terms of EGDI). Despite being amongst the countries with high internet activity and infrastructure in the SADC, South Africa still had a low adoption challenge, qualifying it for further understanding of e-Government adoption status. Each of the selected countries has varying levels of internet penetration, infrastructure, culture, and literacy; aspects that are characteristic of the southern African countries.

4.8 Sampling

The study is focused on MMR at various levels with each of the studies involving a separate set of participants. It is in this vein that this section discusses the participant samples, sample sizes and sampling techniques employed in each study. The participants from the qualitative study were drawn from both Botswana and Zimbabwe with Botswana participants contributing to the qualitative pilot study. The participants were selected from the demand side. The participants were drawn from the following user groups: citizens, residents and immigrants, international users (Bertot, Jaeger & McClure, 2008), and organisations (Rowley, 2011). According to Marshall (1996, p. 522) the appropriateness of a sample size is dependent on adequate answers to research questions. In addition, practically the numbers are known as the research progresses and can only stop when saturation point is reached (Marshall, 1996; Marshall, Bryan; Cardon, Peter; Poddar, Amit; Fontenot, 2013). The saturation point is conceptualised as the point in data collection or analysis at which new information that is collected triggers little or no change in the code book (Gasson, 2003b; Guest, Bunce & Johnson, 2006). However, Patton (2002, p. 244) argues that the sample size depends on what is at stake, the available time and resources and the purpose of the study. Similarly, Mavetera and Kroeze (2009) argue that qualitative research is not about the sample size, but, it is about the rigour with which the data is analysed. Despite all these affirmations on sample size, the underlying factor of the saturation level in qualitative research can only be determined when data collection and analysis has been done.

According to Marshall (1996, p. 522), selecting participants randomly in qualitative studies is inappropriate, citing theoretical and practical reasons including large sampling errors even in small samples; the characteristics of the entire population being hardly known; rarity of representativeness of a random sample whose population characteristics are distributed normally; and the belief amongst qualitative researchers that participant “richness” is unevenly distributed. For this reason, purposive sampling was used in qualitative studies to select units that were best associated with answering the research questions of the study (Teddlie & Yu, 2007). However, selecting individual cases in such a heterogeneous population was difficult. To avoid uninformed responses, the snowball technique was used to reach the target populations.

The sample in the quantitative research was drawn from Zimbabwe, Botswana, Namibia and South Africa. Each of these cases had participants drawn from the demand side as was the case in the qualitative study though at a larger scale. In turn, the collection of the mailing lists for each group formed the sampling frame for this study. Participants were randomly selected from each of the strata so that each sub group is represented in the sample (Teddlie & Yu, 2007).

4.9 Data collection techniques

Since the study adopted a mixed method approach it was inevitable to collect quantitative and qualitative data. Runeson and Höst (2009) concurs with the use of several data sources to complement the interpretations. To achieve that, the collection of the qualitative and quantitative data was done through three different data gathering techniques namely: interviews, a questionnaire and document analysis. Following the ANT principle of 'freedom of movement of data', the sources of the qualitative data were garnered from the heterogeneous sources that included sources from document analysis and the interviews. Cohen, Manion, and Morrison (2007) argue that interviews, as a tool for data collection tool, afford an exchange of views in multiple ways including verbal, non-verbal, spoken and heard. To collect qualitative data from the participants in both the pilot and main study cases, semi-structured interviews were used. The attractiveness of semi-structured interviews owe to their flexibility in allowing for additional questions to be asked by the researcher as a follow up to the participant replies; the order of the questions may vary from interview to interview, and some questions may be omitted depending on the context (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009, p. 320). By using the technique, we expected to elucidate the perspectives of the participants based on their interaction with the technology and the government departments in context. As the semi-structured interviews were conducted, some interviews were audio-recorded using the "Sony Lightweight 4GB MP3 Digital Voice IC Recorder with Built-in Stereo Microphone" where permission was given. Audio recording allowed the researcher to focus on non-verbal cues. In such situations and where permission to audio-record the interview was not given, note-making was used instead. The researcher ensured that the interview environment was quiet. Face to face interviews were used for those who did not want to be recorded.

A structured online and self-administered questionnaire was used for collecting quantitative data from South Africa, Botswana, Namibia, and Zimbabwe participants in the second phase of the study. Furthermore, the questions were close-ended to limit responses to the centre on selected themes. The rationale for using a questionnaire in the second phase of the study was grounded on the fact that the researcher intended to explain the relationships between the e-Government variables in context based on the findings from the qualitative case. In addition, the geographical distribution of the participants was dispersed over four countries. A self-

administered questionnaire was used in the study. However, where the participants had language challenges the interviewer-administered questionnaire was an option.

Saunders et al. (2009) reiterates that the self-administered questionnaire was good for a large sample; it has high confidence that the right person responded if using email; and has a low likelihood of contamination. However, Burgess (2001) argues that the response rates for questionnaires are roughly 20% of the population, hence, it is important that the inquirer sends out five times the number. Similarly the response rate can be as low as 11% for internet-mediated questionnaires (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). It is recommended that the larger the number of respondents, the better to keep the questions structured or closed (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2007; Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009). As part of data collection, the secondary data from written documents such as newspaper clippings, government documents on policies, websites, and journal articles were read to substantiate the perspectives of the participants. It is also important to understand how the e-Government services are communicated to the citizens, hence document analysis aided in this regard. Also, the data collected using the document analysis techniques helped triangulate findings from the other sources discussed above.

4.10 Pilot study data collection techniques

Two pilot studies, one for the qualitative study and the other for the quantitative study, were conducted using the data collection methods intended for the main studies. The pilot study for the main qualitative study was done for Botswana as a selected case for its accessibility, convenience and geographical proximity to the inquirer (Yin, 2009). The pilot for the quantitative study was done online and offline to appeal to and cater for the different needs of the participants. The outcome of the pilot study then moderated and informed the actual data collection methods used in the main quantitative study.

4.11 Data analysis and integration

The MMR exploratory sequential designs are integrated through methods by way of connecting (Creswell, 2003, 2009; Hanson *et al.*, 2005; Fetters, Curry & Creswell, 2013). According to Onwuegbuzie and Teddlie (2003, as cited in Onwuegbuzie & Leech, 2006), the analysis of quantitative and qualitative data in MMR has to go through at least some of the following steps: data reduction, data display, data transformation, data correlation, data consolidation, data comparison and data integration. The data from the three country cases were collected and analysed separately (Caracelli & Greene, 1993) in a two-phase analysis and then integrated. In the first phase, the qualitative data collected from Botswana (pilot) and Zimbabwe (main) was

analysed. The results informed the design of the instrument that was administered in the second data collection phase leading to the second phase analysis.

4.11.1 Qualitative data analysis

“Actor-network theory is a disparate family of material-semiotic tools, sensibilities, and methods of analysis that treat everything in the social and natural worlds as a continuously generated effect of the webs of relations within which they are located. It assumes that nothing has reality or form outside the enactment of those relations. Its studies explore and characterize the webs and practices that carry them. Like other material-semiotic approaches, the actor-network approach thus describes the enactment of materially and discursively heterogeneous relations to produce and reshuffle all kinds of actors including objects, subjects, human beings, machines, animals, “ nature”, ideas, organizations, inequalities, scale and sizes, and geographical arrangements” (Law, 2009, p. 141).

In the extract above, Law (2009) reiterates on the completeness and sufficiency of the reality within the actor-network. The actors within an actor-network have their characteristics influenced by the other actors they interact with – catering for the material-semiotic nature of ANT. Having considerations to anything outside the actor-network is added flavour to controversies assembled in the actor-world, depicting lack of agency by the actors. According to the Innovation Translation, the lack of action by the assembled actors renders the actor with power in ‘potentia’ (paradox of power). The disappointment of flavouring the ANT is captured in the following quote:

“Adding another actor to provide those already described with the energy necessary to act. But, if you must add one, then the network was not complete. And if actors already assembled do not have enough energy to act, then they are not ‘actors’ but mere intermediaries, dopes, puppets. They do nothing, so they should not be in the description anyhow” (Latour, 2005, p. 147).

Latour (2005) emphasises on what sets aside the ANT from the interpretive approaches whose reality is constructed through interpretation by the inquirer. According to Latour (2005) an explanation adds an agent and enriches the description by distorting the original state of the art depicted by the actors themselves. However, adding an explanation renders the actors passive intermediaries. If the actors assemble and reassemble their network, the researcher should just describe the process as it is and there should not offer any explanation by the inquirer. There is a consensus that that actors shape their reality in interaction, which is necessitated by the intermediaries in circulation amongst the actors (Callon, 1990, p. 134; Cordella & Shaikh, 2003). Thus, actors have relational materiality. As such, description gives voice to the actors to express themselves (Wright, 2016) to which Latour (2005) emphasises the unstitutability and irreducibility of an actor in actor-network. In order to trace the webs of relations in e-Government , Latour (2005, p. 134) suggests keeping a manual or digital four notebooks.

Latour's Notebook 1: Log of Inquiry

The notebook serves as an audit trail to keep track of the study details such as who was interviewed, sources of data, dates and time.

Latour's Second Notebook

The notebook is used "... for keeping items in chronological order and to dispatch them into categories which evolve later into more and more refined files and subfiles" (Latour, 2005, p. 134). In this regard, having to produce categories, it was essential to stay close to the participant voices through tagging their quotations from the transcripts and various primary documents. The process entailed *open coding* as it is called in grounded theory. According to Friese (2016, p. 10) open coding can be clearly defined as "the process of attaching labels to data segments". The codes were developed inductively from the collected data to identify the patterns and key ideas in the data. The summaries generated from the comparison of individual responses led to the development of categories and subcategories. Eventually when data is placed in the incorrect code, constant comparisons allow for redirection of the data to be placed where it analytically belongs (Strauss & Corbin, 1990). To keep track of the saturation point in the study, the code network was monitored for any changes in the code book and the code frequency was documented to assess the variability of category expressions by participants as sets of interview transcripts were added (Guest, Bunce & Johnson, 2006). The category exhaustion determined the saturation point. The code definition changes that emerged after a round of analysis was done.

Latour's third Notebook and Theoretical memos

Latour (2005, p. 134-135) posits that the third notebook "should always be there for *ad libitum* writing trials..." As the analyst is coding, there are insights, relationships or questions on events/interactions that come to mind that have to be explored later but have to be written immediately as they are thought of. In grounded theory, that process is called theoretical memo writing (Gasson, 2003b; Friese, 2016). The memos reflect the insights the inquirer has on the relationships between categories, new categories and cross categories during the coding process (Gasson, 2003b). The memos must be linked with the research questions and data for them to be valid, otherwise it would be mere speculation (Wright, 2016).

Latour's fourth Notebook

Latour (2005, p. 135) posits that "the notebook should be kept to register effects of the written account whose world has been unified".

4.11.2 Quantitative data analysis

The second phase of the analysis used data collected from Zimbabwe, Botswana, Namibia, and South Africa cases using structured questionnaires with closed-ended questions. The within-case analysis of each of the quantitative case was done followed by a cross-case analysis of the four country cases. This was aimed at separating the quantitative from the qualitative data insights. Eisenhardt, (1989) argues that corroboration of patterns by data from diverse sources strengthens the grounding. Otherwise if there are conflicts, further probing is done to reveal the cause, or an analysis bias. Accounting for patterns and variations helps in putting the data in the order in preparation for integration (Corbin & Strauss, 1990). Multi-case studies strengthen the findings by allowing for cross-case analysis and improved scope for generalisation compared to single case studies (Yin, 1981, 1994; Rowley, 2002; Flyvbjerg, 2006). Similarly, the cross-case analysis allows the inquirer to look beyond initial impression to seeing through multiple lenses (Eisenhardt, 1989, p. 533); to make generalizations that are particular to a phenomenon in context and also representative of a larger phenomenon (Wieviorka, 1992). The cross-case analysis helps unearth the difference amongst the selected cases including the dynamics behind the differences (Wieviorka, 1992; Thomas, 2011).

4.12 Integration

Integrating through Design: Fetters et al.(2013) argue that integration in MMR is done at three levels namely: design (basic designs, advanced frameworks), method and interpretation and reporting levels using different approaches. The integration *at the design level* employed in the study is the *Sequential Exploratory* one as it explores with the qualitative data and analysis first; and then uses the findings to inform the quantitative phase (Greene, Caracelli & Graham, 1989; Creswell, 2003, 2009, 2014; Johnson & Onwuegbuzie, 2004; Onwuegbuzie & Johnson, 2006; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011). The qualitative findings informed the development of the quantitative instrument and informed the choice of participants. The framework used within the sequential exploratory is that of a case study.

Integration through methods: The integration at methods level in a sequential exploratory or sequential explanatory design happens when the quantitative and qualitative researches are mixed at the analysis stage of the first and the data collection stage of the other (Creswell, 2009); or at the sampling stage in situations where the sample of the second has to be drawn from the participants of the first research (Fetters, Curry & Creswell, 2013). Such type of integration is said to be connecting (Creswell, 2009; Fetters et al., 2013). The study followed both. The second research was quantitative, hence required a larger pool of participants. The results at the analysis stage of the first were used to inform the instrument development of the

quantitative research and similar groups of participants of the qualitative study were included in the second though at a larger scale.

The visual process of integration shown in Figure 4-3 illustrates the connectedness of the study, the sequencing in the implementation of the MMR, and the basis of integration. In MMR, exploratory sequential designs are usually integrated at the interpretation and discussion stage (Hanson *et al.*, 2005). The integrative strategies in MMR include data transformation (Caracelli & Greene, 1993; Fetters, Curry & Creswell, 2013); joint analysis, and integration through narrative (Fetters, Curry & Creswell, 2013). The latter strategy, integration through the narrative is what the study followed. The rest of the strategies are beyond the scope of the current study.

Figure 4-3: Visual model of the Integration process of QUAL-QUAN
 Source: Adapted from Gable (1994, p. 118)

4.13 Building the emergent theory

“The theory is emergent in the sense that it is situated in and developed by recognizing patterns of relationships among constructs within and across their underlying logical arguments” (Eisenhardt & Graebner, 2007, p. 25). Eisenhardt (1989) suggests that the formulation of a research question that addresses a research gap and specification of variables could be used to shape the initial design of theory building. However, the scholar noted that both are tentative, with none guaranteed a place in the theory developed as they are also bound to shift as the research progressed. Furthermore, Eisenhardt and Graebner (2007) argue that the justification of why the research question has to be addressed by theory building rather than theory testing research must be made clear. In this regard, it is evident in the extant literature that there are theories of technology adoption that exist (including TAM, Extended TAM, and UTAUT) and measure the user acceptance of technologies using varying determinants. A plethora of e-Government research has been done (see Chapter Four) deductively testing such theories but not solving the existing challenges. However, the German Philosopher, Immanuel Kant argued that ‘a priori knowledge organises data obtained through the senses (Austin, Orcutt & Rosso, 2001; Bhattacharjee, 2012). This is echoed in the following extract:

“It is through inductive inference, based on our experience of the world that we survive. If we put our hand on the stove and it is burned, we learn that hot stoves will burn us. But then it is through deduction from empirical evidence that we can identify and avoid hot stoves.... Learning depends upon inductive-deductive cycles of analytical thinking” (Gasson, 2003b, p. 85).

It is our view, that the consensus between Kant and Gasson is the need to recognise the importance of induction and deduction, not only as dichotomies, rather as a continuum if research were to provide effective solutions to specific social problems. The inadequacy in the extant theory that addresses such a view owes to the paradigmatic incommensurability debate amongst researchers. As the advocacy of MMR slowly creeps into the research community, the study is motivated to develop a theory that has an abductive vein and considers processes, structures, people, technologies, design issues and their relationships collectively in the endeavour to enhance the success of e-Government adoption. Theory building using a case study would answer the ‘what’, ‘how’ and ‘why’ questions that linger in our minds. The procedure for building such a theory from the analysis stage in the study was guided by the following steps:

- i. Within case analysis of the case of *Zimbabwe*
- ii. Within case analysis of the case of *Botswana*
- iii. Within case analysis of the case of *Namibia*
- iv. Within case analysis of the case of *South Africa*
- v. Cross-case analysis between the case of Zimbabwe, *Botswana*, *Namibia* and the case of *South Africa*

- vi. Integration of steps (i) to (iv) (expected to yield emergent themes)
- vii. Data in cases (i) to (iv) was compared against constructs in (v), for the purposes of refining constructs and building construct measures (Eisenhardt, 1989).
- viii. Verification of emergent relationships using case evidence (replication logic) (Eisenhardt, 1989).
- ix. Compare the emergent theory or concepts with both the confirming and conflicting existing literature (Eisenhardt, 1989; Eisenhardt & Graebner, 2007).

4.14 Literature Review Analysis

The code development was influenced by the document analysis. In Figure 4-3 the engagement of the extant literature in various stages including instrument development, analysis of both the qualitative and quantitative data and integration stages are reiterated. The literature review analysis was done to understand how the findings of the current study corroborate or refute the existing ones documented in the literature review. The purpose of the literature review was to make the inquiry interrogate what already exists hence the literature analysis adds to the existing body of knowledge or rejects it with substantiated reasons from the current study. Eisenhardt (1989) argues that linking findings to existing literature endorses internal consistency since the findings are based on a limited number of cases. The iteration between theory and data stops when there is minimal theory improvement (Eisenhardt, 1989; Gasson, 2003b). The premise was that the consequent product would be a theoretical framework (theory).

4.15 Resources

The software used for the qualitative analysis is ATLAS.ti 8.2. The online questionnaire instrument was developed and deployed using Google Forms. The downloaded version or the same created using Microsoft Word 2016 was administered manually to the participants. For the statistical analysis of the quantitative data the SPSS and AMOS (a Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), a component of the SPSS package); the F. Hayes process tool; and the interaction plotter was used.

4.16 Research ethics

If it is not right, do not do it; if it is not true do not say it.—Marcus Aurelius

A 'case' as an object of study involves people, interpretations of the collected perspectives and the meanings that the people as participants attach to the phenomenon (Yin, 2003). It was therefore imperative that the study considered ethical propriety as a form of research validity.

4.16.1 Treatment of research objects and participants

Ethical issues delimit a how in any kind of research the participants were protected through the application of appropriate ethical principles (Orb, Eisenhauer & Wynaden, 2001; Clark & Ivankova, 2016). It was imperative and inevitable for the study to be proactive on ethical issues considering the involvement of human subjects in data collection. The following principles were observed in the study:

Approval from the Institution (ethical) review board (IRB): Since the study involves human participants, approval was sought from and granted by the Institution Review Board from North-West University Institutional Research Ethics Regulatory Committee (NWU-IRERC, South Africa. NWU-IRERC approved the project based on its approval by the **Human Sciences Research Ethics Committee (HSREC)**. The Ethics certificate number is **NWU-00405-16-A9**. See Annexure A1 for the digital copy of the ethical clearance Certificate

Autonomy- the principle considers the recognition of participants' rights to participation including the right to be informed about the purpose of the study, the right to freely decide whether to participate in a study, the right to withdraw (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009), and the right to ask questions. Participants were informed about the nature of the study, what was to be done with the gathered information, and the benefits of participating. The principle was achieved through the informed consent process confirming that participants are autonomous persons (see Annexure for Informed Consent template). There was a need for permission to gather data from relevant stakeholders by the researcher(s) (Creswell, 2003; Yin, 2009; Clark & Ivankova, 2016). The researcher sought permission from the potential participants prior to conducting the interviews. In the case of questionnaires, the instrument together with consent forms was shared with the participants. The signed consent form endorsed the permission to gather data to be used in the study.

Respect for gatekeepers - Permission to gain access to the participants at their workplaces was sought initially from the authoritative people (Creswell, 2003; Saunders et al., 2009). Emails and consent forms were sent directly to the potential participants. In the case of individuals in organizations, the emails were sent to gatekeepers requesting authorization to conduct the research and to gain access to the potential participants.

Privacy - the principle entailed respecting the participant's privacy (Yin, 2009). "Privacy is the control over others' access to oneself and associated information; preservation of boundaries against giving protected information and receiving unwanted information" (Sieber, 1992, as cited in Miles & Huberman, 1994, p. 293).

Anonymity – “Lack of identifiers, information that indicates which individuals or organizations provided which data” (Sieber, 1992, as cited in Miles & Huberman, (1994, p. 293). The study considered the anonymity of participants throughout the study. This was included in the consent form that their names or identities were not to be written in the instruments or used in the documents resulting from the study. It was communicated that aliases or pseudonyms would be considered in qualitative data. Permission to make identifying information public would be from the concerned participants prior to the publishing of the content (Creswell, 2003).

Confidentiality - “Agreements with a person or organization about what was done and was not done with their data; included legal constraints ”(Sieber, 1992, as cited in Miles & Huberman, 1994, p. 293). The information that was gathered from the participants in the study was used in the study only and could be used to harm their personal dignity (Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill, 2009; Yin, 2009).

Participant control on sensitive issues - According to Saunders et al. (2009), as an ethical consideration, the participant was given control to switch the recorder off where he/she was not comfortable with the questions in the case of audio recording of interviews/responses.

Reciprocity and trust - since the study meant to benefit the participants and the inquirer, the research findings were shared with the participants. This helped the participants in trusting the way the report was written. When betrayed, they would not endorse the findings. Such feelings of trust may come to haunt the researcher as they may not trust my work.

4.17 Chapter Summary

The chapter discussed the procedures for carrying through the study. The procedure included the discussion on the assumptions the study followed and how they influenced the methodological decisions of the study. According to the paradigmatic incompatibility thesis the two main underpinning theories (ANT and TAM) in their individuality followed separate paradigms that were incommensurable. However, pragmatism was the paradigm of choice in the study for its ability to accommodate methods from different worldviews. Consequently, the mixed method research was to be followed in a sequential exploratory way. Processes such as data collection, analysis, and integration of the data were detailed in a visual process that integrated both methods (see Figure 4-3) to guide the remaining part of the study. The procedures that were detailed in the current chapter were then put into practice in the subsequent chapters. The immediate next chapter reports on the data collection and analysis of the qualitative study.

5 QUALITATIVE DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

5.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the processes of the data collection, preparation, and analysis for both the pilot and the main qualitative study. Both studies used the translation process as the basic ontology of analysis. The whole experience of the pilot study brought to fore the lessons learnt which informed the enhancements and rigour of the main qualitative study herein discussed.

5.2 Pilot study

The qualitative data entailed collection of data from a pilot case (Botswana). The pilot study was carried for the following purposes:

- i. Assess the time needed for the participants to complete answering the questions in the qualitative instruments
- ii. Ascertain the resources needed for the study
- iii. Establish whether the participants understood the questions since the data was gathered from different stakeholder groups. If ever there were issues of ambiguities these would be used for the modification of the main studies
- iv. The pilot study analysis was carried out as a learning curve on the use of qualitative software
- v. Assess the extent to which the qualitative instrument could elicit useful data from different stakeholders (pilot study analysis).

5.2.1 Qualitative pilot case interviewee profile

The main qualitative instrument was administered to heterogeneous participants; hence, it was imperative to ascertain whether various groups of people would understand the instrument questions without issues of ambiguity as stated in the preceding section 5.2 iii. In this regard, the qualitative pilot case data were collected from five (5) participants from Botswana through semi-structured interviews. The interviewees were purposefully drawn to represent distinct groups of professionals. The first interviewee, Karabo (pseudonym), was a Fulbright scholar from the United States of America, resident and working in Botswana at the time of collecting the study data. The second interviewee, Galalelo (pseudonym), was an Information technology (IT) graduate employed as a lecturer at a local university and had almost four years of teaching experience at the time of the interview. The third interviewee, Mr Moyo (pseudonym) was an experienced non-IT expatriate lecturer with over ten years of teaching at tertiary level. The fourth interviewee whose pseudo name is Mr Peters was as a farmer, businessman and an educator. Mr Peters claimed that he shuttled between his rural and urban homes fortnightly. The

fifth interviewee, Kamogelo (pseudonym), was a cleaner at a local organisation. The last two were Botswana citizens.

5.2.2 Pilot study data analysis

The pilot data was presented using only the first and second notebooks. These are described in detail in the subsequent sub sections.

5.2.2.1 Latour’s Notebook 1: Log of Inquiry

The notebook served as an audit trail to keep track of the study details such as who was interviewed, sources of data, dates, and time. A digital notebook was kept using a Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software (CAQDAS). ATLAS.ti 8.2 is a specialised CAQDAS that supports the integration of primary documents of different formats including text, pdf, images, and audio files into a project container called the Hermeneutic Unit (HU). In the study the HU was considered the log of inquiry as it was used to store, code, categorise, and retrieve inquiry data as and when needed. All five human participants consented to the interviews being recorded. The interviews were recorded as .wav files and transcribed into rich text format files. The transcription was done verbatim. However, the naming of the files was done in a way that would remain anonymous even to the interviewees. The transcripts were then verified against the respective audio recordings for accuracy as soon as the data was transcribed. In addition, the transcripts were shared with the participants for further verification to ascertain that what was captured in the transcripts was a true reflection of what was said during the interview with the respective participants. Verbatim transcription meant capturing the real names in the transcripts, hence the transcripts needed to be anonymous. The transcripts were then corrected by replacing the names of the participants with pseudonyms where individual and/or company names were given. This was done prior to data analysis. A sample transcript is archived at Annexure A6. Table 5-1 shows the names of both audio and text files and their alignment in terms of the naming convention.

Table 5-1: Qualitative pilot case details

Interviewee document id	Interviewee Pseudonym	Interview audio file name	Interview text file name
D1	Karabo	I01Ma_01.wav I01Ma_02.wav	I01Mt.rtf
D2	Mr Peters	I02Pa.wav	I02Pt.rtf
D3	Galalelo	I03Ta.wav	I03Tt.rtf
D4	Mr Moyo	I04Ra.wav	I04Rt.rtf
D5	Kamogelo	I05La.wav	I05Lt.rtf

The pilot interview transcripts were deposited in the HU as rich text format files (.rtf) as shown in Table 5-1. The resulting network of the primary documents was created as shown in Figure 5-1.

Figure 5-1: Botswana Pilot Primary Documents Network

The semi-structured interviews were used hence the number of questions that were asked was not the same across interviewees owing to their different contexts. To support the pilot case and for triangulation purposes, websites were accessed owing to their being mentioned by participants. These websites were considered as the non-human participants that also needed to be traced to understand the material-semiotic relationality of the actors involved. The network of the screenshots of the websites, representing the non-human participants is shown in Figure 5-2.

Figure 5-2: Botswana e-Service availability evidence network

5.2.2.2 Latour’s Second Notebook

The Hermeneutic Unit that is mentioned in Notebook 1 kept different sources of data as primary documents. The primary documents were numbered as they were entered into the HU (e.g. D1 designates the first primary document). Quotations from D1 were also be preceded by ‘1’ and a

colon ':'). The analysed data from the PDs was stored in the form of codes, memos, code groupings, quotes, networks, network groupings, and memo groupings in the HU giving the data some form of ordering. The data in the hermeneutic unit such as text, audio or video could be coded, refined, and categorised as analysis progressed. The data collected from five participants were coded using open coding. The process started with the first Interview transcript with new codes being added in the HU. As the coding process progressed, if some selected quotation was tagged with a code that already existed in the HU, the List coding was used instead. The five interviews generated forty-seven (47), thirty-eight (38), twenty (20), eighteen (18), and eleven (11) new codes representing 100%, 44%, 19%, 15% and 8% increases, respectively. The code network monitoring was done, though not completely to 0%, because this was a pilot study. It can be noted in Figure 5-3 that the change in the codebook was gradually decreasing for the five interviews demonstrating that the codification process was making use of List coding at some point.

Figure 5-3: Code changes in the pilot code network

A total of one hundred and forty-one (141) codes were created in the pilot HU. These were constituted of one hundred and thirty-four codes (134) from the five pilot interviews and seven (7) codes created from the additional secondary documents such as Botswana Post and Ministry of Agriculture websites represented by document 6 to 10 (D6 to D10) in Figure 5-3. The additional documents were included in HU because they were mentioned by the interviewees. For example, because of Quotation 5-1, D8 was accessed.

D 2: I02Pt - 2:6 There is a Botswana Post application that I use when my car license ex... (3441:3728)

There is a Botswana Post application that I use when my car license expires. I do not have to go and queue, I just need to go to the app and renew the license for my car. I can also renew within the same app, I can also o renew my post Office number because I have to do it every year.

Quotation 5-1: Botswana Post app for car license renewal

Document 8 was accessed and added to the HU in search of the triangulation points. As reflected in Figure 5-4, this represents a screen shot of the Botswana Post website, the Botswana Post App does exist for vehicle license or postal box number renewals as claimed by the participant represented by the transcript I02Pt. The additional documents, D6-D10 were all presented in the HU as '.png' files except for D9 which was added in a portable document format. Each one of them was an evidence file, hence, the fewer the codes reflected in Figure 5-3 for documents 6 to 10.

Figure 5-4: D8 representing www.botspost.co.bw/Botswana post-app-0

Figure 5-5 shows the Initial one hundred and forty-one (141) codes from the first cycle of coding. These were grouped together and a global view network of codes was created (*the initial codes in the HU after the first cycle coding of the pilot data in Annexure G*). The codes in the HU were then reviewed and regrouped, split, and/or merged to appropriately refine the code labels. The process resulted in a reduction of the code swamp from one hundred and forty-one

to one hundred and twenty-five codes in the code book. Axial coding sought to establish the relationships between codes in the HU, leading to the creation of categories and subcategories based on the similarities and differences of the HU codes. The related codes that were placed in the same category were colour-coded to uniquely identify the groupings in networks. To help the reader resonate with the colour coding, the respective descriptions were defined as in Table 5-2. In the process of axial coding, some new codes were created, and some merged or split, causing fluctuations in the total number of codes in the HU. The resulting code groups are shown and described in Table 5-2.

Table 5-2: Colour code Definitions of categories

Category	Category description	Group Code Colour
Place of Consumption	Codes in the category depict various points of accessing the service. The places of consumption facilitate the provision of convenience and reduction of costs to the citizenry	
Awareness	Codes in the category include ways in which the availability of e-service is communicated to the citizenry	
Popular Core services	Codes in the category reflect the common services that participants are aware of	
Facilitating Resources	The codes in the category reflected the intermediaries that are used by the participants in accessing the e-Government services	
Supporting Services	Codes in the category share ways in which participants are supported in the process of interacting with the service	
Intermediary Usage Trends	Codes in the category show how the facilitating resources are used by participants whether directly or indirectly	
e-GOV Benefits	The codes in the group explain the benefits of e-Government as expressed by the participants	
Facilitating Conditions	The category that included codes from both the supporting services and the facilitating resources in accessing the e-Government services	
Trust	Codes in the category reflect the confidence/belief that the trustors (citizens) hold for the e-Government services	
Adoption barriers	The category includes codes that point to predictors of low adoption of e-Government services	
Feedback	The codes in the group reflect on the need to cajole the users of e-services through feedback channels such as email etc.	

Figure 5-5: The Initial Code Book Network in the HU after the second cycle coding of the pilot data in ATLAS.ti 8.2

Category: Place of Consumption - The participants claimed that e-Government services could be consumed directly in walk-in offices of the Government such as the Botswana Unified Revenue Service (BURS), Water Utilities Corporation (WUC) and Botswana Power Corporation (BPC). In such direct interactions, the personnel in the offices assisted the consumer in completing the services. According to the interrelationships of data elicited from the interview transcriptions, there was a merger between BPC, Botswana Post, and Choppies stores in the provision of the service of purchasing electricity tokens. In the case of Choppies, it was an extension of the direct walk-in service provision, whereas the Botswana Post App brought in the element of e-offices with self-service. Within the same App, Botswana Post further integrated the Botswana Department of Transport and Road Services (DTRS) in the provision of vehicle license renewals. This is demonstrated in Figure 5-6.

Figure 5-6: The place of consumption category network

The merger amongst government departments in the provision of the services was an endeavour towards effectiveness through the *whole or one Government approach*. The involved agencies collectively shared the e-Government knowledge and consumption points with the citizenry as a way of enhancing convenience in the service provision. Other than the walk-in channel, consumption of the e-Government services was also through websites. Such services

included the online tax returns, Botswana Animal Information, and Traceability System (BAITS) and the Livestock Identification Traceback System (LITS) from the Ministry of Agriculture.

Awareness - For the citizenry to consume the e-Government services such as the ones mentioned under place of consumption section there was a need for public awareness marketing towards sharing knowledge on the existence of the services and where they could be consumed. From the transcripts, e-Government awareness in Botswana was perceived as a phenomenon triggered by the government agencies through print media, SMS, newspapers, agency websites, and television and email communications. In addition, the participants applauded the communication through SMS and the workshops for e-filing and cybersecurity conducted by BURS. The extract from the experiences of Galalelo in Quotation 5-2 and 5-3 are detailed below:

3:18 That was good of them to do that. Did you find the workshop helpful?..... (6102:6720) - D 3: I03Tt

That was good of them to do that. Did you find the workshop helpful?

P

08:50-09:20

Yes, very much. They told us about what features to look for on a website before transacting, what to look for on an ATM before we insert the card, what body language to use to shield your personal details etc. What I found interesting was the fact that we are used to giving optional details online, we were told to avoid the optional ones, something that I never thought would matter. They gave a role play on the idea, it was eye opening.

3:19 I 09:24-09:47 You said you have been teaching for 4 years. I take it y..... (6724:7976) - D 3: I03Tt

I

09:24-09:47

You said you have been teaching for 4 years. I take it you have filled the tax forms for three years and this is your 4th year. In July, the previous tax registration for year ending 31 July 2017 was done online in Botswana though some chose to do it manually. How did you do and how do you intend to do it this year?

P

09:47-11:00

They sent us the link to register. So, you would register and then you are sent a password that was to last 24 hours after it was sent. The strength of the password was so complicated that you wouldn't remember it soon after you used it. They asked us to change it but still they would require a strong password that need a combination of alpha numeric. For those who did not manage, we needed to go there physically to activate the account. From there, it was optional whether you wanted to complete the online form in their lab or you go and do it at your own convenience at home or work. I chose to do it in their lab. In fact, the people who were helping us were just telling us what to do but I am not sure if people mastered it. However, this year, when they sent the link, I did not respond. But my friend told me it was easy so she will help me. I just can't stand the queues at BURS.

Quotation 5-2: Extract experiences from contexts provided by BURS

The Cyber Security workshops held by BURS to induct the citizenry surely boosted the participants' confidence in using online e-services. In terms of e-filing, the narration in Quotation

5-2 also depicts that it is not all citizens who would learn how to use the e-services on the first time they were taught. This was a lesson learnt that the strategies that are used for marketing e-Government services should be done persistently to address the diversely e-literate population. Still in Quotation 5-2 Galalelo expressed preference to being taught how to use the e-Government service by a friend. Similarly, Mr Moyo alluded to the fact that what drove him to embrace e-services such as internet banking was the influence of a friend. Quotation 5-3 recreates the conversation with Mr Moyo.

D 4: I04Rt - 4:29 So, you were talking about print media, sms, going to google, Is there... (13274:13796)
 So, you were talking about print media, sms, going to google, Is there a way that maybe a friend of yours or a family member who influenced you to use e-services?
 P
 16:52-17:16
 A friend absolutely. In fact, he didn't even tell me but I saw the way he was enjoying using this facility and I felt like perhaps I needed it like yesterday. Because things were so easy. He would tell me that I have already banked my money, I can see my bank balance, I can see all these things. I have bought this online and I got motivated.

Quotation 5-3: Socially and vicariously initiated awareness of e-Government services

Quotation 5-3 transcribed from the interview we had with Mr Moyo demonstrates that socially initiated awareness could play a pivotal role in e-Government adoption. As Mr Moyo recalled, he observed the thrills, the joy, and satisfaction of a friend as the friend interacted with e-services. That convinced the participant to ask for assistance on how to use e-Government services from this friend. In this regard, a code, socially initiated awareness, was created and added in the awareness network as illustrated in Figure 5-7 to emphasise the vicarious experience the participant had.

Figure 5-7: Awareness network based on the pilot study Popular Core services

Based on the discussions with the participants in Botswana, the e-Government services that they were aware of included purchasing of electricity tokens; vehicle license renewal; animal registration; ear tag registration which is a consequence of animal registration; and the most recent e-Government services in Botswana: e- tax registration and e-filing. The participants claimed that these services could be consumed through walk-in interactions such as purchasing electricity tokens at the Botswana Power Corporation offices, at Choppies stores or payment of water bills at the Water Utilities Corporation offices. Such services are termed full-services as they required a human intermediary to complete the service. On the other hand, payments of prepaid electricity through Internet banking, or through the Botswana Post app are examples of self-service which participants experienced in Botswana. The Botswana Post website was then accessed to triangulate the claim that prepaid electricity bills could be paid through the Botswana Post App. The evidence is provided in Figure 5-8 and further shares information on where the App could be downloaded and what to do thereafter.

Figure 5-8: Evidence of availability of Botswana Post App for the purchase of prepaid electricity

Figure 5-8 further clarifies that the Botswana Post App is also used for accessing Botswana Post services. Participants also claimed that the App could be used for the renewal of vehicle licenses and Post Office Box (See evidence in Figure 5-4). Despite access to water being one of the basic services provided by the government, the five participants had little to say about payment of water bills. To understand why the participants hardly mentioned the water utilities

e-services, the Water Utilities Corporation website was explored in pursuit to establish ways in which the citizens could access bill payment and bill inquiry services. On the WUC website, the water bills were either paid as a full service or paid over the internet as a self-service. The services were found to be explicitly available on the website through the links under the child menus of the parent menu entitled “Your Water Account”. The child menus had links about the client’s water account and understanding the client’s bill account. When the participants were probed, some claimed a lack of visibility and for some it was costly to access the service online. Only one of them said that she directly walked in the WUC offices to pay though she does it mid-month when there are not many people. Otherwise she said at the end of the month the queues are longer and quite frustrating.

Figure 5-9 shows the e-Government services that the participants claimed to have accessed.

Figure 5-9: Popular e-services in Botswana (e-Government)

Facilitating conditions - The participants acknowledged having access to facilitating resources such as cell phones, iPhones, iPads, and laptops. They also alluded to having access to supportive services such as workshops, menu-driven services, and links sent through emails by BURS. Since most of the participants also had access to intermediaries that connected to the internet made it possible for them to access the links that were shared with them. The facilitating conditions category included both the facilitating resources and the supporting services as illustrated in Figure 5-10.

Figure 5-10: Facilitating Conditions network

The facilitating conditions were not an end; instead they were the means to an end. The facilitating conditions made it possible for the citizen to interact with the Government through the e-Government services.

E-Government Benefits - When the participants in the pilot study were asked to express the benefits of using e-Government services, they shared views that revolved around three kinds of benefits as shown in Figure 5-11.

Figure 5-11: E-Government benefits (Pilot views)

As compared to the traditional, paper-based system, there was consensus that the e-Government reduced redundancy. Otherwise in the walk-in offices, even though the systems were computerised, the payments of bills were bound to be over the counter, in which case the system was operated by the personnel in the offices. The service was not a self-service. For one to be served quickly depended on the person interacting with the system and the availability of the network. Consequently, especially during month ends when people had their salaries

paid, the offices were usually characterised by long winding queues. In this regard, the participants indicated that e-Government supported the reduction of queues. With respect to the availability of the Botswana App that drivers used for the renewal of vehicle licenses, the participants cited that the App relieved them from paying penalties that are charged for the non-payment/ delayed license renewals.

Intermediary Usage trends - The facilitating resources such as the iPhones, iPads, laptops, and desktop computers were used to access social media tools which participants used for interaction in their social circles of friends, relatives, and/or colleagues. In addition, some participants indicated that they use mobile resources as intermediaries to lookup information from the Botswana Tourism website; pay bills; airtime top-up; pay DSTV subscriptions; access Apps; accessing teaching and learning resources, access webinars; and for communication. While e-services such as airtime top-up and payments for DSTV usage are not e-Government services, these are services that introduced the majority into using technology for transactional services through mobile and internet banking. Figure 5-12 shows what the participants use the intermediaries for.

Figure 5-12: Intermediary Usage trends in Botswana

Though some of the uses of digital technology such as buying of airtime e-top-up and e-subscriptions for DSTV services in Figure 5-12 may not be causally linked to e-Government, they did contribute to equipping the users with the digital skills and competencies necessary for enabling the digital literacy in the digitally permeated world.

Trust - The beliefs that participants had on e-Government were characterised by the trust in the Banking institution, and the trust in technology. The trust in the Banking institution was considered as the belief that the trustors had on the banking institutions that they used in making e-Government payments for the services received such as bill payments. Quotation 5-4 reiterates the faith Karabo has in that regard.

 D 3: I03Tt - 3:21 Yeah, I have shifted banks, I bank with Barclays currently. I have nev... (4975:5112)

Yeah, I have shifted banks, I bank with Barclays currently. I have never had problems, With Barclays I have been doing internet banking.

Quotation 5-4: Trust in the Banking Institution

Security Concerns - In relation to the trust in the Organisation and the trust in Technology, Quotation 5-5 alluded to why a trustor would have confidence in both the trust constructs. The participant endorsed the belief that they are safe in transacting with the Bank whether the service was a self-service or full-service.

 D 4: I04Rt - 4:15 So, you don't worry about security? P 07:16-07:21 Oohh, no. In fact,... (6092:6551)

So, you don't worry about security?

P

07:16-07:21

Oohh, no. In fact, I have been using this for the past three years, and I have never had any breaches of security to my account.

I

07:21-07:26

Ok. But you have heard of other people whose accounts have been breached?

P

07:26-07: 41

I have heard about them. When I heard about them sometimes it really goes into my mind and say " am I safe?" . I would want to say overall, I have full trust in the system.

Quotation 5-5: Security concerns

Quotation 5-5 demonstrates that it was necessary but not sufficient to know how to use facilitating resources to access the e-Government services. Rather, it was important to develop an understanding that aided in making appropriate choices of resources/tools to use in different technological contexts; evaluations and discerning judgments on digital adoption; and making assessments of the risks associated with disclosing personal details online. Despite having heard of security breaches, the participant insisted on maintaining their faith/loyalty with the banking institution. Such behaviour validated the confidence and satisfaction that the participant had in the Banking Institution since the activities were part of the participant's value chain. Internet banking to the participant added the aspect of convenience to the extent that the

security breaches that they heard of were considered as isolated cases since their relationship was that of trust. To the participant, the bank was prepared to protect their accounts from malicious attacks.

Feedback - One of the international participants shared their experiences in the Botswana Tourism website. The participant referred to the importance of feedback and making a follow up to the website visitors as a form of customer relationship management. The participant visited the Botswana Tourism website but never went back to the website to give a rating on the experience on the site. When asked why, the participant claimed that there was no email follow-up on the previous visit compared to other previous experiences with sites like tripadvisor.com. The narrative that the participant shared with the interviewer demonstrated the need for website tracking in all web-based e-Government services. Tracking the website visitor would allow the supply side to glean insights on the e-customer behaviour and preferences and thereby to serve them adequately. Investing in improving user experience is critical in the retention of the users and their tracking for optimising the design. Quotation 5-6 relays the claim.

Quotation 5-6: Need for feedback to website visitors

Quotation 5-6 also points to the criticality of feedback to e-customers for the services they consumed. There is a leaf to borrow from the Online Travel Agents (OTAs) such as Trip Advisor and Booking.com when it comes to e-CRM. E-mail marketing or using the Chabot to cajole the online visitor to be sticky can be a marketing strategy in e-Government. The last comment in Quotation 5-6 shows losing an e-customer takes closing the app/ webpage/window, and they go. The same participant claimed in Quotation 5-7 that one of the reasons they did not do electronic payments especially with Automated Teller Machine cards was to avoid overspending. However, though it may appear as a financial prudence and discipline issue, the

aspect of notifications for the transaction(s) electronically made is important too. The availability of such services to the user has to be addressed. Usage of these notifications may be a choice but the users need to be aware of the service so that they make informed decisions. Notifications also can be used by participants to track their online behaviours and logs of their transactions.

P

08:00:00- 8:05:00

Yeah , I pay cash unless it's a large transaction

I

08:05:00- 8:06:00

Why do you prefer traditional ways?

P

08:07:00- 8:39:00

I think it helps me keep track of my spending [Interviewer laughs], say you take out two hundred dollars a week for example and at the end of that week , and you spend it on food , petrol, whatever, and by end of the week you have 50 dollars leftover , well then you can know that you spent exactly 150 but if you swipe your card here and there and here and there, and then you forget how much you spent

Quotation 5-7: Need for feedback for online transactions

Adoption Barriers - A participant suggested that they became aware of some of the e-Government services through media awareness campaigns such as newspapers (See Quotation 5-8).

P

05:10-05:16

Yes I have heard them. I heard it... it's in the papers.

Quotation 5-8: Evidence of awareness campaigns reaching the citizens

However, when asked why the continuance of traditional ways of bill payments despite having an awareness of a convenient way of making the payments, the participant reiterated that the challenge they faced was lack of the facilitating resources that could allow them to access the services (see Quotation 5-9).

P

05:47-06:02

The e-services...I am interested about this. But I don't have the phone to use them. That phone that is using that.

Quotation 5-9: Why I am not using e-services

Quotation 5-9 also raises the need for awareness campaigns on how cell phones and smartphones could be used to make e-payments for utilities. It suggests that the participant thought it was only smartphones that could facilitate e-Government transactions.

As such, some participants still use the over the counter way of utility payment as reflected in Quotation 5-9 and 5-10. The digital divide in the form of lack of resources amongst the citizens warrants that there are human intermediaries in the provision of e-services over the counter contexts.

P

03:22-03:45

I am checking in the electricity every day to check how much is it left. Then it is low, I am going to buy another one. The water bills, I am going there to pay them at the offices

Quotation 5-10: Evidence of over the counter bill payments 1

P

04:05-04:10

The units of motlakase I am checking them. I used to check them everyday.

I

04:10-04:12

So, how do you buy them?

P

04:12-04:17

How...I am buying them at Choppies or at BPC.

Quotation 5-11: Evidence of over the counter bill payments 2

Based on Quotation 5-9 to-5-11 there is evidence that the participant had the awareness that water and electricity bills could be paid through e-services. The participants lacked knowledge on exactly how to engage with e-Government services. The participant's account suggests that the adoption barriers vary from person to person. For some they have access to the facilitation resources but lack the awareness and for some it may be the procedure of using that lacks amongst others.

5.2.3 Lessons learnt from the pilot study

Learning point 1: Principle of anonymity - The naming of transcripts had to be checked thoroughly, especially if the anonymization was manually done. It emerged that one of the transcripts was added into the Hermeneutic Unit with the actual name of the participant. This was discovered during the open coding process. The sensitive detail was removed and updated. The process of anonymization of data enabled adherence to the ethical principles of confidentiality and anonymity in social research. In addition, it was discovered that the nomenclature (see the circled section of the transcribed document) was important for the recreation of the interview session. Using 'D1' was plausible for the identification of the transcribed document.

1:31 No, I wouldn't say didn't love it coz if I stay in lodge or something..... (9703:10053) - D 1: I01Mt

However, 'I01Mt' which was meant to make reference to the interviewee was alphanumeric and impersonal as show above.

Learning point 2: Interview duration per interviewee - The interview durations ranged between 8 (eight) and 23 (twenty-three) minutes, thus ascertaining that the interviews could be done within 30 (thirty) minutes as evidenced in Table 5-3.

Table 5-3: Pilot interview timings

Interview audio file name	Interviewee Timings
I01QPa_01.wav	00:13:41
I01QPa_02.wav	00:02:38
I02QPa.wav	0:08:09
I03QPa.wav	00:18:55
I04QPa.wav	00:22:36
I05QPa.wav	00:10:03

Learning Point 3: Effectiveness of the instrument - Despite the varying contexts, the pilot qualitative instrument was effective as data on e-Government services could be elicited from different stakeholder groups. The participants understood the questions clearly though some had little awareness of the term 'e-Government', despite having used some e-Government services prior to the interview. These included Galalelo who had the qualifications in technology and Kamogelo. Until then, it was not the first thing to say the participants could resonate with the terminology during the interview process. For this reason, the definition of the unique terms was shared in the questionnaire and with the interviewees where necessary.

Learning point 4: ATLAS.ti software - Pilot analysis aspect helped the researcher receive training on the use of ATLAS.ti as a Computer Assisted Qualitative Data Analysis Software (CAQDAS).

5.3 Main Qualitative Study Analysis

The section presented the analysis of the responses shared by the participants in the main qualitative study through the use of Latour's four notebooks. The translation process was adopted as the appropriate lens of analysis. Hence the notebooks and the stages of translation

were interlaced together to facilitate the description of the e-Government trajectory in Zimbabwe with emphasis on the meanings given by the study participants.

5.3.1 The First Notebook: Log of Inquiry

The same process used in the pilot study was followed with enhancements such as anonymization of individual/company names; and the nomenclature for the HU documents. Owing to the semi-structured interview and actor-network theory, there was no need to have predefined questions but only a few to start the interview. The rest unfolded as responses were being shared by the participants.

5.3.1.1 Problematisation

In the ANT, the actions of actors (both human and non-human) are treated indistinctly. The behavioural intentions to use the technology are equally influenced by human and technological characteristics alike through the process of translation. The Actor-network Theory gave the technological artefacts voices. The artefacts played a vital role in shaping the relationship between technology and the people, thus making information systems research richer. As such the study followed the four moments of the translation process as ontology to understand the relational mechanics of power and its distribution in the in e-Government networks in Zimbabwe (section 3.3.2.1).

To initiate the formation of networks, in alignment with the ICT policy, the government of Zimbabwe and its agencies (deemed the focal actors in the study) defined a problem as the traditional government processes that were bureaucratic and inconvenient to the citizenry (Problematization). Based on the analysis of the website of the office of the president, an ICT solution to the problems that were faced by the citizens in accessing government services and engaging with the government (also defined as the *Obligatory Passage of Point: OPP*) is captured in Figure 5-13.

Current E-Government Landscape in Zimbabwe Online Platforms And E-Services.

Published: Thursday, 24 August 2017 10:15

Hits: 1447

Recognising the critical role of ICTs, the Government of Zimbabwe has made several remarkable strides in the ICT sector. The E-Government Framework and Implementation Strategy 2011 - 2015, has been the key reference and guide for the implementation of e-Government programs and the following are examples of e-government systems to date:

- ☒ Online Passport Application System;
- ☒ E-Taxation - Zimbabwe Revenue Authority;
- ☒ E-health at Chitungwiza Hospital;
- ☒ Online Liquor Application System;
- ☒ Public Finance Management System;
- ☒ E-Visa - Department of Immigration; and
- ☒ High Performance Computing System (HPCS).

This adoption of an e-government thrust is to ensure convenient access to government interactive information, timely delivery of public services and, efficient and effective methods of

Figure 5-13: The extract of the OPP as given by the office of the President
Source: <http://www.theopc.gov.zw/index.php/news/ict-newsletter-blog/258-current-e-government-landscape-in-zimbabwe-online-platforms-and-e-services>, accessed on 09/08/2018

Figure 5-13 represents the solution to the Problematization as defined by the focal actor: Government of Zimbabwe (GoZ) who created an Obligatory Passage of Point (OPP) through which the other actors would pass. The OPP entailed accessing Government services through Information and Communication Technologies including personal computers, telephony, television, radio, the internet, satellite, and cellular networks. To this effect, the citizens were encouraged to embrace technology and adopt the e-Government services so that they could experience the enhanced service provision by the government; access real time and up to date information; improve the interaction between the supply and demand sides; have access to multiple communication channels for engagement; transact effectively at reduced costs, amongst other reasons.

At the time of conducting the study, the e-services that are marked in Figure 5-13 had been put in place by the focal actor as a solution to enhance service delivery.

- i. E-Taxation - the e-service was developed to afford the individual and company taxpayers to pay tax online. The platform would allow one to register for the e-services as a tax payer; file the tax returns; monitor the tax transactions; and receive notifications on filing Tax returns, and refunds through email/SMS or accessing it through the government website. The taxes included Income Tax, Value-added Tax (VAT) and the Pay as You Earn (PAYE). The e-service is accessible from the Zimbabwe Revenue Authority (ZIMRA) website (<http://www.zimra.co.zw/>)
- ii. e-Visa applications and online access to related information (Department of Immigration)
- iii. Zimbabwe Government Portal -The portal is a one-stop shop to all the other ministries. The functions of each of the Zimbabwe government ministries are accessible from the

portal. The portal acts as the gateway to the individual ministry websites and the Zimbabwe e-services Portal (ZimConnect). The site is accessible at <http://www.zim.gov.zw/>

- iv. Registration of companies and deeds online
- v. Online Passport Application System
- vi. e-financial transfers for government services such as customs and Excise services e.g. customs duty, tollgate fees
- vii. e-Municipality services (Informational and bill inquiries and payments)
- viii. Online Liquor Application System
- ix. Prepaid electricity tokens through the counter platforms, mobile and internet banking platforms, and agencies websites
- x. Informational services from the respective government ministries e.g. ictministry.gov.zw
- xi. E-Health services (online payments, telemedicine, Dyna Vision System, Chitungwiza e-Health System)
- xii. e-Education Services (e.g. Higher Education sponsorship, online applications, and admissions to institutions of learning, and fees payment)
- xiii. <https://zimeservices.pfms.gov.zw/>

Alshehri and Drew (2010, p. 39) state that partnerships between the private and public sectors in the provision of resources, skills and capabilities required to launch the e-Government solution were imperative. Through the national ICT policy of 2015, the government of Zimbabwe stated that the ICT sector had challenges including inadequate infrastructure and skilled ICT manpower. It then followed that to provide the solution, the government had to cajole and negotiate with other macro actors (private and public) who would assist in providing the solution. The alliance with actors including the ones shown in Figure 5-14 was formed. The availability of the above-stated e-services ascertained that the problem and solution proposed by the focal actor were consistent with the other actors though not necessarily with the micro actors.

Figure 5-14: Actor-network at the Problematization stage of the Translation process

5.3.1.2 Participant profiles

The actors in the study were the interviewees who were recruited to explore the formation and evolution of the networks in e-Government. The interviewees (termed human actors) were selected from a mix of professionals including 3 teachers, a lecturer with 20 years-experience, a student at a tertiary institution, a technician with three years' experience, a librarian, and a systems designer who were expected to be familiar with e-Government. Since the government is for the people whom it should serve without discrimination, included in the list of the human actors considered in the study was a self-employed participant (airtime vendor).

5.3.1.3 Changes in the main qualitative study influenced by the pilot study

As Latour (2005) would put it, everything from the first telephone call to the prospective interviewee was data that had to be recorded. In that vein, the recordings and transcript files were named using the following nomenclature to capture the necessary details:

<Date>_<pseudonym>_<R / UR>_Int_<1st letter of Country><PS/MS>.<file extension>

'UR' denoted the unrecorded interview whilst 'R' denoted recorded interview. *Int* stands for an interview; while *P* signified that the study was a pilot; and *M* was for the main study. Table 5-4 shows the names of the text files and their alignment in terms of the naming conventions adopted for this study.

Table 5-4: Main qualitative study transcript names

Doc Id	Date of Interview	Start – End time	Interviewee Pseudonym	Interview text file name
D1	2017-10-02	08:30 – 08:57	Zanele	2017_10_02_Zanele_UR_Int_ZMS.rtf
D2	2017-10-03	14:40 – 15:15	Mavis	2017_10_03_Mavis_UR_Int_ZMS.rtf
D3	2017-10-06	09:30 - 10:00	Godfrey	2017_10_06_Godfrey_UR_Int_ZMS.rtf
D4	2017-10-08	09:00 - 09:12	Kainos	2017_10_08_Kainos_UR_Int_ZMS.rtf
D5	2017-10-08	09:00 - 09:12	Tanina	2017_10_08_Tanina_UR_Int_ZMS.rtf
D6	2017-10-10	11:00 - 11:28	Sihle	2017_10_10_Sihle_UR_Int_ZMS.rtf
D7	2017-10-15	15:00 - 15:30	Patience	2017_10_10_Patience_UR_Int_ZMS.rtf
D8	2017-10-70	11:00 - 11:30	Laizah	2017_10_10_Laizah_UR_Int_ZMS.rtf

The interview transcripts were deposited in the HU as rich text format files (.rtf). The resulting network of the primary transcript documents was created as shown in Figure 5-15.

Figure 5-15: The main study transcripts network

The other secondary documents that formed part of the HU included screenshots of websites. These were saved in the HU as images to serve as confirmatory shreds of evidence of the claims made by the participants (see the sample network of these in Figure 5-16).

Figure 5-16: Sample secondary documents network

5.3.2 Latour's second Notebook

The second notebook of Latour kept the information in some order and grouped the codes into categories which were then be refined into subcategories.

5.3.2.1 Monitoring the saturation point

In an analogous manner to the pilot study, soon after transcription, the transcripts were coded one after the other. The code network was checked and code changes were recorded. The three-layer doughnut in Figure 5-17 shows the changes that took place in the code book during the open coding process. The inner layer depicts the number of codes in the code network. The middle layer is the number of new codes in the code book, whilst the last layer represented the percentage increase in the code book. D1 as the first document that introduced codes is the smallest slice in the inner layer but the largest in the outer layer since the initial codes constituted 100% changes in the original code book that had no codes (see the code changes in Figure 5-17 and the values of the changes in Annexure F).

Figure 5-17: Changes in the codebook

As the code book got saturated, D6 showed the larger slice in the inner layer as the number of codes in the network increased with the introduction of new documents. In contrast, the corresponding slice in the outer layer is the smallest as the percentage changes in the code book reduced.

5.3.2.2 Establishing the categories in the code book

The codes in the code network were assessed for codes that needed splitting or merging after which the codes were colour coded to establish the categories. The code networks were created based on the categories.

5.3.2.3 Intéressement

Intéressement - At this stage, the other actors show interest and get attracted to the solution proposed in the Problematization stage. According to (Chikerema, Mavetera and Jantjies, 2016), it is at this stage that the interested actors are detached from any other ties and are locked in the network that cajoled them. To understand whether the focal and macro actors managed to detach the other actors from the traditional ways of accessing e-Government services, the researcher gave the other actors voice to share their experiences on the solutions provided by the focal actor and the storylines as follows:

Fitness in the digital era: The focus at the Problematization stage was on the focal and macro actors, and the solution they proposed to the identified problem whereas the Intéressement phase was hinged on extending the alliance to the other actors. The micro actors in the study were the actual participants who were interviewed and the technology that they interacted with. When the participants were asked to give reasons why they thought they fit in the technology solution, they had this to say:

2:7 Well, as you are aware in Zimbabwe we have a shortage of cash, so I fi..... (827:1051) - D 2: 2017_10_03_Mavis_UR_Int_ZMS

Well, as you are aware in Zimbabwe we have a shortage of cash, so I find myself without an option but to just use e-services. The situation we are in in terms of access to cash, makes usage of e-Government services mandatory.

4:2 P: Yes, due to the shortages of cash in Zimbabwe, we do not have a chop..... (819:933) - D 4: 2017_10_08_Kainos_UR_Int_ZMS

P: Yes, due to the shortages of cash in Zimbabwe, we do not have a choice but to go digital for most transactions.

6:2 P: It is almost impossible to work or conduct business without the use..... (772:895) - D 6: 2017_10_10_Sihle_UR_Int_ZMS

P: It is almost impossible to work or conduct business without the use of ICT, hence one is forced to fit in the digital era

Quotation 5-12: Do I fit in the Digital era?

With reference to Quotation 5-12, the extract shows that the participants from Zimbabwe acknowledged that they had an economically challenging situation whose effect required them to fit in the digital era. To benefit from the e-solution, Mavis through Quotation 5-13, suggested that one needed to be equipped with the relevant skills (such as the ICT skills) in order to navigate the murky transactions in Zimbabwe where currency shortages meant electronic transactions were the only means of conducting business. The participant also acknowledged that not every citizen has this skill.

2:1 Yes, I have the skills that it takes to be fit into the digital era, I..... (463:586) - D 2: 2017_10_03_Mavis_UR_Int_ZMS

Yes, I have the skills that it takes to be fit into the digital era, like I said I hold an MSc degree in Information Systems

2:25 : In my case, I have the IT skills to learn a new service and manage t..... (2687:2805) - D 2: 2017_10_03_Mavis_UR_Int_ZMS

: In my case, I have the IT skills to learn a new service and manage to use. It is not everyone who has the ICT skills.

Quotation 5-13: Skills for a Technology solution

Awareness sources: As Verdegem and Verleye (2009) argued that it follows that one cannot use services that they are not aware of, the participants could only determine whether their interests were consistent with the solution by the focal actor if only they were aware of the e-Government services. Consequently, they could develop intentions to use. Otherwise, the resistance would be based on a fear of the unknown. Hence, participants were asked how the focal actors communicated or raised the awareness of the available e-Government services.

Based on the voices of the participants, an awareness source category was created in which they identified 12 awareness sources of e-Government services including the banks they make transactions with, customer care services, the radio, television, and newspapers(online and physical). The awareness sources network was created showing the quotations from the transcripts and the codes. Figure 5-18 suggests that the awareness channels that the participants were aware of included the media channels such as print media (physical newspapers, printed short USSD codes for mobile transactions), and electronic media (Television, Radio, online newspapers, push messages); and social awareness channels. Some participants claimed that they received messages from Econet (push messages) reminding them of the USSD codes for purchasing the ZINARA and ZBC license, and the motor vehicle insurance

Figure 5-18: Awareness Sources Network

Some even claimed that even when they were not aware, they expected that payments at government institutions, departments or agencies would be in the form of mobile money (see Quotation 5-14).

3:8 When it comes to services where I have to make payments... (1171:1612) - D 3: 2017_10_08_Tanita_UR_Int_ZMS

When it comes to services where I have to make payments to government departments, I do not have to see the advert before I go there. Knowing very well that there is a shortage of cash, I just go and definitely they will be having the options for payment via Eco cash though I was not successful at the central vehicle registry and the toll gates. At the toll gate it does accept but I got to know that the procedure had to be done before.

Quotation 5-14: USSD code marketing as an awareness channel

Quotation 5-14 also shows the importance of keeping the general populace aware of the e-Government services and the acceptable forms of payment in the case of transactional services

to avoid clients' frustrations. According to Verdegem and Verleye (2009), intentions to use e-Government services follow after awareness. The quotation further demonstrates the need for an e-Government awareness strategy to be put in place. Interestingly, as a confirmation of the participants' views that social influence is a source of awareness, Weerakkody, El-Haddadeh and Al-Sobhi (2013) found that social influence had an insignificant causal effect on intentions. The finding motivated the current study to pursue social influence as a factor in the present quantitative study.

5.3.2.4 Enrolment

Enrolment is the moment where the cajoling of and yielding of other actors to be done by the spokesperson of the network.

Experiences of e-Government Services: One way of showing the success of the enrolment stage was to ascertain the use of the e-Government services by participants. The awareness campaign is indicative of negotiations and cajoling strategy by the focal actors whereas the initial and continued usage of the services forms part of the negotiation and yielding respectively. To demonstrate that they had negotiated and yielded to enrolment by the focal actor alliance, the participants were asked to share on the e-Government services that they had used at the time of conducting the study (see Figure 5-19). The services that the participants claimed to have used included the registration of company and deeds; e-filing; informational services such as accessing information from the local city council; accessing land application information from the Zimbabwe e-services website; payments of ZIMRA carbon duty at the country border posts; payments of the road usage services such as tollgate fees; purchase of motor vehicle insurance, ZINARA and ZBC licences, e-health services such as payment of ambulance fees, and health consultation fees; buying of prepaid electricity units; and payment of school fees. The participants claimed that most of the transactional services were paid using at least cash; m-wallets such as EcoCash, telecash, and one-money; or swipe.

Figure 5-19: Extract of e-Government Services Network

Tanita in Quotation 5-15 claimed the company registration and deeds processing were partially available online. This experience was echoed by Godfrey whose preference was to have online services available 24/7. The participant claimed that in reality some of the e-Government services were partially available online as the processes had to be completed offline.

3:12 P: No, because some of the services are in their early stages, they are.....
(1408:1561) - D 3: 2017_10_08_Tanita_UR_Int_ZMS

P: No, because some of the services are in their early stages, they are partially available online for example: company registration and deeds processing.

5:9 I: How have your experience of using e-Government services been like? P.....
(2012:2476) - D 5: 2017_10_06_Godfrey_UR_Int_ZMS

I: How have your experience of using e-Government services been like?

P: My expectations are not being met. The registration of a company online is not 100%. They ask one to bring proof to their offices after the transaction. If the service is online, it should be finished online not to be finished manually. Same with e-filing, it is not 100% online. They are trying but not 100% effective. There is room for improvement

Quotation 5-15: Partial online e-Government Services

To triangulate the claims by the participants on partial availability of some e-Government services, the company registration, Bulawayo and Harare City councils, Zimbabwe Electricity Transmission and Distribution Company (ZETDC) mandated to distribute the electricity to citizens, and the topup.co.zw, an agent for utilities such as ZINWA pre-paid meter, ZESA prepaid electricity tokens, and ZINARA toll gate (top up for the pre-paid ZINARA card) were visited. The topup.co.zw websites offer many e-services including tuition fees payment for

Catholic University of Zimbabwe and Harare Institute of Technology. The ZETDC website was still under construction. The Bulawayo and Harare City councils' websites had a billboard effect as they redirected the online users to the over the counter platforms or the mobile financial platforms. Interestingly, the company registration and topup.co.zw websites were sticky. Shortly after logging on to the company registration website, a Chatbot popped up automatically and initiated a conversation and helped navigate and respond to questions by the online user. The website was at the Interact stage as forms could be filled online. However, one could not transact directly. When the chat bot was asked about this partial online availability, it concurred that it was so. The topup.co.zw website displays various communication channels to choose from telephone calls, chats, email, WhatsApp, or Facebook. On picking the chat, a Chatbot also popped up. The experience was quite different as clarifications about the ZESA prepaid Top-up were done. The researcher then engaged with the transactional service. One could buy prepaid electricity units through EcoCash or online transfers (ZimSwitch, VISA, or MasterCard). Prior to making the payment, one could check the correctness of the account and the details retrieved from the system for the online user to confirm they are transacting for the correct account. After chatting with the Chatbot, a transaction of USD20 for the ZESA tokens was done and the EcoCash option was used. Coincidentally, the researcher experienced what was alluded to by some of the participants that at times the transactions are seemingly successful on one end and not on the other. The researcher received the EcoCash SMS confirming the purchase but luckily on the site there was a digital receipt that indicated that the purchase was unsuccessful. Because the researcher was online, she engaged with the chat bot that requested for the details of the message and the email ID that was used in the purchase. After looking into the issue (still online), the chat bot responded and said the transaction was not successful and assured the researcher it was going to be reversed. As soon as the chat was ended, a transcript together with the details of the query made was sent to the researcher's email ID (the name and email account are captured at the start of the chat). Any challenges faced could be pursued and resolved with the Chatbots. The transactions were fully online.

Weaving back to Quotation 5-15, Godfrey expressed some unsatisfactory user experience owing to the usability goals that were not fulfilled by some e-Government services. Having to take copies of the required documents manually to the office was on its own some form of inefficiency. Secondly, if the service was publicised as online the participant expected it to do what it was supposed to do. That was the reason the participant expressed dissatisfaction with the ineffectiveness of some e-services such as e-filing and company registration. Unless such information is communicated as partially online then the participant would be right to say it is ineffective. On the contrary, the office of the president website communicated that the Online Passport Application System was also partially online and the filled in passport form was only

downloadable. In this case as long as what was stated is followed, the service is effective. In addition, the decision for a downloadable filled form was a security measure to protect the citizens from mischievous people who would download the unfilled form and sell it to other citizens. Table 5-5 shows the maturity stages of e-Government services in Zimbabwe.

Table 5-5: Stages of the e-Government Services

Billboard Stage	Interact Stage	Transact Stage
Ministry Information	Passport Application ----->	ZBC Licence
Local City Council Information	Company and Deeds Registration ----->	Toll gate fees
Econet Push messages on e-Government services	E-Taxation ----->	Purchases of Prepaid Electricity Units
Land Application Information		Motor Vehicle Insurance
TSCZ Push Messages		ZINARA Licence
		School Fees

-----> Transition Stage

Based on the code densities in the Hermeneutic Unit, the popular e-Government services that the participants claim to have accessed were transactional as shown in Table 5-5. The same table shows Zimbabwe has not yet fully reached the interact stage yet there are some services that have reached the transact stage. The finding supports what has been alluded to by research scholars on e-Government maturity stages. The literature claims that e-Government maturity stages need not be followed religiously as there are different factors affecting the success of each stage (Moon, 2002; West, 2004; Shareef *et al.*, 2011, 2014).

Intermediaries: Intermediaries are perceived as creators of facilitating conditions for e-Government users (Weerakkody, El-Haddadeh and Al-Sobhi, 2013). In concordance, participants alluded to using intermediaries as a means through which the citizenry interacted with the e-Government services. Amongst the codes in the codes network were those that facilitated access to the e-Government services. These were then grouped and the code group was named e-intermediaries. That became the third category in the Hermeneutic Unit. A network of the codes was created. See Figure 5-20.

Figure 5-20: e-intermediaries Network

As shown in Figure 5-20, the participants voiced that they used personal resources such as smartphones, cell-phones, and laptops to access e-Government services. However, the facilitating resources were not a means to an end as they needed to have access to yet other intermediaries such as mobile wallets (m-wallets) to complete the transactional e-Government services. The m-wallets in turn needed to have access to the GSM mobile network service providers such as Econet, Telecel and Net*One. In addition, libraries were used as intermediaries for those individuals who did not have access to facilitating resources. Our interaction with the librarian reflected that the library personnel do offer ICT training to those citizens who needed the e-skills that would assist in accessing and using the e-Government services. The groundedness of quotations and densities in codes such as EcoCash, cell-phone, and smartphone was very high depicting the transition in mobile penetration in recent years. According to Zimbabwe_MICT(2014) 13 633 167 subscriptions depicting a 104% saturation point as of the end of December 2013 were registered by POTRAZ.

Human Intermediary: In addition, from the voices of the participants, there is always a need to have a human intermediary to afford those citizens who do not have the appropriate resources or lack the e-literacy skills to access the e-Government services. Quotation 5-16 narrates the conversation we had with participant 2 (Mavis) in this regard.

2:26 Those that are aware of the availability of the services may not be ha..... (2808:2936)
- D 2: 2017_10_03_Mavis_UR_Int_ZMS

Those that are aware of the availability of the services may not be having the resources to use e.g. the phones, the internet etc.

2:28 P: In my case, I have the IT skills to learn a new service and manage..... (2686:3523) -
D 2: 2017_10_03_Mavis_UR_Int_ZMS

P: In my case, I have the IT skills to learn a new service and manage to use. It is not everyone who has the ICT skills. Those that are aware of the availability of the services may not be having the resources to use e.g. the phones, the internet etc.]

I: From your standpoint as an IT person, what would be your suggestion to assist such a group of people?

P: I suggest that the continuation of over the counter services. They may be not a good idea because of long queues and the availability times. As human beings we tire, and we need to rest at some point during the day but our needs they do not stop. Let's say for example, the prepaid electricity units get finished during the evening when shops are closed, we cannot starve ourselves. If there is a relative, a friend or a neighbour whom you can ask to "Juice "for you, we do that

Quotation 5-16: The need for a human Intermediary

Quotation 5-16 brings forth two forms of service perspectives alluded to by Grönroos (2008). Firstly, service is a perspective of customer service logic in which case the participant engages with a self-service. As Mavis put it in Quotation 5-16, there are those amongst citizens who lack the e-skills, facilitating resources to engage with the e-Government services, hence the need of over the counter services. Such is a perspective of supplier service logic, in which case a human intermediary over the counter is needed (full service).

Benefits of e-Government Services: Quotation 5-17 reiterates the experiences of some of the participants as they engaged with e-Government services. Patience and Peter expressed the convenience that emanated from the availability of transactional e-Government services. They both argued that the e-Government services afforded them the chance to make e-payments using m-wallets services, ATM cards, or bank transfers. Patience narrated her experiences in engaging with the e-Health services offered at the Government hospitals and she claimed that the accessibility of the USSD code facilitated the mobile e-payments processes for those who did not have access to the internet. Peter and Laizah stated that e-Government services gave them the convenience of transacting on the go (see Quotation 5-17 for more details).

7:8 P: let me tell you of the experience I had twice so far in paying hosp..... (2784:3335) - D 7: 2017_10_15_Patience_UR_Int_ZMS

P: let me tell you of the experience I had twice so far in paying hospital bills. We had an emergency at home and had to call an ambulance to take the patient to the hospital. I had the money to pay but the ambulance personnel captured the necessary details and we were asked to pay later through city council. At the city council, we were given the billing code and we paid by eco-cash. I found that beneficial because at that time we were left with only to concentrate on our patient. I am not sure if it works with people who reside in the rural areas.

7:9 The second incidence, we had taken yet another person(a friend's rela..... (3338:3845) - D 7: 2017_10_15_Patience_UR_Int_ZMS

The second incidence, we had taken yet another person(a friend's relative) at a different date to hospital. We went to the out-patient wing and they said they could not add the bill to the house bill (water) since they had no money. The person at the out-patients counter said one can only be attended after payment in cash, transfer, swiping the ATM card, or eco-cash. For the latter, the billing code and instructions were clearly written to be visible the clients. We used it and then we were attended.

9:5 P: I found it very convenient in that for the ZESA units, I do not nee..... (1841:2374) - D 9: 2017_10_20_Peter_UR_Int_ZMS

P: I found it very convenient in that for the ZESA units, I do not need to go to the ZESA offices physically to get the units. I can buy the units any time as long as I have enough money in my eco-cash and minimal airtime. As for internet banking account I do need to have data/internet bundles for me to access my account through the browser or through the app. As for swiping I just needed to have money in my account and then ZIMRA office at the border takes care of the availability of the network as they were there to serve us.

Quotation 5-17: Benefits of e-Government Services

Functional benefits through intermediaries encourage the adoption of e-Government services (Weerakkody, El-Haddadeh and Al-Sobhi, 2013). The present study participants argued that ICT skills contribute to the building of intentions of which lack of social influence was an option. In Quotation 5-16, Mavis claimed that the availability of over the counter services was not 24/7 in which case the assistance that one gets in the social circle parallels the over the counter service. The participants alluded to benefits of using e-Government services as a convenience, the flexibility of accessing the services on the go without physically visiting the service provider; having to incur minimal charges; having multiple channels of accessing and paying for the services.

Role of the library in delivering e-Government services: In following the actors, one of the participants interviewed was a librarian (pseudonym Zanele) from a private library. Asked on the library's contribution to enhancing e-Government adoption by the public, Zanele explained how the library contributed indirectly to the enhancement of e-Government development in the country. Zanele mentioned that the role of the library included helping those with limited access to the internet through the library internet café corner; those in need of e-education services; those in need of opening of businesses online; and the library contributes to ICT skills development which in turn would be used to access the e-Government services at later dates. Figure 5-21 captures the main points of the conversation in brief.

Figure 5-21: The role of the library in e-Government

The library in question was not a public library, hence the mention of internet café services on e-Government and the ICT skills development training that are provided to the general populace at a fee for sustainability of the library. However, Bertot, McClure and Jaeger (2008) argue that internet access in public libraries is free in the USA. This is not the case in Zimbabwe, a developing country where sustainable measures have to be invented in a bid to broaden service offerings. Amongst the uses of the internet in public libraries is the provision of training and assistance in accessing the e-Government sites and services. In this regard the government institutions, departments, and agencies make referrals to the general populace to access the public libraries for help on e-Government services. Borrowing from the USA public library experience, and the e-Government experiences from private libraries, there is a need to conduct e-Government education awareness campaigns in Zimbabwe through libraries.

The role of culture in engaging with e-Government Services: As per Callon (1986)'s Intéressement phase, the solution that was proposed by the government (herein called the focal actor) was expected to cut the links with other ways in which the participants would interact with the government (including the traditional ways) only if the proposed solution resonated with the interests of the citizens. However, despite the claim by participants that the economic situation

mandated them to fit in the digital (see Quotation 5-12), mostly the transactional services have been used. The failure to or lack of usage of other services such as accessing informational services and giving feedback on the e-Government services reflects on the culture rooted by the traditional ways of interacting with the government whether consciously or unconsciously.

In Quotation 5-18 and 5-19, Patience, Godfrey, and Peter claimed that the power distance that existed between them, the Government, and its agencies were high.

7:10 I: Do you ever give or receive feedback on the services you used from the governm..... (3847:4649) - D 7: 2017_10_15_Patience_UR_Int_ZMS
I: Do you ever give or receive feedback on the services you used from the government?
P: No. the services that I use for mobile banking do not have the option for giving feedback. I am not sure if they would listen to my views if I give. I once swiped for fuel and was told the

5:12 I: Giving feedback or an evaluation of e-services that you have access..... (2783:3205) - D 5: 2017_10_06_Godfrey_UR_Int_ZMS
I: Giving feedback or an evaluation of e-services that you have accessed is one way of participating in the continual development of the very services. So, tell me, have you had an opportunity to give feedback on an e-Government service? If yes how? If not, what barriers did you face in giving feedback?
P: No. They will not accept it, if they do I don't see them implementing our feedback no matter how good they can be.

Quotation 5-18: Feedback and Power Distance in engaging with e-Government Transactions

Peter claimed that the lack of openness by the government to accept the citizens' views drove him to dread giving feedback on the e-services used.

9:8 I: Besides the feedback that you receive, have you ever given feedback..... (3103:3535) - D 9: 2017_10_20_Peter_UR_Int_ZMS
I: Besides the feedback that you receive, have you ever given feedback on the e-Government services that you have accessed?
P: Well, on that one, I would like to say no, I have never given feedback.
I: Why?
P: I have not seen the section that requests for the feedback.
I: Let us suppose the option is there, would you give feedback?
P: I am not sure.
I: Why are you not sure?
P: I am not sure that they will implement my suggestions

Quotation 5-19: Power Distance in engaging with e-Government transactions 2

To ascertain the claims by the participants the government of Zimbabwe (GoZ) website was visited. Apparently, the website had an option for feedback as shown in Figure 5-22.

Figure 5-22: The Feedback Menu option on the GoZ portal
Retrieved from GoZ Portal 18 September 2018

One could participate in the survey, consultative forum, or simply give feedback. In addition, on the website, towards the bottom of the home page, a thumbnail for the survey results was available at the time of conducting the study. The results of the survey were also accessible on the site. There were captured and are shown in Figure 5-23.

Figure 5-23: The Feedback Survey results on the GoZ portal
Retrieved from GoZ Portal 18 September 2018

Based on Table 5-23, a total of 1 224 participated in the survey with 33% rating the website favourably and 67% either rated it as poor, lacking information, or needing improvement in terms of the design. The study could not ascertain whether the participation in the survey (when

the link was active) was low or not since neither the duration of the availability of the survey nor the number of site hits was known. However, the number of those who participated in the survey was very low with reference to a national population of over 13 million in Zimbabwe. The number of hits on the website could not be ascertained at the time of doing the study. In a similar vein, the low number of feedback participants on the GoZ website resonated with the claim cited by participants of a culture of not participating in feedback surveys. The participants claimed that even if they had the opportunities to give feedback they would not give it as they were not sure if their views would be considered (see Quotation 5-18).

On the other hand, the feedback form link did provide the form with compulsory form fields: full name, telephone, email address, subject and the message with the location being optional. Although capturing these details was meant for sharing responses telephonically or through e-mail, later on e-mail marketing. However, considering that the participants claimed that there was high power distance, the mandatory fields played a role in distancing the participants from sharing feedback. The cultural perspective on Power Distance by the participants echoed the extant findings by scholars such as Al-Hujran, Al-Dalahmeh and Aloudat (2011) who found that that PD significantly influenced the intention to use e-Government services in Jordan and Zhao (2011) whose finding was from participants from 84 countries around the world as published by Hofstede in 2010 and that of e-Government development indexes as published by UNDESA in the same year. On the other hand, the third party vendor websites such as the topup.co.zw website and the online company registration website had Chatbots. The topup.co.zw website had various channels of communication and the feedback option (see Figure 5-24). The options included instant chat, phone call, email, WhatsApp, and Facebook tools.

Figure 5-24: ZESA prepaid Top-Up Interface Retrieved 3 January 2019

The instant chat tool was tested and it worked effectively. To give feedback on this site the online user needed to just click what best described their experience and then provide written feedback prior to sending it.

Retrieved from GoZ Portal 3 January 2019

The availability of the combination of chat and feedback tools parallels the desire to engage with online users. Within the chat facility, the online user was able to send the chat transcript to their email and also the Chatbot does send it automatically after the chat session is ended. The site had an exciting and encouraging experience and its stickiness forced the online users to revisit the site. Similarly, in the online company registration website there were frequently asked questions (FAQs) and Blogs that could guide the online user. Also what was found worth mentioning was that once the online user provides their details (telephone or email) during the chat there is some follow up to the conversation. Borrowing from the international participant from the pilot study, making follow ups on website visitors is a sign of customer relationship management. It was commended that even if company registration processes were partially online, the online experience was exciting and it took out the frustration one would have had if they were entirely alone on the site.

Mavis, in Quotation 5-20 when asked why some citizens would not want to use e-Services, cited that when citizens were uncomfortable with unfamiliar situations of the e-Government services they tended to avoid adoption (see Quotation 5-20).

- 2:30 [Laughs].... Fear of the unknown. The uncertainty of how the..... (3653:4111) - D 2: 2017_10_03_Mavis_UR_Int_ZMS

[Laughs].... Fear of the unknown. The uncertainty of how the technology works may be the driving force to failure to use the e-services. Some of these may be related to one's past experience. It is not everyone who is tech savvy, so unfamiliar situations / services do affect our decision-making processes. It is important that the government keeps its citizens informed of the pros and cons of the services. If there are cons, how to deal with them
- 2:31 P: Inclusion. It is important that the services are known to all. The..... (4115:4540) - D 2: 2017_10_03_Mavis_UR_Int_ZMS

P: Inclusion. It is important that the services are known to all. The citizenry is not a homogenous entity, their preferences differ. Some are visual, some are auditory, and some are tactile, hence the need to address the awareness campaigns in all those forms including language. It may take time to develop systems of various languages but at least the information can be in different languages and the system be in English

Quotation 5-20: Uncertainty avoidance and partial online availability of some e-Government Services

The participant claimed that it was important to educate the citizens on the e-services together with their challenges and benefits. The participant claimed that the lack of knowledge of challenges plays a part in decision making of intentions, supporting Al-Hujran, Al-Dalahmeh and Aloudat (2011) and Al-Hujran *et al.* (2015) who argued that uncertainty avoidance had significant and positive effect towards the intentions adopt e-Government services. However, Zhao (2011), using national cultural dimensions from 84 countries, found out that low uncertainty avoidance had an inconsequential effect on e-Government development. To this effect, the claim by Mavis in the study that the high uncertainty avoidance had a bearing in e-Government adoption had to be advanced in the inferential statistic of the subsequent quantitative analysis.

The participants also argued that the awareness campaigns be presented in ways that addressed different learning styles of the citizens. Whereas the participant argued for the presentation of awareness campaigns to be in multiple local languages even if the system remains in English, the policy statement on e-Government in Zimbabwe was that the e-Government services be availed in languages that people understood (Zimbabwe_MICT, 2015, p. 21). The participant acknowledged that the presentation of e-services in multiple languages could be ambitious, to which he/she suggested educating the citizens on how to use the mono-language system in languages that they understood. The participant knitted together culture and e-Government awareness campaigns emphasising on the need to understand and address the needs of users of the services during awareness campaigns for e-Government to benefit all. The opportunities brought about by the e-Government could be used to un-culture and re-culture the citizenry in new ways of engaging with the government.

Exposure to e-services and Trust Issues

Trust Issues

Trust is integral in e-Government (Colesca, 2009; Papadopoulou & Nikolaidou, 2010; Abu-Shanab, 2014) and the relationship involves two parties: the trustor as the party that trusts; and the trustee as the party to be trusted (Papadopoulou & Nikolaidou, 2010). *As discussed earlier on in this chapter, the popular services that were cited were mainly transactional.* Scholars in the extant literature identify trustworthiness as an influential determinant in intention to use the e-Government services (Warkentin *et al.*, 2002; Abu-Shanab, 2012; Al Hujran, Aloudat & Altarawneh, 2013; Abu-Shanab, 2014), especially in the transact stage (Shareef *et al.*, 2011, 2014; UN, 2014). The criticality of trust in determining BI to adopt e-Government services by the citizens owed to the phenomenon being an “open domain”, making it being prone to risks (Abu-Shanab, 2012, p. 39).

Participants were asked to share their experiences on the transactional e-Government services and how they dealt with trust issues. Amongst the participants, Peter acknowledged that failure to receive services transacted for was true, though it was just part of the experience since the service providers do reverse incomplete processes where necessary. The description given by Peter reflected the perspective of someone who had high levels of trust on the reliability of the technology, e-Government, the government and its agencies (See Quotation 5-21).

9:6 : Are there any challenges that you faced ? if so, how did you communi.....
 (2377:2725) - D 9: 2017_10_20_Peter_UR_Int_ZMS

: Are there any challenges that you faced ? if so, how did you communicate the challenges with the concerned departments/offices?

P: Well, I have never faced any challenges per se with using my ATM card for the ZIMRA carbon duty. There are always notifications though at times they are delayed. I have had some challenge with buying of electricity units through Eco cash. My neighbour had exhausted their electricity units; they requested that I buy them the units. I did buy the units and the money was deducted but I did not get the Token at the time. The good thing was that I had the trust that the system would correct the issue. I never reported the issue but within 2 to 3 days the money was reversed together with the service charge. My trust was based on the experience I had when using the e-services, I bought airtime through Eco Cash and tried up to four times without the airtime reflecting. It took some good 20 mins for the money to be reversed. However, one day I had the same inconvenience when I bought airtime for 2USD and only to receive it as 5USD airtime accompanied with a message Eco cash was awarding me the airtime for the inconvenience they caused me. With all these experiences I have grounded my trust in the e-Services and their providers. I just have to wait for the notifications for the reversals where the transactions were seemingly successful.

Quotation 5-21: Influence of Trust in e-Government and Government

Peter in Quotation 5-21 alluded to the fact that some of the experiences he faced in using the e-services gave him the exposure and when faced with similar challenges in using e-Government services, he did not lose the trust. Whilst Peter claims he was rewarded for the inconvenience that was caused to him by the service provider, some participants claimed that they received notifications of USD2 or USD2.50 credited to their bank accounts for buying the airtime through their bank accounts. Similarly, it was also found that one of the ZINARA toll gate payments agencies in Zimbabwe topup.co.zw has adopted the same strategy for ZINARA and ZINWA payments. Figure 5-25 shows the incentive for ZINARA payments.

Figure 5-25: ZINARA agent motivational incentive
 Retrieved 3 January 2019

Such motivational ways through incentives were found to be effective in cajoling users into a voluntary shift to online channels (Jait, 2012) in the emergence of trust issues and challenges faced online.

In addition, Kainos shared the different challenges he faced when interacting with the e-municipality services of buying of prepaid electricity units. The participant claimed that despite having trust in the e-Government services, his trust in e-Government was not shaken when he could not get the e-service on time. However, he acknowledged that the unreliability of the service could be inconveniencing at times (see Quotation 5-22).

 4:7 What challenges have you faced in accessing e-government services? P:.....
(1295:1474) - D 4: 2017_10_08_Kainos_UR_Int_ZMS

What challenges have you faced in accessing e-government services?

P: I once had a challenge when the prepaid electricity units got used up at home. I recall it was 7 pm on a Sunday. The ZESA offices do not open on Sunday and it was late. As usual we had the trust that we could buy them online. It was a different story on that day. We tried all avenues to top up the electricity units several ways and times in vain. We had to try Eco cash, bank transfer, those people that sell the units in the kiosks, to an extent that we had to call a relative to try buying the units for us from Harare, but we were not successful. This is one challenge that I remember vividly as I needed to work on something on my laptop on that Sunday and share with a colleague on Monday morning. Adding salt to the wound, when I tried to buy the units the next day, I received a message that my balance was insufficient and less than <some certain number that the participant failed to understand>. We only managed to get them on Monday around 4pm. It was really an inconvenience.

I: Did you try buying these directly from ZESA on that Monday?

P: No, we did not. Somehow, we had the faith that we will eventually manage because we have been using the service and we had no problems though we had other people narrating such a challenge.

Quotation 5-22: Influence of Trust in e-Government

Design Thinking and successful adoption of e-Government services: One of the long-standing contributing factors to e-Government scarce successes in the developing countries has been linked to the Design-Reality gap (Heeks, 2002b; Santos & Heeks, 2003). In mirroring the technical functionality, the designers can be influenced by their own contexts and the assumptions about the situation of the user (Heeks, 2002b). Thus even without the design-reality gap, there would be a disconnection due to technical design that does not meet human needs or abilities. Amongst those that participated in the survey in Figure 5-23, the majority found the website poor, lacking some information, or needing some form of improvement. With a high-power distance expressed by the current study participants, the study sought to find out to what extent they were involved in the design of the e-services they consumed. Godfrey denied having been given an opportunity to participate in making design decisions.

 5:11 I: Have you had an opportunity to be involved in the design of an e-Go.....
(2689:2781) - D 5: 2017_10_06_Godfrey_UR_Int_ZMS

I: Have you had an opportunity to be involved in the design of an e-Government service?

P: No

Quotation 5-23: Views on Participation in the Design of e-Government services

Sihle also echoed Godfrey's sentiment of non-involvement of citizens in the design of e-Government services. However, the participant had some expert advice to those that launch the services. The participant's advice pointed to the need for incorporating various user viewpoints in the design of the e-Government services for the citizenry to feel some sense of ownership in the resultant services. The needs of the citizenry would have to be captured and implemented in

the development of such services for them to be able to fit in as solutions of the citizens' problems. Otherwise, the people would have to fit in the usage of the services without solving their problems. The advice was captured in Quotation 5-24.

 6:10 I: What expert advice would you give to those responsible for launchin.....
(2317:3503) - D 6: 2017_10_10_Sihle_UR_Int_ZMS

I: What expert advice would you give to those responsible for launching e-Services.

P: If I were given an opportunity to share what I would do in their positions to win the satisfaction of the citizens was to involve them in the design process. If we are to make our services adoptable by the citizen, the best this would be to balance the power. The power in the sense that they get involved in making decisions about the services that they will consume. You know it is easier to complain or criticise where you have no input. If the way one uses the service goes in an unplanned way, they will be quick to point fingers. It might not be all, but their representation is key. From a personal experience as a designer, there is always that idea that you think is right no matter what the user thinks, and you would enforce it in the way you understand it. The power is solely with you to decide. Involving the citizenry would help in instilling that sense of responsibility that if one is objective they would accept where they went wrong. In such cases accepting feedback becomes the way in which other people's views are incorporated. At the end of the day, we all claim ownership.

Quotation 5-24: How to design popular e-Government services

The issue of the sense of ownership captured in Quotation 5-24 supports what was also argued by Axelsson *et al.* (2010) that there was a close link between a feeling of involvement and participation. That view of being a co-creator of design proposals does make a difference in the way one views the final product. The participant in her expert advice reiterated the claim in the participants' views that the citizenry wanted to be heard. The participant suggested that citizens could be involved by incorporating their views in the design of e-Government services. The participant's view supports the finding by extant research scholars that the tendency in developing countries of transferring technologies or opportunities that have flourished in developed countries without holistically understanding the target audience needs is therefore inadequate, unrealistic and would not yield a complete success (Chen *et al.*, 2006; Gupta, Dasgupta & Gupta, 2008, p. 141). The wider the design-reality gap, the more the likelihood of failure and the more it demonstrates the tendency of *adopting* instead of *adapting* the e-Government best practices and strategies from the success stories of other countries. Advancing the aspect of balancing the power between the designers and the citizenry Sihle had this to say:

 6:11 I: very insightful, however, when you mention that citizens should be.....
(3505:3989) - D 6: 2017_10_10_Sihle_UR_Int_ZMS

I: very insightful, however, when you mention that citizens should be given power, my question is are they able to make designerly decisions?

P: they may be not; their involvement is to be able to ideate and then the involved designers would make designerly decisions based on the contribution by all parties. You know it is one thing to have a citizen conform to the system instead of having to understand the needs of the citizen and then develop a system that suits their context.

 6:12 Well put. But if so many stakeholders are involved, would that create.....
(3994:4558) - D 6: 2017_10_10_Sihle_UR_Int_ZMS

Well put. But if so many stakeholders are involved, wouldn't that create many communication paths that will then see the failure of the collective effort?

P: What makes us not agree is that, we have a tendency of recycling systems, or products instead of being creative and innovative. That divergence if ideas amongst the participants is the starting point. The next thing would be to then come to an understanding that will give us the best solution that is useable by all. That convergence does not come cheap. We might need to have prototypes repeatedly.

Quotation 5-25: Views on Design and Design Thinking

Sihle alluded to the fact that if the solutions that are given by the focal actors were to be consistent with non-focal actors, their voices needed to be heard. The non-focal actors' views and ideas on the solution would be in layman's language. The designers as the experts would find ways of making the divergent ideas converge to a solution that would be innovative, thus creating new solutions for the new problems. Axelsson *et al.* (2010) argues that the involvement of citizens in the design and development of e-Government services is important if the e-services were to succeed. The scholars further argue that users may have different roles in their participation such as sharing and discussing the design proposals.

5.3.2.5 Mobilisation

Mobilisation This stage sought to develop loyal delegate actors. With reference to the awareness sources voiced by the participants, it showed that the macro actors were in their individuality raising awareness on the e-services that they offer as service providers in alignment with the government services. These included the banking institutions, the government agencies and departments, and the mobile network operators. The banking institutions have introduced utility transactions such as electricity and water bill payment through internet banking, and the mobile network operators have linked with banking institutions to offer the mobile banking services and mobile money solutions. Similarly, phone manufacturers, mobile network operators, and Internet service providers have afforded people the opportunity to access e-Government information on the go. Each of the macro actors in some way acted as spokesperson of the focal actor. One example is that of the subnetwork of third-party vendors (TPVs), the mobile network operators such as Econet, Telecel, and NetOne who have embraced the decentralisation of the distribution of prepaid ZESA tokens through their mobile financial platforms. These TPVs have to balance the needs of the focal actor and their own. These mobile financial platforms are in turn used by the over the counter platforms and web-based platforms. The network has a capability of growing because with one link pointing at an actor, it means that eventually the actor may establish a whole lot more links. The study makes reference to the TECHZIM report dated 16 August 2016. See Figure 5-26.

Figure 5-26: The growing network of spokespersons
Retrieved 3 January 2019

Figure 5-25 shows that ZB bank as a network with regards to prepaid electricity top-up emphasising that the source of action is not ZB bank, but the agents that ZB cajoles toward it. This supports the hyphenated expression of 'actor-network' and 'black-boxing' as a necessity of agency (Latour, 2005; Law, 2009, p. 147). Similarly, Figure 5-27 shows that ZB bank is a non-focal member of the PowerPlus network, thereby demonstrating the ordering struggle of the ANT.

Figure 5-27: PowerPlus actor-network
Retrieved from GoZ Portal 3 January 2019

It was noted that some nodes in Figure 5-27 were in themselves black boxes that when opened reveal that they are actor-networks. Figure 5-28 therefore shows the actor-world sketch of the spokespersons in e-Government in Zimbabwe.

Figure 5-28: The growing network of spokespersons

5.3.3 Latour's Third and Fourth Notebook

Latour (2005, p. 134-135) suggests that the third notebook “should always be there for *ad libitum* writing trials...” The third book was used to write theoretical memos. The fourth book served to register the effects of participants’ actions. In the current study, the two books were presented in combination and in alignment with answering the research questions.

RQ1: How does the translation process aid in understanding the e-Government adoption trajectory in SADC?

The exploratory research question above was explored in order to unearth the complexities of e-Government by sticking to Latour’s ANT slogan: “Follow the actors themselves or rather that which makes them act.” The notion of following the actors meant that the traces of the actors could only be understood if the ANT was used as ontology instead of the lens. Hence the study was guided by the participants’ storylines using Latour’s notebooks to describe their experiences of e-Government in their respective countries. As such Chapter 5, specifically section 5.3.3 put together the views the participants held on the meaning of e-Government.

5.4 Answering Research Question 2

RQ2: *What are the factors of e-Government adoption that derive from non-focal actors' experiences of e-Government in the SADC?*

E-Government familiarity

Listening to the participants varying stories on e-Government experiences made the researcher understand the extent of knowledge the participants had on e-Government. Regardless of the level of education one had reached, it was established that participants in Zimbabwe were either familiar or not with the e-Government concept. There were those who were familiar and demonstrated some level of comfort with the concept. Then were those that were not familiar and therefore uncomfortable with the same e-Government concept. Following through our conversations with the latter group indicated that these were divided into two groups: those that were not familiar with the concept but have used e-Government services blindly. This group claimed that they had not used e-Government services until the interviewer gave examples. Only then would the interviewer hear a statement like "Oh, I have used that before...". Some in this group were not even sure if there were any other e-Government services besides the ones they have already used in the past. It is one thing to say, 'I am aware' and the other when one says, 'I have used'. This group of participants lacked familiarity with e-Government as a concept. The other group was made up of those who claimed non-familiarity with the e-Government concept and have never used the services either. It is against this backdrop that the study found out that there is a concept gap in the awareness strategies. The finding supports the claim by Weerakkody, Jones and Olsen (2006) that understanding the definition of e-Government was amongst the most fundamental components in the implementation of the phenomenon. Tracing back to the extant literature, Abu-Shanab (2017) argues that holistic awareness strategies geared towards enhancing knowledge on e-Government services and concepts were needed. The scholar argues that familiarity with e-Government concepts had a significant effect on the perceptions of the citizenry about the phenomenon. As a consequence, the current researcher questioned the sufficiency of the e-Government awareness strategies that were being used in Zimbabwe.

Mandated adoption

Figure 7-1 shows that mandatory adoption was asserted as a factor in the enhancement of e-Government in Zimbabwe from the participants' voices in the qualitative study (See Quotation 5-12) as they argued how they fit in the digital era. Linking their claim and the voices, the assertion was validated by the fact that the participants clearly spelt the lack of options or choices on the use of technology as there was a cash crisis in the country. The economic situation (cash crisis) in question was echoed by Sakarombe and Marabada (2017).

Consequently, the solution by the focal actor became an automatic Obligatory Passage of Point for transactional e-services (see Figure 5-29).

Figure 5-29: Application of Toulmin's Model in the Mandatory adoption claim

It is the lack of any options or choices that Al-Arabiati (2014) posits as what defines the mandatoriness in e-Government services. In supporting the assertion, Chopra and Rajan (2016, pp. 17–18) argue that emphasis on voluntary adoption of e-Government in extant literature owes its assumptions to the adoption models in the field. However, the scholars assert that empirically the adoption is often mandatory as the citizens are forced to adopt appropriate technologies that afford them the opportunity to access and engage with e-Government services.

Awareness strategies

Since awareness was found to be a critical key in e-Government (Weerakkody, Jones & Olsen, 2006) this current study sought a clearer picture of how the participants came to be aware of the e-Government services available to them. Those that were aware of the e-Government services in Zimbabwe claimed awareness through media channels (television, radio, physical and electronic newspapers), push messages from Econet (USSD code marketing), local banks (websites, mobile applications), social Influence, and libraries. Based on the participants' views, the study found that the general populace was at varying levels of digital literacy. In order for the e-Government solution to be usable by all citizenry, the participants suggested that the e-Government awareness strategies be inclusive to address different learning styles.

Interestingly, taking a leaf from the pilot study conducted in Botswana, one of the strategies that could readily address the inclusivity issue was target marketing. The participants in the pilot

study claimed the marketing team from the BURS conducted some visits to target populations such as institutions or organisations to raise awareness of e-Taxation to the taxpayers. The participants claimed that the campaigns the BURS marketing team would hold included workshops where they did some presentations to educate the target market on the e-Services followed by demonstrations on how to register for e-filing. The participants claimed that the workshops were hands-on as there was allotted time to register, and demonstration on what to do when faced with challenges on registration. This also resonated with what the participants from Zimbabwe claimed (refer to Quotation 5-20). Also, the Botswana participants claimed that those who faced challenges of registration were helped by the BURS team where possible; otherwise they were referred to BURS e-services help-desk offices for further help. In triangulation, Botswana Unified Revenue Service (2015, p. 24) reported that the awareness initiatives in 2015 included conducting taxpayers education workshops, participation in fairs, open-days, shows, and raising public awareness campaigns on e-Taxation through reminders in radio stations through GABZ FM and Yarona FM. Then the live education workshops were conducted in 2016 to encourage the uptake of e-services by users, create a conversation with users, and for garnering feedback from the fully recruited users (Pinielo, 2016). The hands-on workshops helped in developing exposure amongst users thereby increasing the familiarity with the e-Government services. Some of the participants in the main qualitative study also claimed that some of the challenges they faced as they engaged in e-Government services did not affect their attitude owing to the exposure they had in using other e-services. They claimed that in fact that exposure to other e-services somehow tended to boost their confidence and trust. The finding reiterates the conclusions reached by Al-Jaghoub, Al-Yaseen and Al-Hourani (2010) that familiarity in one system boosts confidence in using similar systems in the future. Participants indicated having yet other forces that guided them into adopting an obligatory passage of point (OPP). They suggested that their social circles significantly assist them in accessing the e-Government services in many ways. Those that do not have the skills or technology resorted to their social circles to access the services on their behalf. The early adopters tend to have the skills and technology; the potential adopters lean on their social circles when they encounter challenges in the network. Some alluded to accessing the services through internet café corner in the library or stand-alone internet cafés. The participant's experience implied that the actor without the facilitating resources or services but determined, could be pulled through the OPP by the social circles, libraries, or the internet cafés as shown in Figure 5-30.

Figure 5-30: An indirect pulling effect on the OPP based on participants' views
 Adapted from Callon (1986, p.21)

In agreement with the claim that social influence was an important determinant of intentions (Hung, Chang and Yu, 2006), Figure 5-30 shows that it is not only the Government (focal actor) that could persuade the citizenry to adopt the e-Government services. However, in recent years, the findings on social influence and intentions are at crossroads with some scholars supporting and others not supporting the claim. In the extant literature, Rana and Dwivedi (2015) argued that social influence was found to have a significant effect in behavioural intention and outcome expectation amongst Indians in using the Online Public Grievance Redress System (OPGRS) and Weerakkody, El-Haddadeh and Al-Sobhi (2013) alluding to the contrary in the usage of e-Government services through intermediaries. The present study participants contradict the finding by Weerakkody, El-Haddadeh and Al-Sobhi (2013). The participants claim that other citizens who according to Callon (1986) would have gone through the enrolment and Intéressement stages of the translation process and adopted the role of a spokesperson of the focal actor influence their behavioural intentions to use the e-Government services. It is against this argument that they start mobilising members of their social circles (those who lack the facilitating services or resources to use e-Government services) to expand and stabilise the network in which they belong. Since the finding was based on a few participants and the varying findings on social Influence, it was prudent and motivational to further explore the claim in the quantitative study.

In searching for the e-services of Zimbabwe with particular mention of ZESA prepaid electricity e-service through a search engine, the researcher got to know about the topup-co.zw. Though

sceptical in the first place, the researcher took a risk and used the services based on her individual evaluation of the website. Whilst search engines may lead online users to e-Government services, considering the varying levels of digital citizenships in which participants are in, it is how one becomes aware of the e-services that matter in this era of cybersecurity. As most of the services that participants engaged with were transactional, it cannot be overemphasized that digital security and safety is a major concern in online contexts. To borrow a leaf from Singapore which is ranked seventh (dropped from 4th position in 2016) of one hundred and ninety-three countries by United Nations in 2018 with an EGDI of 0.8812, CitizenConnect portal was visited. CitizenConnect, just like ZimConnect is the e-services portal for Singapore. The portal makes the citizens' life easier by listing all the agencies that facilitate communication with the government and the number of e-services each agency provides. The websites clearly list the top agencies, the top e-services, and all the agencies. It is motivational to agencies to know the adoption levels of their e-services against others as it pushes them to do better and reach the desired level. Similarly, the government has an immediate online audit snapshot of how each ministry performs on e-Government. Figure 5-31 and Figure 5-32 illustrate the groupings.

Figure 5-31: Singapore e-Government services agency listing
 Last Accessed from (<http://www.citizenconnectcentre.sg/all/U-Z>) 02/02/2019

Figure 5-32: e-Government services listings by Agency
 Last Accessed from (<http://www.citizenconnectcentre.sg/all/agency/URA>) 02/02/2019

It is encouraging that the CitizenConnect portal is in a true sense, a gateway for all the e-Government services in Singapore. It acts as a point of reference for e-Government services. The more one gets to navigate the portal, the more one gets to be aware of more e-Government services available for the citizenry in that country. Consequently, the agency listings on the e-Government e-services portal of a country are a strategy that is useable to enhance knowledge on e-Government.

Facilitating Conditions

The participants claimed that facilitating conditions influenced the intention to use the e-Government services. The storylines identified the ICT skills, facilitating resources (e-intermediaries, e-offices) and to be the facilitating conditions. The warrants were supported by the extant literature: ICT skills (Ngulube, 2007; Alshehri & Drew, 2010; Shareef *et al.*, 2011, 2014; UN, 2012); and human intermediary (Heeks, 2002a; Chopra & Rajan, 2016), e-intermediaries (Heeks, 2002a). In addition, Venkatesh, Chan and Thong (2012) posit that facilitating conditions are not only made up of facilitating resources, rather include the supporting services. These are the services that citizens may use to resolve problems they encounter and to boost their confidence in using the e-services (e.g. technical support). From the participants' experiences on some websites such as topup.com and online company registration, the participants alluded to being assisted by the Chatbots. See Figure 5-32.

Figure 5-33: Application of Toulmin’s Model of argumentation in the Facilitating conditions factor

The study found that participants claimed that the impossibility of conducting business without the use of ICT (borrowing from a participant’s quote) somehow justified the ownership of the facilitating resources to access e-services by the participants. The claim by the participants that it was a requirement that they owned at least a phone resonated partly with the findings by Venkatesh *et al.* (2010) that facilitating conditions had a significant and positive effect in user satisfaction in the mandatory contexts. When the use of technologies is pushed to the citizens by the government and its agencies, it can only be logical that *access to the facilitating resources and services* be a requirement though it does not guarantee usage. The aspect of usage would be affected by other factors such as skillset to create value in use. However, the fact that each of the participants owned a cell phone or smartphone did not mean that they were all aware of the e-Government services as evidenced by the discussion on awareness earlier in the present section of the document.

Co-creation of Value

Because of the experiences shared in quotation 5-16, a new category crept into the researcher’s mind. It was named co-creation of Value. The participant in the stated quotation argued that there was a need for a human intermediary to assist those with a lack of skills. The human intermediary could as well be an employee from the service provider or a member from the social circle. If it is a service provider employee, one is likely to be given a full service, where the one with lack of skills only shares the details as requested by the human intermediary and the service is completely done on their behalf. Similarly, from the conversation with the participants’, they stated that if one lacks the skillset to create value in e-Government services,

the social circles would do the services for them. However, Ravald and Grönroos(1996) argue that a service is not just about what is given to the customer but the sacrifice that the customer should make in the endeavour to benefit from the service. In this regard, the value creation is possible only when the customer has the skill of using the provided service (Grönroos, 2008). It is against this backdrop that the study claims that services done over the counter or through social influence are not enough; there is a need for strategies to be put in place to benefit those who are e-illiterate. One of the motivational constructs in the classic TAM model includes the Perceived Ease of Use commonly abbreviated as PEOU. In the current study, based on the voices of the participants and the contribution by Ravald and Grönroos (1996) and Grönroos (2008), it is about the users' ability to engage with the e-Government services. Therefore, instead of advancing the PEOU, the study advanced the Perceived ability to use (PATU) which was taken to mean the extent to which the user thinks that he/she has the appropriate skill to create value in use.

Cultural issues

The participants from the qualitative study claimed the existence of high-power distance between the government and the citizens. They further argued that the Power distance has affected their effort of giving feedback on the services that they would have used. Many of the participants said they never gave feedback, neither have they been given the opportunity to do so in their interactions with the e-Government services. The mobile financial platforms which were mostly used by the participants do not offer such services. However, there some sites such as the city of Harare website and ZimConnect website that does not offer the feedback facility.

The participants also claimed that uncertainty avoidance also affected their decision-making process of using e-Government services. The participants cited that unfamiliar situations gave them some discomfort. This further underscored the need for using a mix of e-Government services awareness strategies such as demonstrations for familiarity and exposure, and advancement for follow-ups. If governments would organize the workshops such as the BURS e-filing workshops, the issue of unfamiliar situations could be addressed on the go.

There is a consensus amongst authors that the barriers to greater e-engagement are cultural, organizational, and constitutional not technological. These may be closely related to cultural resistance to new forms of economic development, new relationships and new forms of citizenship(OECD, 2010; Pina, Torres & Royo, 2010). As argued by the participants, resistance takes lack of skills needed to create value in use, lack of resources, and lack of awareness, cost

implications, or trust issues especially on transactional services. *The claim by the participants on culture was then advanced in the quantitative study.*

Opportunities to encourage the Disconnected: Whilst participants alluded to the inaccessibility of the internet depending on the location or the network connectivity and/or the lack of e-intermediaries, Evans and Yen (2006) stressed that “the digital have-nots would struggle to be at the same technological level“ unless they receive substantial commitments of technological and educational resources”(p. 220). Reinforcing the argument by Callon (1986) that solutions to problems are embraced if users resonate with the alignment of the solution with their needs and priorities, awareness initiatives must be built around the citizens’ needs and improve accessibility through influence sources such as free internet access in public libraries. Equally, as pointed by the participant librarian, the private libraries also indirectly provide the e-literacy skills to the citizens (see Quotation 5-26).

Quotation 5-26: Transcript extract on the role of the library

The participant librarian was optimistic that partnership between the libraries and the government would go a long way in providing e-Government awareness, training, skills development and above all open opportunities for the libraries.

Direct and Indirect Impact of e-Government services adoption in Zimbabwe

It was found that the lack of choices by the citizenry led them to transact with virtual money as a solution to the physical shortage of cash in Zimbabwe. As such the e-Government adoption in Zimbabwe is somewhat seemingly mandatory specifically for services that require one to transact. In this regard, Al-arabiat (2014) argued that intentions to use or actual usage of e-Government services is not reflective of user satisfaction in mandatory environments. In a similar vein, Al-Jabri (2010) argued that perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and social expectations were among factors that influenced the satisfaction of mandatory technology

adoption. The scholar argued that these factors in turn were influenced by the regulatory, cultural or economic contexts one of which the present participants have alluded to. The perceived ease of use and the perceived usefulness parallel the sacrifice that the customer goes through when using e-services and the actual creation of value in use respectively (Ravald & Grönroos, 1996; Grönroos, 2008; Grönroos, 2011), thereby echoing participant 2's view that ICT skills are needed to engage with e-Government services. The view supported that ICT skills are essential in the usage of online processes (Alshehri & Drew, 2010). E-Government services are not an exception, they are technological and technology is an enabling tool. The e-Government services adoption is dependent on the ICT skillset that is needed for value (value in use) creation. The notion of value creation is in this case concomitant with satisfaction. In this regard, whether the problem and solution given by the government were consistent with the interests of the participant depended mostly on the level of adoption of the e-Government services by the general populace. Indirectly, the mandatory nature of e-Government services in Zimbabwe contributed to the diffusion of ICT literacy and skills development amongst the citizenry. Though not voluntary adopters per se, participants acknowledged the value the services brought in as they interacted with the e-Government services. They cited convenience and flexibility as they could conduct mostly e-Government transactions on the go. These benefits of the e-Government services to the citizens supported what was communicated in the ZIMCONNECT portal under the 'About Us' tab. In the same portal the impact to the focal actor was enhanced service delivery (social) and enhanced revenue collection and cost containment (economic). The *provision of e-Government services has seen the decentralisation of access points by government departments*. Based on the participants' views the Zimbabwe Electricity Supply Authority (ZESA) has expanded its sale of electricity units to third party vendors for the sale of prepaid electricity. The move changed the attitude of those who saw opportunities in the decentralisation as it became a source of income.

Zimbabwe E-Government services Portal (ZimConnect)

Having garnered the participants' storylines on the type of services that they were aware of or interacted with most, a visit to the ZimConnect e-services portal was done to assess the extent of usage and alignment of the e-services as given by both the participants and as communicated on the ZimConnect portal. Table 5-6 shows the e-Government services that are communicated in the Zimbabwe e-services portal.

Table 5-6: Consolidated e-Government services (ZimConnect Portal)

<p>Ministry of Industry and Commerce Online Services</p> <p>1. Enterprise Development * Application for Import Licence * Application for Export Licence * Application for Import Licence Issuance * Application for Export Licence Issuance</p> <p>Online payments forms</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> All mobile payment platforms, 	<p>Ministry of Women Affairs Gender and Community Development Online Services</p> <p>1. Online Application for Women's Development Fund Loan 2. Online Applications for Skills Development Centres 3. Online service to report cases of gender based violence</p> <p>Required documents to be attached. SMS Notifications</p>	<p>Ministry of small to medium enterprises online services</p> <p>1. Cooperatives Registration (Downloadable requirements) 2. Applications for exhibiting local, regionally and internationally 3. Application for business management skills training 4. Business linkage Application</p>	<p>Ministry of Local Government, Public Works and National Housing</p> <p>1. Stateland Department (Title Deeds) o Church Title Deeds o Crèche Deeds o Early Title Deeds o Full Title Deeds o School Title Deeds o Lease Agreement Renewal 2. Stateland Department (Stands) o School Stand o Church Stand o Company Stand o Crèche Stand o Local Stands 3. Estates and Valuations Department o Accommodation</p>	
<p>Ministry of Home Affairs Board of Census online services</p> <p>1. Application for Cinematograph film/ Advertisement/ Public Entertainment 2. Application for Recorded Video/ Film Material Distribution Licence. 3. Application for Reviews and Appeals.</p>	<p>Ministry of Higher and Tertiary Education, Science and Technology Development</p> <p>1. Higher Education Programs o University Council Members o Scholarship Application o Advanced Level Students o Registration 2. Quality Assurance and Standards o Skilled worker registration o Technical Institution registration o Duplicate certificate application o Exemption Application o Apprenticeship Program o Registration of Technical Training Institutes o Exam Related Request 3. Projects and Technology Transfer IPR 101 Training</p>	<p>Public Service Commission</p> <p>1. Registration for employment in the civil service 2. Updating registration details 3. Application for employment in the civil service in response to an advert</p>	<p>Ministry of Environment, Water and Climate</p> <p>1. National ozone Unit o Import/Export Licence o Amend Licence to Import/Export o Replacement of Licence Import/Export o Intention to Dispose 2. Meteorological Department o Data Request Form o Weather Data Subscription o Weather Confirmation Certificate</p>	<p>Government of Zimbabwe</p> <p>Could not open from the ZimConnect Portal. However from the GoZ portal, the e-Government services were as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> E-Learning programme: Online Passport application and processing High Performance Computing (HPC) system Zimbabwe Revenue Authority: e-Taxation Chitungwiza Hospital e-Health Project Liquor License Online Applications Online Deeds and Company registry Public Service Commission: Online HRM Information System including e-Recruitment; Land Information Management System, including Online Application for Land; Mines and Mining Development: Online Prospecting Licence Application and Processing; Immigration: e-Visa Application, Processing and Travellers Clearance; Economic Planning and Investment Promotion: Online Investment Project Application and Processing

Source: Compiled from ZimConnect portal (Last accessed: 4/02/2019)

The ones that are highlighted in green were the ones that were common from the e-services portal and from the participants' voices. The participants in Zimbabwe in the qualitative study claimed they were familiar and engaged in e-Government services such as Toll gates payments, purchases of ZESA prepaid tokens, company registrations; land applications, e-filing, payment for ZIMRA services for local municipality services such as ambulance fees. The participant librarian also claimed that they have assisted citizens in applying for Government jobs. Most participants were familiar with transactional services with very few of the participants accessing informational services. The participants' voices showed the e-Government services that resonated with them or were aware of at the time of conducting the study. The finding also underscored the need for enhancing the e-Government awareness strategies to develop knowledge amongst the citizenry of what e-services are available to them on the phenomenon. Compared to the Singapore CitizenConnect, ZimConnect demonstrated a disconnection with the other Government departments in that not all the e-Government Services are listed. Regular updates to the government websites are needed and should be made integral to governments online. It only takes an online user closing the website or portal to disengage as they are easily frustrated by being alone online and not finding what they are looking for. To ease the bad

online user experience, the top.co.zw and company online registration websites have adapted to using the Chatbots on their sites as a strategy to enhancing the stickiness of their sites. Such designs can boost confidence in online users and gives them a sense of being safe and secure online as they are given seamless attention online and over the counter. A closer look at the e-services that participants' claimed to interact with showed that interacting with the e-services coupled with the cash crisis in Zimbabwe was inevitable as these affected the day-to-day operations of the participants. This finding loops back to the first moment of translation (Problematization) by Callon. Callon (1986) argued that the other actors would form an alliance with the focal actor only if the problem that the focal actor defined was consistent with their interests. Hence, the payment with the virtual money solution then became a mandatory Obligatory Passage of Point (OPP) that could no longer be negotiated in the advent of the cash crisis in Zimbabwe. Table 5-6 shows different e-services that suit different groups of citizens (individual, businesses, or companies). Based on Callon's argument on 'Problematization', not everyone would resonate with all the e-Services; hence target marketing would go a long way in enhancing e-Government adoption and increasing popularity of the other e-Government services in Zimbabwe.

5.4.1 The Research Model

In accordance with the resulting factors from the analysis of qualitative data collected from the participants from Zimbabwe and the literature gleaned from previous studies, the following hypothesis was tested, with specific emphasis on the selected SADC states:

- H₁:** The citizens' perceived ability to use (PATU) has a positive influence on their perceived value (PV) of e-Government services
- H₂:** The citizens' perceived ability to use (PATU) has a positive influence on the attitudes towards using e-Government services
- H₃:** The citizens' perceived value (PV) has a positive influence on attitudes toward using e-Government services
- H₄:** The citizens' attitudes have a significant influence on Behavioural Intention (BI) to use e-Government services
- H₅:** The citizens' social influence (SI) will positively reinforce attitudes towards e-Government
- H₆:** The citizens' perceived privacy and security concerns (P&SC) have a significant effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)
- H₇:** The citizens' perceived e-Service Quality (PerSQ) has a direct effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)
- H₈:** The citizens' perceived trust in technology (TiT) has a direct effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)

- H₉:** The citizens' perceived trust in the government (TiG) has a direct effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)
- H₁₀:** The citizens' perceived internet familiarity (PIF) has a significant effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)
- H₁₁:** The citizens' perceived ability to use (PATU) have a positive influence on the trust they have in e-Government (TieG)
- H₁₂:** The citizens' trust in e-Government (TieG) has a significant influence on their attitudes toward e-Government services
- H₁₃:** The citizens' trust in e-Government (TieG) has a significant influence on their intentions to use e-Government services
- H₁₄:** The facilitating conditions (FC) have a significant influence on the citizens' intentions to use e-Government services
- H₁₅:** The citizens' intentions have a significant influence on the actual usage of e-Government services
- H₁₆:** The higher uncertainty avoidance (UA) has a positive moderating effect of intentions to engage with e-Government services
- H₁₇:** Higher power distance (PD) in the nation has a significant influence on the actual usage of e-Government services
- H₁₈:** The effects of e-Government adoption antecedents' are stronger in Zimbabwe than in Botswana

The resultant graphical representation of the proposed model is shown in Figure 5-34.

Figure 5-34: The proposed conceptual Extended TAM

To measure the scales in the model, an instrument was used whose scale items were either adopted or adapted from antecedent related research or formulated by the author.

5.4.2 Sources of instrument scale items used for estimating the research model

The scale items used for estimating the extended TAM model were adopted, adapted, or authored in the current research as shown in Table 5-7.

Table 5-7: Sources of scale items

Item Code	Scale Item	Source(s)
<i>Perceived Ability to Use (PATU)-is the extent to which the user thinks that he/she has the appropriate skill to create value in use (Author defined).</i>		
PATU1	"Using e-Government services will be easy for me"	(Abu-Shanab, 2014, p. 489)
PATU2	E-Government services are clear, understandable and have an easy to follow the structure	Adapted from (Abu-Shanab, 2014, p. 489)
PATU3	It is easy to access the e-Government services that I need	Adapted from (Abu-Shanab, 2014, p. 489)
PATU4	It is easy to learn to interact with e-Government services	Adapted from (Alsaghier & Ford, 2009, p. 306)
PATU5	E-Government services are provided in a language that I am easy to understand	Author
PATU6	Communication with the government is easier through e-Government websites	Adapted from (Alsaghier & Ford, 2009, p. 306)
<i>Perceived Value (PV) - is the extent to which the user thinks the system benefits him/her (Grönroos, 2008).</i>		
PV1	Using e-Government services will help me conduct transactions with the government faster	Author
PV2	Using e-Government services can save me time, compared to face to face service.	Author
PV3	Using e-Government services can improve the service quality that I will receive, compared to the face to face interaction	Author
PV4	Generally using e-Government websites is useful to access government information and related services	Adapted from (Colesca, 2009b, p. 11)
<i>Trust in e-Government (TieG) –is the extent to which the participants think they have trust in the government, technology and other related trust factors.</i>		
TieG1	I expect that e-Government services are designed to perform to the best interests of the users.	Author
TieG2	I believe that e-Government services are trustworthy	(Colesca, 2009a, p. 43)
TieG3	I believe that e-Government services promote the availability of Government services 24/7	Author
TieG4	I think I can have trust in e-Government	Adapted from (Colesca, 2009a, p. 43)
<i>Trust in Government (TiG)</i>		
TiG1	I trust that the citizen's interests are the number one priority of the government.	(Abu-Shanab, 2014, p. 489)
TiG2	I trust the government's capability in providing safe e-services	(Abu-Shanab, 2014, p. 489)
TiG3	I think e-Government agencies can be trusted in the provision of electronic services to the citizenry	Adapted from (Abu-Shanab, 2014, p. 489)
<i>Trust in the technology used for accessing e-Government services (TiT)</i>		
TiT1	I trust the technologies supporting the system are reliable all the time.	(Colesca, 2009a, p. 43)
TiT2	I trust the technologies supporting the system are secure all the time.	(Colesca, 2009a, p. 43)
TiT3	In overall, I have confidence in the technology used by government agencies to operate the e-Government services	(Colesca, 2009a, p. 43)

TiT4	I trust the mobile device(s) or computer that I use for accessing e-Government services	Adapted from (Abu-Shanab, 2014, p. 489)
TiT5	I trust the technologies used for accessing e-Government services	Author
Social Influence (SI) - is the extent to which people in one's social circles hold the belief that one should use the e-Government services (Venkatesh <i>et al.</i>, 2003, p. 451; Weerakkody, El-Haddadeh & Al-Sobhi, 2013, p. 718; Abu-Shanab, 2014, p. 499).		
SI1	People who influence my behavior think I should use the e-Government services	Adapted from (Venkatesh <i>et al.</i> , 2003, p. 460; Weerakkody, El-Haddadeh & Al-Sobhi, 2013, p. 724)
SI2	I would use the e-Government services if people in my social circle use them	Adapted from (Weerakkody, El-Haddadeh & Al-Sobhi, 2013, p. 724)
SI3	People who influence my behavior think accessing and transacting through e-Government websites or apps is efficient and effective	Adapted from (Weerakkody, El-Haddadeh & Al-Sobhi, 2013, p. 724)
SI4	People in my social circle trust intermediaries (e-offices) a lot	Adapted from (Weerakkody, El-Haddadeh & Al-Sobhi, 2013, p. 724)
SI5	People who are important to me think that I should use the e-Government services	Adapted from (Venkatesh <i>et al.</i> , 2003, p. 460; Weerakkody, El-Haddadeh & Al-Sobhi, 2013, p. 724)
Technical Support (TS)		
TS1	I expect to get the help I need when accessing government services	Adapted from (Venkatesh, Chan & Thong, 2012, p. 130)
TS2	It would be easy for me to get assistance when faced with problems in accessing government services (e.g. there are contact details, FAQ, help options)	Adapted from (Venkatesh, Chan & Thong, 2012, p. 130)
TS3	I expect clear instructions or guidelines when accessing government services	Adapted from (Venkatesh, Chan & Thong, 2012, p. 130)
TS4	I would expect feedback to be prompt once I request help through the contact details on the government website	Author
Privacy and security concerns (PrSC)		
PrSC1	Generally, I trust that e-Government institutions have security mechanisms in place to guard against malicious attacks	Author
PrSC2	I believe my bank can protect me in case of problematic transactions	Author
PrSC3	e-Government websites have policy statements on privacy and security on my interactions with the sites	Author
PrSC4	I feel confident that that encryption and other technological advances on the internet make it safe for me to do business there	(Alsaghier & Ford, 2009, p. 306)
PrSC5	I feel assured of privacy and security in doing business on the internet with the continued upgrades on security structures my bank puts in place	Adapted from (Alsaghier & Ford, 2009, p. 306)
PrSC6	I trust that all parties involved as I interact with the e-Government systems do protect my personal information	Author
Perceived Internet Familiarity (PIF)		
PIF1	I have used electronic sites and the Internet many times	Author
PIF2	I am familiar with using e-Government websites and the Internet	Adapted from (Alsaghier & Ford, 2009, p. 306)
PIF3	My experience in electronic websites is high	Author
PIF4	I am familiar with looking for e-Government services on the internet	Adapted from (Alsaghier and Ford, 2009, p. 306)
PIF5	I am familiar with internet banking	Author
Perceived Service Quality (PerSQ)		
PerSQ1	Generally, e-Government systems provide feedback mechanisms	(Colesca, 2009b, p. 11)
PerSQ2	Generally, the e-Government websites are regularly updated to provide accurate information	Adapted from (Colesca, 2009b, p. 11)
PerSQ3	Generally, the e-Government services provide relevant information	Adapted from (Colesca, 2009b, p. 11)
PerSQ4	Generally, the e-Government services provide significant user interaction	(Colesca, 2009b, p. 11)
PerSQ5	Generally, the e-Government services are easy to navigate structures	Author
PerSQ6	Generally, e-Government systems have easily accessible contact details for the users to communicate with the government and its agencies	Author
PerSQ7	Generally, e-Government services are designed with the user in mind	Author
PerSQ8	Generally, I am satisfied with the quality of e-Government services	Author

<i>Culture: Power Distance (PD) is "the extent to which a less powerful person in the society tolerates inequality of power in the society" (Hofstede, 1984, p. 390).</i>		
PD1	Generally, I am involved in e-Government systems/ services decision making.	Author
PD2	Generally, the government and its agencies ask for my opinion of the e-service prior to the launch of the e-Government services.	Author
PD3	Generally, the e-Government services have provided more opportunities for social interaction with people in government positions.	Author
PD4	Generally, I just use e-Government services without question.	Author
PD5	I often give feedback on the e-Government services that I have used	Author
<i>Culture: Uncertainty Avoidance (UA) is "the extent to which people within a culture are made nervous by situation that they consider unstructured , unclear or unpredictable and the extent to which they have to avoid such situations by adopting strict codes of behavior and a belief in absolute truth" (Hofstede, 1984, p. 390).</i>		
UA1	I enjoy using e-Government systems or services that have clear and easy to understand instructions or guidelines so that I always know what I'm expected to do	Author
UA2	It is important to closely follow instructions and procedures to avoid mistakes	Author
UA3	Generally, the e-Government services that I use have a menu for guidance	Author
UA4	It is usually difficult to find out on my own how the technology works	Author
<i>Facilitating Services and Goods (FS-G)</i>		
FS-G1	I have the resources needed to engage with e-Government systems or services	Adapted from (Venkatesh <i>et al.</i> , 2003, p. 460)
FS-G2	I have the technical skills to engage with e-Government services	Author
FS-G3	I have the technical skills to engage with e-Government services but lack awareness	Author
FS-G4	I access e-Government services through the self-service terminals in the bank	Author
FS-G5	I access e-Government services through the public library	Author
FS-G6	I access e-Government services through the state library	Author
FS-G7	I access e-Government services through rural kiosk.	Author
FS-G8	Given the necessary resources and equipped with technical skill, it would be easy to access e-Government services.	Adapted from (Venkatesh <i>et al.</i>, 2003, p. 460)
<i>Attitude (ATT)</i>		
ATT1	My attitude to using e-Government systems or services is high	
ATT2	My attitude to using e-Government services has been changed by the economic situation in my country	Author
ATT3	Engaging with e-Government services is an innovative idea	Adapted from (Al-Hujran <i>et al.</i> , 2015)
ATT4	Using e-Government services is associated with high internet costs	Author
ATT5	I am not worried about security and privacy concerns because there are safeguards to protect me from malicious attacks.	Author
ATT6	I am not really a fan of technology	Author
ATT7	With exposure it would be easy to use the e-Government services	Author
<i>Behavioural Intention to Use e-Government services (BI)</i>		
BI1	I intend to visit e-Government websites in quest of information	Adapted from (Venkatesh <i>et al.</i> , 2003, p. 460)
BI2	I plan to use e-Government service (such as paying municipality bills) in the following months	Adapted from (Venkatesh <i>et al.</i> , 2003, p. 460)
BI3	Given the assurance, I am likely to disclose personal identification details on e-Government services	Adapted from (Alsaghier and Ford, 2009, p. 306)
BI4	I plan to continue using the e-Government services	Author
BI5	<i>I intend to make e-Government my first choice of doing business with the government</i>	Author

5.5 Proposed E-Government Framework

The proposed framework is viewed from a TAMANT perspective as it is derived from the lens of the TAM and ontology of the ANT. What distinguishes the ontology of ANT from the foundational interpretive constructivism is that the former focuses on the how as compared to

the whys. The reality of this perspective is hinged on the stories of actors who are in turn influenced by the factors in context. These factors included the intra-individual factors, the e-Government awareness strategies, and objectives at local, national or sectorial level. The components of the framework included the translation process, the actor worlds, OPP and the intra-individual factors (see Figure 5-35).

Figure 5-35: The proposed SADC e-Government framework based on the TAMANT perspective

5.6 Chapter Summary

The chapter communicated the lessons learnt from the pilot study and how they informed the main qualitative study. Using the translation process and the notebooks of Latour, the chapter presented the analysis of the main qualitative study. In the spirit of using the Actor-Network Theory as ontology in the study, the narratives of the actors were used to drive the analysis. The experiences shared by the participants led to the identification of categories such as fitness

in the technology solution that led to a new category called mandatory adoption. E-intermediaries ownership resulting from the mandatory adoption; human intermediary as a result of lack of resources by other citizenry; social influence as a supporting force that pulled those with lack of skills or resources up the obligatory passage of point; and the digital skills as a requirement for value creation were amongst factors established to be the antecedents of e-Government adoption in Zimbabwe. In addition, as part of the narratives, the participants' voiced issues that touched on insufficiency of awareness strategies that influence use of e-Government services and knowledge creation about the phenomenon, e-Government services design issues, attitude, facilitating conditions, trust, culture, and technical support whose validity could only be ascertained by interpolating them in the quantitative study. The derived factors were further explored and systematized in connection with the related extant e-Government literature. As a consequence, a conceptual research model and an early contextual SADC e-Government framework were developed (See Figure 5-34 to 35). These are then interrogated and clarified in the following chapter.

6 ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF QUANTITATIVE DATA

6.1 Introduction

This chapter extends the processing of the quantitative data collected from different country cases by establishing interconnections and meanings of these in relation to the problem and research questions stated in Chapter 1. The analysis of the main quantitative data in this chapter was done using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21 with AMOS.

6.2 General Overview

The questionnaire used for eliciting data was divided into two sections: one for demographic data, and the other for assessing the participants' responses on the resultant factors of the qualitative study. The two sections of the questionnaire were analysed and detailed separately in the subsequent sections of the document. As stated in the methodology chapter, the study elicited data from residents in four member states of the SADC. Consequently, the analysis was at a global level (looking at the four countries as a unit), within and across cases. The analysis comprised descriptive statistics in conjunction with univariate, bivariate and multivariate analysis. Consequently, frequency, distribution ranges, measures of central tendency and standard deviations were estimated in different tests. Inferential statistics were carried out to elicit predictive data and significant values at 95% or 99% confidence interval to the analysis. Chi-Square test, t-test, analysis of variance (ANOVA) and factor analysis were used in the psychometric analysis of the measures of the samples.

6.3 Quality of the instrument and pilot study reporting

To measure the quality of the instrument prior to its administration, content validity was done through the face validation and item validity with the experts in the field. The instrument was then pilot tested. The content validity and pilot study processes are explained in detail in sections 6.3.1 and 6.3.2.

6.3.1 Content Validity

Content validity measures “the extent to which the items on an instrument represent the content being measured” (Onwuegbuzie *et al.*, 2007, p. 116). Prior to administering the questionnaire to the main sample, a logically based validity assessment was conducted to ascertain content validity. Firstly, *face validity* and *item validity* were conducted concurrently by the author and two experts in the field whose feedback informed the modifications of the content in the instrument. The modifications included alignment of instrument questions with the knowledge areas as

specified in the research questions and propositions; question #26 was also aligned to the scores of the Likert scale as requested by one of the experts who also advised that the atomicity of the latent questions be checked. As suggested, the instrument items were checked and those that were double-barrelled were split. Some latent questions were added, removed, or rephrased. The experts then affirmed the *sample validity* by endorsing the suitability of the instrument scales and their corresponding items in measuring e-Government adoption according to the research questions.

6.3.2 Pilot study and lessons learnt

Thereafter, a pilot study was conducted in September 2017 with the intention to pre-test the face-validated instrument for the wording of the questionnaire; to gain familiarity with the participants; and to assess the response rate to the instrument. Initially, the instrument was pre-tested using a mixture of online questionnaires where a link was sent via email; and, some were hand-delivered to the participants. Amongst the recipients of the link that was sent via email, some participants (especially older ones) requested that the form be sent to them preferably as an email attachment. Consequently, the third method of administration was included to address the different needs, preferences, and e-literacy levels of the participants. A total of one hundred and sixty (160) questionnaires were administered for the pilot study of which ninety (90) were sent as a link to the online questionnaire, thirty (30) were sent through e-mail as an attachment, and forty (40) were hand-delivered to the participants. For the questionnaire whose link was sent via email, only twenty-one (21) online responses were gotten of which seven (count: 7; 33.3%) of them were completed by females and fourteen (count: 14; 67.7%) by males as shown in Figure 6-1. The results shown in Figure 8-1 were extracted from the online analytics of the piloted study. The twenty-one (21) who responded through the online questionnaire constituted twenty-three percent (23%) of those who received the questionnaire via the first method. Equally, the second and third administration methods had lower numbers of respondents with five (5) and eleven (11) respondents respectively. A total of thirty-seven (37) responses were returned from one hundred and sixty (160) questionnaires that were sent out. The response rate was not good, at approximately twenty-three percent (23%), considering the three administration methods.

1. What is your gender?

21 responses

Figure 6-1: Extract of the pilot study Google forms online analytics on Gender

The response rates for each of the methods that were used for distributing the questionnaire and how they were spread gender-wise is shown in Table 6-1.

Table 6-1: Response rate for the pilot study

Method of Administration	No. of Questionnaires				Response rate per method (%)
	Sent	Returned		Total	
		F	M		
Online (Questionnaire Link sent via email)	90	7	14	21	23,33
Email (Questionnaire Link sent via email as an attachment)	30	1	4	5	17,5
Face to face (Hand Delivered)	40	4	7	11	27,5
Total	160	12	25	37	23,13

Lessons Learnt

From the process of the pilot study, there were some lessons that were learnt. These included the following:

- a. Amongst the online questionnaire respondents, some were early respondents who responded soon after they received the link. There were also some late respondents who tried to access the link when the online questionnaire was not accepting responses anymore and this was evidenced by those who got back through the e-mail that sent the questionnaire link. Consequently, it was found that participants needed to be constantly reminded to fill in the questionnaire.
- b. The online questionnaire on its own managed to capture the first four of the six age groups as shown in Figure 6-2.

Figure 6-2: Extract of Age group representation from the online analytics of the questionnaire (Pilot study)

The 25-34-year age group had the highest online representation at 38.1%; the 35-44-Year age group was at 33.3%; the 45-54-year age group was at 23.8%; and the 55-66-year age group was represented at 4.8%. The 15-24-year age group and that above 67 years were not represented.

- c. It was learnt that none of the methods could guarantee a high response rate. This was dependent on the participant interest in the study, and the time that was allocated to the participants to return the questionnaire. As such, some needed to be constantly reminded about filling in the questionnaire.
- d. For hand-delivered questionnaires, some claimed to have misplaced the questionnaire and one had to administer the questionnaire again if they were willing to fill the second administered questionnaire and return it. In contrast, the online questionnaires needed that at most the reminders of the link be sent to prospective participants.
- e. The advantage the hand-delivered questionnaires method had over others was when the participants needed to be helped in filling the form owing to challenges in reading and/or understanding English. The presence of the human intermediary for some participants, especially the elderly, proved fruitful. It was through this method that we got errors such as missing letters and repeated questions communicated by the participants.

6.4 Main Quantitative Study

Having addressed the changes that arose from the pilot study, the main quantitative questionnaire was then distributed to a total sample of 1 390 including 300 online; 90 email; and 1 000 face-to-face. The total number of participants who responded and returned the

questionnaire was three hundred and thirty-five (335) of which eighty-five (85) responded online, two hundred and forty (233) responded through face-to-face and administered questionnaires, and seventeen (17) from e-mail administered questionnaires. The 85 online responses were all usable. Of the two hundred and forty (240) face-to-face and e-mail returned questionnaires, eighteen (18) were incomplete with missing responses and therefore were unusable. The missing values were identified when the frequencies for each scale were computed. Having exempted the incomplete questionnaires, three hundred and seventeen (317) questionnaires were usable and were considered in the quantitative analysis of the study. The three hundred and seventeen (317) returned questionnaires meant that the return rate was 23% in total, closely resembling the return rate established from the pilot study.

6.4.1 Descriptive Analysis: Demographic Information of Participants

The questionnaire had two sections. The first section elicited demographic data whose descriptive statistics are presented in this section of the document. The participants’ countries of origin extended outside of SADC as the elicited data showed that they were drawn from Belgium, Ethiopia, India, Lesotho, Malawi, Mozambique, Namibia, Nigeria, South Africa, Sri Lanka, Swaziland, Tanzania, Zambia and Zimbabwe.

Figure 6-3: Participants’ Countries of Origin

The participants were not residing in their countries of origin at the time of the data collection. Zimbabwe was highly represented at sixty-two percent (62%), Botswana at 18%, South Africa at 6%, Namibia at 5%, and the rest of the countries were represented at less than 10% altogether. Figure 6-3 illustrates the countries of origin, the frequency, and the percentage frequency in relation to the total number of the considered participants (317) in the study. At the time of conducting the study, the participants were resident in one of the four SADC sampled countries namely: Zimbabwe, South Africa, Namibia, and Botswana. For this reason, the subsequent analysis was presented for the individual countries and collectively for the purposes of carrying out cross-case analysis. The demographic characteristics of the participants in Table 6-2 included gender, age, level of education and professional status. These are discussed below.

Gender

Table 6-2 showed that at a macro level across the sample, the gender participation was dominated by males (count: 188; 59.3%), and the rest (count: 129; 40.7%) were females. The domineering male trend in participation was also evident at country level in all the sampled SADC member states cases with Botswana at 58.1%, Namibia at 61,1%, South Africa at 60%, and Zimbabwe at 59,3%.

Age

At whole sample level, all the age groups were represented at 13.2% (15-24 years); 33.1% (25-34 years); 35.3% (35-44 years); 14.8% (45-54); and 3.5% (55-66 years). More than 65% of the participants were aged between 25 and 44 years. The most represented age group was the 35-44 years. At the micro level, all age groups were represented in all the four country cases except for the 55-66 age groups which were only represented in Botswana and Zimbabwe. The age group of most participants from Botswana (79.7%) were aged between 25 and 44 years. The most represented group (25-34 years) accounting for 43.2% participation from both males and females at the country level. In the Namibian sample, most participants were aged between 25 and 54 years representing 88.9% of the country total. Similarly, the 25-34 years age group (Generation Y: the participants in the group were born and bred in the digital environment between 1981 and year 2000) dominated in the Namibian case at 36.1%. The South African case had 88.9% of the participants aged between 25 and 54, with the popular age group being 35-44 years at 48.6%. Similarly, the 35-44 years age group dominated the participation in the Zimbabwean case at 34.1%.

Table 6-2: Demographic characteristics of the participants

Demographic Characteristic	Current country location of the participant (freq)				Total	Current country location of the participant (%)				Total	
	Botswana	Namibia	South Africa	Zimbabwe		ALL	Botswana	Namibia	South Africa		Zimbabwe
AGE RANGE	Male	43	22	21	102	188	58,1%	61,1%	60,0%	59,3%	59,3%
	Female	31	14	14	70	129	41,9%	38,9%	40,0%	40,7%	40,7%
	15-24 yrs.	2	4	1	35	42	2,7%	11,1%	2,9%	20,3%	13,2%
	25-34 yrs.	32	13	9	51	105	43,2%	36,1%	25,7%	29,7%	33,1%
	35-44 yrs.	27	9	17	59	112	36,5%	25,0%	48,6%	34,3%	35,3%
	45-54 yrs.	7	10	8	22	47	9,5%	27,8%	22,9%	12,8%	14,8%
	55-66 yrs.	6	0	0	5	11	8,1%	0,0%	0,0%	2,9%	3,5%
LOCATION	rural area	1	4	8	17	30	1,4%	11,1%	22,9%	9,9%	9,5%
	Peri-urban	6	1	7	7	21	8,1%	2,8%	20,0%	4,1%	6,6%
	urban area	67	31	20	148	266	90,5%	86,1%	57,1%	86,0%	83,9%
LEVEL OF EDUCATION	Secondary school or less	5	3	0	50	58	6,8%	8,3%	0,0%	29,1%	18,3%
	High school (F5, F6 or equivalent)	1	8	2	31	42	1,4%	22,2%	5,7%	18,0%	13,2%
	College but no degree	2	5	2	45	54	2,7%	13,9%	5,7%	26,2%	17,0%
	University (bachelor's degree or equivalent)	22	10	9	31	72	29,7%	27,8%	25,7%	18,0%	22,7%
	University (postgraduate degree)	41	10	20	15	86	55,4%	27,8%	57,1%	8,7%	27,1%
	Other	3	0	2	0	5	4,1%	0,0%	5,7%	0,0%	1,6%
PROFESSION	Student	8	4	1	43	56	10,8%	11,1%	2,9%	25,0%	17,7%
	Teacher	8	5	6	17	36	10,8%	13,9%	17,1%	9,9%	11,4%
	University/ college lecturer	40	14	11	14	79	54,1%	38,9%	31,4%	8,1%	24,9%
	Farmer	0	1	0	6	7	0,0%	2,8%	0,0%	3,5%	2,2%
	e-Government project manager	0	0	2	0	2	0,0%	0,0%	5,7%	0,0%	,6%
	Developer	2	1	2	2	7	2,7%	2,8%	5,7%	1,2%	2,2%
	Designer	1	3	0	3	7	1,4%	8,3%	0,0%	1,7%	2,2%
	Librarian	5	1	2	13	21	6,8%	2,8%	5,7%	7,6%	6,6%
	Freelancer	0	1	5	4	10	0,0%	2,8%	14,3%	2,3%	3,2%
	Unemployed	0	2	1	28	31	0,0%	5,6%	2,9%	16,3%	9,8%
	Other	10	4	5	42	61	13,50%	11,10%	14,30%	24,40%	19,20%
TOTAL	74	36	35	172	317	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	100,0	

Most participants from Zimbabwe were aged between 15- and 44-years accounting for 84.3% at the country level. The 35-44 years age group most represented in the South Africa and Zimbabwe cases was mostly a generation X though it tapped slightly into generation Y. Generation X is the age group that witnessed the shift from written to digital knowledge archives. The generation Z (the tech-savvy group) was represented in all country cases with notable participation of 20.3% in Zimbabwe.

Profession

In terms of the participants' occupational status, the participants were drawn from heterogeneous groups including students, farmers, teachers, lecturers, designers, developers, and the unemployed with the most represented profession status being university/college lecturers (24.9%) at the macro level. The participants' level of education ranged from secondary school or less to the postgraduates spread across Botswana, Namibia, South Africa, and Zimbabwe.

Level of Education

The most represented level of education of the participants was the Bachelors' degree across the sample. At the micro level, most participation was from the postgraduate degree holders in Botswana (54.4%), bachelors' or postgraduate degree (27.8%) in Namibia, a postgraduate degree (57.1%) in South Africa, and secondary school or less (29.1%) in Zimbabwe.

6.4.2 Descriptive analysis: Ownership of e-intermediaries amongst participants

To ascertain a digital connection with the respective governments and as a stepping stone to the adoption of e-Government services, the participants were asked about ownership of e-intermediaries such as cell phones, smartphones, iPads, laptops, desktop computers and landline phone/extension in question 8 of the administered questionnaire. At macro level, the responses indicated that participants have direct ownership of cell phones (77%), smartphones (64%), iPads (17%), laptops (59.3%), desktop computers (14.2%), and landline phones/extension or equivalent (6.6%). In addition, the participants have an indirect ownership of e-intermediaries including of those owned in the family: cell phones (2.2%), smartphones (7.9%), iPads (10.1%), laptops (6%), desktop computers (7.9%), and landline phones/extension (14.8%); owned work/school: cell phones (0.9%), smartphones (2.5%), iPads (7.6%), laptops (5.0%), desktop computers (20.5%), and landline phones/extension or equivalent (29%); and owned at the internet café or libraries : desktop computers (5.0%), and landline phones/extension or equivalent (3.2%). Amongst the participants, are those that have multiple ownership of the e-intermediaries in person, family, work/school: cell phones (10.1%), smartphones (3.5%), iPads (3.2%), laptops (5.4%), desktop computers (5.4%), and landline

phones/extension or equivalent (2.2%); in family and at work/school: cell phones (3.5%), smartphones (5.7%), iPads (16.4%), laptops (6.0%), desktop computers (7.9%), and landline phones/extension or equivalent (6.6%); in person, family, work/school and in the Internet Cafés/libraries: desktop computer (1.9%). Showing the persistent digital divide in terms of access to e-intermediaries amongst the citizens is the non-ownership of these by participants. At least 6.3% does not own each of the stated e-intermediaries. Figure 6-4 show the ownership status of e-intermediaries in detail.

Figure 6-4: Spread of e-intermediaries as owned by the participants at the macro level

Figure 6-4 demonstrates the unequal access of e-intermediaries which are needed to access the e-Government services. The participants’ responses reveal that there were those who had non-ownership but had direct use of institutionally owned e-intermediaries in the libraries, schools, at work, and at the internet café. Despite having other citizens with multiple accesses to e-intermediaries, some had none. The penultimate entry in Figure 6-4 revealed that the desktop computer is owned universally in person at home, work/school, and internet café and in the libraries by 1.9%. Approximately 6.3% participants claimed non-ownership of cell phone; 16.4 % (smartphone); 45.7% (iPad); 18.3% (laptop); 3.2% (desktop computer); and 37.5% (landline phone or equivalent). This is visually evidenced by the rightmost bars of each category in Figure 6-4. Owing to multiple accesses of intermediaries by some participants, not all the participants represented by the rightmost bars in Figure 6-4 were strictly non-owners of e-intermediaries. 6 % (count: 18) claimed to only directly own cell phones. The cell phone only owners had no direct access to the internet. These were mostly unemployed, traders, security personnel, or freelancers aged between 15 and 54 years. Sixty-six percent of these were aged

between 25 and 44 years. This finding echoes the finding from the main qualitative study. A participant from the qualitative study, Laizah, submitted that her motivations of using the cell phones are linked to the lack of income to buy a smartphone. The participant disclosed using the phone for communicating with friends and relatives. In addition, she could manage her airtime and electricity units selling a business using the cell-phone at minimal charges. This showed that the primary reason for owning the phone was the need to manage a micro business rather than seeing it as an alternative channel of communicating with the Government.

At the micro level, South Africa dominated indirect cell phone ownership at 88.6%, Botswana at 87.8%, Namibia at 83.3% and Zimbabwe at 68.6%. In terms of direct ownership of smartphones, Botswana recorded 93.2%, South Africa 68, 6%, Namibia 63.9% and Zimbabwe at 50.6%. Botswana continued to dominate in direct laptop ownership at 79.7%, Namibia 72.2%, South Africa at 65.7 % and Zimbabwe trailing at 46.5%. The iPad, Desktop Computer and the Tel/ext. or equivalent was each represented at lower than 30% in each country with direct ownership ranging between 4.1% and 28.6% (see the radar in Figure 6-5 for more details on the ownership of e-intermediaries in the study). All the participants in the qualitative study owned at least a cell phone or a smart phone, with some having multiple ownership of these devices. Similar views were echoed in the quantitative study. The study reports an update of direct ownership in person of the e-intermediaries. The participants responses showed that a greater part directly owns cell phone (77%), Smartphone (64%), and laptop (59%). The iPad, Desktop Computer and the telephone ext. or landline are owned by the minority.

Figure 6-5: Intermediary spread per country

6.4.3 Descriptive analysis: Awareness of e-Government

One cannot use a service that they are not aware of. Hence, for the adoption levels of e-Government to increase, there have to be some high levels of awareness (directly or vicariously) of the e-Government services by the citizenry.

6.4.3.1 The participant's awareness levels

To ascertain the awareness levels of e-Government, participants were asked to rank their awareness levels ranging between 'not at all aware' and extremely aware'. At country level a lowly represented number in each of the four countries claimed complete lack of awareness: 5.4% (Botswana), 8.3% (Namibia), 5.7% (South Africa) and 9.9% (Zimbabwe). Consolidated, the complete lack of awareness accounts for 8.2%. The greater part of the participants from Botswana, Namibia and South Africa and across the sample alluded to be moderately aware as evidenced by the outstandingly longer purple bars in Figure 6-6. However, 27.3% of participants from Zimbabwe (representing the greater part) were slightly aware, followed by 23.8% being extremely aware and slightly lower percentage being somewhat aware. Over 50% of the participants in both Botswana and Namibia revealed that they have a considerable level of awareness. Although the consolidated level of awareness was also slightly above 50%, South Africa and Zimbabwe responses showed frequencies slightly below fifty percent at 48.6% and 45.9 % respectively.

Figure 6-6: Participants level of Awareness of e-Government

6.4.3.2 Sources of Awareness of e-Government

The participants were asked in question 10 about the sources through which they become aware of the e-Government services in their respective countries where they resided at the time of data collection. At the macro level, all sources such as government websites, social influence, print media, television, radio, customer care centres and pamphlets from government offices were accessible to the participants. Figure 6-7 shows how the participants got to be aware of the e-Government services

Figure 6-7: Sources of e-Government services awareness by Government

Figure 6-7 shows that the popularity of the sources of e-Government services awareness came from the social Influence including families and friends at 61.2 % (count: 194) of the participants. The sources that followed closely in raising the much-needed awareness were the television at 49.8% (count: 154); radio attracted 36.6% (count: 116) of the participants, print media at 36% (count: 114), and Government websites at 33.8% (count: 107). The rest attracted less than 25 % of the participants each with the least source (telephone calls from Government departments or related agents) attracting 5.7% (count: 18). At country level, the responses from the participants as evidenced in Figure 6-8 shows that all the sources indicated in the questionnaire were used in each of the countries. In Botswana, South Africa and Zimbabwe, the participants claimed that the popular source was the social influence through their circles, friends, and families amongst others. The claim coincided with the most popular source at all country cases level except for Namibia. Namibia recorded highly on print media and television each at 15.9%, followed by the social influence and radio at 15.3 % each.

Figure 6-8: Sources of e-Government awareness per country

In Namibia, the most popular was the print media. Government websites were amongst the second or third most popular source of e-Government awareness in Botswana and South Africa. In the four countries television was a common source with each country attracting at least 13 % of the participants per country. Figure 6-8 suggests that all the sampled countries have at least some representation in each of the studied sources from the participants. This finding shows the effort that the governments exert efforts in their endeavours to reach as many citizens as possible.

6.4.4 Descriptive analysis: The participants’ e-Government services access level

Given a wide range of e-services to choose from, the participants established that there is at least some trace that they access each service collectively (at the macro level) at varying levels (See Figure 6-9). Whilst basic services such as registration of birth / death certificates are done frequently, as an e-service it is rarely used with approximately 68% of the participants claiming non-usage. The top five e-services that are used by the participants (periodically, rarely or every time) include social communication (92%), research (92.1%), reading online newspapers (84%), mobile banking (86%) and e-education services (79%).

Figure 6-9: Level of access to e-services by participants

The levels at which these are accessed can be used by the supply side to cajole the citizenry into adopting the e-Government services. Reading the graph from the bottom shows the most accessed services. Reading from the top shows the least accessed services.

Figure 6-10: Level of access of e-services by country

By simply knowing where they congregate (social media), it then should be taken as the target place to share with the citizens at the least, e-Government information. Figure 6-9 showed that online newspapers were widely read. Hence, online newspapers could be used vigorously as an awareness campaign. Each online newspaper reader relates to yet other people, with whom they share the information from the newspaper, increasing the sought awareness amongst the citizenry. The unequal access of the e-services is also exacerbated by the unequal access to the intermediaries (see the summarised access levels detail in Figure 6-9 and more in Annexure H). The data garnered on the e-service access level was also presented to reflect the extent to which each e-service is accessed at the country level (see Figure 6-10 and more in Annexure H). Some services were commonly accessed by at least 50% of the participants in each case country. These included services such as e-education (Botswana: 58.1%; Namibia: 75%; South Africa: 65.7%, and Zimbabwe: 56.4%); internet banking (Botswana: 70.3 %; Namibia: 69.4%; South Africa: 65.7%, and Zimbabwe: 55.2%); informational services (Botswana: 51.3 %; Namibia: 69.4%; South Africa: 71.5%, and Zimbabwe: 63.4%); and mobile banking (Botswana: 70.2 %; Namibia: 77.8%; South Africa: 80%, and Zimbabwe: 76.2%). Included amongst the popular e-services are the two services that have been circled in Figure 7-10: social communication, and research. Not only are they popular, but these are services that most of the participants in each case the country claimed to be using 'every time'. Whilst internet banking is amongst the top e-services commonly accessed by participants, online submission of tax declarations was not as popular (Botswana: 59.5 %; Namibia: 55.5%; South Africa: 40%, and Zimbabwe: 15.2%). It emerged that Zimbabwe was rather slow in embracing the e-filing system. On the other hand, the e-municipality services were fairly accessed in Namibia and Zimbabwe (Botswana: 35.2%; Namibia: 55.6%; South Africa: 28.5%, and Zimbabwe: 55.2%); e-Health services were fairly accessed in Zimbabwe with the rest of the case countries scoring lowly (Botswana: 37.8 %; Namibia: 33.4%; South Africa: 22.8%, and Zimbabwe: 54.6%). It was established that the participants from Namibia claimed that they fairly engaged with their government through e-services (58.4%), with South Africa trailing behind at 40 %. Botswana and Zimbabwe participants claimed that they are lowly engaged with their governments at 29.7 % and 25.6% respectively.

6.4.5 Scale Internal Consistency reliability

The second section of the questionnaire assessed the interrelationships of the variables that resulted from the qualitative study and were intended to measure the adoption levels of e-Government from the participants. There were fifteen variables and these were captured from question 12 to 26 in the questionnaire. These variables were in the form of Likert Scale questions which had at least three scale items each measured through a five-point Likert Scale. To measure the interrelatedness of the scale items, and also to measure the amount of

measurement error in the test, the internal consistency reliability was estimated for Cronbach's Alpha (α) values using multi-scale items for each scale measured (Gliem and Gliem, 2003; Tavakol and Dennick, 2011).

There are different interpretations of Cronbach α values (minimum and maximum) in literature: Hinton, McMurray and Brownlow (2014, p. 356) recommended an α value scale of above 0.75 (as high reliability), between 0.5 and 0.75 (as moderately reliable), and an α value below 0.5 (as low reliability). On the other hand, Lee, Kim and Ahn (2011), Pallant (2011), and Yong and Pearce (2013) suggested the minimum acceptable Cronbach α value of 0.70, and Streiner (2003) and Tavakol and Dennick (2011) recommended a maximum α value of 0.90. The study acknowledges and respects the different findings on Cronbach α values. However, it is important to note that all the scales in the study have less than 10 scale items. Hence, in the current study, the acceptable Cronbach α value range was between 0.70 and 0.90. The Cronbach α values was estimated for the study scales and were summarized in Table 6-3. The measures in Table 6-3 pointed to the greater part of the scales being internally consistent as the Cronbach α values were found to be in a preferable range: greater than 0,7 and less than ,90 as suggested by (Pallant, 2011). UA and ATT (*circled*) scale were an exception as they proved to be at low and moderate levels respectively as stated by Hinton, McMurray & Brownlow, (2014, p. 356). In a similar vein, Pallant (2011) posited that the Cronbach test is susceptible to the number of items such that α values can be small for scales with less than ten items. For UA and ATT (*circled*) scales with α values that were less than the minimum of 0.70, their inter-items and inter-item correlations were checked to ascertain homogeneity of the respective scale items, and the results are shown in Table 6-4. The means of each of the scales including for UA and ATT showed that they were close to each other (see the mean ranges: Minimum and maximum of the means in Table 6-3).

Table 6-3: Internal Reliability Statistics

QUESTION NUMBER)	SCALE	N	(MEAN)		INTER-ITEM MEANS	STD DEVIATION	CRONBACH'S ALPHA ON STANDARDIZED ITEMS	NUMBER OF SCALE ITEMS
			Min.	Max.				
12	PATU	317	3.306	3.814	3.538	.73727	0.808	6
13	PV	316	3.956	4.171	4.051	.78940	0.833	4
14	TieG	317	3.757	4.11	3.901	.72587	0.825	4
15	TiG	317	3,562	3,703	3,621	,88850	0,83	3
16	TiT	317	3,514	3,798	3,625	,79888	0,889	5
17	SI	317	3,596,	3,767	3,68	.79429	0.845	5
18	TS	317	4.183	4.423	4.3	.82186	0.853	4
18	PrSC	317	3.637	3.82	3.722	.71429	0.844	6
20	PIF	317	3.7	4.249	3.89	.81803	0.869	5
21	PerSQ	317	3.435	3.656	3.586	.71060	0.898	8
22	PD	317	2.47	3.151	2.834	.84170	0.765	5
23	UA	317	3.369	3.804	3.75	.64705	0.522	4
24	FS-G	317	2.546	3.732	3.237	.74412	0.794	8
25	ATT	317	3.088	4.022	3.584	.66320	0.66	7
26	BI	317	3.215	4.006	3.825	.72888	0.777	5

According to Briggs and Cheek (1986, p.114) in Pallant, (2011), the acceptable range of mean inter-item correlation is between 0.2 and 0.4 for the optimal homogeneity level. Table 6-4 demonstrates that the sought values were within the acceptable range of homogeneity.

Table 6-4: Inter-Item Correlations for UA and ATT scales

SCALE		MEAN	NUMBER OF ITEMS
UA	Item Means	3.750	4
	Inter-Item Correlations	.267	4
ATT	Item Means	3.584	7
	Inter-Item Correlations	.217	7

Thus, the Cronbach α values of UA, ATT, and the rest of the scales in Table 6-3 were acceptable as they satisfied the statistic.

6.4.6 Validity

To measure the validity of the scale empirically, a construct validity test was done. Construct validity is “the extent to which an instrument can be interpreted as a meaningful measure of some characteristic or quality” (Onwuegbuzie *et al.*, 2007, p. 116; Pallant, 2011). To this effect, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) test was used as an extraction method so that interpretation of scale items could be done using the total variance derived from a smaller set of

underlying components without losing much information (Pallant, 2007, 2011; Hair *et al.*, 2010). Firstly, the sample size and the ratio of participants to items were assessed for the factorability of the data. The sample size of 317 was large enough for the factors that were obtained to be generalised and the ratio of participants to items was at least 39:1 which was far higher than the recommended 10:1.

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of sampling adequacy (KMO-MSA) and Bartlett's tests were considered to determine the appropriateness of factor analysis results on the data. Kaiser and Rice (1974) classified the KMO-MSA value in the 0.60s as "mediocre" whilst Pallant (2007, 2011) state that 0.6 is the minimum acceptable. Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) argue that most of the correlation matrix coefficients should be greater than 0.3 for factor analysis to be used in a study. Similarly, Hair *et al.* (2010) suggested that the anti-image correlation matrix is checked for the KMO-MSA values of each item/variable (must be greater than 0.5). Both methods were considered in the study. The Bartlett's Test was used to check if the original correlation matrices of the items were comparable to identity matrices. Pallant (2007, 2011) suggests that Bartlett's Test of Sphericity should be significant at $p < 0.05$. On the number of components retained, Zwick and Velicer (1982), after the comparison of four rules which included KAISER rule known for considering eigenvalues greater than unity (Kaiser, 1960); BART rule known as the Bartlett's Test (Bartlett, 1950); Scree Test ; and the Minimum Average Partial method (MAP) which is based on the matrix of partial correlations (Velicer, 1976) recommended that the Scree Test be used in the PCA test. In a similar vein, Osborne and Costello (2009) argued that MAP and Parallel Analysis were the most accurate and easy to use. In the current study, both the KAISER and the Scree plot tests were used. The latter was used for confirmatory purposes. Where there was a mismatch, the Parallel Analysis test analysis was used for triangulation purposes. The PCA was conducted for each Likert Scale in which case the total number of components retained in the Total Variance Explained table was checked against the scree plot per scale.

Perceived Ability to Use (PATU)

Table 6-5 shows the PCA for the PATU scale. Most of the Pearson correlation coefficients of all the paired PATU items were found to be above 0.3 and all were less than 0.9 except the pairs that lay in the primary diagonal. Only four of the 36 correlations were above 0.2 but less than 0.3. The anti-image correlation matrix echoed the reasonable factorability of the items as the leading diagonal correlations were all above 0.5 ranging between 0.814 and 0.859. The KMO-MSA value scored 0.833 which was above the recommended value. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 = 556.539$; $DF = 15$; $p < 0.05$). The results showed that the KMO-MSA classified as "meritorious" using the description used by Kaiser and Rice (1974) as it

exceeded 0.80. This further supports the fact that there was at least a pair of items that shared a common variance. Therefore the tests supported the suitability of factor analysis on the data set from the PATU scale of 6 items. As per the Total Variance Explained table (see Annexure I), it was evident that the correlation matrix of PATU items was reducible using a one (1) dimension solution. The only eigenvalue greater than unity was that of the first component which was found to be 3.090 ($e_1 > 1.0$), explaining 51.03% of the variance of the items in the scale. Consequently, the construct satisfied the convergent validity criterion since the average variance explained (AVE) is 0.5485 ($AVE > 0.5$).

Table 6-5: The Principal Component Analysis for Perceived Ability to Use e-Government services

PATU ITEMS	CORRELATION MATRIX ^a						FL	COMM
	1	2	3	4	5	6		
e-Government services easy to use (1)	0.814^b						0.623	0.388
E-Government is clear. Understandable. easy to follow (2)	0.438	0.816^b					0.774	0.598
Easy to access e-Government services (3)	0.275	0.538	0.815^b				0.759	0.577
Easy to learn to interact with e-Government services (4)	0.361	0.466	0.546	0.844^b			0.773	0.597
e-services are provided in a language that is easy to understand (5)	0.344	0.533	0.515	0.502	0.859^b		0.763	0.582
Communication is easy through e-Government websites (6)	0.362	0.286	0.312	0.394	0.32	0.849^b	0.589	0.347

a. Determinant = .169;
 b. KMO-MSA for each item
 Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis
 AVE=51.03.
 FL-Factor Loading
 COMM-Communality

Using the Scree plot rule (see Annexure I) supported the finding of only one component retained evidenced by the only component that lay above the scree (gradual tapping of the rest of the components). Thus, results showed that factor analysis of the PATU dataset would be meaningful with a one-component solution. All the component loadings in Table 6-5 were greater than 0.3 (Osborne & Costello, 2009). All the component loadings were found to be practically significant as they had loadings greater than 0.5 (Hair et al., 2010), suggesting that the components were sufficiently explained by the factor solution. None of the scale items were removed. Hence, the internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha value was maintained at 0.808.

Perceived Value (PV)

Table 6-6 shows the PCA for the PV scale. All the Pearson correlation coefficients of all the paired PV items were found to be above 0.3 and all were less than 0.9 except the pairs that lay in the primary diagonal. The anti-image correlation matrix echoed the reasonable factorability of the items as the leading diagonal correlations were all above 0.5 ranging between 0.753 and 0.843. The KMO-MSA value scored 0.788 which was above the recommended value. The Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity was significant ($\chi^2= 487.462$; $DF=6$; $p<0.05$) suggesting a very significant group of correlations that are not reducible to an identity matrix.

Table 6-6: The Principal Component Analysis for Perceived Value of e-Government services

PV ITEMS	CORRELATION MATRIX ^a				FL	COMMU
	1	2	3	4		
e-Government services help conduct transactions with government faster (1)	0.753^b				0.862	0.742
e-Government services save time compared to face to face service (2)	0.686	0.756^b			0.84	0.705
e-Government services can improve the service quality compared to face to face interaction (3)	0.578	0.581	0.826^b		0.817	0.667
e-Government services are useful to access government information (4)	0.524	0.452	0.507	0.843^b	0.745	0.556

a. Determinant = **.211**;
 b. The KMO-MSA for each item
 Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis
 AVE=61.740
 FL-Factor Loading
 COMM-Communality

This further supported the fact that there was some pair(s) of items that shared a common variance. As per the Total Variance Explained Table, it was evident that the correlation matrix of PV items could be summarised using a one (1) dimension solution. The only eigenvalue of the first component was found to be 2.670 ($e_1 >1.0$), explaining 66.740% of the variance of the 4 items in the scale. Consequently, the construct satisfied the convergent validity criterion (AVE=0.668).The Scree Plot (see Annexure I) supported the finding of only one component retained as per the Total Variance Explained Table of PV (Annexure I). The tests supported the use of factor analysis on the data set from the PV scale of 4 items. All the component loadings were found to be greater than 0.5 making them practically significant. As such, the resultant communalities were greater than 0.5 signifying that the components were sufficiently explained by the factor solution. None of the items were removed. Hence, the internal consistency using Cronbach’s alpha value was maintained at 0.833.

Trust in e-Government (TieG)

Table 6-7 shows the PCA for the TieG scale. The Pearson correlation coefficients of all the paired TieG items were greater than 0.3 and less than 0.9 except the pairs that lay in the primary diagonal. The anti-image correlation matrix echoed the reasonable factorability of the items as the leading diagonal correlations were all above 0.5 ranging between 0.724 and 0.843. The results show that the KMO-MSA is greater than 0.5 at 0.771. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was found to be significant ($\chi^2= 477.309$; DF = 6; $p<0.05$) suggesting that the correlation matrix of the TieG elements is not comparable to an identity matrix. The tests supported the use of factor analysis on the data set from the TieG scale of 4 items. Only the eigenvalue of the first component was found to be 2.628 ($e_1 >1.0$), explaining 65.706% of the variance of the items in the scale. Consequently, the communalities column demonstrates the establishment of the convergent validity criterion ($AVE>0.5$).

Table 6-7: The Principal Component Analysis for Trust in e-Government services

TIEG ITEMS	CORRELATION MATRIX ^a				FL	COMM
	1	2	3	4		
e-Government services are designed to the best interest of users (1)	0.843^b				0.730	0.533
e-Government services are trustworthy (2)	0.440	0.747^b			0.829	0.688
e-Government services promote availability of government services 24/7 (3)	0.513	0.524	0.808^b		0.813	0.661
I trust e-Government services (4)	0.471	0.697	0.596	0.724^b	0.864	0.746

a. Determinant = .219;

b. The KMO-MSA for each item

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

FL-Factor Loading

COMM-Communality

The component became the only one to be retained as supported in the Scree Plot (see Annexure I). None of the items were removed. The component factors ranged from 0.730 to 0.864 (practically significant) with communalities ranging between 0.533 and 0.746. Therefore the TieG components were sufficiently explained by the factor solution. None of the items were removed. Hence, the internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha value was maintained at 0.825.

Trust in Government (TiG)

Table 6-8 shows the PCA for the TiG scale. The Pearson correlation coefficients of all the paired TiG items were found to be greater than 0.3 and less than 0.9. Similarly the anti-image

correlation matrix echoed the reasonable factorability of the items as the leading diagonal correlations were all above 0.5 ranging between 0.629 and 0.775. The KMO-MSA value was acceptable at 0.680. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was found to be significant ($\chi^2= 389.746$; $DF = 3$; $p < 0.05$) suggesting that the correlation matrix of the TiG elements was not comparable to an identity matrix. The BART test showed that there was some pair of items that shared a common variance. The tests supported the use of factor analysis on the data set from the TiG scale of 3 items. The scale had only three items, rather brief and unpopular to think that it needed to be reducible beyond what it was with only three items. In this regard, Bergkvist and Rossiter (2007) argue that there was no difference in predictive validity between multiple and single item scales. The argument was based on the fact that one or two items with a moderate or high error correlation (0.60) could outperform the scale with multiple items with high or moderate error correlations. As per the Total Variance Explained Table, it was evident that the correlation matrix of TiG items was reducible using a one (1) dimension solution. The only eigenvalue of the first component was found to be 2.242 ($e_1 > 1.0$), explaining 74.735% of the variance of the items in the scale. Running the PCA test for the TiG scale yielded the same number of components to be retained as the Scree Test (see Annexure I). As per the suggestion by Osborne and Costello (2009) the two tests should point to a same number of components. The three component loadings were high and their communalities were equally high ranging between 0.660 and 0.829.

Table 6-8: The Principal Component Analysis for Trust in Government

TiG ITEMS	CORRELATION MATRIX ^a			FACTOR LOADINGS	COMMUNALITIES
	1	2	3		
Citizen' interest is the top priority of the Government (1)	0.775^b			0.813	0.66
Government can provide safe e-services (2)	0.618	0.629^b		0.91	0.829
Government Agencies can be Trusted (3)	0.515	0.724	0.676^b	0.868	0.753

a. Determinant = .289;

b. The KMO-MSA for each item

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Therefore the TiG components were sufficiently explained by the one-factor solution and satisfied the convergent validity criterion ($AVE=0.747$). None of the items were removed. Hence, the internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha value was maintained at 0.83.

Trust in Technology (TiT)

Table 6-9 show the PCA for the TiT scale. The Pearson correlation coefficients of all the paired TieG items were found to be greater than 0.3 and less than 0.9 except the pairs that lay in the

primary diagonal. The anti-image correlation matrix echoed the reasonable factorability of the items as the leading diagonal correlations were all above 0.5 ranging between 0.770 and 0.882. The results show that the KMO-MSA is greater than 0.5 at 0.819. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was found to be significant ($\chi^2= 898.084$; $DF = 10$; $p<0.05$) suggesting that the correlation matrix of the TiT elements was not comparable to an identity matrix. This further supports that there was some pair of items that shared a common variance. As per the Total Variance Explained Table (see Annexure I), it was evident that the correlation matrix of TiT items was reducible using a one (1) dimension solution. The only eigenvalue of the first component was found to be 3.468 ($e_1 > 1.0$), explaining 69.361% of the variance of the items in the scale. The Scree plot (see Annexure I) supported the finding of only one component solution. All the TiT component loadings are practically significant and their squares are equally high.

Table 6-9: The Principal Component Analysis for Trust in Technology

TiT ITEMS	CORRELATION MATRIX ^a					FACTOR LOADINGS	COMMUNALITIES
	1	2	3	4	5		
Trust the e-Government technology is reliable always (1)	0.810^b					0.798	0.636
Trust the e-Government technology is secure always (2)	0.708	0.770^b				0.868	0.754
Have confidence in technology used by government agencies for the e-Government (3)	0.566	0.719	0.824^b			0.871	0.758
Trust in Mobile device(s) or computer(s) that I have (4)	0.556	0.540	0.668	0.822^b		0.808	0.654
Trust in technology used in e-Government services (5)	0.504	0.631	0.652	0.614	0.882^b	0.817	0.667

a. Determinant = .057;

b. The KMO-MSA for each item

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Therefore the TiT components were sufficiently explained by the one-factor solution. None of the items were removed. Hence, the internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha value was maintained at 0.889. In addition, the construct satisfied the convergent validity criterion (AVE=0.694).

Social Influence (SI)

Table 6-10 shows the results of the principal components analysis for Social Influence (SI) scale. The Pearson correlation coefficients of all the paired SI items were found to be greater than 0.3 and less than 0.9 except the pairs that lay in the leading diagonal. The anti-image correlation matrix echoed the reasonable factorability of the items as the leading diagonal

correlations were all above 0.5 ranging between 0.817 and 0.862. The results showed that the KMO-MSA was greater than 0.5 at 0.840. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was found to be significant ($\chi^2= 638.396$; $DF =10$; $p<0.05$) suggesting that the correlation matrix of the SI elements was not comparable to an identity matrix. This further supports that there was some pair of items that shared a common variance. As per the Total Variance Explained Table (see Annexure I), it was evident that the correlation matrix of SI items was reducible using a one (1) dimension solution. The only eigenvalue of the first component was found to be 3.106 ($e_1 >1.0$), explaining 62.127% of the variance of the items in the scale. The Scree plot (see Annexure I), supported the finding of only one component retained. All the SI component loadings were practically significant. The communalities were all in an acceptable range.

Table 6-10: The Principal Component Analysis for Social Influence on using e-Government Services

SI ITEMS	CORRELATION MATRIX ^a					FACTOR LOADINGS	COMMUNALITIES
	1	2	3	4	5		
Social influence think I should use e-Government (1)	0.817^b					0.833	0.695
Would use e-Government services if people in my social circle use them (2)	0.601	0.858^b				0.754	0.569
My social influence think e-Government services are efficient and effective (3)	0.606	0.477	0.857^b			0.809	0.655
My social circle has trust in intermediaries (4)	0.396	0.350	0.458	0.862^b		0.674	0.455
Important people think I should use e-Government services (5)	0.636	0.545	0.621	0.533	0.823^b	0.856	0.733

a. Determinant = .131;
 b. KMO-MSA for each item
 Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Therefore the SI components were sufficiently explained by the one-factor solution. None of the items were removed. Hence, the internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha value was maintained at 0.845. Consequently, the construct satisfied the convergent validity criterion (AVE>0.5).

Technical Support (TS)

Table 6-11 shows the results of the principal components analysis for the Technical Support scale. The Pearson correlation coefficients of all the paired TS items were found to be greater than 0.3 and less than 0.9 except the pairs that lay in the primary diagonal. The anti-image correlation matrix echoed the reasonable factorability of the items as the leading diagonal correlations were all above 0.5 ranging between 0.775 and 0.800. The results showed that the

KMO-MSA was greater than 0.5 at 0.804. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was found to be significant ($\chi^2= 542.481$; $DF = 6$; $p<0.05$) suggesting that the correlation matrix of the TS elements was not comparable to an identity matrix. This further supported that there was some pair of items that shared a common variance. As per the Total Variance Explained Table (see Annexure I), it was evident that the correlation matrix of TS items was reducible using a one (1) dimension solution. The only eigenvalue of the first component was found to be 2.775 ($e_1 > 1.0$), explaining 69.383% of the variance of the items in the scale. The Scree plot (see Annexure I), supported the finding of only one component retained. Consequently, the construct satisfied the convergent validity criterion ($AVE > 0.5$). All the TS component loadings were practically significant and their squares pointed to having sufficient explanation from the one-factor solution. Therefore the TS components were sufficiently explained by the one-factor solution. None of the items were removed. Hence, the internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha value was maintained at 0.853.

Table 6-11: The Principal Component Analysis for Technical Support when accessing e-Government Services

TS ITEMS	CORRELATION MATRIX ^a				FACTOR LOADINGS	COMMUNALITIES
	1	2	3	4		
Expect to get the help I need when accessing e-Government services (1)	0.800^b				0.838	0.702
It is easy to get assistance when faced with problems (2)	0.545	0.842^b			0.793	0.629
Expect clear instructions when accessing e-Government website (3)	0.572	0.587	0.807^b		0.841	0.708
Feedback should be prompt when help is needed (4)	0.669	0.534	0.640	0.775^b	0.858	0.736

a. Determinant = .178;

b. The KMO-MSA for each item

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Privacy and Security Concerns (PrSC)

Table 6-12 shows the results of the principal components analysis for the PrSC scale. The Pearson correlation coefficients of all the paired PrSC items were found to be greater than 0.3 and less than 0.9 except the pairs that lay in the primary diagonal. The anti-image correlation matrix echoed the reasonable factorability of the items as the leading diagonal correlations were all above 0.5 ranging between 0.875 and 0.925. The results showed that the KMO-MSA was greater than 0.5 at 0.872. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was found to be significant ($\chi^2= 700.483$; $DF = 15$; $p<0.05$) suggesting that the correlation matrix of the PrSC elements was not comparable to an identity matrix. This further supported that there was some pair of items that shared a common variance. As per the Total Variance Explained Table (see Annexure I), it was evident that the correlation matrix of PrSC items was reducible using a one (1) dimension

solution. The only eigenvalue of the first component was found to be 3.399 ($e_1 > 1.0$), explaining 56.646% of the variance of the items in the scale. The Scree plot (see Annexure I) supported the finding of only one component retained. All the PrSC component loadings were practically significant and their squares pointed to having sufficient explanation from the one-factor solution. Therefore the PrSC components were sufficiently explained by the one-factor solution. None of the items were removed. Hence, the internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha value was maintained at 0.844. Additionally, the construct satisfied the convergent validity criterion (AVE= 0.567).

Table 6-12: The Principal Component Analysis for Privacy and Security Concerns when accessing e-Government Services

PrSC ITEMS	CORRELATION MATRIX ^a						FACTOR LOADINGS	COMMUNALITIES
	1	2	3	4	5	6		
Trust e-Government services have privacy and security mechanisms in place (1)	.875^b						0.772	0.597
Trust my bank can protect me in case of the problematic transaction (2)	0.526	.888^b					0.703	0.494
Government websites have policy statements on privacy and security (3)	0.397	0.320	.925^b				0.601	0.361
Encryption and technological advances make it safe to do business (4)	0.516	0.454	0.385	.859^b			0.809	0.654
Assured of privacy and continued security in my bank (5)	0.521	0.451	0.381	0.586	.875^b		0.801	0.641
All parties involved during my e-Government services do protect my personal information (6)	0.508	0.444	0.363	0.645	0.617	.844^b	0.808	0.653

a. Determinant = .107; 0

b. The KMO-MSA for each item

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Perceived Internet Familiarity (PIF)

Table 6-13 shows the results of the principal components analysis for the PIF scale. The Pearson correlation coefficients of all the paired PIF items were found to be greater than 0.3 and less than 0.9 except the pairs that lay in the primary diagonal. The anti-image correlation matrix echoed the reasonable factorability of the items as the diagonal correlations were all above 0.5 ranging between 0.838 and 0.879. The results showed that the KMO-MSA was greater than 0.5 at 0.855. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was found to be significant ($\chi^2=719.640$; $DF = 10$; $p<0.05$) suggesting that the correlation matrix of the PIF elements was not comparable to an identity matrix. This further supported that there was some pair of items that shared a common variance. As per the Total Variance Explained Table (see Annexure I), it was evident that the correlation matrix of PIF items was reducible using a one (1) dimension solution. The only eigenvalue of the first component was found to be 3.282 ($e_1 > 1.0$), explaining 65.639% of the variance of the items in the scale. The Scree Plot (see Annexure I), supported the finding of only one component retained. All the PIF component loadings were practically significant and their squares pointed to having sufficient explanation from the one-factor solution. Therefore the PIF components were sufficiently explained by the one-factor solution. None of the items were removed. Hence, the internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha value was maintained at 0.869.

Table 6-13: The Principal Component Analysis for Perceived Internet Familiarity

PIF ITEMS	CORRELATION MATRIX ^a					FACTOR LOADINGS	COMMUNALITIES
	1	2	3	4	5		
Have used electronic sites and the internet always (1)	.847^b					0.797	0.635
Familiar with e-Government websites and internet (2)	0.571	.838^b				0.849	0.721
High experience in electronic websites (3)	0.652	0.593	.843^b			0.823	0.678
Familiar in search for e-Government services on internet (4)	0.511	0.629	0.536	.879^b		0.790	0.624
Familiar with Internet banking (5)	0.496	0.630	0.548	0.532	.875^b	0.790	0.624

a. Determinant = .101;

b. The KMO-MSA for each item

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The construct also met the convergent validity criterion since $AVE > 0.5$ as evidenced in the range of the communalities in Table 6-13.

Perceived Service Quality (PerSQ)

Table 6-14 shows the results of the principal components analysis for the PerSQ scale. The Pearson correlation coefficients of all the paired PerSQ items were found to be greater than 0.3 and less than 0.9 except the pairs that lay in the primary diagonal. The anti-image correlation matrix echoed the reasonable factorability of the items as the leading diagonal correlations were all above 0.5 ranging between 0.842 and 0.926. The results showed that the KMO-MSA was greater than 0.5 at 0.883. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was significant ($\chi^2 = 1353.853$; $DF = 28$; $p < 0.05$) suggesting that the correlation matrix of the PerSQ elements was not comparable to an identity matrix. This further supported that there was some pair of items that shared a common variance. As per the Total Variance Explained Table (see Annexure I), it was evident that the correlation matrix of PerSQ items was reducible using a one (1) dimension solution. The only eigenvalue of the first component was found to be 4.739 ($e_1 > 1$), explaining 59.233% of the variance of the items in the scale. The Scree plot (see Annexure I), supported the finding of only one component retained. All the PerSQ component loadings were practically significant and their squares pointed to having sufficient explanation from the one-factor solution. Therefore the PerSQ components were sufficiently explained by the one-factor solution. The construct satisfied the convergent validity criterion ($AVE > 0.5$). None of the items were removed. Hence, the internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha value was maintained at 0.898.

Table 6-14: The Principal Component Analysis for Perceived Service Quality of e-Government Services Familiarity

PERSQ ITEMS	CORRELATION MATRIX ^a								FACT OR LOAD.	COM.
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8		
e-Government systems provide feedback mechanisms (1)	.926^b								0.699	0.489
e-Government websites are regularly updated for accurate information (2)	0.524	.845^b							0.794	0.630
e-Government services provide relevant information (3)	0.504	0.682	.842^b						0.822	0.676
e-Government services provide reliable information (4)	0.493	0.572	0.743	.890^b					0.811	0.658
e-Government provide significant user interaction (5)	0.528	0.493	0.582	0.595	.917^b				0.776	0.602
e-Government services are easy to navigate structures (6)	0.478	0.467	0.494	0.519	0.561	.928^b			0.741	0.549
e-Government systems have accessible contact details for communication (7)	0.416	0.483	0.516	0.528	0.486	0.554	.901^b		0.743	0.552
e-Government services are designed with the user in mind (8)	0.408	0.641	0.494	0.505	0.528	0.510	0.609	.845^b	0.762	0.581

a. Determinant = .013;

b. The KMO-MSA for each item

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Power Distance (PD)

The principal components analysis for PD scale showed that most of the Pearson correlation coefficients of the paired PD items were found to be greater than 0.3. All were less than 0.9 except the pairs that lay in the primary diagonal. The anti-image correlation matrix echoed the reasonable factorability of the items as the leading diagonal correlations were all above 0.5 ranging between 0.660 and 0.732. The results showed that the KMO-MSA was greater than 0.5 at 0.696. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was found to be significant ($\chi^2= 454.973$; DF = 10; $p<0.05$) suggesting that the correlation matrix of the PD elements was not comparable to an identity matrix. This further supported that there was some pair of items that shared a common variance. As per the Total Variance Explained Table (see Table 6-15) it was evident that the correlation matrix of PD items was reducible using a two (2) dimension solution. The first eigenvalue ($e_1 = 1.969$) showed that the first factor explained 39.385 % of variance, and the

second ($e_2 = 1.662$) explained 33.24% of variance of the items in the scale. The construct met the convergent validity criterion.

Table 6-15: Number of components retained in the first run of PCA in SPSS
TOTAL VARIANCE EXPLAINED

Comp.	Initial eigenvalues			Extraction sums of squared loadings			Rotation sums of squared loadings		
	Total	% of Var.	Cum. %	Total	% of Var.	Cum %	Total	% of Var.	Cum. %
1	2.578	51.551	51.551	2.578	51.551	51.551	1.969	39.385	39.385
2	1.054	21.074	72.625	1.054	21.074	72.625	1.662	33.240	72.625
3	0.626	12.511	85.135						
4	0.386	7.717	92.852						
5	0.357	7.148	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

However, the Scree Plot (see Figure 6-11) for PD suggested otherwise, up to a maximum of three components were to be retained as shown by the point of inflexion at component 4 shown in dotted lines.

Figure 6-11: Scree Plot for PD Scale showing likelihood of 3 component solution

Faced with the ambiguity, as suggested by Osborne and Costello (2009), the PCA test was re-run fixing the number of components to be retained between 1 and 6. The one with the “cleanest” component structure (item loadings > .30; no cross-loadings; and no factors with fewer than 3 items), the single component solution survived the test. The Parallel Test was run for triangulation and generated the following results in Figure 6-12.

Figure 6-12: Parallel Test results for UA scale items

The PCA test confirmed the use of a single component as the solution as the e_1 from the TVE table was 1.608 and the e_2 was 1.109. The test was then re-run fixing a single component to be retained. The total variance explained was 51.551%. The results on factor loadings and communalities are summarised in Table 6-16. The component loadings were practically significant with values ranging from 0.699 to 0.734. The corresponding communalities point that one component solution explains the items sufficiently.

Table 6-16: The Principal Component Analysis for Power Distance Scale

PD ITEMS	CORRELATION MATRIX ^a					FACTOR LOADINGS	COMMUNALITIES
	1	2	3	4	5		
Involved in e-Government systems /decision making (1)	.660^b					0.703	0.495
Government and its agencies ask for people' opinion prior to launching its services (2)	0.622	.664^b				0.699	0.488
e-Government services have opportunities for social interaction with people in gvt positions (3)	0.319	0.359	.774^b			0.724	0.524
Use e-Government services without question (4)	0.254	0.261	0.527	.668^b		0.734	0.539
Give feedback on e-Government services i have used (5)	0.353	0.293	0.384	0.570	.732^b	0.729	0.531

a. Determinant = .234;

b. The KMO-MSA for each item

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The AVE was calculated at 0.515 showing the establishment of the convergent validity. None of the items were removed. Hence, the internal consistency using Cronbach’s alpha value was maintained at 0.765.

Uncertainty Avoidance (UA)

The principal components analysis for the UA scale showed that all Pearson correlation coefficients of the paired UA items were found to be less than 0.9 except the pairs that lay in the primary diagonal. The anti-image correlation matrix echoed the reasonable factorability of the items as the leading diagonal correlations were all above 0.5 ranging between 0.511 and 0.579. The results showed that the KMO-MSA was greater than 0.5 which is barely acceptable as it is slightly below 0.60 value suggested by Pallant (2007, 2011). The Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity was found to be significant ($\chi^2= 97.675$; $DF = 6$; $p<0.05$) suggesting that the correlation matrix of the UA elements was not comparable to an identity matrix. This further supported that there was some pair of items that shared a common variance. As per the Total Variance Explained Table it was evident that the correlation matrix of UA items was reducible using a two (2) dimension solution.

Table 6-17: TVE table for Uncertainty Avoidance
TOTAL VARIANCE EXPLAINED

Comp.	Initial eigenvalues				Extraction sums of squared loadings				Rotation sums of squared loadings			
	Total	% of Variance	of	Cumul. %	Total	% of Variance	of	Cumul. %	Total	% of Variance	of	Cumul. %
1	1.608	40.211		40.211	1.608	40.211		40.211	1.432	35.793		35.793
2	1.109	27.737		67.948	1.109	27.737		67.948	1.286	32.155		67.948
3	0.662	16.551		84.499								
4	0.620	15.501		100.000								

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

The first eigenvalue ($e_1 = 1.432$) showed that the first factor explained 35.793 % of variance, and the second ($e_2 = 1,286$) explained 32.153% of variance after Varimax rotation. Collectively the two-factor solution accounted for 67.948% of the variance. *The Scree Plot (see Annexure I) for UA echoed the retention of two components.* To reduce the clutter in the factor loadings, the correlations less than the absolute value of 0.30 were suppressed. Table 6-18 shows the clearly marked two groups of items that loaded together on different components. The component loadings were practically significant with values ranging from 0.724 to 0.864. The corresponding communalities suggested that the two component solution explained the items sufficiently.

Table 6-18: Principal Component Analysis for Uncertainty Avoidance in the use of e-Government Services

UA ITEMS	CORRELATION MATRIX ^a	FACTOR	COMMUNALITIES
----------	---------------------------------	--------	---------------

	LOADINGS						
	1	2	3	4	Factor 1		
Enjoy services that have clear and easy to understand instructions (1)	.571^b				0.801	0.657	
Important to follow procedures to avoid mistakes (2)	0.370	.570^b			0.819	0.671	
e-Government services I use have menu for guidance (3)	0.244	0.186	.579^b		0.724	0.630	
Difficult to figure out how the technology works (4)	0.056	0.018	0.293	.511^b	0.864	0.760	

a. Determinant = .733;

b. The KMO-MSA for each item

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization

Rotation converged after 3 iterations

The component shows that participants found following the procedures to avoid mistakes was heavily related to the e-Government services having clearly laid down instructions. In addition, the component speaks to the availability of instructions which still relates to their being followed to avoid mistakes. Similarly, the effort that users need to find out how the technology works in accessing e-Government services is intricately linked to the availability of menus for guidance. The availability of some guidance makes it almost effortless to use the technology. Conceptually, there is need for clarity of procedures and the skillset that one must use the technology tools in accessing e-Government services. In nationalities where they are high in uncertainty avoidance, guidance or laid down procedures reduces the effort of taking risks. The reliability was maintained at 0.522 and construct validity criterion was met.

Facilitating services and Goods (FS-G)

The principal components analysis for FS-G scale showed that all Pearson correlation coefficients of the paired FS-G items were found to be less than 0.9 except the pairs that lay in the primary diagonal. The anti-image correlation matrix echoed the reasonable factorability of the items as the leading diagonal correlations were all above 0.5 ranging between 0.618 and 0.876. The results showed that the KMO-MSA was greater than 0.5 at 0.753. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was found to be significant ($\chi^2= 929.970$; $DF = 28$; $p<0.05$) suggesting that the correlation matrix of the FS-G elements was not comparable to an identity matrix. This further supported that there was some pair of items that shared a common variance. As per the Total Variance Explained Table and scree plot (see Annexure I) it was evident that the correlation matrix of FS-G items was reducible using a two (2) dimension solution. The two-component solution was further triangulated using parallel analysis.

Table 6-19: The Principal Component Analysis for Resources needed to use e-Government Services

FS-G items	Correlation Matrix ^a								Factor Loadings		Communalities
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	Factor 1	Factor 2	
Got resources needed to engage with e-Government services (1)	0.743^b									0.773	0.618
Got technology skills to engage with e-Government services (2)	0.579	0.633^b								0.872	0.761
Got technology skills to engage with e-Government services but lack awareness (3)	0.382	0.396	0.876^b							0.624	0.461
Access e-Government services through self-service terminals (4)	0.341	0.274	0.382	0.859^b					0.609		0.515
Access e-Government services through public library (5)	0.225	0.162	0.273	0.539	0.783^b				0.864		0.766
Access e-Government services through the state library (6)	0.291	0.229	0.322	0.468	0.737	0.728^b			0.878		0.806
Access e-Government services through the rural kiosk (7)	0.168	0.053	0.207	0.385	0.59	0.704	0.753^b		0.846		0.716
Given resources and equipped with tech skill. it would be easy to access e-Government services (8)	0.174	0.369	0.182	0.147	0.169	0.143	0.198	0.618^b	0.497	0.257	

A. DETERMINANT = .051;

B. THE KMO-MSA FOR EACH ITEM

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.
 Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization
 Rotation converged after 3 iterations

The first eigenvalue ($e_1 = 2.707$) showed that the first factor explained 33.833 % of variance, and the second ($e_2 = 2.194$) explained 27.419% of variance after varimax rotation. Collectively the two-factor solution accounted for 61.252% of the variance. Table 6-19 summarises the PCA test for the FS-G scale items. The rotated Component matrix showed the two components and how they loaded on the group items. The rest of the loadings were practically significant except for the loading on item 8. Although the loading was above 0.4 it was only statistically significant for a sample size of above 250 but practically insignificant (Hair *et al.*, 2010). The 0.497 loading on item 8 translated to the low communality of 0.257 evidenced by the circled extraction value in Table 7-19. The low communality showed that the item was not sufficiently explained by the factor solution. However, in this study we retained the item as it slightly shies away from the recommended 0.5 loading. The first component clearly related to *e-offices provided by the Government and its agencies* in using the e-Government services. The component spoke directly to the access points needed to access the e-Government services. These included the rural kiosks, public and state libraries, and the much-needed self-service terminals. The second component was named *awareness, self, or vicarious ownership of resources, and skills*. The item 8 loaded lowly in the second component because even with the technical skills and resources, one cannot have a behavioural intention of using what they are not aware of. The new Cronbach alpha values were 0.842 and 0.680 respectively. The convergent validity of the components was found to be 0.613 and 0.612 which were above 0.5.

Attitude (ATT)

The PCA test for Attitude toward e-Government scale items showed that anti-image correlation matrix elements in leading diagonal were above 0.5. The KMO-MSA values for each item ranged between 0.562 and 0.800. The overall KMO-MSA value was found to be 0.640. The BART test was found to be significant ($\chi^2 = 375.644$; $DF = 21$; $p < 0.05$) suggesting that the correlation matrix of the ATT elements was not comparable to an identity matrix. This further supported that there was some pair of items that shared a common variance. As per the Total Variance Explained Table, scree plot, and parallel analysis (see Annexure I) it was evident that the correlation matrix of ATT items was reducible using a one-component solution which accounted for 67.125% of the variance. Table 6-20 shows the factor loadings and their corresponding communalities.

Table 6-20: The Principal Component Analysis for Attitude towards the use of e-Government Services

ATT ITEMS	FACTOR LOADINGS	COMMUNALITIES
High att. to e-Government services (1)	0.861	0.773
Att. changed by the country' economic situation (2)	0.728	0.564
Engaging with e-Government services is good (3)	0.898	0.814
e-Government services are associated with high internet costs (4)	0.810	0.739
Not Worried about security and privacy concerns because there are safeguards (5)	0.873	0.778
I am a fan of technology (6)	0.647	0.456
With exposure. it would be easy to use e-Government services (7)	0.730	0.574

Extraction method: principal component analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

Rotation converged in 4 iterations.

The component loadings were practically and statistically significant with values ranging from 0.647 to 0.861. The communalities indicated that the scale items were sufficiently explained by the one-component solution as the convergent validity was achieved at 0.671. The Cronbach alpha value was maintained at 0.66.

Behavioural Intention (BI)

Table 6-21 shows the results of the principal components analysis for the BI scale. The Pearson correlation coefficients of all the paired BI items were found to be greater than 0.3 and less than 0.9 except the pairs that lay in the primary diagonal. The anti-image correlation matrix echoed the reasonable factorability of the items as the leading diagonal correlations were all above 0.5 ranging between 0.737 and 0.8366. The results showed that the KMO-MSA was greater than 0.5 at 0.782. The Bartlett's Test of Sphericity was found to be significant ($\chi^2=401.795$; $DF = 6$; $p<0.05$) suggesting that the correlation matrix of the BI elements was not comparable to an identity matrix. This further supported that there was some pair of items that shared a common variance. As per the Total Variance Explained Table (see Annexure I), it was evident that the correlation matrix of BI items was reducible using a one (1) dimension solution. The only eigenvalue of the first component was found to be greater than unity ($e_1 = 2.531$), explaining 63.270% of the variance of the items in the scale. The Scree plot (see Annexure I), supported the finding of only one component retained. The construct met the convergent criterion of $AVE>0.5$. All the BI component loadings were practically and statistically significant and their squares pointed to having sufficient explanation from the one-factor solution. Therefore the BI components were sufficiently explained by the one-factor solution. Only one item was removed. Hence, the internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha value was changed from 0.777 to 0.803.

Table 6-21: The Principal Component Analysis for Behavioural Intention to use e-Government Services

BI ITEMS	CORRELATION MATRIX ^A				FACTOR LOADINGS	COMMUNALITIES
	1	2	3	4		
Intention to use of e-Government services regularly in the quest for information (1)	0.836^b				0.759	0.577
Plan to use of e-Government services in the following months (2)	0.446	0.836^b			0.750	0.563
I plan to continue to use e-Government services (3)	0.512	0.511	0.737^b		0.848	0.720
I intention to making e-Government first choice in doing business (4)	0.480	0.459	0.642	0.756^b	0.819	0.671

a. Determinant = .278;

b. The KMO-MSA for each item

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

6.4.7 Testing the Univariate, Bivariate and Multivariate Assumptions

Based on the review of the related e-Government literature as informed by the research questions, and the findings of the qualitative study, an extended TAM model constituting of sixteen variables was proposed constituting of direct and moderating relationships. As a result, there was a need to establish the interrelatedness of the variables through some bivariate and multivariate analysis. However, the potential distortions or biases caused by a large number of variables and their complex relationships in the bivariate and multivariate analysis could be detrimental if the corresponding statistical assumptions are violated (Hair *et al.*, 2010, p. 103; Pallant, 2011). In that regard, to ensure the validity and accuracy of the results resultant from the bivariate and multivariate analysis, the statistical underlying assumptions such as *normality*, *linearity*, *co-linearity*, and *homoscedasticity* were tested. Prior to these tests, the Likert scale data of the variables was transformed from being ordinal to continuous data through the calculation of the composite means of their corresponding Likert scale items.

6.4.7.1 Univariate Normality

The normality of the variable scores was tested using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov with Lilliefors Significance Correction and Shapiro-Wilk tests. According to Ghasemi and Zahediasl (2012), Shapiro-Wilk test is a better choice when it comes to the power of measuring whether the data deviates from the Gaussian ideal or not. Having tested the data with both tests, there was evidence that the two tests converged to the same normality result for the DV, and all the independent variables (see Table 6-22).

Table 6-22: Testing univariate normality

Scale	N	Shape Descriptors				Test of Normality			
		Skewness		Kurtosis		Kolmogorov-S ^a		Shapiro-Wilk	
		Skewness	Z _{Skewness} ss	Kurtosis	Z _{Kurtosis} S	Statistic	Sig.	Statistic	Sig.
PATU_TR	317	-.395	-2.880	.499	1.830	.095	.000	.971	.000
PV_TR	317	-1.034	-7.550	1.377	5.040	.173	.000	.909	.000
TieG_TR	317	-.367	-2.240	-.425	-1.560	.132	.000	.958	.000
TiG_TR	317	-.408	-2.980	-.302	-1.110	.179	.000	.951	.000
TiT_TR	317	-.308	-2.250	.018	.070	.103	.000	.967	.000
SI_TR	317	-.518	-3.780	.089	.330	.145	.000	.965	.000
TS_TR	317	-1.378	-10.060	1.688	6.180	.197	.000	.819	.000
PrSC_TR	317	-.009	-.070	-.503	-1.840	.095	.000	.970	.000
PIF_TR	317	-.969	-7.070	1.125	4.120	.143	.000	.929	.000
PersQ_TR	317	.141	1.030	-.188	-0.690	.114	.000	.963	.000
PD_TR	317	.041	.300	-.142	-0.520	.065	.002	.988	.010
ATT_TR	317	-.023	-.170	-.097	-0.360	.057	.016	.985	.002
TSkills_RsrcOw nership	317	-0.377	-2.752	-0.105	-0.766	.119	.000	.972	.000
e_Offices	317	0.351	2.56	-0.415	-3.029	.101	.000	.965	.000
UA_TR	317	-.489	-3.570	-.248	-.910	.167	.000	.957	.000
BI_TR	317	-.715	-5.219	.503	1.842	.107	.000	.943	.000
eGov_adoption_ TR	317	0.048	-0.350	-0.230	-0.842	.036	.200*	.994	.279

- a. Lilliefors Significance Correction;
SE_{Skewness}=-0.137; SE_{Kurtosis}=0.273
*. This is a lower bound of the true significance

Of the 17 variables, only the outcome variable was found to be univariate normal, yet the predictor variables were not. The shape of the distributions was then analysed using the **z** values calculated using the following statistics:

$$Z_{\text{Skewness}} = \frac{\text{Skewness} - 0}{SE_{\text{Skewness}}} ; \quad Z_{\text{Kurtosis}} = \frac{\text{Kurtosis} - 0}{SE_{\text{Kurtosis}}}$$

where,

SE is the standard Error, and

|z| < 2.58 signifies sufficiency to establish Normality

The balance (skewness) and the peakedness / flatness (Kurtosis) of the distributions and the **z** scores are shown in visual results of the departures from normality, the shape of the distributions, see Figure Table 6-24 with the circled values suggesting the sufficiency to establish normality based on the **z** scores. The rest showed positive and negative skewness

with some peakedness. For more details see Table 6-13 and *Annexure J for the histograms, Q-Q plots, and Boxplots.*

Figure 6-13: Visual results for normality tests for sample variables

The non-normality of most of the data drawn from a sample of 317 cases was not without precedence as it resonated with the finding of normality test results for samples larger than 200 in the literature (Hair *et al.*, 2010; Pallant, 2011).

6.4.7.2 Identification of Outliers

The univariate outliers could be seen in the box plots in Figure 6-12. However, not all outliers are influential; hence the influential outliers were checked using the standard deviation statistic. For large samples, the outliers are those cases whose standard deviation is greater than four (4) (Hair *et al.*, 2010). Table 6-23 showed that none of the variables had univariate outliers.

The bivariate outliers were not considered because of the large number of the variables included checking the scatterplots. Tabachnick and Fidell (2007) posit that the multivariate outliers are those data points with standardised residuals that have an absolute value greater than 3.3. In addition, the outliers were also identified using the Mahalanobis Distance in the Residual Statistics Table and the critical chi-square values at the 0,001 level of significance. Using Mahalanobis Distance in the TieG regression model, cases 256, 147,267, 157 and 62

were found to be outliers. Case 171 was found to have a standardised residual value higher than |3.3|. Since not all outliers are influential in the regression line, the leverage was checked for the possible outliers. Marshall and Karadimitriou (no date) stated that leverage is given by $(k+1)/n$ where k is the number of predictor variables and n is the number of observations.

Table 6-23: Identification of Univariate and Multivariate Outliers

Scale	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	Univariate Outliers (Cases with SD>4)	Multivariate Outliers (Possible Cases with standardised residual > 3,3)
PATU_TR	3.5379	.73727	317	No case(s)	-
PV_TR	4.0473	.78940	317	No case(s)	No case(s)
TieG_TR	3.9006	.72587	317	No case(s)	256, 147,267, 157,62, 171
TiG_TR	3.6215	.88850	317	No case(s)	-
TIT_TR	3.6278	.79888	317	No case(s)	-
SI_TR	3.6801	.79429	317	No case(s)	-
TS_TR	4.3005	.82186	317	No case(s)	-
PrSC_TR	3.7219	.71429	317	No case(s)	-
PIF_TR	3.8902	.81803	317	No case(s)	-
PersQ_TR	3.5857	.71060	317	No case(s)	-
PD_TR	2.8341	.84170	317	No case(s)	-
ATT_TR	3.5845	.66320	317	No case(s)	No case(s)
TSkills_RsrcOwnership	3.6215	.77963	317	No case(s)	-
e_Offices	2.8517	1.00636	317	No case(s)	-
UA_TR	3.6546	.64705	317	No case(s)	-
BI_TR	3.9779	.75073	317	No case(s)	110,129
eGov_adoption	3.6801	.48809	317	No case(s)	-

-The scale is an Independent Variable

They also stated that observations with 2 or 3 times leverage scores are said to have high leverage. The scatter for the standardised residuals against the leverage in the TieG model was then plotted using the saved values. Amongst the possible cases, Case 256 had the highest leverage of 0.12006 but not an outlier making it just an extreme value, and only case 171 was found to be an outlier with a standardised residual of -3.582 and low leverage of 0.2449. (See Figure 6-14).

Because the singled-out outlier was not in a high leverage position, the outlier was retained as its position did affect neither the slope nor intercept of the regression line. Based on the scatter plot in Figure 6-14, none of the possible outliers were influential data points in the TieG model. The rest of the multivariate outliers for other dependent variables listed in the Table 6-23 were assessed in an analogous manner and were also retained based on their low leverages.

Figure 6-14: The TieG Model Scatterplot of standardized residuals and leverage

6.4.7.3 Testing Bivariate Linearity Assumptions

The linearity relationships between independent variables and the dependent variable were also checked using the scatter Matrix. Owing to the substantial number of variables involved, over 100 scatter plots needed to be analysed. As such a scatter matrix was used instead. The shape of the scatter plot for each pair of variables may not be that clear owing to the larger number of variables in the matrix scatter. The line fit was drawn using SPSS for each scatter plot in the matrix and the coefficients of determination were generated by SPSS (see Figure 6-15).

Figure 6-15: Matrix Scatter of the study variables and linearity results

The coefficients of determination between variable pairs revealed that the linearity assumption was not violated at differently shared variances between them. Two scatter matrices with fewer variables are presented in Annexure K for clarity of the scatter shapes.

6.4.7.4 Testing the Bivariate Multicollinearity Assumptions

The linear correlation between pairs of variables in the study was measured using Pearson’s correlation (See Table 6-24). The bivariate correlations allowed for checking two important aspects: the divergent validity between predictor variables; and how the predictor variables correlated with the outcome variable. All the predictor correlations were found to be positive and significant at the level of $p < 0.01$ except for three relationships that were significant at $p < 0.05$ (TS < -- > TIT: $r=0.142$, $p= 0.011$; e-Offices < -- > PIF: $r=0.134$, $p= 0.017$; PD <-- > TS: $r=0.133$, $p= 0.018$) and only one relationship that was negative (e_Offices < - - > TS; $r=-0.032$, $p=0.573$). Table 7-24 shows that the correlations between the predictor variables were not divergent with the highest correlation strength found to be 0.637 (between Trust in Government and Trust in

Technology). This highest correlation had a coefficient of determination of approximately 0.406 meaning that the shared variance between the involved scales was 40.6%. Consequently, all the bivariate predictor relationships in the study were found to be not multicollinear as evidenced by the correlation coefficients that were less than 0.7 (Pallant, 2011). More on the multicollinearity assumption was also reported under the regression analysis.

Table 6-24 depicts the association of the predictor variables with the *outcome variable* (See the circled correlations in Table 6-24). All the predictor variables correlated with the outcome variable in a positive direction; at a strength that exceeded 0.35; and were significant at $p < 0.01$ level. The minimum correlation was between the outcome variable and the technical support (TS) ($r=0.375^{**}$) at medium strength. As cited by the participants in the qualitative study, the citizens hardly had technical support from the government and its agencies as most of the e-services that they engaged with were menu driven. The support that they tend to receive was from social influence. Amongst the participants, though fewer, were those that needed a human intermediary to carry out the e-services owing to their lack of technology literacy and awareness. The association between the outcome variable and the perceived ability to use (PATU) had the strongest significance ($r=0.763^{**}$, $p<0.01$). The second strongest and significant association was with privacy and security concerns (PrSC) ($r=0.757^{**}$, $p<0.01$). All the correlations between the outcome and predictor variables had shared variances between 14-58% between variables.

Table 6-24: Pearson Correlations of variables in the study

		Correlations															
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
PATU_TR (1)	Pearson Corr	1															
	Sig. (2-tailed)																
PV_TR (2)	Pearson Corr	,606**	1														
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000															
TiG_TR (3)	Pearson Corr	,498**	,353**	1													
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000														
TIT_TR (4)	Pearson Corr	,525**	,391**	,637**	1												
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,000													
PrSC_TR (5)	Pearson Corr	,527**	,380**	,555**	,583**	1											
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,000	,000												
PIF_TR (6)	Pearson Corr	,359**	,447**	,109	,187**	,239**	1										
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,053	,001	,000											
PersQ_TR (7)	Pearson Corr	,562**	,373**	,576**	,612**	,628**	,234**	1									
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000										
TieG_TR (8)	Pearson Corr	,544**	,531**	,519**	,495**	,581**	,305**	,534**	1								
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000									
SI_TR (9)	Pearson Corr	,410**	,318**	,364**	,352**	,453**	,152**	,350**	,404**	1							
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,007	,000	,000								
ATT_TR (10)	Pearson Corr	,374**	,344**	,332**	,300**	,441**	,328**	,346**	,368**	,252**	1						
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000							
TS_TR (11)	Pearson Corr	,206**	,257**	,191**	,142*	,299**	,022	,163**	,197**	,249**	,169**	1					
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,001	,011	,000	,694	,004	,000	,000	,003						
TSkills_ RsrcOwnership (12)	Pearson Corr	,435**	,499**	,301**	,304**	,412**	,497**	,388**	,395**	,316**	,517**	,215**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000					
e_Offices (13)	Pearson Corr	,405**	,176**	,316**	,347**	,303**	,134*	,463**	,232**	,228**	,344**	-,032	,379**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,002	,000	,000	,000	,017	,000	,000	,000	,000	,573	,000				
PD_TR (14)	Pearson Corr	,434**	,287**	,479**	,462**	,405**	,178**	,483**	,254**	,278**	,375**	,133*	,370**	,509**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,001	,000	,000	,000	,000	,018	,000	,000			
UA_TR (15)	Pearson Corr	,339**	,335**	,361**	,259**	,411**	,185**	,485**	,351**	,291**	,449**	,250**	,368**	,303**	,352**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,001	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000		
Gov_ adoption (16)	Pearson Corr	,763**	,669**	,700**	,691**	,757**	,467**	,748**	,705**	,581**	,618**	,375**	,651**	,507**	,624**	,604**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	,000	

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed)

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2 tailed)

Only one pair of relationships was found to have had inconsequential statistical strength. The lowest relationship of was between PIF and technical support (PIF < --- > TS, $r=0.022$, $p=0.694$) with an unexplained variance close to 100%. This meant that the two variables were largely not correlated. The finding suggests that citizens in e-Government environments tend to have higher expectations that must be managed by the supply side to build long term value relationships.

6.4.7.5 Testing Assumptions for Multivariate Analysis

The assumptions for multivariate analysis: normality, linearity and homoscedasticity were estimated using the regression standardised residual, Scatterplot and P-P plots for dependent variables. Amongst the regression models in the study is the TieG model. The results of the visual plots for the TieG model showed non-violation of normality (see Figure 6-16a: regression standardised residuals vs. frequency) as the histogram of standardised residuals was near normal. The P-P plots for the TieG variable demonstrated the linearity amongst the variables (see Figure 6-16b: observed vs. expected cum prob), and homoscedasticity was also not violated as the scatter plot of the residuals formed a cigar shape with a concentration of points at the centre (see Figure 6-16c: standardised residual of predicted values vs. standardised residual). For more of these tests on the other 4 regression models, see Annexure L.

Figure 6-16: Testing assumptions for multivariate analysis of the TieG model

6.4.8 Bivariate and multivariate analysis

Figure 6-17: Graphical representation of the hypothesized research model

To address the quantitative research questions, it was essential to determine the significance of the different predictor variables on the dependent variables in the study as expressed in the study hypotheses. Figure 6-17 shows the updated graphical representation of the hypothesized model after principal component analysis. The hypotheses were estimated using simple and multiple regression models. The collinearity assumptions were also reported concurrently with the regression analysis results. Further assessment of collinearity of the variables in the regression analysis was based on the following criteria: the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) should not exceed 10 and tolerance (TOL) should be greater than 0.1 (Hair *et al.*, 2010; Pallant, 2011).

6.4.8.1 Whole group Analysis

Simple regression was used to test H₁. The generic model of approximation for simple regression is given by: $Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + e_1$

Where:

- Y** -The Outcome index associated with the predictor index
- b₀** -The intercept coefficient
- b₁** -The regression coefficient associated with the only predictor index X₁
- X₁** - The only predictor index associated with the study observations?

e_1 - The error term for the only predictor index associated with the study observations?

Predictors of perceived value (PV) of e-Government services

The first dependent variable in the model that was tested using the simple linear regression is the Perceived Value (PV). The PV model that was tested is shown in Figure 6-18.

H_1 : The citizens's perceived ability to use (PATU) has positive and significant influence on the perceived value (PV) of e-Government services

Results from the simple regression of the perceived ability to use (PATU) on the dependent variable (PV) revealed that the Pearson's correlation between the two variables was significantly large ($r = 0.606$; $p < 0.001$). The relationship between the perceived ability to use and the perceived value was positive based on the unstandardized coefficient ($B = 0.648$) meaning that for each unit increase in the perceived ability there would be 0.648 increase in the perceived value of e-Government. The t-test also showed that the coefficient of PATU was significant ($t(315) = 13.509$; $p < 0.5$). As such, it was evident that the citizens' perceived ability to use e-Government services has a positive and significant influence on the perceived value (PV) of e-Government services (see Table 6-25).

Table 6-25: Predictors of the perceived value

Coefficients ^a					ANOVA ^a						
Predictor Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta								
(Constant)	1.753	0.173		10.106	0.000	Regress.	72.236	1	72.236	182.503	.000 ^b
PATU_TR	0.648	0.048	0.606	13.509	0.000	Resid.	124.679	315	0.396		
						Total	196.915	316			

a. Dependent Variable: PV_TR

b. Predictors: (Constant), PATU_TR

Adjusted R² = 0.365

Approximately 37% variability of the perceived value was explained by the PATU variable (Adj R² = 0.365). Based on the corresponding ANOVA table of the PV model in Table 6-25 the model variability was found to be significant: $F(1, 315) = 182.503$; $p < 0.05$). The finding implied that H_1 was accepted. The fitted model that can be used to predict the perceived value from the perceived ability to use e-Government services is given by:

$$PV = 1,753 + (0,648 * PATU) + e_1$$

This implies that as the citizen gets equipped with the technical know-how of using the e-Government technology the perceived value increases at the level of 0.648 per one standard

deviation increase of the perceived ability to use. Multiple regression was done for the dependent variables with at least two independent variables. The model of approximation of the multiple regressions is given by the formula:

$$Y = b_0 + \sum_{i=1}^k (b_i X_i + e_i)$$

Where:

- Y** -The outcome variable index associated with the predictor indices
- b₀** -The intercept coefficient
- b_i** -The regression coefficient associated with the ith predictor index
- X_i** -The ith predictor index associated with the study observations
- e_i** -The error term for the ith predictor index associated with the study observations?
- k** -The number of predictor indices

The standard regression method was used to ascertain the extent to which the variability of the dependent variables was explained by the corresponding set of the predictor variables in the submodels.

Predictors of the attitude (ATT) towards the e-Government Model

The attitude model included three predictor variables (PATU, PV, and TieG). The model is shown in Figure 6-19.

H₂: The citizens's perceived ability to use (PATU) has positive and significant influence on the attitudes towards using e-Government services

H₃: The citizens's perceived value(PV) has a positive and significant influence on attitudes toward using e-Government services

H₁₂:The citizens' trust in e-Government (TieG) has significant and positive influence on their attitudes toward e-Government services

Figure 6-19: The ATT Model

All the bivariate Pearson correlations were either moderate or large as they ranged from 0.344 to 0.606. The correlations of each of the independent variables with the attitude variable were all positive and moderate in strength (PATU: r=0.374**, strongest; PV: r=0.344**, weakest; and TieG=0.368**) and significant at the p<0.01 level. Similarly, the regression results for the ATT model showed that the model data points did not violate the multicollinearity assumption as Tolerance and VIF values were in the acceptable ranges. The tolerance value for PATU showed that 54.4 % of the variance could not be explained by either by TieG or PV; 64% of the variance in TieG could not be explained by PV or PATU; and 56.4% of the variance for PV could not be

explained by TieG and PATU. None of the residuals could be identified as influential outliers. The possible outliers based on the Mahalanobis or Cook’s Distances were retained as the standardised residuals were within the acceptable range [-2.71597; -2.96031]. Autocorrelation was assessed using the Durbin Watson’s Test static of independence of residuals and the score was found to be 1.794. The Durbin Watson score showed that the residuals were positively correlated based on the criteria of less than the critical value 2 (Field, 2009, p. 236). TieG and PATU coefficients were found to be importantly significant at p<0.01 level (TieG: $\beta=0.198$, $t(313) = 3.108$, $p=0.002$; PATU: $\beta=0.192$, $t(313) = 2.827$, $p=0.005$) and PV was found to be insignificant at p<0.1 (PV: $\beta = 0.122$, $t(310) = 1.822$, $p=0.069$). The model showed that 17.9 % of the variability in the attitudes of the participants was explained by their perceived ability to use, their perceived value, and their trust in e-Government services (Adj R² =0.179). The variability, though seemingly low was found to be significant (F (3.310) =23.942; p< 0.005). From the standardised coefficients, we could conclude that the Trust in e-Government has the highest effect ($\beta= 0.198$) in predicting the citizens’ attitude followed by TieG ($\beta= 0.181$) and then PV ($\beta= 0.103$). The scatter plots, P-P plots and the histogram showed that the standardised residual met the homogeneity of variance, linearity, and normality assumptions (See Annexure L). Table 6-26 shows additional regression details.

Table 6-26: Regression Analysis results for the ATT model

Predictor Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		DW
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF	
(Constant)	1,852	0.210		8.836	0.000			
PATU_TR	0.173	0.061	0.192	2.827	0.005	0.564	1.773	1.794
TieG_TR	0.181	0.058	0.198	3.108	0.002	0.640	1.563	
PV_TR	0.103	0.056	0.122	1.822	0.069	0.576	1.737	

F (6.310) = 23.942; p=0.000; R= 0.432; R²= 0.187; Adj R²= 0.179; standardised error of estimate =0.60097

The equation of the line that could be used to predict the citizenry’s attitudes towards e-Government services using the citizenry’s perceived ability to use, the perceived value of, and trust in e-Government services is given by:

$$ATT = 1,852 + (0,173 * PATU) + (0,181 * TieG) + (0,103 * PV) + \sum_{k=1}^3 e_k$$

Predictors of the Trust in e-Government (TieG) Model

The dependent variable Trust in e-Government (TieG) index which was measured using 6 indicators: PATU, PrSC, PerSQ, TiT, TiG, and the PIF. The following hypotheses were tested

for the prediction of the TieG Model (see Figure 6-20). The multiple regressions for the TieG model showed no violation of the multicollinearity assumption (TOL range: 0.464-0.853; VIF range: 1.172-2.155). One of the assumptions that were checked in the multiple regressions was the independence of residuals using the Durbin Watson test statistic. The Durbin Watson score of 1.980 showed that the residuals were tenable based on criteria of less than the critical value 2 (Field, 2009, p. 236). There was no influential outlier detected in the TieG Model. The strength of the associations between the TieG and predictor variables were significantly large at $p < 0.01$: PATU ($r=0.544$); TiG ($r=0.519$); TiT ($r=0.495$); PrSC ($r=0.581$); and PerSQ ($r=0.534$), except for PIF ($r=0.305$) whose strength was moderate. The coefficients of the predictor variables reflected positive relationships with the outcome variable (TieG). For every unit increase in PATU there would be 0.192 increase in TieG ($B=0.192$); for a unit increase in TiG there would be 0.145 increase in TieG ($B=0.145$); for TiT there would be 0.037 increase in TieG ($B=0.037$); for PrSC there would be 0.265 increase in TieG ($B=0.265$); for PIF there would be 0.108 increase in TieG ($B=0.108$), and for PerSQ there would be 0.107 increase in TieG ($B=0.107$).

- H₆: The citizens' perceived privacy and security concerns (PrSC) have a significant positive effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)*
- H₇: The citizens' perceived e-Service Quality (PerSQ) has a significant and positive effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)*
- H₈: The citizens' perceived trust in technology (TiT) has a significant and positive effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)*
- H₉: The citizens' perceived trust in the government (TiG) has a significant and positive effect on trust in e-Government (TieG)*
- H₁₀: The citizens's perceived internet familiarity (FI) has a significant and positive effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)*
- H₁₁: The citizens's perceived ability to use (PATU) e-Government services has a significant and positive effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)*

Figure 6-20: The TieG Model

To ascertain the significance of the coefficients, the t statistic was used and the alpha values corresponding to the t values are shown in Table 6-27. Using the alpha values, the predictor variables' coefficients for perceived ability to use the e-Government services (PATU), Trust in government (TiG), perceived privacy and security concerns (PrSC), and perceived internet familiarity (PIF) was found to be statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ in predicting the trust in e-Government variable. Similarly, perceived service quality (PerSQ) was found to be statistically significant at $p < 0.1$ ($p=0.086$) in predicting the trust in e-Government (TieG). Although the trust

in technology (TiT) had a positive relationship with trust in the e-Government variable, the former was found to lack the predictive power of the latter (p=0.508). The predictor variables namely PATU, TiG, TiT, PIF, PerSQ, and PrSC taken as a group were found to have a coefficient of multiple determination (Adj R²=0.452) that reflected that the predictor variables accounted for 45.2% of the variance in the TieG variable. This showed that the predictor variables had considerable explanation or effect in the TieG model. The statistical significance of the variance that was accounted for by the predictor variables was corroborated by the F statistic F (6.310) = 44.523; p<0.005 reflecting that the positive relationship between the outcome and predictor variable(s) in the model was significant. The results of the multiple regressions for the TieG model are summarised in Table 6-27.

Table 6-27: Multiple regression results for the TieG Model

Predictor Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	sig.	collinearity statistics		Durbin Watson
	B	Std. Error				Tolerance	VIF	
(CONSTANT)	0.773	0.206		3.752	0.000			
PATU_TR	0.192	0.055	0.195	3.473	0.001	0.552	1.813	
TiG_TR	0.145	0.048	0.178	3.029	0.003	0.503	1.986	1.980
TiT_TR	0.037	0.055	0.040	0.662	0.508	0.470	2.129	
PrSC_TR	0.265	0.060	0.261	4.449	0.000	0.503	1.986	
PIF_TR	0.108	0.040	0.122	2.698	0.007	0.853	1.172	
PersQ_TR	0.107	0.062	0.105	1.721	0.086	0.464	2.155	

F (6.310) = 44.523; p=0.000; R= 0.680; R²=0. 463; Adj R²=0.452; standardised error of estimate = 0.53711

The fitted TieG model shows how much change in the Trust in e-Government would take place when there was one-unit change (measured in standard deviations) in each of the predictor variables represented.

$$TieG = 0,773 + (0,192 * PATU) + (0,145 * TiG) + (0,037 * TiT) + (0,265 * PrSC) + (0,108 * PIF) + (0,107 * PerSQ) + \sum_{k=1}^6 e_k$$

The Behavioural Intention Model (BI)

The behavioural Intention model conceptually included predictor variables such as : Attitude (ATT), TieG, Technical Support (TS), availability of e_Offices, and the technical skills and ownership of resources needed to access the e-Government services, and the Social Influence (SI) as the moderator variable as shown in Figure 6-21.

H₄: The citizens's attitudes (ATT) will have a positively significant influence on behavioural Intention (BI) to use e-Government services

H₅: The citizens's social influence (SI) has a moderating effect on the association between attitudes and behavioural intention to use e-Government services

H₁₃: The citizens' trust in e-Government (TieG) has significant and positive influence on their intentions to use e-Government services

H_{14a}: The Technical Support (TS) has a significant and positive influence on the citizens' intentions to use e-Government services

H_{14b}: The availability of e_Offices has a significant and positive influence on the citizens' intentions to use e-Government services

H_{14c}: The technical Skills and Resource ownership (TSkills_RsrcOwnership) has a significant and positive influence on the citizens' intentions to use e-Government services

Figure 6-21: The Behavioural Intention

F-Hayes process macro was used to probe the moderation significance of the social Influence in the ATT < - -> BI relationship. The results of the regression of the BI model showed that the moderation was insignificant (B= - 0.098; t (309) = -1.0441; p= 0.086 as shown in Figure 6-22.

```

*****
OUTCOME VARIABLE:
BI_TR

Model Summary
      R      R-sq      MSE      F(HC3)      df1      df2      P
      ,6123      ,3749      ,3603      25,2549      7,0000      309,0000      ,0000

Model
      coeff      se (HC3)      t      p      LLCI      ULCI
constant      2,4796      ,3396      7,3008      ,0000      1,8113      3,1479
ATT_TR      ,3079      ,0732      4,2062      ,0000      ,1638      ,4519
SI_TR      ,1601      ,0588      2,7221      ,0069      ,0444      ,2758
Int_1      -,0977      ,0936      -1,0441      ,2973      -,2818      ,0864
TieG_TR      ,0879      ,0570      1,5126      ,1239      -,0242      ,2000
TS_TR      ,0346      ,0488      ,7095      ,4786      -,0614      ,1306
TSkills_      ,2298      ,0557      4,1231      ,0000      ,1201      ,3395
e_Office      ,0657      ,0419      1,5694      ,1176      -,0167      ,1481

Product terms key:
Int_1      :      ATT_TR      x      SI_TR

```

Figure 6-22: Social Influence Interaction results

Having Social Influence as significant in the model meant that social influence does have the additive value taken together with other predictors. However, the insignificance of the interacting term meant that there was a lack of the multiplicative power (moderating power) to influence the intentions. As such the Social Influence could not moderate the attitude variable on behavioural Intention. To this effect, the regression was rerun with all the predictor variables including social influence variable as covariates. The results of the rerun are detailed in Tables 6-28 and 6-29.

Table 6-28: Behavioural Intention Model Correlations

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
BI_TR (1)	1.000	.373	.378	.499	.314	.191	.481
TieG_TR (2)	.373	1.000	.404	.395	.232	.197	.368
SI_TR (3)	.378	.404	1.000	.316	.228	.249	.252
TSkills_RsrcOwnership (4)	.499	.395	.316	1.000	.379	.215	.517
e_Offices (5)	.314	.232	.228	.379	1.000	-.032	.344
TS_TR (6)	.191	.197	.249	.215	-.032	1.000	.169
ATT_TR (7)	.481	.368	.252	.517	.344	.169	1.000

The Pearson bivariate correlations of the Behavioural Intention variables were all positive except for the association between Technical Support and e-Offices ($r = -0.032$; weakest). The strongest relationship was between the technical skills and resource ownership and the behavioural Intention pointing to the fact that the more the participant has the skills and the resources to use, their intention equally heightens. All the bivariate associations between predictor variables were less than 0.7 demonstrating non-violation of collinearity assumptions as corroborated in Table 6-28. The associations between the predictor variables and the behavioural Intention variable were all at least moderate at $p < 0.001$ level of significance.

Cases 110 and 256 that were identified as possible outliers were retained since the cases had low leverage and they did not pose a threat to the slope or intercept. Autocorrelation was assessed using the Durbin Watson's Test static of independence of residuals and the score was found to be 1.672. The Durbin Watson score showed that the residuals were positively correlated based on Field (2009, p. 236) criteria of less than the critical value 2. See Table 8-31. The multicollinearity assumption was not violated as the Tolerance and the VIF values were in the acceptable ranges with each of the predictor variable showing a minimum of 63% that is not accounted for in other predictor variables (see Table 6-29).

Table 6-29: Behavioural Intention model multiple regression results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		DW
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF	
(Constant)	.845	.266		3.172	.002			1.672
TieG_TR	.094	.055	.091	1.715	.087	.728	1.374	
SI_TR	.166	.048	.175	3.425	.001	.773	1.294	
TSkills_RsrcOwnership	.234	.055	.243	4.275	.000	.628	1.594	
e_Offices	.059	.038	.079	1.556	.121	.794	1.259	
TS_TR	.036	.044	.039	.814	.416	.887	1.128	
ATT_TR	.276	.062	.244	4.452	.000	.677	1.477	

F (6.310) = 30.440; p=0.000;
R= 0.609; R²=0.371; Adj R²=0.359; standardised error of estimate = 0.60126

Table 6-29 also showed that the model coefficient was 0.845 and importantly significant. In addition, all predictor variables reflected positive relationships with the behavioural intention variable (ATT: B=0.276; SI: B=0.166. TieG: B=0.094; TSkills_RsrcOwnership: B =0.234; and e_Offices: B= 0.059). To ascertain the significance of the coefficients, the t statistic was used and the alpha corresponding to the t values showed that the predictor variables' coefficients for attitude towards the e-Government services (ATT), Social Influence (SI), and the technical skills and resource ownership were found to be significantly significant at p<0.001 in predicting the citizens behavioural Intention to use e-Government services. However, the Trust in e-Government services (TieG) was significant at p<0.1. The e-offices and technical support were insignificant. The fitted BI model was significant at F (6.310) = 30.440; p<0.05 with the predictor variables accounting for almost 36% of the variability in the intentions to use e-Government services (Adj R²=0.359). The BI model shows how much change in the intentions to use e-Government services would take place when there was one-unit change (measured in standard deviations) in each of the predictor variables included in the BI model.

$$BI = 0,845 + (0,276 * ATT) + (0,166 * SI) + (0,094 * TieG) + (0,036 * TS) + (0,234 * TSkills_RsrcOwnership) + (e - Offices * 059) + \sum_{k=1}^4 e_k$$

The E-Government adoption predictors

The final sub model that was assessed was the e-Government adoption model which had three predictor variables (including two moderator variables) conceptually (see Figure 6-23).

H₁₅: The citizens's intentions (BI) have a significant influence on the e-Government services adoption

H₁₆: The higher uncertainty Avoidance (UA) has a positive moderating effect of the intentions on e-Government services adoption.

H₁₇: High power distance (PD) has a significant moderating influence on the adoption of e-Government services

Figure 6-23: The e-Government adoption multiple regression with the moderation model (conceptual)

Statistically this meant having up to 5 predictor variables with the two interaction variables *included*. The F. Hayes process macro was used to assess the moderation of the behavioural intentions of using e-Government services by Uncertainty Avoidance and the Power Distance (model 2 from Hayes templates). However, the uncertainty avoidance moderation was found to be insignificant ($\Delta R^2 = 0.000$; $p=0.848$). Hence, the macro was rerun with the only one moderator (Power Distance) and the uncertainty avoidance was entered as a covariate in the model (model 1 from Hayes templates) as it was no longer considered a moderator.

The resulting regression with one moderator and one covariate is given in Figure 6-24. The corresponding coefficients of the predictor variables were all found to be positive and significant((BI_TR: B1= 0.278; $t(312)= 11.123$; $p <0.05$), (PD_TR: B2= 0,231; $t(312)= 10,030$; $p <0.05$), (Int_1: B3= 0.076; $t(312)= 3.250$; $p <0.05$)), (UA_TR: B4= 0.204; $t(312)= 7.468$; $p =0.001$), and (Int_1: B3= 0.033; $t(312)= 7.262$; $p <0.05$).

```

*****
Model : 1
Y : eGov_ado
X : BI_TR
W : PD_TR

Covariates:
UA_TR

Sample
Size: 317

*****
OUTCOME VARIABLE:
eGov_ado

Model Summary

R          R-sq      MSE      F (HC3)      df1      df2      p
,829      ,688      ,075      144,929      4,000      312,000      ,000

Model

      coeff      se (HC3)      t      p      LLCI      ULCI
constant 2,920      ,105      27,895      ,000      2,714      3,126
BI_TR    ,278      ,025      11,123      ,000      ,229      ,327
PD_TR    ,231      ,023      10,030      ,000      ,186      ,276
Int_1    ,076      ,023      3,250      ,001      ,030      ,123
UA_TR    ,204      ,028      7,262      ,000      ,149      ,260

Product terms key:
Int_1      :      BI_TR      x      PD_TR

```

Figure 6-24: Multiple regression with one moderator in the e-Government adoption model

To better understand the significance and the effects of the moderation at three distinct levels of Power Distance (low, medium, and high levels), the interaction data that was generated by SPSS was plotted using a scatter gram (See Figure 6-25 (a)). The scatter gram indicated positive relationships formed by group scatters of the three levels. For a clearer and simplified view of the moderator effect at each level, the data were recoded and line graphs of the marginal means of the relationship between the intentions and the adoption for low, medium, and high levels of PD values were plotted (see 6-25 (b)). Figure 6-25 shows that there is a positive relationship between the Behavioural intention and the e-Government adoption at each of the three levels of power distance moderation. Figure 6-24 shows that the model was significant, and the four predictor variables taken as a group significantly accounted for 68.8% ($R^2= 0.688$; $F(4.312) = 144.929$; $p < 0.05$) of the variability in the e-Government adoption variable (DV).

Figure 6-25: Effect of distinct levels of PD on the BI_TR -eGov_adoption relationship

The e-Government adoption model was then represented by

$$eGov_Adoptio = 2,920 + (0,278 * BI) + (0,231 * PD) + (0,076 * BI * PD) + (0,204 * UA) + \sum_{k=1}^4 e_k$$

Summary of the regression models in the whole group

The overall research model was divided into 5 submodels whose regression results were presented separately in the preceding sections. Table 6-30 recollected the separate results for a clearer picture of the overall research model. Most of the hypothesis were accepted (77%) at either $p < 0.1$; $p < 0.01$; $p < 0.05$; or $p < 0,001$ significance level. The predictor variable(s) in each sub-model in Table 6-30 were arranged in the order of their predictive power starting from the highest based on their beta values.

Table 6-30: Summary of Regression Models

Model	Regr. Analy. type	Hypothesis	Independent Variable	Dependent Variable	β	t	p value	Result
1	Simple	H ₁	PATU	PV	0.606****	13.509	0.000	<i>accepted</i>
2		H ₁₂	TieG		0.198***	3.108	0.002	<i>accepted</i>
		H ₂	PATU	ATT	0.192***	2.827	0.005	<i>accepted</i>
		H ₃	PV		0.122*	1.822	0.069	<i>accepted</i>
		H ₆	PrSC		0.261****	4.449	0.000	<i>accepted</i>
3		H ₁₁	PATU		0.195***	3.473	0.001	<i>accepted</i>
		H ₉	TiG	TieG	0.178***	3.029	0.003	<i>accepted</i>
		H ₁₀	PIF		0.122***	2.698	0.007	<i>accepted</i>
		H ₇	PerSQ		0.105*	1.721	0.086	<i>accepted</i>
		H ₈	TiT		0.04	0.662	0.508	na
4	Multiple	H ₄	ATT	BI	0.244****	4.452	0.000	<i>accepted</i>
		H _{14c}	TSkills_RsrcO wnership		0.243****	4.275	0.000	<i>accepted</i>
		H ₅	SI		0.175***	3.425	0.001	<i>accepted</i>
		Int_3	ATT * SI		0.098 ^a	1.044	0.297	na
		H ₁₃	TieG		0.091*	1.715	0.087	<i>accepted</i>
		H _{14b}	E_Offices		0.079	1.556	0.121	na
		H _{14a}	TS		0.039	0.814	0.416	na
5		H ₁₅	BI	eGov Adoption	0.278**** ^a	11.123	0.000	<i>accepted</i>
		H ₁₇	PD		0.231**** ^a	10.030	0.000	<i>accepted</i>
		H ₁₆	UA		0.204**** ^a	7.262	0.000	<i>accepted</i>
		Int_1	BI * PD		0.076** ^a	3.250	0.001	<i>accepted</i>
		Int_2	BI * UA		0.005 ^a	-0.191	0.848	na

Statistical Significance

**** Coefficient is significant at < 0.001

*** Coefficient is significant at < 0.01

** Coefficient is significant at < 0.05

* Coefficient is significant at < 0.1

a. is the b value no β (based on F. Hayes process macro)

Moderators: ATT * SI. BI * PD. BI * UA

Na: not accepted

6.4.8.2 Country level *research model* regression analysis

To ascertain the e-Government factors that affect individual countries regression analysis was carried out for Zimbabwe and Botswana.

ZIMBABWE

Based on the responses from the participants from Zimbabwe the following hypothesis was tested in model 1 (PV model) and it was found that the *PATU* coefficient was significant at $p < 0.001$ level (*PATU*: $\beta = 0.655$, $t(170) = 7.352$, $p = 0.000$). The model showed that 42.9 % of the variability in the perceived value of e-Government services by the participants was explained by their perceived ability to use ($R^2 = 0.429$). The variability was significant ($F(1,170) = 127.687$; $p < 0.001$).

In the Attitude model, *TieG* was found to be importantly significant at $p < 0.001$ (*TieG*: $\beta = 0.314$, $t(168) = 3.686$, $p = 0.000$). *PV* and *PATU* coefficients were found to be insignificant at $p < 0.1$ level (*PV*: $\beta = 0.133$, $t(168) = 1.451$, $p = 0.149$; *PATU*: $\beta = 0.113$, $t(168) = 1.176$, $p = 0.241$). The model showed that 23.4 % of the variability in the attitude of the participants towards e-Government services was explained by their perceived ability to use, their perceived value, and their trust in e-Government services ($\text{Adj } R^2 = 0.234$). The variability, though seemingly low was found to be significant ($F(3,168) = 17.100$; $p < 0.001$). From the standardised coefficients, we could conclude that the Trust in e-Government has the highest effect ($\beta = 0.314$) in predicting the citizens' attitude followed by *PV* then *PATU*.

In the *TieG* model, it was found that *PrSC*, *PATU*, *PerSQ*, and *TiT* were importantly significant at varying levels of significance (*PrSC*: $\beta = 0.266$, $t(165) = 3.049$, $p = 0.003$; *PATU*: $\beta = 0.194$, $t(165) = 2.268$, $p = 0.009$; *PerSQ*: $\beta = 0.148$, $t(165) = 1.702$, $p = 0.091$; *TiT*: $\beta = 0.164$, $t(165) = 2.065$, $p = 0.040$). *TiG* and *PIF* coefficients were found to be insignificant at $p < 0.1$ level (*TiG*: $\beta = 0.094$, $t(165) = 1.255$, $p = 0.211$; *PIF*: $\beta = 0.023$, $t(165) = 0.399$, $p = 0.691$). The model showed that 53.4 % of the variability in the *TieG* model was explained by *PrSC*, *PATU*, *PerSQ*, *TiT*, *PIF* and *TiG* ($R^2 = 0.534$). The variability was found to be significant ($F(6,165) = 31.560$; $p < 0.001$). From the standardised coefficients, we could conclude that the *PrSC* has the highest effect ($\beta = 0.266$) in predicting the citizens' trust in e-Government followed by *PATU*, *TiT*, *PerSQ*, *TiG*, then *PIF* respectively.

Table 6-31: The BI model regression results (Zimbabwe case)

```

OUTCOME VARIABLE:
  BI_TR

Model Summary
      R      R-sq      MSE      F (HC3)      df1      df2
P      ,627      ,393      ,431      17,503      7,000      164,000
,000

Model
      coeff      se (HC3)      t      p      LLCI      ULCI
constant      1,876      ,484      3,874      ,000      ,920      2,833
ATT_TR      ,320      ,119      2,696      ,008      ,086      ,554
SI_TR      ,046      ,074      ,620      ,536      -,101      ,193
Int_1      -,146      ,125      -1,172      ,243      -,392      ,100
TSkills_      ,282      ,089      3,173      ,002      ,106      ,457
TieG_TR      ,163      ,091      1,780      ,077      -,018      ,343
e_Office      ,056      ,075      ,747      ,456      -,092      ,203
TS_TR      ,093      ,065      1,441      ,152      -,034      ,221

Product terms key:
Int_1      :      ATT_TR      x      SI_TR

Test(s) of highest order unconditional interaction(s):
      R2-chng      F (HC3)      df1      df2      p
X*W      ,008      1,375      1,000      164,000      ,243
-----

```

The participants in Zimbabwe seemed to claim that the only factors that are influential in changing their behavioural intentions to use e-Government services are attitude, technical skills, and ownership of appropriate resources to access e-Government services, and the trust in e-Government. It was found that the participants did not find social influence, availability of e-offices, and the technical support significant. The interaction ATT X SI was also not found to be significant. This can be seen in Table 6-31 where the R² change was found to be insignificant. See Table 6-37 for supporting details. The model showed that 39.3 % of the variability in the BI model was explained by the other variables (R² =0.393). Also, it is important to note in Table 6-31, the interaction ATT X SI was found to be insignificant and the Social Influence was also insignificant as a covariate.

The participants in Zimbabwe claimed that the BI, PD, UA, PD*BI were influential in e-Government adoption at p<0.001 level of significance (BI: β =0.451, t (166) = 9.404, p=0.000; PD: β =0.359, t (166) = 8.426, p=0.000; PD*BI: β =0.310, t (166) = 6.705, p=0.000; UA*BI: β =0.203, t (166) = 4.270, p=0.000). It was found that higher uncertainty Avoidance (UA) did not have a positive moderating effect of the intentions on e-Government services adoption. The model showed that 76.9 % of the variability in the BI model was explained by the other variables (R² =0.769) and significant (F (5.166) =110.419; p=0.000).

Botswana

In an analogous manner, the 5 regression models were tested separately for the Botswana participant responses. The following hypothesis was tested first. It was found that the PATU

coefficient was importantly significant at $p < 0.001$ level (PATU: $\beta = 0.405$, $t(72) = 3.762$, $p = 0.000$). The model showed that 16.9 % of the variability in the perceived value of e-Government services by the participants was explained by their perceived ability to use ($R^2 = 0.169$). The variability was found to be significant ($F(1,72) = 14.156$; $p < 0.001$).

In the Attitude Model, contrary to the Zimbabwe participants, the Botswana participants *perceived* TieG to be insignificant at $p < 0.05$ (TieG: $\beta = -0.050$, $t(70) = -0.429$, $p = 0.670$). PV and PATU coefficients which were found to be insignificant with the Zimbabwe sample, were found to be importantly significant at varying levels of significance (PV: $\beta = 0.221$, $t(70) = 1.832$, $p = 0.071$; PATU: $\beta = 0.425$, $t(70) = 3.797$, $p = 0.000$). The model showed that 28.4% of the variability in the attitude of the participants towards e-Government services was explained by their perceived ability to use, their perceived value, and their trust in e-Government services ($R^2 = 0.284$). The variability was found to be significant ($F(3,70) = 9.271$; $p < 0.001$). From the standardised coefficients, we could conclude that the PATU had the highest effect ($\beta = 0.425$) in predicting the citizens' attitude followed by PV then TieG.

In the TieG model, it was found that TiG coefficient was found to be the only significant at $p < 0.1$ level of significance (TiG: $\beta = 0.320$, $t(67) = 2.578$, $p = 0.012$). PrSC, PATU, PIF, PerSQ, and TiT were insignificant at $p < 0.05$ (PrSC: $\beta = 0.115$, $t(67) = 3.049$, $p = 0.363$; PATU: $\beta = 0.107$, $t(67) = 0.840$, $p = 0.404$; PIF: $\beta = 0.077$, $t(67) = 0.605$, $p = 0.548$; PerSQ: $\beta = 0.055$, $t(67) = 0.453$, $p = 0.652$; TiT: $\beta = 0.078$, $t(67) = 0.532$, $p = 0.697$). The model showed that 29.1 % of the variability in the TieG model was explained by PrSC, PATU, PerSQ, TiT, PIF and TiG ($R^2 = 0.291$). The variability was found to be significant ($F(6,67) = 4.589$; $p = 0.001$).

The BI Model, Table 6-38 shows that the attitude, social influence, and trust in e-Government are influential in changing behavioural intentions to use e-Government services. The skills, e-offices, and technical support may be influential but the Botswana participants claim that it is rather ones' attitude and the influence from social circles that matter when it comes to the behavioural intentions. The participants did not find any influence in the interaction path owing to a very insignificant change in the R-squared (see Table 6-32). The results after running the F. Hayes macro are shown in Table 6-32 as follows:

Table 6-32 : Regression results of the BI model (Botswana)

```

*****
OUTCOME VARIABLE:
  BI_TR

Model Summary
      R      R-sq      MSE      F(HC3)      df1      df2
P
,0000 ,7649 ,5850 ,2142 13,4266 7,0000 66,0000

Model
      coeff      se(HC3)      t      p      LLCI      ULCI
constant 2,7120 ,7382 3,6739 ,0005 1,2382 4,1858
ATT_TR ,3909 ,1386 2,8211 ,0063 ,1142 ,6675
SI_TR ,3171 ,0902 3,5169 ,0008 ,1371 ,4972
Int_1 -,1716 ,2148 -,7988 ,4273 -,6004 ,2573
TSkills_ ,1851 ,1199 1,5435 ,1275 -,0543 ,4246
TieG_TR ,1567 ,0913 1,7155 ,0910 -,0257 ,3391
e_Office ,0653 ,0633 1,0319 ,3059 -,0610 ,1916
TS_TR -,0377 ,1093 -,3447 ,7314 -,2558 ,1805

Product terms key:
Int_1 : ATT_TR x SI_TR

Test(s) of highest order unconditional interaction(s):
      R2-chng      F(HC3)      df1      df2      p
X*W ,0093 ,6381 1,0000 66,0000 ,4273
-----

```

In the Model e-EGov_adoption, the participants in Botswana claim that the focal predictor BI, and the moderating variables PD, and SI as covariates were importantly significant in predicting the e-Government adoption. However, the two interactions were insignificant as indicated by the small changes in the corresponding R-squares. See Table 6-33. The model showed that 77.53 % of the variability in the BI model was explained by the other variables ($R^2=0.7753$) and significant ($F(5.68)=40.4724$; $p=0.000$).

Table 6-33: EGov_adoption model regression results (Botswana)

```

*****
OUTCOME VARIABLE:
  eGov_ado

Model Summary
      R      R-sq      MSE      F(HC3)      df1      df2
P
,0000 ,8805 ,7753 ,0408 40,4724 5,0000 68,0000

Model
      coeff      se(HC3)      t      p      LLCI      ULCI
constant 3,6972 ,0260 142,3755 ,0000 3,6454 3,7490
BI_TR ,3689 ,0414 8,9015 ,0000 ,2862 ,4516
PD_TR ,1224 ,0407 3,0046 ,0037 ,0411 ,2037
Int_1 -,0379 ,0569 -,6670 ,5070 -,1514 ,0756
UA_TR ,1698 ,0534 3,1821 ,0022 ,0633 ,2763
Int_2 ,0443 ,0452 ,9818 ,3297 -,0458 ,1344

Product terms key:
Int_1 : BI_TR x PD_TR
Int_2 : BI_TR x UA_TR

Test(s) of highest order unconditional interaction(s):
      R2-chng      F(HC3)      df1      df2      p
X*W ,0022 ,4449 1,0000 68,0000 ,5070
X*Z ,0034 ,9639 1,0000 68,0000 ,3297

```

6.4.9 Path Analysis and Model Development using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM)

Because of the complexity of the quantitative research model, computation of 5 different models of approximation was done in the preceding sections and the following multiple regression equations were arrived at:

$$PV = 1,753 + (0,648 * PATU) + e_1 \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

$$ATT = 1,852 + (0,173 * PATU) + (0,181 * TieG) + (0,103 * PV) + \sum_{k=1}^3 e_k \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

$$TieG = 0,773 + (0,192 * PATU) + (0,145 * TiG) + (0,037 * TiT) + (0,265 * PrSC) + (0,108 * PIF) + (0,107 * PerSQ) + \sum_{k=1}^6 e_k \quad (\text{Eq.3})$$

$$BI = 0,845 + (0,276 * ATT) + (0,166 * SI) + (0,094 * TieG) + (0,036 * TS) + (0,234 * TSkills_{RsrcOwnership}) + (e - Offices * 059) + \sum_{k=1}^4 e_k \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

$$eGov_Adoption = 2,920 + (0,278 * BI) + (0,231 * PD) + (0,076 * BI * PD) + (0,204 * UA) + \sum_{k=1}^4 e_k \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

It was evident that some of the dependent variables became independent variables in other equations (e.g. PV in Equation 1 was a dependent variable but acted as an independent variable in equation 2) making the measurement of the model complex. In practice, e-Government factors do influence each other simultaneously. This complexity could cause an incorrect rejection of the null hypotheses in the regression analysis. Accordingly, to test how well the proposed model fit the sample data, the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) was used as the general fitting framework with the Analysis of Moment Structures (AMOS) in SPSS version 21 used as the statistical software. AMOS acted as the unifier of the separate yet interdependent regression equations, thus giving us a combined effect of the independent variables in the study model. That desirability of AMOS to test all the relationships between latent variables and interactions simultaneously would act as a (dis)confirmatory analysis of the regression analysis results. Additionally, SEM was used in the study because it is known for its ability to account for the measurement of error which we tend to overlook in regression analysis (Hair *et al.*, 2010). Since the study was multi-case, using AMOS for multi-group analysis was handy as it allowed the analysis of groups whilst at the same time preserving the complexity of the model. There is a consensus in the literature on the cut-off points of the goodness of fit (GOF) indices with improvements on unique variances including sample sizes, degrees of freedom, and complexity of the model on the influential indices suggested by Hu and Bentler (1999). Some of the indices include CMIN (Chi-Square) which is expected to have insignificant p values at p<0.05 level; root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) < 0.08 with values close to zero denoting a close fit; and the Comparative Fit Index (CFI) or the Tucker-Lewis

Index (TLI) ranging from 0.90 or above depending on the number of observed values and the sample sizes (Hair *et al.*, 2010). Despite Hu and Bentler (1999) having communicated that the cut off points had limitations in their work, researchers have chosen to turn a blind eye and use the fit indices as the “Golden rules”. However, as ‘Golden rules’ as they may seem, they are not without criticisms. Some of the models that are considered to be of close data-model fit based on the ‘Golden rules’ may be having a poorer quality of the measurement or vice versa (Marsh, Hau & Wen, 2004; Hancock & Mueller, 2011; Heene *et al.*, 2011; McNeish, An & Hancock, 2018). Hu and Bentler (1999) reported the GOF indices after simulating models with high factor loadings (between 0.70 and 0.80). In the study the scholars only manipulated conditions such as deviations from the Gauss model, sample sizes, and model types whilst holding the measurement quality constant. However, Hancock and Mueller (2011) questioned the practicality of such high factor loading in empirical data and then focused their critique of the GOF indices on the analysis of the variances in factor loadings and holding constant conditions such as misspecification and sample sizes.

The following extract in Table 6-34 summarises their findings of GOF indices for models with factor loadings of 0.4 up to those with factors that load at 0.95 (increments of 0.05 of the factor loadings was done).

Table 6-34: Fit Index Values for varied measurement Quality

Index	.40 ^a	.45	.50	.55	.60	.65	.70	.75	.80	.85	.90	.95
Model $\chi^2_{(129)}$	51.07	80.77	121.24	174.26	241.85	327.20	434.97	570.03	733.31	923.83	1147.50	1417.03
Null $\chi^2_{(153)}$	843.22	1252.75	1782.52	2455.50	3301.89	4363.37	5700.42	7406.21	9636.04	12679.44	17182.79	25196.26
SRMR	.019	.025	.032	.042	.053	.065	.080	.097	.120	.145	.172	.202
RMSEA	.000	.000	.000	.019	.030	.039	.049	.058	.068	.079	.089	.100
GFI	.994	.990	.985	.979	.971	.960	.948	.935	.923	.911	.900	.888
AGFI	.992	.987	.980	.972	.961	.947	.931	.913	.897	.882	.867	.852
CFI	1.000	1.000	1.000	.980	.964	.953	.945	.939	.936	.937	.940	.949

Note. SRMR = standardized root mean square residual; RMSEA = root mean square error of approximation; GFI = goodness-of-fit index; AGFI = adjusted goodness-of-fit index; CFI = comparative fit index.

a. This model had disturbance variance parameter ψ_{55} constrained to zero. All other models were fitted without incident.

Source: (Extracted from Hancock & Mueller, 2011, p. 321)

With reference to Table 6-34, contrary to the GOF cut of points, the models with factors that load as lowly 0.40 seem to be the ones with a close fit. These findings also corroborate the findings in the work of Heene et al. (2011), who in the same year investigated the influence of factor loadings in detecting model data fit by focusing on commonly reported indices (RMSEA, CFI, and the standardised root mean residual (SRMR)). For the three indices, they found out

that the lower the factor loadings the lower the three GOF indices and the chi-square value. Hence, the catchy phrase: *the reliability paradox of the GOF indices* in the work of Hancock and Mueller (2011). In support of the criticism, Kenny (2015) posited that religiously following the rules of thumb was not recommended. The scholar also recommended that if the RMSEA of the independence model is less than 0.158, then the CFI was not to be reported. In the ongoing debate of the GOF indices paradox in SEM, it has been argued that achieving the GOF indices is necessary but not sufficient for the validity of the interpretation of the default model in question (Marsh, Hau & Wen, 2004). Alternatively, there is a consensus in reporting the factor loadings of the indicator measures together with the GOF cut-off points for a better interpretation of the model fit by the intended audience (Heene et al., 2011; McNeish, An & Hancock, 2018).

6.4.9.1 The structural model

In the current study, the measurement model included all the components found in the principal component analysis together with the three hypothesized interactions. All latent variables in the model were indirectly quantified using the corresponding measured indicator responses from the study questionnaire. The maximum likelihood was used as the method of estimation for the model fit. Three commonly reported indices drawn from three categories of model fit were considered and were found to be as follows (see Table 6-35):

Table 6-35: Model Fit Indices

CATEGORY	INDEX	DEFAULT MODEL INDEX VALUE	LO 90	HI 90	INDEX PCLOSE
Absolute Fit	RMSEA	0.087	0.085	0.089	.000
Incremental Fit	CFI	0.541			.000
Parsimonial Fit	CMIN/DF	3.394			.000

The model was fit without any incident.

The chi-square value is hardly used as the GOF index on its own as it is affected by the sample size. As the sample sizes increase, the chi-square p-values are hardly insignificant (Thoemmes, Rosseel & Textor, 2018). As such, the significance of the CMIN/df is not without precedence. In addition the CMIN/DF is below the upper limit of 5 (Hair et al., 2010).

Table 6-35 showed that the absolute and incremental fit indices are unacceptable based on rule of thumb. On the other hand, the study model had a mixture of indicator loadings ranging between 0.32 and 0.93 which meant that some of the indicator measures were not reliably good. So, the improvements of the model fit were to be done. Improvements of the model fit based on the modification Indices are widely contested in literature as the practice tends to fit

empirical data which may lead to issues of generalization in other models and contexts (McNeish, An & Hancock, 2018). In the study, construct validity assessment was done to ascertain the strength of the latent variables' relationships. Borrowing from the suggestion by Hooper, Coughlan and Mullen (2008), each construct was assessed and all the items whose squared correlations were weaker than 0,2 were weeded out. Only factor loadings that had a minimum load of 0.5 were retained. In addition, the convergent validity of the constructs was ascertained by retaining indicator measures that contributed to the minimum average variance explained (AVE) of 0.5. The strongest latent construct correlation (BI--- >EGov_adoption: r=0.79) was found to have a coefficient of determination Of 0.62. The second strongest was PATU--- >PV: r=0.58 with a coefficient of determination of 0.34. Consequently, the uniqueness of measures in the model (discriminant validity) was ascertained. See table 6-36 for the post hoc model fit results.

Table 6-36: Model Fit Indices (Post Hoc)

CATEGORY	INDEX	DEFAULT MODEL INDEX VALUE	LO 90	HI 90	INDEX PCLOSE
Absolute Fit	RMSEA	0.088	0.085	0.090	.000
Incremental Fit	CFI	0.651			.000
Parsimonial Fit	CMIN/DF	3.436			.000
<i>RMSEA of the Null model</i>		<i>0.143</i>	<i>0.141</i>	<i>0.145</i>	<i>.000</i>

The Parsimonious fit index: CMIN/DF was found to be acceptable and less than the upper limit of 5. Similarly, the absolute fit Index: RMSEA was found to point to a poor fit model (close fit :< = 0.05; fair fit: 0.05 – 0.08; poor fit: > 0.1). The CFI was found to be 0.651 as opposed to 0.95. The *Null* model RMSEA was found to be 0.145 (LO 90: 0.142; HI 90: 0.147). The corresponding structural model showing the factor loading, communalities and the correlations is shown in Figure 6-26. As reflected in Figure 6-26, the indicator variables with factor loading greater than 0.5 were retained. In addition, the AVE of each construct needed to be greater than 0.5. Based on the experiences of the current study, the more one improves the factor loadings in the structural model, the higher the three indices get. This is in concordance with the debate on the paradox of GOF cut off points in the literature (Hancock & Mueller, 2011; Heene *et al.*, 2011; McNeish & Hancock, 2017; McNeish, Hancock,2018).

Figure 6-26: The structural model with factor loadings and variances.

6.4.10 Path confirmatory analysis

The standardized estimates in Figure 6-26 show that the explained variance of the model is 78% ($R^2=0.783 \approx 0.78$). The variability values in the submodels were comparable to the ones achieved in the regression analysis (PV: 33%; TieG: 35%; ATT: 12%; and BI: 24%).

Table 6-37: Unstandardised and Standardised Regression weights (SEM)

Hypot	Path		B	β	S.E.	C.R.	P
hesis							
H ₁₅	ZeGov_adoption	<--- BI	0.756	0.792	0.036	21.283	***
H ₁	PV	<--- PATU	0.499	0.577	0.068	7.297	***
H ₆	TieG	<--- PrSC	0.373	0.458	0.051	7.281	***
H ₄	BI	<--- ATT	0.617	0.391	0.110	5.622	***
H ₁₇	ZeGov_adoption	<--- PD	0.454	0.379	0.051	8.902	***
H ₉	TieG	<--- TiG	0.237	0.281	0.050	4.767	***
H ₃	ATT	<--- PV	0.305	0.277	0.102	3.005	0.003
H ₅	BI	<--- SI	0.501	0.216	0.146	3.435	***
H ₁₁	TieG	<--- PATU	0.151	0.177	0.053	2.931	0.003
H _{14b}	BI	<--- e_Offices	0.211	0.175	0.069	3.043	***
H ₇	TieG	<--- PerSQ	0.138	0.146	0.054	2.550	0.011
H _{14a}	BI	<--- TS	0.152	0.117	0.075	2.011	0.044
Int_3	ZeGov_adoption	<--- BI_x_PD	0.108	0.109	0.031	3.432	***
H ₈	TieG	<--- TiT	0.085	0.094	0.051	1.655	0.098
H ₁₂	ATT	<--- TieG	0.103	0.093	0.077	1.337	0.181
H ₂	ATT	<--- PATU	0.071	0.074	0.088	0.811	0.417
H ₁₀	TieG	<--- PIF	0.04	0.047	0.049	0.816	0.414
Int_1	BI	<--- SI_x_ATT	-0.001	-0.001	.060	-.011	,991

The path analysis showed that all the paths between the observed endogenous variables and the unobserved exogenous variables were significant at $p < 0.001$ level. Table 6-37 shows the standardised and the unstandardized estimates of the paths between the latent variables in the

order of their importance. Contrary to the regression analysis results, H_{14b}, H₇, and H_{14a} were found to be significant at the 0.5 level and H₈ at 0.1 level of significance. Similarly, H₁₂, H₂ and H₁₀ were found to be insignificant yet the regression analysis had proved it otherwise. The rest of the paths that are Table 6-37 were confirmed significant except Int_1 that was confirmed to be insignificant in SEM as in the regression analysis demonstrating the convergence of the results. Three paths were deleted from the model based on their failure to have the AVE greater than 0.5. The paths are TSkills_RsrcOwnership -- >BI; BI_x_UA -- > ZeGov_adoption; UA -- > ZeGov_adoption. Despite their deletion from the model, the estimates confirmed the regression results. The estimates for the deleted paths are shown in Table 6-38.

Table 6-38: Estimates for deleted paths

Hypothesis	Path		B	β	S.E.	C.R.	P
Int_2	ZeGov_adoption	<---	BI_x_UA	0.001	0.002	0.020	0.957
H ₁₆	ZeGov_adoption	<---	UA	0.856	0.418	0.170	***
H _{14c}	BI	<---	Tskills_rsrc	0.253	0.228	0.061	***

The structural equation modelling thus confirmed the insignificance of two of the hypothesized interactions in the model. However, as covariates, all three interactions were found to be significantly and positively significant. Unlike in the regression analysis, AMOS lacks the capability of interpreting the interactions. Instead an interaction plotter tool was used. The BI_x_PD interaction using AMOS data confirmed the interaction in Figure 6-25(b) as depicted in Figure 6-27.

Figure 6-27: The BI_x_PD interaction effect using SEM results

For more details on how the interaction plots were reached, see Annexure O.

6.4.11 Multigroup Analysis of the e-Government Antecedents

Having fitted the model, the following hypothesis was assessed using the chi-square difference test using AMOS (See Annexure N for structural weights models).

H₁₈: The effect of e-Government adoption antecedents' is stronger in Zimbabwe than in Botswana

Firstly, the multigroup analysis of the model was done for Zimbabwe and Botswana to check if there were any differences in the models (that is all factors taken as a group). Based on the model in Figure 6-27, the two models were freely estimated using Chi-Square difference test and the results in Table 6-39 indicate that the difference was significant ($p=0,000$).

Table 6-39: Model comparison results (Zimbabwe vs. Botswana)

Model	DF	CMIN	P	NFI Delta-1	IFI Delta-2	RFI rho-1	TLI rho2
Structural weights	119	248,381	,000	,016	,021	-,003	-,003

To ascertain which of the model paths were significantly different, the same test was carried out except that each of the paths (structural weights) was constrained at a time across the two groups. The paths which were significantly different had to be further assessed on their strength by comparing the standardised estimates. Table 6-40 shows the results.

Table 6-40: Significantly different paths (Zimbabwe vs. Botswana)

Path	Model: Structural weights	D F	CMIN	P	NFI Delta-1	IFI Delta-2	RFI rho-1	TLI rho2	Standardised estimates	
									ZW	BW
TieG ---- >ATT	b1_1=b2_2	1	5.985	0.014	0	0	0	0	0.09	0.11
PV---- >ATT	b2_1=b2_2	1	4.601	0.032	0	0	0	0	0.28	0.2
SI ---- >BI	b7_1=b7_2	1	5.501	0.019	0	0	0	0	0.22	0.29
PATU ---- > ATT	b10_1=b10_2	1	5.283	0.022	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.13
SI_x_ATT ---- > BI	b14_1=b14_2	1	6.121	0.013	0	0.001	0	0	0.2	0.1

6.4.12 Consolidated research model results

The results from regression analysis, model fit analysis, and multi group effect analyses were consolidated and are presented in Table 6-41 for a clearer comparative view.

Table 6-41: Snapshot of the Research Model results

Hypo.	Hypothesis Narration	Path and multigroup effect			SEM	Regression:		
					Fitted Model	whole group	Zimbabwe	Botswana
H ₁₅	The citizens' intentions (BI) have a significant influence on the e-Government services adoption	ZeGov_adoption	<---	BI	✓	✓	✓	✓
H ₁	The citizens' perceived ability to use (PATU) has a positive influence on their perceived value (PV) of e-Government services	PV	<---	PATU	✓	✓	✓	✓
H ₆	The citizens' perceived privacy and security concerns (P&SC) have a significant effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)	TieG	<---	PrSC	✓	✓	✓	x
H ₄	The citizens' attitudes (ATT) have a positive significant influence on behavioural Intention (BI) to use e-Government services	BI	<---	ATT	✓	✓	✓	✓
H ₁₇	High power distance (PD) has a significant moderating influence on the adoption of e-Government services	ZeGov_adoption	<---	PD	✓	✓	✓	✓
H ₉	The citizens' perceived trust in the government (TiG) has a direct effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)	TieG	<---	TiG	✓	✓	x	✓
H ₃	The citizens' perceived value(PV) has a positive influence on attitudes toward using e-Government services	ATT	<---	PV	✓	✓	x	✓
H ₅	The citizens' social influence (SI) has a positive effect on behavioural intention to use e-Government services	BI	<---	SI	✓	✓	x	✓
H ₁₁	The citizens' perceived ability to use (PATU) have a positive influence on the trust they have in e-Government (TieG)	TieG	<---	PATU	✓	✓	✓	x
H _{14b}	The availability of e_Offices has a significant and positive influence on the citizens' intentions to use e-Government services	BI	<---	e_Offices	✓	x	x	x
H ₇	The citizens' perceived e-Service Quality (PerSQ) has a direct effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)	TieG	<---	PerSQ	✓	✓	✓	x
H _{14a}	The Technical Support (TS) has a significant and positive influence e on the citizens' intentions to use e-Government services	BI	<---	TS	✓	x	x	x
Int_3	High power distance (PD) has a significant moderating influence on the adoption of e-Government services	ZeGov_adoption	<---	BI_x_PD	✓	✓	✓	x
H ₈	The citizens' perceived trust in technology (TiT) has a direct effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)	TieG	<---	TiT	✓	x	✓	x
H ₁₂	The citizens' trust in e-Government (TieG) has significant influence on their attitudes toward e-Government services	ATT	<---	TieG	x	✓	x	x
H ₂	The citizens's perceived ability to use(PATU) has positive influence on the attitudes towards using e-Government services	ATT	<---	PATU	x	✓	✓	✓
H ₁₀	The citizens's perceived internet familiarity (PIF) has a significant effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)	TieG	<---	PIF	x	✓	x	x
H ₁₃	The citizens' trust in e-Government (TieG) has significant and positive influence on their intentions to use e-Government services	BI	<---	TieG	✓	✓	✓	✓
Int_1	The Social Influence (SI) has a positive moderating effect of the Attitude toward e-Government services adoption	BI	<---	SI_x_ATT	x	x	x	✓
Int_2	The higher uncertainty Avoidance (UA) has a positive moderating effect of the intentions on e-Government services adoption	ZeGov_adoption	<---	BI_x_UA	x	x	x	x
H ₁₆	The higher uncertainty Avoidance (UA) has a positive of the intentions on e-Government services adoption.	ZeGov_adoption	<---	UA	✓	✓	✓	✓
H _{14c}	The technical Skills and Resource ownership (TSkills_RsrcOwnership)) has significant and positive influence e on the citizens' intentions to use e-Government services	BI	<---	TSkills_rsrc	✓	✓	✓	x

✓..... Accepted at varying levels of significance
 x.....Rejected

A< ---- B Effect stronger in Zimbabwe

A< ---- B Effect stronger in Botswana

Table 6-41 shows interesting results such as:

- i. It established across tests and accepted in both country and whole model regression analysis and in SEM that Power Distance, Uncertainty Avoidance, and Behavioural Intentions has significant influence on e-Government adoption; Trust in e-Government and Attitude influences Behavioural Intentions; and perceived ability to use as influential in determining the perceived value. Similarly, Uncertainty Avoidance was rejected across tests as having a moderating effect on intentions.
- ii. Two of the five paths established to have multigroup effect when individually constrained to be equal across groups were also accepted in the fitted model.
- iii. The other three parts had effect when individually constrained to be equal across groups but were disconfirmed in the fitted model.
- iv. The effect of sub model analysis vs. all sub models taken together

6.5 Chapter Summary

The chapter presented the results of the quantitative data analysis that was carried out using SPSS v21 with AMOS, F. Hayes process and the interaction plotter tools. The latter tools were used for the interpretation of the interactions. The demographic data were analysed both at macro and micro levels and it was found that the study was domineered by males at both levels. The popular age group of participants was between 35 and 44. The research model that was proposed in the previous chapter was tested using single and multiple regressions. Seventy-three percent (73%) of the hypothesis were accepted at the $p < 0, 05$ significance level for both the whole sample and at country levels. Upon validating the model using structural equation modelling, there was a convergence of 16 of the results (significant), and divergence of 6 results. Of the 6 results, 3 were significant and the other three were insignificant based on the regression results and these could not be confirmed using SEM. The BI_x_PD interaction was unanimously confirmed in regression, Hayes process tool, AMOS, and using the interaction plotter tool.

The multigroup effect analysis indicated that there were some differences in the research model across groups. On constraining one path to be equal across groups at a time, only five paths were established to be significantly different. As such the individual analysis of the paths also ascertained which paths were different and which ones were the same. The differences were mainly drawn from the paths in the attitude and behavioural intention sub models. The individual case analysis also shed a clearer and better view of in multi-case analysis. The interpretation of the results in relation to the research questions is discussed in the succeeding chapter.

7 ANSWERING RESEARCH QUESTIONS

7.1 Introduction

This chapter ties the findings of the study to the research questions presented in Chapter 1. The integration of the findings was done through narrative integrative strategy using the Toulmin's Model of argument (claim, data, warrant, backing, and rebuttal).

7.2 Answering Research Question 1

RQ1: How does the translation process aid in understanding the e-Government adoption trajectory in SADC?

The exploratory research question above was explored in order to identify the complexities of e-Government by sticking to Latour's ANT slogan: "Follow the actors themselves or rather that which makes them act." The notion of following the actors meant that the traces of the actors could only be understood if the ANT was used as ontology instead of the lens. Hence, the study was guided by the participants' storylines using Latour's notebooks to describe their experiences of e-Government in their respective countries as detailed in section 5.3.3 on the answer to the research question.

7.3 Answering Research Question 2

RQ2: What are the factors of e-Government adoption that derive from non-focal actors' experiences of e-Government in the SADC?

From the participants' storylines, it was established that in Zimbabwe mandated settings have influence on e-Government adoption. The adoption of transactional e-Government services was increased owing the lack of alternatives to pay for the services consumed. The unavailability of e-Government centres and kiosks puts the burden on the citizens to source their means of reaching the government suggesting that the infrastructural problems are pushed to the intermediary organisations. As such the intermediary organisations such as topup.com and online company registration become the e-offices. Their existence is critical in enabling uptake of the e-Government services, making them facilitating resources. Weerakkody, El-Haddadeh and Al-Sobhi (2013) argue that the intermediary organisations play a critical role in driving the adoption of e-Government services as they bridge the technical gaps with their own infrastructure. Similarly, the existence of the e-offices was not a means to an end as these pushed the infrastructural problems further to the citizens. The move coerces users to increase ownership of mobile technologies as *e-intermediaries* in order to engage with e-Government services.

Whilst the mandatoriness of transactional e-Government services saw an increase in the access to e-intermediaries, the actual usage of e-Government services was not guaranteed. According to the participants' views in the qualitative study, technical support was found to be important in the enhancement of the users' experience in virtual settings especially when one is faced with challenges. As such the facilitating conditions comprised of the access to e-intermediaries, technical support, and e-offices were found to be a contributing factor to e-Government adoption. It was further established that facilitating conditions were not sufficient to increase adoption. The additional factors included attitudes, behavioural intentions, culture, awareness, design issues, trust issues, social Influence, and design issues. Chapter 5, especially section 5.3.3 provides ample demonstration of these facets.

7.4 Answering Research Questions 3 and 4

“Our common cultural and social affinities, common historical experiences, common problems and aspirations remain a firm and enduring foundation for common actions to promote regional economic welfare, collective self-reliance and integration; in the spirit of equity and partnership”(SADC, 1998, p. 1).

This section discusses the results of the quantitative study and at the same time weaving the two quantitative research questions into the qualitative study results.

7.4.1 Variable relationships

RQ3: How do the derived factors that influence e-Government services adoption relate?

The study acknowledges that almost every participant in both the qualitative and quantitative studies had access to some e-intermediaries directly or indirectly with some having multiple ownerships. From the qualitative study, the participants argued that whilst they had access to various e-intermediaries it did not guarantee e-Government adoption as they needed to have the necessary skills to create value in use. The same sentiments are echoed in the quantitative study as participants suggest that the technical skills and resource ownership influence behavioural intentions. The finding was accepted at macro and country levels except for Botswana who value social influence as effective in developing intentions. Whilst all participant countries claim social influence as the most popular source of awareness (see Figure 6-8), the effect is stronger in Botswana (see Table 6-41). It was also established that the popular e-services that citizens' access is the social communication followed by research and mobile banking (see Figure 6-10).

The proposed research model had five dependent variables whose results are discussed below. At whole sample level, the perceived ability to use was found to have an effect in predicting the perceived value in use. The finding shows that the participants suggested that they perceived

the value when they were able to use the technologies. In turn the perceived value and their ability to use the e-Government services did influence their attitudes. All the predictor variables in the TieG Model were found to have a direct effect in influencing the Trust in e-Government by the participants except for the trust in technology (TiT) which was found to be insignificant. The participants expressed that the PrSC, PerSQ, TiG, PIF, and PATU collectively mattered most to them before their trust in technology when it comes to the trust in e-Government. Figure 7-1 graphically illustrates the model hypothesis testing results.

Figure 7-1: The hypothesis testing results as per regression analysis of the whole sample

The participants' ability to use the e-Government services and their ownership of the resources needed to access the e-Government services stood out as the only significant variable of the three variables that made up the facilitating conditions. The SI and UA were found to be insignificant as moderators but significant as covariates in the BI and TieG models respectively. The PD was the only moderator that was found to be importantly significant. On analysing the effect, it was found that as the power distance increased, the association between the Behavioural Intention and the e-government adoption increased positively and tended to be better with each level. For more details on the PD moderation results, see Annexure M.

H₁: *The citizens' perceived ability to use (PATU) has a positive influence on their perceived value (PV) of e-Government services*

The first dependent variable was the perceived value which was predicted using PATU. This relationship was found to be significant at $p < 0,001$ at region and at the country level. The current finding echoed the findings from Davis (1989, 1993); Wangpipatwong, Chutimaskul and Papasratorn (2008); Mahadeo (2009). Similarly, this finding resonates with the value creation factor from the qualitative study. Ravald and Grönroos (1996) argue that a service is not just about what is given to the customer but the sacrifice that the customer makes in the endeavour to benefit from the service. In this regard value creation is possible only when the customer has the functional skill of using the provided service (Grönroos, 2008).

The Attitude model was predicted by three constructs (PATU, PV, and TieG)

H₂: *The citizens' perceived ability to use (PATU) has a positive influence on the attitude towards using e-Government services*

H₃: *The citizens' perceived value (PV) has a positive influence on attitudes toward using e-Government services*

H₁₂: *The citizens' trust in e-Government (TieG) has a significant influence on their attitudes toward e-Government services*

The results showed different combinations of the constructs at varying significance levels in the attitude. At the whole group level, the perceived value was found to be the only influential construct in forming attitudes (significant at $p < 0,05$). This finding confirms the sub model finding at the same significance level. It was also shared with the participants from Botswana though at $p < 0,1$ level of significance. This finding reinforces the same finding by Davis (1989, 1993); Davis, Bagozzi & Warshaw (1989); Lee, Kozar & Larsen (2003); Belanche, Casaló & Flavián (2012); Gracia & Ari (2015). The perceived ability to use was found to be insignificant at whole and subgroup analysis. This was also confirmed by Subramanian (1994); Igbaria, Guimaraes & Davis (1995); Keil, Beranek & Konsynski (1995); Belanche, Casaló & Flavián (2012). Contrary to this finding, Zimbabwe and Botswana participants suggested that the perceived ability to use was influential ($p < 0,001$) in the sub model at the country level.

From the qualitative study, the participants in Zimbabwe claimed that their attitudes were influenced by the economic situation of their country and this was advanced as one of the scale items in the attitude scale. The results showed that the corresponding item was practically and statistically significant as the communality was more than 0,5 as suggested by Hair *et al.* (2010).

The TieG model was predicted using six constructs.

- H₆:** The citizens' perceived privacy and security concerns (P&SC) have a significant effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)
- H₇:** The citizens' perceived e-Service Quality (PerSQ) has a direct effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)
- H₈:** The citizens' perceived trust in technology (TiT) has a direct effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)
- H₉:** The citizens' perceived trust in the government (TiG) has a direct effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)
- H₁₀:** The citizens' perceived internet familiarity (PIF) has a significant effect on Trust in e-Government (TieG)
- H₁₁:** The citizens' perceived ability to use (PATU) have a positive influence on the trust they have in e-Government (TieG)

All the constructs were found to be significant at varying levels except for the perceived Internet familiarity. The finding resonates with findings from Abu-Shanab (2014). Interestingly, the Botswana participants claimed that of the six constructs only one of them: trust in Government (TiG) was influential in the trust in e-Government. On the contrary, the Zimbabwe participants found all the constructs significant except TiG.

Model e-EGov_adoption

H₁₅: The citizens' intentions (BI) have a significant influence on the e-Government services adoption

H₁₆: The uncertainty Avoidance (UA) has a positive moderating effect of the intentions on e-Government services adoption.

H₁₇: Power distance (PD) has a significant moderating influence on the adoption of e-Government services

It was established that there was a consensus that cultural factors such as uncertainty avoidance and power distance had an effect as covariates with other factors in e-Government adoption at whole and subgroup analysis and at country levels at $p < 0.001$ level of significance except for Botswana participants who found these significant at $p < 0.05$. However, there were variances when they were taken as moderating variables on behavioural intention as the focal factor. The result resonated with the finding by Al-Hujran, Al-Dalahmeh and Aloudat (2011) that PD and UA influence the intentions. The participants from Zimbabwe claimed that power distance has a moderating effect on the adoption of e-government services. The finding

corroborates the participant's views mentioned in the qualitative study. They also suggested that it is affecting their participation in giving feedback on the e-Government services. At whole and subgroup level the PD was found significant at $p < 0.001$ just like in the Zimbabwe case. The Botswana participants were of a different view. It was insignificant. The finding from Botswana may be influenced by the relationship the Government of Botswana has with its citizens. However, uncertainty avoidance as a moderating factor was found to be insignificant across all cases. The finding supported the results from the qualitative study.

The BI Model:

H₄: *The citizens' attitudes (ATT) will have a positive significant influence on behavioural Intention (BI) to use e-Government services*

H₅: *The citizens' social influence (SI) has a moderating effect on the association between attitudes and behavioural intention to use e-Government services*

H₁₃: *The citizens' trust in e-Government (TieG) has a significant and positive influence on their intentions to use e-Government services*

H_{14a}: *The Technical Support (TS) has a significant and positive influence e on the citizens' intentions to use e-Government services*

H_{14b}: *The availability of e_Offices has a significant and positive influence e on the citizens' intentions to use e-Government services*

H_{14c}: *The technical Skills and Resource ownership (TSkills_RsrcOwnership) has a significant and positive influence e on the citizens' intentions to use e-Government services*

Unexpectedly, Zimbabwe participants did not find social influence significant as a covariate despite being the case that derived the factor. It is understandable give that the participants draw for the qualitative study were not the same that participated in the quantitative study. Regardless of this, Venkatesh *et al.* (2003) found social influence influencing intentions in mandatory situations as they face the pressure from the government to use the services. Similarly Gupta, Dasgupta and Gupta (2008) found social Influence significant on intentions. However, all the other cases found social influence significant as a covariate. However, it is important to note that mandatoriness to use e-Services can be effective if those being mandated have the intermediaries to use. As a moderating factor, social Influence was unanimously found to be insignificant.

As shown in Table 6-41, the technical support was not found to be influential on intentions both in individual and when countries are taken together. Give the rise status of (e)-literacy, internet and mobile penetration in the knowledge era, it takes the clarity of instructions and steps of

usage for one to use the e-services. Once the design of the services is needs and human based there is hardly the need for technical support at the level of the demand side. .

The fitted Model

The results indicated the variance in perceptions of e-Government adoption per country and collectively as SADC member states. It should be noted that some of the factors cut across countries leading to their acceptance as a region. Some are influential at the country level but not when the countries are taken as a group. The results do reflect that the country characteristics are not homogenous. Each country has its own peculiarities that make it stand out uniquely as a country.

Figure 7-2: The fitted Model

The homogeneity of SADC member states is hinged on the socio-technical characteristics that the member states share. The inadequate ICT infrastructure, telecommunication networks, lack of skilled labour, continued power outages, low economic development; low literacy; lack of confidence in the existing solutions; and lack of native language options (Rorissa and Demissie, 2010; Asogwa, 2012; Mtingwi and Belle, 2012; Bwalya, Du Plessis and Rensleigh, 2014) are amongst factors that bring them together. However, peculiar to each of the SADC countries is

the cultural sensitivity and context which are essential to the e-Government launch and adoption.

The SEM results were a consequence of the five sub-models tested simultaneously, the resulting fitted model is shown in Figure 7-2. The red font shows the paths that were not supported in SEM. The fitted model used the data collected from all the sampled case countries. This meant that the perceptions or meanings that the participants held for their individual countries were moderated to represent a common view of the phenomenon under investigation. As such, the model represents the common perceptual view for the participating countries as representatives of the SADC member states. For a specific country representation of the model, the individual country path results would be represented instead.

RQ4: How do the participants' perceptions of e-Government factors differ by country in SADC?

Table 6-40 shows that the effect of trust in e-Government (TieG) on attitudes (ATT) and social Influence of Behavioural Intention (BI) were found to be stronger in Botswana. Similarly, the effect of perceived value (PV) and perceived ability to use (PATU) on attitude were individually established to be stronger in Zimbabwe than in Botswana. While SI was stronger in Botswana as a covariate with other predictors on BI, in Zimbabwe it was stronger as a moderating variable (SI_x_ATT). The finding suggests that the differences are mainly centred on the attitude and behavioural intention models while the models remain the same in the other three sub models.

7.5 E-Government Adoption Framework for SADC

RQ4: How can the e-Government implementation and adoption be enhanced in the region?

Based on the findings of research questions 1, 2, 3, and 4, and the review of the extant literature this section communicates the framework that is aimed at promoting an enhanced implementation and adoption of e-Government in SADC countries. As can be visualized in Figure 7-2, the framework is two phased: the pre-launch and post-launch phases. The upper part is for the pre-launch and it communicates the activities that need to be carried out prior to the actual launch. The derived theory is descriptive and developed from the participants story lines of the meanings they held about e-Government in the qualitative study. As such the framework is built from the contextual factors.

As one of the findings in the study, was the low level of awareness or its lack of. However, Susanto and Goodwin (2010) argued that where there is an insufficiency of awareness other means to encourage it should be sought. As a result, there is a need to increase the effort of raising awareness guided by the awareness strategy.

Figure 7-3: Contextual Framework for e-Government Adoption in the SADC

The components of the framework are explained in Table 7-1.

Table 7-1: Elements of the framework (Descriptive theory)

PHASE	ELEMENT	SUB ELEMENT	DESCRIPTION
PRE-LAUNCH	e-Government strategy	Best Practices	Benchmarking with the surrounding countries as a learning point. The SADC countries are at this stage expected to take along knowledge on how the processes used in those Governments could be used in transforming their own.
		National Government Strategy and ICT policy	Each country is expected to have a national strategy that will be used to drive the e-Government agenda. The strategy should be aligned to the country ICT policy.
		Local/sectorial strategies	The local e-Government strategy should be derived from the national strategy to address the local /sectorial contexts. Local governments should find ways of engaging the citizenry to reduce the power distance and to enhance the sense of ownership of the e-Government decisions and solutions.

	Understanding the problem space	Translation Process	Understanding the present situation of e-Government by giving the actors voices through the four moments of translation (Problematization, Intéressement, enrolment, and mobilisation).
		Context	To provide the successful solutions the context under which the e-Government service is to be used should be considered otherwise the design-reality gaps will be widened.
		Problem Space	In understanding the context and engagement of all stakeholders, the problem at hand is then identified and understood.
	Feasibility Study	Needs Assessment	The feasibility study should be carried out focusing on the needs of the citizenry, economic status of the country and the technical feasibility which will guide decisions on the solution being sought.
		Economic Feasibility Study	
		Technical Feasibility Study	
	Stakeholder Involvement	Strategies for citizen involvement and participation	Strategies for involving citizenry should be defined to enhance the sense of ownership of e-Services by the citizens. It will be easier to convince them to use the e-services once they feel they contributed to the birth of the e-services.
		Innovation	As the stakeholders are involved, what is sought are a creative and innovative solutions that will help address the existing problem realities. One of the positives of design thinking is that its emphasis is on experiential innovation that balances the technical and human dimensions.
		Opportunities	stakeholder involvement opens opportunities for participation, solution brainstorming, enhances the likelihood of solution acceptance ad usage
			Design thinking
POST LAUNCH	Awareness Strategies		The citizenry has different needs and preferences on how to access the e-Government content. Hence an inclusive awareness strategy that will cater to the visual, auditory, tactile, and those that need face to face sessions. The strategies should include promotional, demonstrations, education, and training, follow up, and vicarious awareness with user-generated content (UGC)
	Skills development		Undoubtedly, citizens are at varying levels of technology literacy and abilities. As they encounter their social world, these gaps can be reduced through scaffolding by those that they hold close in their life including family, friends, and peers. By an appropriate selection of awareness strategies such as education and training, skills can be developed.

	Partnerships with Libraries	These can be established to boost skills development, and e-Government awareness. The lack of motivation to access e-Government websites owes to the associated cost, hence partnerships with libraries to give free access to Wi-Fi are important. However strategies of funding must be put in place. This also links with economic feasibility.
	Design thinking	The design thinking process will help bring together the pre-launch activities, allowing for divergent perspectives to converge to solutions that will close the design-reality gap and address the human needs. The e-participation of stakeholders in making designerly decisions is key.

The arrows in the framework show that the phases are interrelated, and the process is a continuous cycle.

7.6 Chapter summary

The chapter discussed how the study responded to each of the research questions. In doing so, the findings from the qualitative and quantitative study were woven together to consolidate the findings of the two approaches used. Based on the integrated solution, a contextual framework was arrived at, presented and explained. The next chapter concludes, recommends, and shares limitations of the study based on findings discussed in this chapter.

8 CONCLUSIONS, IMPLICATIONS, AND LIMITATIONS

8.1 Introduction

This penultimate chapter presents the conclusions of the study based on the results of the data analysis process and consequently their evaluation against the objectives of the study and the proposed e-Government Framework

8.2 Research Aim and Objectives restated

The study aimed at investigating factors that affect e-Government adoption and pursued the possibilities of increasing e-Government adoption in the SADC.

Research Objectives

To achieve the aim, the objectives of the study were set out to:

- i. Investigate the dynamic interaction of human and non- human e-Government actors in the SADC to inform opportunities that promote the adoption of e-Government in SADC
- ii. Develop a SADC e-Government framework that takes into cognisance the technical, context, social, cultural dimensions and multiplicity of stakeholders involved.

The motivation behind the study was the continued low levels of e-Government adoption in developing countries despite a wealth of research that has garnered the challenges that the countries face in the phenomenon. The study then sought to understand the trajectory of e-Government in the SADC by giving the voice to the human and non-human actors. It is against this background that three theoretical perspectives were used namely: Actor-Network Theory, Technology Acceptance and Use Model, and Innovation Translation. To address the classic findings by Heeks that the failure of the phenomenon under investigation in developing countries owes to the design-reality gap, design thinking was added in the mix.

Instead of addressing the extreme on a continuum of perspectives, the study sought to address the middle ground: socio-technical. To this effect, a mixed method approach was used where the design was exploratory. The ANT was used as ontology to analyse the qualitative study results. From the results, factors affecting the e-Government adoption were derived and were incorporated in the quantitative study. The relationship amongst these variables was explored statistically using SPSS version 21 with AMOS, F. Hayes macro, and the Interaction plotter tool. SPSS was used for data preparation to test the reliability of constructs, descriptive statistics, scale validity, assumptions, regression analysis, and moderation variables. AMOS was used for

structural equation modeling to validate the model. The latter two were mainly used for assessing the effects of the moderating factors. Chapter 7 amplified these in detail.

8.3 Conclusions

Objective i) and ii) were achieved using the research questions 1, 2, 3 and 4. In analysing the qualitative data, it was found that the success of the e-Government adoption did not depend only on the citizenry as users of the e-Government systems and consumers of their services. By using the actor-network theory, it was established that we got a deeper understanding of the phenomenon as opposed to identifying the challenges and addressing them out of context. For example, identification of a challenge such as lack of awareness and resolving it with increasing awareness campaigns may not be viable. However, using the awareness strategies directed at solving the awareness problem at hand would help increase awareness of e-government amongst the citizens. In the study, the ANT has its arguments hinged on the translation process. The process helped to understand that what makes the users adopt an e-government service is because the proposed solution resonated with the problem at hand and they agree to that. As a result, in the study, there has been an inclination to adopting some services and not others.

In terms of lack of awareness, we conclude that users cannot use services that they are not aware of. In raising the awareness, effort should not be put based on quantity. Awareness sources should address a mix of awareness strategies as their intent is to achieve different objectives. Most of the awareness which we found in the study was mostly to publicize the services. Taking into consideration that being aware does not translate to use, other factors such as hands on workshops are needed to create value in use. Not everyone has these skills. Improvement of the services does not only focus on the technical functionalities but on addressing the human needs. It is in this vein that the participants had raised concern over the power distance that exists in countries that makes them not to contribute to the feedback on the services. Giving feedback or evaluation of e-services that one has accessed is one way of participating in the continuous development and refinement of the very services. Accepting feedback from the citizenry as users of the e-Government services is a form of incorporating their views. The lack of its acceptance distances the citizenry from the adoption path for the solution needs to be consistent with the needs of the clientele.

Also, the issue of power distance emanates from the fact that e-Government services at the local government are often neglected. If the local or sectorial departments focus on engaging with the citizenry in e-Government, adoption would certainly increase as the citizens would appreciate that they have a new role in co-creation of decisions. There is a need for synergy

between the demand side and supply sides to design solutions that are successfully adopted by all. The synergies in question could be brought to the table by incorporating the design thinking in e-Government.

It is interesting to note that the ownership of resources by the citizenry is awesome. Some have multiple ownerships. The cause of the decline in direct ownership of the desktop computers and the landline telephones whilst the smartphones, cell phone and iPad ownership increased owed to the preference of convenience of mobility over other factors such as cost. The mobile telephony is becoming the new way of communicating and interacting across communities (Law, 2009; Kyem, 2016) as evidenced by the lowly owned desktop computers and landlines phones amongst participants. The contemporary population prefers to interact 'on the go'. Also, amongst the participants were those that did not have direct ownership or direct access to institutionally owned e-intermediaries because of lack of the skill that is required to interact with the technology. According to Wilson and Heeks (2000) in Heeks (2002a) as part of the citizen folk, such citizens are also entitled to enjoy the benefits of e-Government through re-intermediation, which essentially entails the introduction of a human intermediary (intelligent intermediary) to help in creating the value of the e-service. Value in an e-service is created when the user interacts with the system/technology that mediates the service. In the case of re-intermediation, the human comes back in the picture to create the value on behalf of the one receiving the service. Similarly, the need for the human intermediary from the quantitative study echoes the view expressed by participants in the qualitative study.

The study findings on e-intermediaries for e-Government consolidate the findings of the Pyramid Research (2000) in (Heeks, 2002a) who posited that in Africa e-intermediaries direct ownership will be applicable to the minority for a foreseeable future. It is nearly a decade and a half year ago since the Pyramid Research findings were communicated by the scholars. At the time ICT penetration in Africa was at its nascent stages. The dynamic on going mobile penetration has influenced the change to the existing findings. In the wake of e-Government, the citizens are presented with an innovative way of accessing government services and interacting with the government. The e-intermediaries play an important role in the e-Government ecosystem. On the other hand, governments may need to de-culture from the traditional approaches to being inclusive. An inclusive government need to recognise that citizens are a people with different capabilities in terms of using the e-Government services, hence, the need to have human intermediaries to assist value creation on behalf of those with lack of e-literacy skills; citizens are a people at different levels of technophobia, some are early and some are late adopters of technology; some have e-literacy skills some do not; some have knowledge and education on e-Government some do not; and some are quick to trust because of exposure but for some it

takes time. The antidote to the e-Government challenges that individual countries are facing may be hinged on developing technology solutions approached from a design thinking perspective to be able to develop innovative and creative solutions that take into consideration the human needs. In addition, there is need for rethinking the awareness strategies to those that will enhance the citizens' knowledge and familiarisation with e-Government concepts to enhance e-Government adoption.

8.4 Implications

The study is expected to have implications on the implementation of e-Government services and the related areas such as:

Policy: The current research findings are expected to contribute in influencing policy and decision making in the adoption of e-Government projects in the SADC. The study sought to raise awareness amongst the governments in developing countries of the need to desist from just transferring knowledge on how things are done in developed countries, but instead, take along knowledge on how the processes used in those Governments in transforming their own. The expectation could be achieved through presentations of the findings in e-Government workshops and talks involving the concerned stakeholders.

E-Government research: The novelty of the study was in the mix of the underpinning theories that were used. The study is expected to contribute to the body of knowledge by being an addition to the Actor-Network Theory, the Technology Acceptance Model, and Design thinking literature. The mix will benefit the researchers in providing the theoretical rigor to strengthen the ontological and epistemological stances that can be used to aid explanation and promotion of understanding of the e-Government phenomenon. The mix is expected to aid governments to provide services that not just meet user but human needs and afford the governments an opportunity to achieve their primary goal: to serve the people. The study also sought to reduce the dearth of e-government studies in the region by being an addition to the e-Government literature in Zimbabwe and equally in the SADC.

The adoption of e-government services: Multiple stakeholder involvements including the citizenry are key in e-Government. Affording stakeholders an opportunity to share their experiences and expectations increases their sense of ownership of the solutions, thereby embracing their existence. For the supply side, it promotes understanding of the context of the problem and to design solutions that are effective.

E-government marketing team: Consideration of the inclusive marketing strategies to raise awareness should go a long way in addressing the needs of the citizenry be it publicity, training or it follows up training. The varying awareness sources that have been identified in the study could help strengthen the efforts of the team. Investing in target marketing may increase adoption as it addresses challenges of those with a lack of digital skills to create value. Investing in User-generated Content as a marketing strategy may increase awareness faster.

Website Developers: The use of Chatbots in the e-Government website may allow for the capturing of visitors details and later use them for email marketing. Also, they help the user in getting what they are looking for quicker before they are frustrated by not finding what they are looking for. Besides, if they do not find what they are looking for but get help on time, it may increase repeat visits.

8.5 Limitation(s) of the Study

Firstly, the SADC region is composed of fifteen-member states but only a few were included in the study. The choice of participating countries was driven by the proximity of the researcher to the participating countries for the purposes of collecting data. In as much as it is possible to make the instruments available online to all the SADC countries, it was the actual usage of e-services that was a bone of contention in the study. To this effect, physical visits to these countries were made only for Zimbabwe and Botswana for data collection.

Secondly, from the on-set, the study speculated that a holistic approach would go a long way in understanding the interplay of the two perspectives (supply side and demand side) towards the enhancement of the e-Government adoption levels. However, the researcher could not get the responses from the supply side to which the focus then shifted to the demand side only. The responses from the supply side will be pursued in the future and presented through publications.

8.6 Future research

This current study established the existence of the e-Government concept gap in Zimbabwe. As a follow up, an investigation into the extent to which the familiarity with e-Government concepts influences e-Government adoption by the demand side is in progress. It is also suggested and recommended that future studies conduct research on e-Government that captures the views of both the demand and supply sides in the same research.

8.7 Chapter Summary

The chapter concludes the chapter bringing to fore the pointers drawn from the study analysis to illuminate the e-Government adoption trajectory. In addition, the implications and limitations of the study are communicated. The next chapter evaluates the quality of the study.

9 EVALUATION OF THE STUDY

9.1 Introduction

The evaluation of the entire research with a focus on how it contributes to the body of knowledge is discussed.

9.2 Evaluation of the quality of the study

The criteria of evaluating the generated theory include three broad categories: quality and rigour of the research; quality of the generated theory; and principles for enhancing the qualitative aspects of the study. These are discussed in the following sections.

9.2.1 Quality and rigour of the study

Gasson (2003) argues that the quality and rigour criteria in research are closely knit to the principal worldviews: positivist or interpretivist. The scholar further submits that the two worldviews use different criteria because of their incommensurability. The proposed four aspects of quality and rigour in a rationalist worldview are internal validity, external validity, reliability and objectivity which are translated to their naturalistic counterparts in determining trustworthiness (Guba, 1981). Mapping the criteria down to the methodologies, Mavetera (2011) posits that the quality and rigour criteria of qualitative research cannot be used for quantitative research. As such these criteria are presented separately as follows:

Objectivity vs. Confirmability

The issue of concern in the objectivity/ confirmability criterion is the representativeness of findings, the extent to which findings are free from researcher bias (Kaplan & Maxwell, 1994; Gasson, 2003b; Mavetera, 2011). Objectivity: In a positivist worldview, the epistemic assumption is that truth can be found independently of the researcher. In this regard, the tables of raw data and data reflecting statistical relations of variables with explanations of how results were interpreted were amplified in the previous chapters.

Confirmability: This is a quality criteria used in qualitative research. Gasson (2003, p. 90); Lincoln and Guba (1981, as cited in Miles & Huberman, 1994) argue that confirmability is the extent to which “conclusions depend on subjects and conditions of the study, rather than the researcher.” The researcher collects, analyses, and presents the findings as impartially as possible by demonstrating self-awareness through making assumptions explicit, where they come from, and justification of new conceptualisations. As explained in the sampling procedures, data was gathered from a diverse stakeholder group to clearly reveal the picture of

inquiry. The plurality of participant groups involved in data collection and sources of data collection methods helped in triangulation (Guba, 1981).

Reliability vs. Dependability/Auditability

In quantitative studies, reliability is the extent to which the findings can be replicated independent of context, time or researcher (Gasson, 2003b, p. 90; Yin, 2009, p. 45). As long as there is an audit trail to detail what was done, quantitative studies have statistical procedures that could be replicated for the re-analysis of the same data. Guba (1981) posits that the ontological assumption that there is a single truth to which the inquiry converges enforces some level of consistency as any shifts can then be treated as error amongst rationalist enquirers.

In qualitative studies, dependability/auditability is the extent to which a study process is consistent and reasonably stable over time and between researchers (Gasson, 2003b, p. 90; Yin, 2009, p. 45). The case study protocol included in the study assisted in achieving dependability/auditability as it explained the various procedures of the study including sampling, data collection, data analysis, integration, and reporting. This technique ensures consistency if the study was to be carried out again. Also, the stability of findings could be achieved by other researchers as they would have access to the procedures that led to the ultimate findings presented and replicate the procedures with other participants. In both studies, the audit trails of the audio records, categories and their relationships; interview interactions; raw data; detailed data collection and analysis procedures could be retained and shared when need arises for reanalysis provided the ethical considerations documented in the study are exercised. The updated case study protocol detailing the study procedures, presentation of evidence, findings, conclusions, and their connections to the existing related e-Government literature is attached and archived in the appendices section.

Internal validity vs. internal consistency

Internal validity is the extent to which a “statistically significant relationship is established to demonstrate that certain conditions are associated with other conditions” (Gasson, 2003b, p. 90). To establish the stability of measures studied across items, the Cronbach’s Alpha test was used. Where the alpha coefficient was less than 0.7 (0.7 is generally considered as the acceptable level) instruments were modified and subjected to the same test again. In a similar vein, a high degree of stability translates into a high degree of reliability and consequently demonstrates repeatability.

Internal consistency: This measures the extent to which the research is credible and consistent to the intended audience, and authentic (“findings should be related to significant elements in the research context/situation”) (Gasson, 2003b, p. 90). Guba (1981) posit that credibility could be achieved through member checks in two ways: firstly, data and verification or extending interpretations as they are derived from the participants; secondly, testing the overall report with the participants at the end of the study. The truth value of multiple realities in the participants’ minds was compared with data from other inductive sources and extant literature. Guba (1981) also argues that it is necessary to check every datum and interpretations with all the others for contradictions, structural corroborations, and coherence. As constructs and relationships of the developed theory are verified, replications of these in different situations ground their credibility. In addition, the comparison of the emergent theory with the existing literature (both confirming and conflicting with the theory) was done to ensure internal consistency and disconfirmations of relationships were further probed (Eisenhardt, 1989). The scholar also posits that discovering the underlying theoretical reasons for why relationships and making comparisons of the emergent theory with extant literature enhance internal consistency.

As an authenticity criterion, fairness is the extent to which the all participant views, perspectives or beliefs are reflected in the text. The criterion addresses issues of marginalization in favour of inclusion and a balance of voices (Denzin et al.,1994). E-government as a phenomenon was never meant to be essentialist. It is never meant to discriminate and demonstrate preference of some citizens over others. It is in this regard that the study listens to the voices of heterogeneous stakeholder groups.

External Validity/Generalizability vs. Transferability

The extent to which research findings and conclusions have implications for other studies and other situations earns it great value (Gasson, 2003b, p. 90; Yin, 2011, p. 99). In quantitative studies, generalizations are statistical as they are drawn from the relationship between the sample and the population sizes (Yin, 2009, pp. 15,38-39). However, considering the nature of the study, it becomes exceedingly difficult to say a case (in this study a country such as Zimbabwe) is representative of the SADC countries. In as much as the selected cases are multiple, it still poses a problem because no one country is ever exactly the same as the other. They have a different culture, population sizes, economic conditions, literacy levels, technology advancement and infrastructure, that even the countries not selected in this study could still be unrepresented. In a similar argument, Stake, 1978 (p. 7) suggests that the cases are often thought of as a constituent member of the target population, at times the case is a person, an enterprise, or a country which is what makes case studies less generalizable as the cases poorly represent the whole population. According to Yin (2009), cases are not sample units,

they represent experiments and follow ‘a replication logic’. However, Yin (2009), further argues that in case of studies, the generalization should be analytic. In this study a multi-case approach was adopted, hence the aspect of replication of the findings in the cross-case analysis was projected to allow for the analytic generalizability of the findings and development of theory (Guba, 1981; Yin, 2011). The scholar further states that such a study does not seek generalisations across other population countries pursuing a similar phenomenon; rather it seeks to develop and discuss how such findings might have implications for an improved understanding of particular concepts in other contexts and environs (Yin, 2011, p. 100).

Thick descriptions were used in the case study protocol so that other researchers in different contexts could appropriately assess the extent of transferability to their own contexts as suggested by Kaplan and Maxwell (1994). As the case study is a multi-case, it implies efforts of replication and robustness from multiple empirical case evidence are in place. However, areas that need further replication are submitted as a part of recommendations for the other stakeholders.

Table 9-1 underscores the four aspects of quality and rigour in rationalist worldview (internal validity, external validity, reliability and objectivity)

Table 9-1: Quality and rigour for positivist and interpretive worldviews

<i>Issue of Concern</i>	Positivist Worldview	Interpretive Worldview
<i>Representativeness of findings</i>	Objectivity: findings are free from researcher bias.	Confirmability: conclusions depend on subjects and conditions of the study, rather than the researcher.
<i>Reproducibility of findings</i>	Reliability: the study findings can be replicated, independently of context, time or researcher.	Dependability/Auditability: the study process is consistent and reasonably stable over time and between researchers.
<i>Rigor of method</i>	Internal validity: a statistically-significant relationship is established, to demonstrate that certain conditions are associated with other conditions, often by "triangulation" of findings.	Internal consistency: the research findings are credible and consistent, to the people we study and to our readers. For authenticity, our findings should be related to significant elements in the research context/situation.
<i>Generalizability of findings.</i>	External validity: the researcher establishes a domain in which findings are generalizable.	Transferability: how far can the findings/conclusions be transferred to other contexts and how do they help to derive useful theories?

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rice: Gasson (2003b, p. 90)

9.2.2 Evaluation of the quality of the generated theory

- i. Concept Development:**
 - a. Parsimony: Pfeiffer,(1982) as cited in Eisenhardt (1989) submits that single case studies usually generate complicated theory with more detail unlike in multi-case

studies where there are more relationships and replications across cases. Hence, the theory should fully exploit the available evidence.

- b. Logical Coherence: Pfeiffer(1982, as cited in Eisenhardt, 1989) argues that the process includes the assessment of “fit” of data integration. The fit of data integration entails the assessment of coherence of the qualitative and quantitative findings, i.e. whether they confirm, expand or are in discordance with each other (Fetters, Curry & Creswell, 2013).
- ii. Theory should unify various, previous unrelated problems or concepts (Entrona,1992, as cited in Mavetera, 2011). Theory building in case studies should not only include common features of cases, but the inclusion of unique features of each case also makes it adequate. The unique features give guidance on where the theory can grow (Stiles, 2007).
- iii. Adequacy of the research process: The theory should show the strength of the method that generated and elaborated the theory. *The* sampling, data collection and analytical procedures should fit with the theory (Eisenhardt, 1989; Corbin & Strauss, 1990).
- iv. Evidence grounding the theory: *The* inductive data and information, and construct evidence should have a good fit with the theory. Evidence needs to be availed for the readers to conduct their own assessment of the fit of data with the theory (Eisenhardt, 1989; Corbin & Strauss, 1990). The shared evidence should include the major themes; how or what led to their selection; relationships of themes and their subthemes; discrepancies and how they were resolved (Corbin & Strauss, 1990).
- v. Plausibility and value theory: In theory building, it is important that the theory generates new or frame-breaking insights. If the theory is less ambitious and simply replicates past theory then the theory is modest (Eisenhardt, 1989; Corbin & Strauss, 1990). Additionally, new insights and perspectives should “lead to a new understanding of the problem under investigation” (Introna, 1992, as cited in Mavetera, 2011, p. 88). It is important to know what the study does for the researched and the researchers and participants (Miles & Huberman, 1994, p. 280).

9.2.3 Principles of interpretive research

The pragmatist paradigm that the study adopted makes Klein and Myers’s principles applicable and valuable to the interpretive component of the study. Klein and Myers (1999) posit that the seven principles that they propose are applicable to any interpretive research of a hermeneutic nature but are not obligatory. As such, only the ones that were considered in this research are discussed below.

The fundamental principle of the hermeneutic cycle

The hermeneutic cycle principle is hinged on the iterative nature of interpretive research. The principle is evident throughout the research process as inquirers make constant connections to and reflections on the individual chapters, research questions, research procedures and their relationship as a whole in the generation of theory in case study research. More so, the process was more evident in the development of the code book and tying the data to it. The three stages of coding reflect the iteration between parts (categories and subcategories generation) and the whole (the identification of a "core category and establishing and refining categories and their relationship to the core category of the phenomenon). In a similar vein, Mavetera (2011) underscores that the principle is in use when inquirers gather evidence from single cases and knit them together to make a holistic understanding of the whole. In essence, according to Klein and Myers (1999) "... the hermeneutic cycle suggests that we come to understand a complex whole from preconceptions about the meanings of its parts and their interrelationships."

The principle of contextualization

The contextualization principle requires that the inquirers present the phenomenon in its social and historical situation for the intended audience to understand how it has emerged (Klein & Myers, 1999, p. 73).

The principle of interaction between the researcher and the participants

The principle requires that the inquirers understand the participants as co-creators of meanings in the data collection process (Klein & Myers, 1999).

The principle of abstraction and generalization

The principle reinforces the extent of transferability in case studies departing from the position by Yin (2009) that cases are not to be treated as 'samples of cases.' Case studies have an emphasis on the context in which the phenomenon occurs (Eisenhardt & Graebner, 2007, p. 25) and generality is carried by the theory (Stiles, 2007).

The principle of dialogical reasoning

The hermeneutic rule focuses on the conflict between the inquirer's prior knowledge of the guiding lenses of the research design and the data that emerges through the research process (Klein & Myers, 1999, p. 76).

The principle of multiple interpretations

“The principle requires the researcher to examine the influences that the social context has upon actions under study by seeking out and documenting multiple viewpoints along with the reasons for them” (Klein & Myers, 1999, p. 77).

The principle of suspicion

The principle requires that the inquirers be in a position to identify any forms of systematic biases or distortions in the inductive data from participants (Klein & Myers, 1999).

9.3 Chapter Summary and study conclusion

The chapter evaluated the quality of the study with respect to the procedure that was followed in conducting the study. Consequently, an e-Government Framework (see Table 7-2 and Figure 7-2) validated in the SADC is presented as the ultimate tangible contribution to the frontiers of knowledge.

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ANNEXURE A: ETHICS CERTIFICATE

NORTH-WEST UNIVERSITY
YUNIBESITHI YA BOKONE-BOPHIRIMA
NOORDWES-UNIVERSITEIT

Private Bag X8001, Potchefstroom,
South Africa, 2520

Tel: (018) 299-4900
Fax: (018) 299-4910
Web: <http://www.nwu.ac.za>

Institutional Research Ethics Regulatory Committee
Tel: +27 18 299 4849
Email: Ethics@nwu.ac.za

ETHICS APPROVAL CERTIFICATE OF PROJECT

Based on approval by the Human Sciences Research Ethics Committee (HSREC) on 23/08/2016, the North-West University Institutional Research Ethics Regulatory Committee (NWU-IRERC) hereby approves your project as indicated below. This implies that the NWU-IRERC grants its permission that, provided the special conditions specified below are met and pending any other authorisation that may be necessary, the project may be initiated, using the ethics number below.

Project title: A contextual framework for e-government implementation in the SADC region: A case of Zimbabwe.	
Project Leader/Supervisor: Prof N Mavetela & Dr M Jantjies.	
Student: T Chikerema	
Ethics number:	N W U - 0 9 4 0 5 - 1 6 - A 9
	<small>(Ethics: N = Conservatory N = Postdoctoral, P = Postgraduate, A = Application)</small>
Application Type: PhD Application	
Commencement date: 2016-08-18	Expiry date: 2019-08-18
Risk:	N/A

Special conditions of the approval (if applicable):

- + Translation of the informed consent document to the languages applicable to the study participants should be submitted to the HRREC (if applicable).
- + Any research at governmental or private institutions, permission must still be obtained from relevant authorities and provided to the HRREC. Ethics approval is required BEFORE approval can be obtained from these authorities.

<p>General conditions:</p> <p>While this ethics approval is subject to all declarations, undertakings and agreements incorporated and signed in the application form, please note the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> + The project leader (principle investigator) must report in the prescribed format to the NWU-IRERC via HRREC: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - annually (or as otherwise requested) on the progress of the project, and upon completion of the project - without any delay in case of any adverse event (or any matter that interrupts sound ethical principles) during the course of the project. - Annually a number of projects may be randomly selected for an external audit. + The approval applies strictly to the protocol as stipulated in the application form. Would any changes to the protocol be deemed necessary during the course of the project, the project leader must apply for approval of these changes at the HRREC. Would there be deviations from the project protocol without the necessary approval of such changes, the ethics approval is immediately and automatically forfeited. + The date of approval indicates the first date that the project may be started. Would the project have to continue after the expiry date, a new application must be made to the NWU-IRERC via HRREC and new approval received before or on the expiry date. + In the interest of ethical responsibility the NWU-IRERC and HRREC retains the right to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - request access to any information or data at any time during the course or after completion of the project; - to ask further questions, seek additional information, require further modification or monitor the conduct of your research or the informed consent process. - withdraw or postpone approval if: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - any unethical principles or practices of the project are revealed or suspected, - it becomes apparent that any relevant information was withheld from the HRREC or that information has been false or misrepresented, - the required annual report and reporting of adverse events was not done timely and accurately, - new institutional rules, national legislation or international conventions deem it necessary. + HRREC can be contacted for further information via Linda.DuPlessis@nwu.ac.za or 018 289 2873.

The IRERC would like to remain at your service as academic and researcher, and wishes you well with your project. Please do not hesitate to contact the IRERC or HRREC for any further enquiries or requests for assistance.

Yours sincerely

Prof LA Du Plessis
Digitally signed by Prof LA Du Plessis
Date: 2016.09.27 14:35:04 +02'00'

Prof Linda du Plessis
Chair NWU Institutional Research Ethics Regulatory Committee (IRERC)

ANNEXURE B: INVITATION TO PARTICIPATE IN THE RESEARCH

Dear

As a resident/citizen/tourist/immigrant/visitor / [other] in<country>....., you are receiving this email/letter because you are thought of as a prospective participant in the study entitled:

“A contextual framework for e-Government implementation in the SADC region: A case of Zimbabwe”.

The study is **conducted** by Teresa Chikerema a PhD student at North West University, Mafikeng campus. You are cordially invited to participate in an interview conducted by the above-mentioned student for the fulfillment of her doctoral studies. The purpose of the study is to develop an in-depth understanding of e-Government in the context of the Southern African Development Community (SADC). Consequently, the study intends to establish how its findings from SADC case countries have implications for the enhancement of e-Government adoption in the region.

Participation in this study will require 30 minutes of your time at most. The interview will be audiotaped with your permission. A telephonic follow up will be made later prior to the analysis of the collected data to check if any of your feelings have changed.

If you are interested in participating, please respond to this email. Attached is a consent form that you need to read and understand prior to signing it. Endorsing your signature would mean you have agreed to participate.

Please contact me with any arising questions. Thank you in advance.

Teresa Chikerema

Signature here

(Student number: 2639515).

ANNEXURE C: INFORMATION SHEET

Title of the research: A contextual framework for e-Government implementation in the SADC region: A case of Zimbabwe

Name and Position of the researcher: Teresa Chikerema, Final Year PHD student, Department of Decision Sciences and information systems, North West University, South Africa

Purpose of the study: *The purpose of the study is to develop an in-depth understanding of e-Government in the context of the Southern African Development Community (SADC). Consequently, the study intends to establish how its findings have implications for the enhancement of e-Government adoption in the SADC with a special mention of Zimbabwe.*

Benefits of participation: *The expected benefit of your participation is that, agreeing to participate in this research means that you are making your voice heard through this study as a user of e-Government services in relation to your expectations and experiences or as a provider of e-services. The challenges and perceived benefits of e-Government are not new per se. Hence you are making an effective action for a recurring problem.
In turn, the findings of this research are expected to inform decision and policy making on the implementation of the e-Government.*

Confidentiality *None of the demographic or sensitive information that you will disclose in this study will be used for other purposes or revealed in the resulting documentation beyond the data collection stage.*

Anonymity *Whenever there is a need to use a name(s) in the findings, pseudo names will be used instead*

Withdrawal from Participation: *You can withdraw at any point of data collection if you feel uncomfortable. Please note that none of your personal details or the data you provide for this study will be used for other purposes.*

Incentives for Participation: *Participation in the study is on voluntary basis, no incentives will be provided.*

Procedure: *You are free to ask any questions, if you have any.
If you do not have any questions, you are requested to sign a consent form attached to this information sheet as a confirmation that the purpose of the study and how the data will be used has been explained to you. If you are happy with this, you can go ahead fill and sign the form.*

.....
Participant Signature

.....
Researcher Signature

ANNEXURE D: INTERVIEW CONSENT FORM

Title of the research: A contextual framework for e-Government implementation in the SADC region: A case of Zimbabwe

Name and Position of the researcher: Teresa Chikerema, PHD student, Department of Decision Sciences and information systems, North West University, South Africa

Please mark with a '✓' where appropriate

i.	I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet for the above study	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>
ii.	I understand that my participation is voluntary and free to withdraw at any time without penalty	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>
iii.	I have had an opportunity to ask questions pertaining to my participation in the study	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>
iv.	I agree to take part in the study	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>
v.	I agree with the interview being audio recorded NB: You are free to turn off the audio recorder at any point to keep something off the record	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>
vi.	I agree with the use of pseudonyms in any publication of the above-mentioned study	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>

.....
Participant Signature

.....
Interviewer Signature

ANNEXURE E: INTERVIEW PROTOCOL FOR THE DEMAND SIDE

Script prior to Interview and setting up the recorder

[2mins]

I would like to thank you for taking the time to participate in the data collection phase of the study entitled "A contextual framework for e-Government implementation in the SADC region: A case of Zimbabwe".

As mentioned in the information sheet and the invitation letter, the study seeks to develop an in-depth understanding of e-Government in the context of the Southern African Development Community (SADC) with a special mention of Zimbabwe. As such, our interview is aimed at eliciting the critical success factors in e-Government adoption: what works well or not for you in the entire process of e-Government through your experiences in using e-services provided by the government and its agencies. Consequently, the study intends to establish how its findings have implications for the enhancement of e-Government adoption in the SADC.

You completed a consent form prior to this meeting indicating that I have (do not have) the permission to audio record our interview session. Have you changed your mind in that regard?

Yes No

If no, thank you! Please remember that you are free to turn off the recorder at any point you feel the need to keep what you say off record. If yes, thank you! I will take brief notes of our conversation. The interview will take between at most thirty (30) minutes of your time.

Before we begin our interview, do you have any questions? [These are discussed if there are any]. Please feel free to ask any questions as they arise during our interview. Questions [if any] by the participant **[1min]**

Interview Question 1: Let's begin by discussing your background information: Tell me about your background

Follow up:

- i. Ask questions to elicit Age, level of education, languages, and profession
- ii. Basic literacy:
 - a. (If they cannot read nor write): Is there a member of your family who can read and write

[2mins]

Interview Question 2: Access to e-Intermediaries

[3 mins]

With the proliferation of the Internet and technology development, do you see yourself fitting in this digital era? How so?

Follow up:

- i. Do you own any of these: Cell phone/Laptop /Tablet/ iPad/ Desktop Computer etc.?
 - a. In person?
 - b. Family?
 - c. Work/school?
- ii. Does any of the devices you own connect to the Internet?
- iii. What do you often use these for?

Interview Question 3: Are you aware that there are some e-Government services that you can enjoy as a citizen/ immigrant/ resident /pensioner/ student/ tourist [Use the option that applies to the interviewee] and how did you come to know about them? **[2mins]**

follow up if the user is not aware:

You probably have used e-Government services or resources [e.g. bill payments through your mobile or internet-connected devices, online applications for government Scholarships, and accessing Government information electronically. *Shed some light by giving examples in case the interviewee is not aware that they fall under e-Government services*] for interacting with the government or government agencies such as municipalities, Banking institutions, tax and revenue authorities electronically. Are you aware of these? How did you come to know about them?

Interview Question 4: What are the diverse ways in which you use ICTs for e-Government purposes? How often?

[2mins]

Interview Question 5: What are preferences: online interactions with the government and its agencies or traditional face to face interactions with representatives? Why? **[2 mins]**

Interview Question 6: Please comment on your experiences, and expectations of using e-Government services. **[1 min]**

Follow Up:

- i. What draws you to understanding the context of and using the service? Are you satisfied using the service? Are your expectations being met? If not, which ones of your expectations are not being met?

Interview Question 7:

[4 mins]

- i. Which intermediaries do you often use to access e-Government services
- ii. How effective are the e-Government services or resources? Do they allow you to access the information you need or carry out the services as expected? Giving examples? Why or Why not?
- iii. What challenges have you faced, if any, to learn how to use the e-Government services or resources?
- iv. What kind of support do you get from the website/system/device (interface support) when using e-Governments services or resources to help you remember how to use the e-services? E.g. is there a menu from which you choose options? Is it easy to grasp the steps for future use?

Interview Question 8: Have you at any given point had an opportunity to be involved in the design of an e-Government service or resource interface? It could be your involvement in the elicitation of the needs of the public or testing a near complete or complete interface? **[3 mins]**

Interview Question 9: Giving feedback or an evaluation of the e-services that you have received is one way of participating in the continual development of the very services. So, tell me, have you had an opportunity to give feedback on an e-Government service? If yes, how? If not, what barriers did you face in giving the feedback? **[2 mins]**

THANK YOU FOR YOUR PARTICIPATION

ANNEXURE F: QUALITATIVE STUDY APPENDICES

The initial codes in the HU after the first Cycle coding of the pilot data

Code changes in the code network (Main Qualitative Study)

Document ID	Number of codes in the code network	Number of new codes in the codebook	Percentage increase
D1	18	18	100%
D2	53	35	66%
D3	60	7	12%
D4	65	5	8%
D5	70	5	7%
D6	75	5	7%
D7	88	13	15%
D8	99	11	11%
D9	112	13	12%

SRQ1: What are the experiences of citizenry usage of e-Government services?

ANNEXURE G: SURVEY PROTOCOL

Title of the research: A contextual framework for e-Government implementation in the SADC region: A case of Zimbabwe

Name and Position of the researcher: Teresa Chikerema, PhD student, Department of Decision Sciences and information systems, North West University, South Africa

The purpose of the study is to develop an in-depth understanding of e-Government in the context of the selected Southern African Development Community (SADC) member states. In addition, the study intends to establish how its findings have implications for the enhancement of e-Government adoption in the SADC. In consequence, a framework for e-Government in the SADC will be presented.

Participation: You are requested to participate in the study. *None of the demographic or sensitive information that you will disclose in the study will be used for other purposes or revealed in the resulting documentation beyond the data collection stage.*

Please mark with a '✓' where appropriate

vii.	I confirm that I have read and understood the purpose of the study	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>
viii.	I understand that my participation is voluntary	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>
ix.	I agree with the use of pseudonyms in any publication of the above-mentioned study	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>
x.	I agree to take part in the study	Yes	<input type="checkbox"/>	No	<input type="checkbox"/>

A: Demographic details

1. What is your gender?

- Male Female

2.

- | | | |
|---|---|--|
| <input type="radio"/> Angola
<input type="radio"/> Botswana
<input type="radio"/> Democratic Rep. of Congo
<input type="radio"/> Lesotho
<input type="radio"/> Madagascar
<input type="radio"/> Other _____ (Please specify) | What is your country of origin?
<input type="radio"/> Malawi
<input type="radio"/> Mauritius
<input type="radio"/> Mozambique
<input type="radio"/> Namibia
<input type="radio"/> Seychelles | <input type="radio"/> South Africa
<input type="radio"/> Swaziland
<input type="radio"/> United Rep. of Tanzania
<input type="radio"/> Zambia
<input type="radio"/> Zimbabwe |
|---|---|--|

2.

In which of the following countries are you located at the time of answering this Questionnaire?

- Botswana
 Namibia
 South Africa
 Zimbabwe

3.

Which category includes your age?

- 15-24 years
 25-34 years
 35-44years
 45-54 years
 55-66 years
 67 years or older

4.

What is the highest level of education you have completed?

- Secondary School or Less
 High School (e.g. Form 5, Form 6 or equivalent)
 College but no degree
 University (bachelor's degree or equivalent)
 University (Postgraduate degree)
 Other _____ (Please specify)

5.

Which of the following categories apply to your professional status?

- Student
 Teacher
 University/College lecturer
 Farmer
 E-Government project manager
 Developer
 Designer
 Librarian
 Government Employee
 Private sector employee

- Freelancer
- Unemployed
- Other _____ (Please specify)

6. In which of the following categories does your location fit in?

- Rural area
- Peri-urban
- Urban Area

B: e-Intermediaries, e-Government services, and usage status

7. Which of the following categories apply to you? (*Tick all that apply*)

e-Intermediary	Owned in person	Owned in the family at home	Owned at work/school	Accessed at the Internet Café
Cell-phone	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Smartphone	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Laptop	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
iPad	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Desktop Computer	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Telephone landline / extension	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	

- Other _____ (Please specify)

8. Which category would correctly rank your awareness of e-Government and its services? (*Please select only one option*)

- 1: Not at all aware
- 2: slightly aware
- 3: Somewhat aware
- 4: Moderately aware
- 5: extremely aware

9. Through which means did you become aware of the e-Government services provision? (*Please tick all that apply*)

- Government websites
- Social Influence (Family member(s), friends, peers, workmates, etc.)
- Print media such as physical newspapers or magazines
- Television
- Radio
- Billboard (traditional or digital)
- Customer Care service
- Pamphlets from Government offices
- Pamphlets accessible from public or state libraries
- SMS from government departments or its agencies
- Emails from government departments or its agencies
- Postal services (e.g. printed letter sent to your house)
- A telephone call from a government department or its agency

10. How often do you use the following services? (*Please choose one per row*)

e-Services	1 Never	2 Rarely	3 Periodically	4 Every-time
Internet Banking services (i.e. accessing banking services through a browser/ app that needs internet connection)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
mobile Banking services (i.e. accessing banking services through your mobile device without a need for internet connectivity)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e-Municipality services: online checking of and /or payment of water bills and debts	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
online checking and payment of electricity bill and/or debts	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

e-Health services (e.g. receiving SMS /emails/calls on information such as health bills, health bill payment, reminders on vaccination dates etc.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e-Education Services (e.g. Higher Education sponsorship, online applications, and admissions to institutions of learning, Fees payment)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e-Visa applications and online access to related information	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Receiving information on filing Tax returns, tax refunds etc. through email/SMS or accessing it through the government website	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e-financial transfers for government services such as customs and Excise services e.g. customs duty	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online taxpayer registration	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online submission of tax declarations	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online applications for employment in the government departments or their agencies	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online application of birth/ death certificates	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Real-time contact with government officials or departments via telephone, Skype calls etc.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
communicate with government officials or departments via chat rooms, blogs, media library, discussion forums, social media etc.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Informational services such as accessing information from government departments on their website, via social media including Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, YouTube etc.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Social Communication with friends and/relatives	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Research	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Reading Online newspapers	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online registration of animals and related services such as livestock transfer between farmers, relocation, and removals (death/slaughter)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

11.

Please rate the following statements to reflect the level of difficulty that you face when using e-Government services
(Please choose one per row)

Perceived Ability to Use (PATU) items	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
Using e-Government services will be easy for me	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
E-Government services are clear, understandable and have an easy to follow the structure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is easy to access the e-Government services that I need	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is easy to learn to interact with e-Government services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
E-Government services are provided in a language that I am easy to understand	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Communication with the government is easier through e-Government websites	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

12.

Please rate the following statements to reflect how useful you perceive e-Government services (Please choose one per row)

Perceived Value (PV) items	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
Using e-Government services will help me conduct transactions with the government faster	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Using e-Government services can save me time, compared to face to face service.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Using e-Government services can improve the service quality that I will receive, compared to the face to face interaction	<input type="radio"/>				
Generally using e-Government websites are useful to access government information and related services	<input type="radio"/>				

13.

Please rate the following statements to reflect your level of trust in e-Government? *(Please choose one per row)*

Trust in e-Government (TieG) items	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
I expect that e-Government services are designed to perform to the best interests of the users.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I believe that e-Government services are trustworthy	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I believe that e-Government services promote the availability of Government services 24/7	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I think I can have trust in e-Government	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

14.

Please rate the following statements to reflect your level of trust in Government *(Please choose one per row)*

Trust in Government (TiG) items	1-Strongly Disagree	2-Disagree	3-Neutral	4-Agree	5-Strongly Agree
I trust that the citizen's interests are the number one priority of the government.	<input type="radio"/>				
I trust the government's capability in providing safe e-services	<input type="radio"/>				
I think e-Government agencies can be trusted in the provision of electronic services to the citizenry	<input type="radio"/>				

15.

Please rate the following statements to reflect your level of trust in Technology *(Please choose one per row)*

Trust in the technology used for accessing e-Government services (TiT)	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
I trust the technologies supporting the system are reliable all the time.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I trust the technologies supporting the system are secure all the time.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
In overall, I have confidence in the technology used by government agencies to operate the e-Government services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I trust the mobile device(s) or computer that I use for accessing e-Government services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I trust the technologies used for accessing e-Government services use for accessing e-Government services.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

16.

Please rate the following statements to reflect how your friends, relatives, workmates etc. have influenced your intention to use e-Government services *(Please choose one per row)*

Social Influence (SI) items	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
People who influence my behavior think I should use the e-Government services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I would use the e-Government services if people in my social circle use them	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
People who influence my behavior think accessing and transacting through e-Government websites or apps is efficient and effective	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
People in my social circle trust intermediaries (e-offices) a lot	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
People who are important to me think that I should use the e-Government services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

17.

Please rate the following statements to reflect your needs on technical support when accessing e-Government services

(Please choose one per row)

Technical Support (TS) items	1 Not at all important	2 Slightly important	3 Neutral	4 Moderately important	5 Very important
I expect to get the help I need when accessing government services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It would be easy for me to get assistance when faced with problems in accessing government services (e.g. there are contact details, FAQ, help options)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I expect clear instructions or guidelines when accessing government services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I would expect feedback to be prompt once I request help through the contact details on the government website	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

18.

Please rate the following statements to reflect your privacy and security concerns when accessing e-Government services

(Please choose one per row)

Privacy and security concerns (PrSC) items	1 Strongly Disagree	2 D isagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
Generally, I trust that e-Government institutions have security mechanisms in place to guard against malicious attacks	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I believe my bank can protect me in case of problematic transactions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
e-Government websites have policy statements on privacy and security on my interactions with the sites	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel confident that that encryption and other technological advances on the internet make it safe for me to do business there	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I feel assured of privacy and security in doing business on the internet with the continued upgrades on security structures my bank puts in place	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I trust that all parties involved as I interact with the e-Government systems do protect my personal information	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

19.

Please rate the following statements to reflect your familiarity with the internet

(Please choose one per row)

Perceived internet Familiarity (PIF) items	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
I have used electronic sites and the Internet many times	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am familiar with using e-Government websites and the Internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My experience in electronic websites is high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am familiar with looking for e-Government services on the internet	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am familiar with internet banking	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

20.

Please rate the following statements to reflect your perception of the service quality of e-Government services

(Please choose one per row)

Perceived Service Quality (PerSQ) items	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
Generally, e-Government systems provide feedback mechanisms	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Generally, the e-Government websites are regularly updated to provide accurate information	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Generally, the e-Government services provide relevant information	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Generally, the e-Government services provide significant user interaction	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Generally, the e-Government services are easy to navigate structures	<input type="radio"/>				
Generally, e-Government systems have easily accessible contact details for the users to communicate with the government and its agencies	<input type="radio"/>				
Generally, e-Government services are designed with the user in mind	<input type="radio"/>				
Generally, I am satisfied with the quality of e-Government services	<input type="radio"/>				

21. **Please rate the following statements to reflect your perception of the Power Distance regarding the launch of e-Government services** (Please choose one per row)

Culture: Power Distance (PD) items PD: "the extent to which a less powerful person in the society tolerates inequality of power in the society" (Hofstede, 1984, p. 390).	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
Generally, I am involved in e-Government systems/ services decision making.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Generally, the government and its agencies ask for my opinion of the e-service prior to the launch of the e-Government services.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Generally, e-Government services have provided more opportunities for social interaction with people in government positions.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Generally, I just use e-Government services without question.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I often give feedback on the e-Government services that I have used	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

22. **Please rate the following statements to reflect your perception of uncertainty avoidance regarding e-Government service provision** (Please choose one per row)

Culture: Uncertainty Avoidance (UA) items UA: "the extent to which people within a culture are made nervous by the situation that they consider unstructured , unclear or unpredictable and the extent to which they have to avoid such situations by adopting strict codes of behaviour and a belief in absolute truth" (Hofstede, 1984, p. 390).	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
I enjoy using e-Government systems or services that have clear and easy to understand instructions or guidelines so that I always know what I'm expected to do	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is important to closely follow instructions and procedures to avoid mistakes	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Generally, the e-Government services that I use have a menu for guidance	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
It is usually difficult to find out on my own how the technology works	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

23. **Please rate the following statements to reflect your perception of the facilitating services and goods for e-Government adoption** (Please choose one per row)

Facilitating Services and Goods (FS-G) items	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
I have the resources needed to engage with e-Government systems or services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have the technical skills to engage with e-Government services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I have the technical skills to engage with e-Government services but lack awareness	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I access e-Government services through the self-service terminals in the bank	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I access e-Government services through the public library	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I access e-Government services through the state library	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

I access e-Government services through rural kiosks.	<input type="radio"/>				
Given the necessary resources and equipped with technical skill, it would be easy to access e-Government services.	<input type="radio"/>				

24. **Please rate the following statements to reflect your attitude toward using e-Government services** (Please choose one per row)

Attitude (ATT) items	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
My attitude towards using e-Government systems or services is high	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
My attitude towards using e-Government services has been changed by the economic situation in my country	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Engaging with e-Government services is an innovative idea	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Using e-Government services is associated with high internet costs	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am worried about security and privacy concerns because there are safeguards to protect me from malicious attacks.	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am not really a fan of technology	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
With exposure it would be easy to use the e-Government services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

25. **Please rate the following statements to reflect your intention to use e-Government services** (Please choose one per row)

Intention to Use e-Government services (BI) items	1 Strongly Disagree	2 Disagree	3 Neutral	4 Agree	5 Strongly Agree
I intend to visit e-Government websites in quest of information	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I plan to use e-Government service (such as paying municipality bills) in the following months	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Given the assurance, I am likely to disclose personal identification details on e-Government services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I plan to continue using the e-Government services	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I intend to make e-Government my first choice of doing business with the government	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Thank you for your participation

ANNEXURE H: ADDITIONAL DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS

RESULTS

Intermediaries per country

		CURRENT COUNTRY LOCATION OF THE PARTICIPANT							
		Botswana		Namibia		South Africa		Zimbabwe	
		f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
CELL PHONE	in person	65	87,8	30	83,3	31	88,6	118	68,6
	family, friends, etc.	2	2,7	0	0,0	2	5,7	3	1,7
	school/work	1	1,4	1	2,8	0	0,0	1	,6
	in person, family, work/school	0	0,0	2	5,6	0	0,0	30	17,4
	family, work/school	0	0,0	1	2,8	2	5,7	8	4,7
	non-ownership	6	8,1	2	5,6	0	0,0	12	7,0
SMART PHONE	in person	69	93,2	23	63,9	24	68,6	87	50,6
	family, friends, etc.	3	4,1	2	5,6	6	17,1	14	8,1
	school/work	1	1,4	0	0,0	0	0,0	7	4,1
	in person, family, work/school	0	0,0	2	5,6	2	5,7	7	4,1
	family, work/school	1	1,4	0	0,0	2	5,7	15	8,7
	non-ownership	0	0,0	9	25,0	1	2,9	42	24,4
LAPTOP	in person	59	79,7	26	72,2	23	65,7	80	46,5
	family, friends, etc.	4	5,4	1	2,8	2	5,7	12	7,0
	school/work	6	8,1	0	0,0	2	5,7	8	4,7
	in person, family, work/school	3	4,1	3	8,3	1	2,9	10	5,8
	family, work/school	1	1,4	1	2,8	6	17,1	11	6,4
	non-ownership	1	1,4	5	13,9	1	2,9	51	29,7
IPAD	in person	16	21,6	5	13,9	10	28,6	23	13,4
	family, friends, etc.	12	16,2	1	2,8	11	31,4	8	4,7
	school/work	8	10,8	0	0,0	5	14,3	11	6,4
	in person, family, work/school	0	0,0	4	11,1	0	0,0	6	3,5
	family, work/school	27	36,5	4	11,1	6	17,1	15	8,7
	non-ownership	11	14,9	22	61,1	3	8,6	109	63,4
DESKTOP COMPUTER	in person	22	29,7	2	5,6	8	22,9	13	7,6
	family, friends, etc.	11	14,9	4	11,1	0	0,0	10	5,8
	school/work	23	31,1	6	16,7	9	25,7	27	15,7
	internet café, Library etc.	4	5,4	0	0,0	6	17,1	6	3,5
	in person, family, work/school	2	2,7	1	2,8	2	5,7	12	7,0
	family, work/school	4	5,4	2	5,6	3	8,6	16	9,3
TEL/EXT	in person, family, wrk/sch, cafe/lib	0	0,0	0	0,0	2	5,7	4	2,3
	non-ownership	8	10,8	21	58,3	5	14,3	84	48,8
	in person	8	10,8	2	5,6	4	11,4	7	4,1
	Family, friends, etc.	11	14,9	8	22,2	4	11,4	24	14,0
	school/work	43	58,1	7	19,4	15	42,9	27	15,7
	internet café, Library etc.	0	0,0	1	2,8	4	11,4	5	2,9
TOTAL	in person, family, work/school	0	0,0	0	0,0	0	0,0	7	4,1
	family, work/school	3	4,1	1	2,8	2	5,7	15	8,7
	non-ownership	9	12,2	17	47,2	6	17,1	87	50,6
TOTAL		74	100,0	36	100,0	35	100,0	172	100,0

Awareness Sources

	yes	no	3.00
	Row N %	Row N %	Row N %
Government websites	33.8%	66.2%	0.0%
Social influence family, friends, etc.	61.2%	38.8%	0.0%
Print media	36.0%	64.0%	0.0%
Television	49.8%	50.2%	0.0%
Radio	36.6%	63.4%	0.0%
Billboard	16.1%	83.9%	0.0%
Customer care service	24.4%	75.6%	0.0%
Pamphlets from government offices	14.8%	85.2%	0.0%
Pamphlets accessible from public or state libraries	12.7%	87.3%	0.0%
SMS from government departments	17.4%	82.6%	0.0%
Emails from government departments	12.0%	88.0%	0.0%
Postal services	9.8%	90.2%	0.0%
Telephone call from government agencies	5.7%	94.0%	0.3%

E-Services access levels at macro and micro levels

	never		rarely		periodically		every time	
	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %	Count	Row N %
Internet banking services	65	20.5%	57	18.0%	104	32.8%	91	28.7%
Mobile banking services	47	14.8%	31	9.8%	93	29.3%	146	46.1%
e-Municipality services	114	36.0%	52	16.4%	83	26.2%	68	21.5%
Online bill checking and payments	87	27.4%	62	19.6%	84	26.5%	84	26.5%
e-Health services	113	35.6%	62	19.6%	80	25.2%	62	19.6%
e-Education services	68	21.5%	59	18.6%	98	30.9%	92	29.0%
e-Visa application	127	40.1%	77	24.3%	79	24.9%	34	10.7%
Receiving information on filing tax returns	122	38.5%	56	17.7%	96	30.3%	43	13.6%
e-Financial transfers	152	47.9%	65	20.5%	71	22.4%	29	9.1%
Online tax payer returns	142	44.8%	66	20.8%	72	22.7%	37	11.7%
Online submission of tax declarations	138	43.5%	68	21.5%	78	24.6%	33	10.4%
Online application for employment in the government	145	45.7%	71	22.4%	73	23.0%	28	8.8%
Online application for death/ birth certificates	215	67.8%	61	19.2%	31	9.8%	10	3.2%
Contact with government officials	156	49.2%	60	18.9%	84	26.5%	17	5.4%
Communication with government officials	149	47.0%	63	19.9%	67	21.1%	38	12.0%
Informational services	70	22.1%	50	15.8%	94	29.7%	103	32.5%
*Social communication	23	7.3%	16	5.0%	45	14.2%	233	73.5%
Research	22	6.9%	27	8.5%	80	25.2%	188	59.3%
Reading online newspapers	50	15.8%	36	11.4%	79	24.9%	152	47.9%
Online Registration of Animal and Related Services	217	68.5%	29	9.1%	30	9.5%	41	12.9%

e-Service	Botswana				Namibia				South Africa				Zimbabwe			
	never	rarely	periodically	every time	never	rarely	periodically	every time	never	rarely	periodically	every time	never	rarely	periodically	every time
	Internet banking services	16,2%	13,5%	33,8%	36,5%	11,1%	19,4%	19,4%	50,0%	20,0%	14,3%	28,6%	37,1%	24,4%	20,3%	36,0%
Mobile banking services	18,9%	10,8%	32,4%	37,8%	8,3%	13,9%	27,8%	50,0%	14,3%	5,7%	42,9%	37,1%	14,5%	9,3%	25,6%	50,6%
e-Municipality services	39,2%	25,7%	23,0%	12,2%	27,8%	16,7%	52,8%	2,8%	65,7%	5,7%	17,1%	11,4%	30,2%	14,5%	23,8%	31,4%
Online bill checking and payments	32,4%	17,6%	27,0%	23,0%	16,7%	27,8%	47,2%	8,3%	37,1%	22,9%	17,1%	22,9%	25,6%	18,0%	23,8%	32,6%
e-Health services	41,9%	20,3%	24,3%	13,5%	30,6%	36,1%	30,6%	2,8%	48,6%	28,6%	11,4%	11,4%	31,4%	14,0%	27,3%	27,3%
e-Education services	14,9%	27,0%	32,4%	25,7%	11,1%	13,9%	61,1%	13,9%	11,4%	22,9%	37,1%	28,6%	28,5%	15,1%	22,7%	33,7%
e-Visa application	41,9%	24,3%	21,6%	12,2%	22,2%	30,6%	38,9%	8,3%	34,3%	11,4%	40,0%	14,3%	44,2%	25,6%	20,3%	9,9%
Receiving information on filing tax returns	14,9%	16,2%	48,6%	20,3%	19,4%	25,0%	41,7%	13,9%	31,4%	11,4%	48,6%	8,6%	54,1%	18,0%	16,3%	11,6%
e-Financial transfers	51,4%	20,3%	20,3%	8,1%	38,9%	13,9%	47,2%	0,0%	40,0%	28,6%	20,0%	11,4%	50,0%	20,3%	18,6%	11,0%
Online tax payer returns	28,4%	14,9%	39,2%	17,6%	25,0%	25,0%	38,9%	11,1%	17,1%	28,6%	25,7%	28,6%	61,6%	20,9%	11,6%	5,8%
Online submission of tax declarations	24,3%	16,2%	43,2%	16,2%	22,2%	22,2%	44,4%	11,1%	31,4%	28,6%	17,1%	22,9%	58,7%	22,1%	14,0%	5,2%
Online application for employment in the government	40,5%	24,3%	25,7%	9,5%	38,9%	13,9%	44,4%	2,8%	22,9%	31,4%	28,6%	17,1%	54,1%	21,5%	16,3%	8,1%
Online application for death/ birth certificates	71,6%	17,6%	8,1%	2,7%	50,0%	25,0%	19,4%	5,6%	60,0%	28,6%	5,7%	5,7%	71,5%	16,9%	9,3%	2,3%
Contact with government officials	52,7%	17,6%	27,0%	2,7%	22,2%	19,4%	52,8%	5,6%	40,0%	20,0%	34,3%	5,7%	55,2%	19,2%	19,2%	6,4%
Communication with government officials	59,5%	18,9%	14,9%	6,8%	30,6%	19,4%	41,7%	8,3%	51,4%	25,7%	17,1%	5,7%	44,2%	19,2%	20,3%	16,3%
Informational services	24,3%	24,3%	29,7%	21,6%	13,9%	16,7%	47,2%	22,2%	11,4%	17,1%	48,6%	22,9%	25,0%	11,6%	22,1%	41,3%
Social communication	5,4%	4,1%	8,1%	82,4%	2,8%	0,0%	38,9%	58,3%	5,7%	11,4%	14,3%	68,6%	9,3%	5,2%	11,6%	73,8%
Research	2,7%	8,1%	35,1%	54,1%	5,6%	2,8%	36,1%	55,6%	0,0%	11,4%	22,9%	65,7%	10,5%	9,3%	19,2%	61,0%
Reading online newspapers	13,5%	9,5%	25,7%	51,4%	16,7%	13,9%	22,2%	47,2%	17,1%	11,4%	40,0%	31,4%	16,3%	11,6%	22,1%	50,0%
Online Registration of Animal and Related Services	60,8%	8,1%	10,8%	20,3%	66,7%	2,8%	13,9%	16,7%	65,7%	17,1%	11,4%	5,7%	72,7%	9,3%	7,6%	10,5%

ANNEXURE I: PCA APPENDICES

PV Total Variance Explained and Scree plot

Total Variance Explained

Scree Plot

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.090	51.503	51.503	3.090	51.503	51.503
2	.844	14.074	65.578			
3	.702	11.700	77.277			
4	.499	8.318	85.596			
5	.474	7.901	93.496			
6	.390	6.504	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

PV Total Variance Explained and Scree plot

Total Variance Explained

Scree Plot

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.670	66.740	66.740	2.670	66.740	66.740
2	.579	14.486	81.226			
3	.445	11.136	92.362			
4	.306	7.638	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

TieG: Total Variance Explained and Scree plot

Total Variance Explained

Scree Plot

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.628	65.706	65.706	2.628	65.706	65.706
2	.623	15.581	81.287			
3	.456	11.398	92.685			
4	.293	7.315	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

TiG Total Variance Explained and Scree plot

Total Variance Explained

Scree Plot

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.242	74.735	74.735	2.242	74.735	74.735
2	.500	16.663	91.398			
3	.258	8.602	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

TiT Total Variance Explained and Scree plot

Total Variance Explained

Scree Plot

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.468	69.361	69.361	3.468	69.361	69.361
2	.562	11.231	80.592			
3	.426	8.529	89.121			
4	.345	6.900	96.022			
5	.199	3.978	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

SI Total Variance Explained and Scree plot

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.106	62.127	62.127	3.106	62.127	62.127
2	.701	14.017	76.143			
3	.499	9.980	86.124			
4	.362	7.232	93.356			
5	.332	6.644	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

TS Total Variance Explained and Scree plot

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.775	69.383	69.383	2.775	69.383	69.383
2	.505	12.621	82.004			
3	.413	10.327	92.332			
4	.307	7.668	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

PrSC Total Variance Explained and Scree plot

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.399	56.646	56.646	3.399	56.646	56.646
2	.722	12.038	68.683			
3	.659	10.976	79.659			
4	.457	7.612	87.271			
5	.416	6.935	94.205			
6	.348	5.795	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

PIF Total Variance Explained and Scree plot

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.282	65.639	65.639	3.282	65.639	65.639
2	.573	11.461	77.100			
3	.469	9.377	86.477			

4	.347	6.943	93.420			
5	.329	6.580	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

PerSQ Total Variance Explained and Scree plot

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
	1	4.739	59.233	59.233	4.739	59.233
2	.708	8.844	68.078			
3	.641	8.015	76.092			
4	.556	6.955	83.048			
5	.448	5.601	88.648			
6	.413	5.158	93.807			
7	.292	3.652	97.459			
8	.203	2.541	100.000			

Scree Plot

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

PD Total Variance Explained and Scree plot

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
	1	2.578	51.551	51.551	2.578	51.551
2	1.054	21.074	72.625			
3	.626	12.511	85.135			
4	.386	7.717	92.852			
5	.357	7.148	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

ANNEXURE J: TESTING THE ASSUMPTIONS FOR UNIVARIATE NORMALITY

Scale	Histogram	Normal Q-Q Plot	Box Plot
ACCESSLVL			
PAIU_TR			
PV_TR			
TieG_TR			
TIG_TR			
TIT_TR			

ANNEXURE K: TESTING THE ASSUMPTIONS FOR UNIVARIATE NORMALITY: REDUCED SCATTER MATRICES

ANNEXURE L: TESTING ASSUMPTIONS FOR MULTIVARIATE ANALYSIS

Normality, Linearity and Homoscedasticity for multivariate analysis

Dependent Variable: TieG.
Predictors: PATU, TiT, TiG, FI, PrSC, PerSQ

Dependent Variable: ATT.
Predictors: PATU, PV, TieG

Dependent Variable: BI.
Predictors: SI, ATT*SI, ATT, TieG, Facil_Cond

Dependent Variable: E-Government adoption.
Predictors: BI, UA, PD

Behavioural Intention regression model leverage on residual

The scatter plot for the BI shows that the two identified cases of outliers could not be removed as they had no effect on the slope of the regression line based on the leverage,

e-Government Adoption regression model leverage on residual

ANNEXURE M: REGRESSION ANALYSIS

TieG= F (PrSC+ PerSQ + TiT + TiG + PIF +PATU)

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.680 ^a	.463	.452	.53711	.463	44.523	6	310	.000	1.980

a. Predictors: (Constant), PersQ_TR, PIF_TR, TiG_TR, PATU_TR, PrSC_TR, TiT_TR

b. Dependent Variable: TieG_TR

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	77.065	6	12.844	44.523	.000 ^b
	Residual	89.430	310	.288		
	Total	166.495	316			

a. Dependent Variable: TieG_TR

b. Predictors: (Constant), PersQ_TR, PIF_TR, TiG_TR, PATU_TR, PrSC_TR, TiT_TR

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations			Collinearity Statistics		
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF	
1	(Constant)	.773	.206		3.752	.000						
	PATU_TR	.192	.055	.195	3.473	.001	.544	.194	.145	.552	1.813	
	TiG_TR	.145	.048	.178	3.029	.003	.519	.170	.126	.503	1.986	
	TiT_TR	.037	.055	.040	.662	.508	.495	.038	.028	.470	2.129	
	PrSC_TR	.265	.060	.261	4.449	.000	.581	.245	.185	.503	1.986	
	PIF_TR	.108	.040	.122	2.698	.007	.305	.151	.112	.853	1.172	
	PersQ_TR	.107	.062	.105	1.721	.086	.534	.097	.072	.464	2.155	

a. Dependent Variable: TieG_TR

PV= f (PATU)

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.606a	.367	.365	.62913

a. Predictors: (Constant), PATU_TR

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	72.236	1	72.236	182.503	.000b
	Residual	124.679	315	.396		
	Total	196.915	316			

a. Dependent Variable: PV_TR

b. Predictors: (Constant), PATU_TR

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.753	.173		10.106	.000
	PATU_TR	.648	.048	.606	13.509	.000

a. Dependent Variable: PV_TR

ATT= f (PATU + PV + TieG)

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.432a	.187	.179	.60097	.187	23.942	3	313	.000	1.794

a. Predictors: (Constant), PV_TR, TieG_TR, PATU_TR

b. Dependent Variable: ATT_TR

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	25.942	3	8.647	23.942	.000 ^b
	Residual	113.045	313	.361		
	Total	138.987	316			

a. Dependent Variable: ATT_TR

b. Predictors: (Constant), PV_TR, TieG_TR, PATU_TR

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	1.852	.210		8.836	.000					
	PATU_TR	.173	.061	.192	2.827	.005	.374	.158	.144	.564	1.773
	TieG_TR	.181	.058	.198	3.108	.002	.368	.173	.158	.640	1.563
	PV_TR	.103	.056	.122	1.822	.069	.344	.102	.093	.576	1.737

a. Dependent Variable: ATT_TR

BI = f (SI + ATT + TieG + Facil_Cond)

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change	
1	.586 ^a	.344	.335	.61209	.344	40.839	4	312	.000	1.664

a. Predictors: (Constant), Facil_Cond, TieG_TR, SI_TR, ATT_TR

b. Dependent Variable: BI_TR

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	61.202	4	15.301	40.839	.000 ^b
	Residual	116.893	312	.375		
	Total	178.095	316			

a. Dependent Variable: BI_TR

b. Predictors: (Constant), Facil_Cond, TieG_TR, SI_TR, ATT_TR

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance
1	(Constant)	.699	.266		2.626	.009	.175	1.222					
	ATT_TR	.348	.060	.308	5.831	.000	.231	.466	.481	.313	.267	.755	1.324
	SI_TR	.171	.049	.181	3.463	.001	.074	.268	.378	.192	.159	.774	1.293
	TieG_TR	.119	.055	.115	2.165	.031	.011	.228	.373	.122	.099	.741	1.349
	Facil_Cond	.249	.071	.192	3.513	.001	.109	.388	.440	.195	.161	.706	1.416

a. Dependent Variable: BI_TR

E-Government adoption = f (BI +UA +PD + Interaction)

Product terms key:

Int_3: BI_TR x PD_TR

Test(s) of highest order unconditional interaction(s):

R2-chng F (HC3) df1 df2 p

X*W .011 10.564 1.000 312.000 .001

Focal predict: BI_TR (X)
Mod var: PD_TR (W)

Conditional effects of the focal predictor at values of the moderator(s):

PD_TR	Effect	se (HC3)	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
-.842	.214	.028	7.670	.000	.159	.269
.000	.278	.025	11.123	.000	.229	.327
.842	.342	.035	9.666	.000	.273	.412

There are no statistical significance transition points within the observed range of the moderator found using the Johnson-Neyman method.

Conditional effect of focal predictor at values of the moderator:

PD_TR	Effect	se (HC3)	t	p	LLCI	ULCI
-1.834	.138	.044	3.118	.002	.051	.225
-1.634	.153	.040	3.793	.000	.074	.233
-1.434	.169	.037	4.584	.000	.096	.241
-1.234	.184	.033	5.506	.000	.118	.250
-1.034	.199	.030	6.560	.000	.139	.259
-.834	.214	.028	7.715	.000	.160	.269
-.634	.230	.026	8.893	.000	.179	.281
-.434	.245	.025	9.951	.000	.197	.293
-.234	.260	.024	10.723	.000	.213	.308
-.034	.276	.025	11.100	.000	.227	.324
.166	.291	.026	11.091	.000	.239	.342
.366	.306	.028	10.802	.000	.250	.362
.566	.321	.031	10.358	.000	.260	.382
.766	.337	.034	9.857	.000	.269	.404
.966	.352	.038	9.358	.000	.278	.426
1.166	.367	.041	8.889	.000	.286	.448
1.366	.382	.045	8.463	.000	.294	.471
1.566	.398	.049	8.080	.000	.301	.495
1.766	.413	.053	7.740	.000	.308	.518
1.966	.428	.058	7.437	.000	.315	.542
2.166	.444	.062	7.168	.000	.322	.565

Data for visualizing the conditional effect of the focal predictor: Paste text below into SPSS syntax window and execute to produce plot.

DATA LIST FREE/

BI_TR PD_TR eGov_adoption .
BEGIN DATA.

-.751 -.842 3.311
.000 -.842 3.472
.751 -.842 3.632
-.751 .000 3.457
.000 .000 3.666
.751 .000 3.875
-.751 .842 3.603
.000 .842 3.861
.751 .842 4.118

END DATA.

GRAPH/SCATTERPLOT= BI_TR WITH eGov_adoption BY PD_TR.

ANNEXURE N: AMOS INTERACTION ANALYSIS RESULTS

The following are the data used with the interaction plotter tool for the BI X PD interaction in AMOS

Simple Slopes for a 2-way Interaction SEM BI_X_PD.xls [Compatibility Mode] - Microsoft Excel

File Home Insert Page Layout Formulas Data Review View Foxt PDF

E26 fx

1 Designed by Jamie DeCoster & Anne-Marie Iselin 2005-11-12. This and other Excel spreadsheets are available at <http://www.stat-help.com>
 2 Last modified 2009-08-25
 3
 4 This spreadsheet produces graphs and tests to explore the nature of a 2-way interaction in regression.
 5 You must first enter the coefficients from the regression equation in the dark blue boxes.
 6 Then you must enter the maximum and minimum values for X1 (the IV on the X-axis) in the purple boxes.
 7 Then you must enter the values X2 will take on the different lines in the plot, along with labels for these lines in the maroon boxes.
 8 Finally, if you want to obtain tests of whether each simple slope is significant, you must enter the sample size and the necessary coefficient covariances in the light blue boxes.
 9 Graphs will appear in the worksheet entitled "Graphs." The middle three values will be used in the 3-line graph.
 10 Estimates of each simple slope coefficient and a test whether it is significantly different from zero will appear in the worksheet entitled "Estimates."

Constant	X1 Coefficient (IV on the X-axis)	X2 Coefficient (IV represented by separate lines)	X1*X2 Coefficient
4	0.152	0.454	0.108

Minimum value for X1	Maximum value for X1
1	5

Values for X2	Label for X2 value
-2	Very Low PD
-1	Low PD
0	Med PD
1	High PD
2	Very High PD

Values used for 3-line graph

Sample Size	Variance of X1 Coefficient	Variance of X1*X2 Coefficient	Covariance between X1 Coefficient and X1*X2 Coefficient
317	0.841	1.282	-0.1

Data Graphs Estimates

The following are the graphs generated with the BI X PD interaction data in the above screenshot

Simple Slopes for a 2-way Interaction SEM BI_X_PD.xls [Compatibility Mode] - Microsoft Excel

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1 The graphs are unprotected so you can add a title and labels on the axes. You can also edit other features of the graphs.
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	1	5
Low PD	3.59	3.766
Med PD	4.152	4.76
High PD	4.714	5.754

	1	5
Very Low PD	3.028	2.772
Low PD	3.59	3.766
Med PD	4.152	4.76
High PD	4.714	5.754
Very High PD	5.276	6.748

Data Graphs Estimates

The following are the estimates generated with the BI X PD interaction data

ANNEXURE O: MULTIGROUP ANALYSIS USING AMOS

Structural Weights Model

Standardised Estimates for Zimbabwe Case

Standardised Estimates for Botswana Case

10 ANNEXURE P: REGRESSION ANALYSIS AT COUNTRY LEVEL

Zimbabwe

Model	Hypothesis	IV	DV	β	t	p value	F statistic. R ²	Result
1	H ₁	PATU	PV	0.655****	7.352	0.000	<i>F (1.170) =127.687; p=0.000</i> R²=0.429	<i>accepted</i>
								<i>accepted</i>
2	H ₁₂	TieG	ATT	0.314****	3.686	0.000	<i>F (3.168) =17.100; p=0.000</i> R²=0.234	<i>accepted</i>
	H ₂	PATU		0.113	1.176	0.241		<i>na</i>
	H ₃	PV	0.133	1.451	0.149	<i>na</i>		
	H ₆	PrSC	0.266***	3.049	0.003	<i>F (6.165) =31.560; p=0.000</i> R²=0.534	<i>accepted</i>	
3	H ₁₁	PATU	TieG	0.194***	2.628	0.009	<i>F (5.166) =110.419 p=0.000</i> R²=0.769	<i>accepted</i>
	H ₉	TiG		0.094	1.255	0.211		<i>na</i>
	H ₁₀	PIF		0.023	0.399	0.691		<i>na</i>
	H ₇	PerSQ		0.148*	1.702	0.091		<i>accepted</i>
	H ₈	TiT		0.164**	2.065	0.040		accepted
*5	H ₁₅	BI	eGov Adoption	0.451****	9.404	0.000	<i>F (5.166) =110.419 p=0.000</i> R²=0.769	<i>accepted</i>
	H ₁₇	PD		0.359****	8.426	0.000		<i>accepted</i>
	H ₁₆	UA		0.203****	4.270	0.000		<i>accepted</i>
	Int_1	BI * PD		0.310****	6.705	0.000		<i>accepted</i>
	Int_2	BI * UA		-0.018	-0.370	0.712		na